

Rotwildmonitoring Aletsch

Korrelation von Wetter und Bewegungsgeschwindigkeit

Abbildung 1: Visualisierung GPS Bewegungsdaten des Rotwildmonitoring Aletsch Projekts als Tracks je Tier in Arcgis Pro

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Marco Heinzen
Hegdornweg 6E
3904 Naters

info@alpine-robotics.com
www.alpine-robotics.com

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1. Einleitung

1.1. Abstract:

Mit einem grossflächig angelegtem Studienaufbau wurde Rotwild in der Region Aletsch (Oberwallis) besendert. Die Sender waren mit GPS, Temperatur und «Inertial Measuring Unit» (IMU) ausgestattet. In meinem Abschlussprojekt des CAS Rauminformationssysteme ETH ging es darum, die GPS-Daten in Distanzen bzw. Geschwindigkeiten umzuformen und diese mit Wetterdaten zusammenzuführen. In erster Linie wurde der Bezug Bewegungsgeschwindigkeit vs. Temperatur untersucht. Die darauffolgenden statistischen Analysen (Statistik, Plots, Seaborn Autocorrelation, Granger Causality Test, als kurzer «Test» Random Forrest Regression / ML) ergaben, eine Korrelation / Granger Kausalität mit der Temperatur, eine leichte Granger-Kausalität mit dem Luftdruck, aber keinen signifikanten direkten oder indirekten Zusammenhang mit anderen Wetterparameter. Auch der Machine Learning Test ergab als wichtigster beitragender Faktor die GPS-Temperatur. Die Einteilung in Temperaturklassen (Unter Null, kalt, warm, heiss) ergab ein Ergebnis: Das Rotwild bewegt sich durchschnittlich am meisten zwischen 0 und 15 °C. Ein Zusammenhang zur Tages- und Jahreszeit bzw. zeitlich bedingtes Verhalten konnte festgestellt werden. Die Komplexität des Wetters insgesamt macht eine einfache Statistische Analyse fast unmöglich. Auch könnten andere Gründe mehr ins Gewicht fallen als einzelne Wetterparameter. So könnten Umweltfaktoren wie beispielsweise Tourismus, Jagd, natürliches Verhalten (zB. Brunft, Wechsel der Einstände) oder das Nahrungsangebot eine wichtigere Rolle spielen als das Wetter – oder es könnten sich systemische Fehler eingeschlichen haben (Messfehler, mangelnde Datenqualität und Quantität, Methodik etc.) – welche im zeitlichen Rahmen dieser Arbeit nicht vertiefter untersucht werden konnten. Auch war das Zeitintervall des Datensatzes (1h) eventuell zu gross, so dass die wahre, angenäherte Distanz nicht korrekt berechnet werden konnte. Eine genaue Kenntnis der Bewegungsgeschwindigkeit und Distanz des Rotwilds in Bezug zu Wetterdaten wäre nicht nur aus wissenschaftlicher Sicht (Biologie, Ökologie) interessant, sondern auch aus praktischen Gründen (zB Wildtiermanagement, Schutzwald, Naturschutz, Tierbeobachtungen, Tourismus und Freizeitaktivitäten). In Zukunft wäre es sicherlich interessant mit multivariate Time Series Analysis (Machine Learning, Deep Neural Networks, Reservoir Computing) zu arbeiten.

1.2. Beschrieb Projekt Rotwildmonitoring

Für einen sachgemässen Umgang mit dem Rothirsch in der Region Aletsch-Goms fehlen bislang wichtige Grundlagen, insbesondere hinsichtlich der Raumnutzung dieser Wildtierart. In einem umfassenden, rund 5 Jahre dauernden Rothirschprojekt sollen die vorhandenen Wissenslücken nun geschlossen werden. Die für die Praxis wichtigen Erkenntnisse können nur mit einer umfassenden Raumnutzungsstudie angegangen werden. Dazu müssen Rothirsche eingefangen, markiert und besendert werden. Der Einfang erfolgt meist durch Beschuss mittels Narkosegewehr. Alle behändigten Rothirsche erhalten eine eindeutige Ohrmarke. Einige ausgewachsene Tiere werden zudem mit GPS-GSM-Sendern ausgestattet. Für die erforderlichen Eingriffe an den Rothirschen wurde beim Veterinäramt Wallis ein Tierversuchsgesuch eingereicht und bewilligt. Das Projekt wurde im Herbst 2017 von der Walliser Dienststelle für Jagd, Fischerei und Wildtiere DJFW und der Forschungsgruppe Wildtiermanagement der ZHAW initiiert. Als Projektpartner beteiligen sich auch die Dienststelle für Wald, Flussbau und Landschaft, das Bundesamt für Umwelt sowie Pro Natura (Dienststelle für Jagd, Fischerei und Wildtiere, Kanton Wallis 2018)

1.3. Beschrieb Analyse Wetterdaten vs. Bewegungsgeschwindigkeit

Die GPS-Daten des Rotwildprojektes sollen in Zusammenhang mit Wetterdaten gebracht und Korrelationen errechnet werden, insbesondere die Bewegungsgeschwindigkeit des Rotwilds in Abhängigkeit zur Temperatur. Nach der Erstellung eines Datenmodells (UML) für die verschiedenen Datenprovider (ZHAW, ETH, MeteoSchweiz, Meteo Oberwallis, ArcGIS Online Portal, Swisstopo) werden die Daten in Tabellenform (SQL und CSV) bzw. Rasterdaten aggregiert und in Datenbanken gespeichert. Das Projekt wurde hauptsächlich mit Jupyter Notebook (Kluyver u. a. 2016) geschrieben. Da die Datenmenge relativ gross war entschied ich mich die Datenbanken mittels Pandas (The pandas development team 2020) zu bearbeiten. Die Bewegungsgeschwindigkeit der einzelnen Tiere wurde als euklidische Distanz mittels Python für die einzelnen Intervalle (1 Stunde) berechnet. Dazu wurden die GPS Daten (WGS84) mittels GeoProj (PROJ contributors 2021) in Python nach CH1903+ LV95 projiziert. Die Wetterdaten wurden mittels Datenbankabfrage Meteo Schweiz, IDAWEB, Meteo Oberwallis SQL) heruntergeladen, bereinigt, zusammengeführt und dann lokal zum jeweiligen Aufenthaltsort mittels «Inverse Distance Weighting» (IDW) interpoliert. Zudem wurden mithilfe des DEM25 Höhenmodells von Swisstopo (Bundesamt für Topographie 2021) die Höhendaten des GPS verbessert. Die GPS-Daten und Bewegungsgeschwindigkeit wurden mittels Standortabfrage mit den Wetterdaten in Verbindung gebracht und in einer neuen Datenbank gespeichert. Für die verschiedenen Fragestellungen wurden Statistik, Autokorrelationen sowie Plots errechnet. Zusätzlich wurde mittels Python die Granger-Kausalität ermittelt («Granger Casualty Test») (Seabold und Perktold 2010). Zu Testzwecken wurde auch mittels Scikit Learn (Pedregosa u. a. 2011a) ein Machine Learning Modell erstellt (Random Forrest Regression) um ein Indiz zur Wichtigkeit / zum Beitrag einzelner Wetterparameter zu finden. Dieser Teil der Arbeit müsste aber noch vertieft und die Methodik entsprechend angepasst werden.

2. Datengrundlage

Abbildung 2: Konzeptionelles Datenmodell, detaillierte Ansicht in Appendix B

Die Daten sind nach einer ersten Konvertierung (SQL zu CSV) bzw. direkt als CSV nach Download manuell bereinigt worden. Detaillierte Angaben zu den jeweiligen Daten weiter unten. Grundsätzlich benötigte es für dieses Projekt alle Daten in 1 Stunden Schritten. Die GPS-Daten benötigen eine TierID (Primärschlüssel) sowie Zeiten in UTC (Sekundärschlüssel). Dazu brauchte es die GPS-Koordinaten und Höhe je Tier und Zeit. Weitere Angaben wie Jahreszeit, GPS-Sensor Temperatur, Geschlecht, Gebiet etc. ergänzen die GPS-Daten für die spätere Statistik. Die Wetterdaten brauchen einen Stationsname (Primary Key) mit Ortskoordinaten (WGS84 und CH1903+) sowie die Wetterparameter mit UTC Zeit (Sekundärschlüssel). Die Wetterdaten wurden auf den grössten gemeinsamen Nenner gebracht. Bei manchen Wetterdaten musste ein Resampling (1h) gemacht werden. Nicht alle Wetterstationen besitzen dieselben Sensoren bzw. messen dieselben Werte. Als wichtigster Wert in diesem Projekt galt die Temperatur des GPS-Sensors, sowie die interpolierte Temperatur von Messstationen. Daneben wurden aber auch andere Parameter wie: Taupunkt, Luftfeuchtigkeit, Luftdruck, Luftdruckänderung, Niederschlag, Schnee und Solarstrahlung und Sonnenscheindauer etc. berücksichtigt. Die Werte von MeteoOberwallis mussten vom imperialen ins metrische System konvertiert werden. Durch die grosse Datenmenge (Endprodukt: 333993 Zeilen mal 85 Spalten, DEM 64Gb) war es erforderlich, die Daten in Zwischenschritten jeweils als CSV abzuspeichern. Die Daten wurden in einer Ordnerstruktur, lokal sowie durch die Python Skripts verwaltet. Innerhalb der Skripts werden die Daten durch Pandas Dataframes (McKinney 2010) verwaltet. Originaldaten wurden kopiert und danach erst weiterverarbeitet. In ArcGIS Pro wurde eine File Geodatabase (gdb) angelegt. Da die meisten Schritte in Jupyter Notebook / Python erfolgten, wurde auf die Verwendung des ArcGIS Pro- internen Jupyter Notebooks verzichtet.

2.1. GPS Daten

Datenquelle: ZHAW - WILMA & Kanton Wallis («Wildlife Management Research Group» 2021) / (Dienststelle für Jagd, Fischerei und Wildtiere, Kanton Wallis 2018). Format: CSV. Dateien: GPS-Daten (CSV), Legende (CSV) (ursprünglich Individuelle_Sendedauer_20210309.xlsx), Beschrieb Daten (Excel).

2.2. Meteo Schweiz (IDAWEB)

Datenquelle: MeteoSchweiz IDAWEB (MeteoSchweiz 2021), Datenformat: CSV, je eine Datei pro Gruppe von Parametern (Luftfeuchtigkeit, Temperatur, Schnee, Luftdruck, Niederschlag, Sonnenscheindauer, Strahlung etc. Innerhalb CSV jede Station durch Leerzeile getrennt. Durch die grosse Datenmenge konnte nicht der ganze Datensatz als eine Datei heruntergeladen werden. Beschränkung der Dateigrösse durch IDAWEB, daher Download der Daten je Parametergruppe. Zusätzliche Werte, Einheit, Datenquelle, Ort, Koordinaten etc. Grundsätzliches Problem: nicht alle Stationen messen dieselben Parameter, Vereinheitlichung der verschiedenen Datenschemas zu einem einheitlichen Dataframe.

2.3. Meteo Oberwallis

Datenquelle: Meteo Oberwallis (Schnidrig 2021), Datenformat: SQL Datenbank → Export SQL → SQL Browser → Konvertierung zu CSV. Die Wetterdaten von Meteo Oberwallis ergänzen die Daten von Meteo Schweiz, da Meteo Schweiz im Oberwallis nur wenige Wetterstationen betreibt, welche sich zusätzlich meist leicht ausserhalb der genauen Projektregion befinden. Die Wetterstationen von Meteo Oberwallis sind alle desselben Typs (Davis Instruments, Wireless Vantage Pro2) und werden auch als Messstationen für Agrikultur verwendet. Zum Teil werden dieselben Parameter erfasst wie von Meteo Schweiz, zum Teil aber auch andere Werte. Da es sich um amerikanische Sensoren handelt, wird intern alles im Imperialen System (Fuss, Inches etc.) gespeichert. Darum mussten diese Daten alle in das metrische SI-System konvertiert werden.

2.4. ArcGIS Pro Online Portal

Gemeinden CH Polygon Datenquelle: ArcGIS Online Portal (Esri 2021)

2.5. Bundesamt für Topografie – Swisstopo

Datenquelle: Bundesamt für Topographie – Swisstopo. DEM Wallis (Swissalti3d) (Bundesamt für Topographie 2021)
Format: GeoTiff Kacheln vom Kanton Wallis (64 Gb)

Die Daten wurden heruntergeladen und lokal gespeichert, in ArcGIS Pro wurden die Kacheln zusammengeführt und danach mit dem Oberwallis verschnitten, um die Dateigrösse zu reduzieren.

3. Methoden

Abbildung 3: vollständiges kartografisches Modell, die einzelnen Bilder (in gross) befinden sich im Appendix C

Nach dem Download der Daten wurden diese als erstes manuell mit Notepad++ (Ho 2021) bereinigt. Die Daten von Meteo Oberwallis wurden als SQL heruntergeladen und mittels DB Browser SQLite (DB Browser for SQLite 2021) in CSV Dateien umgewandelt. Die Daten wurden mit Python (Van Rossum 2020) / Jupyter Notebook (Kluyver u. a. 2016) bearbeitet und analysiert. Dazu wurden die Daten in Pandas Dataframes (The pandas development team 2020) geladen. Da es sich um sehr grosse Datenmengen handelt und dadurch (trotz Code Optimierung und Multiprocessing / Ipyparallel (IPython 2015)) sehr lange Prozessierungszeiten beanspruchte, wurden die Daten nach einzelnen Zwischenschritten in CSV Dateien zwischengespeichert um bei einem Abbruch oder bei Änderungen des Codes nicht jedes Mal die gesamten 4 Scripts ausführen zu müssen.

Insgesamt gab es mehrere Iterationen/Versionen der 4 Python Scripts. Nach der Feststellung von fehlerhaften Höhendaten durch das GPS wurden in ArcGIS Pro die Höhendaten mit Hilfe des Höhenmodells (DEM) von Swisalti3d (Bundesamt für Topographie 2021) korrigiert. GPS-Daten wurden mit Python zusammengeführt, angereichert, bereinigt, nach CH1903+ LV95 (EPSG2056) projiziert und zwecks Weiterverarbeitung grob statistisch analysiert sowie geplottet. Die Distanzen und dadurch die Bewegungsgeschwindigkeit der einzelnen Tiere wurde mit einem eigens implementierten Algorithmus bestimmt (Euclidian Distance Function per Deer per Hour) («Euclidean Distance - Wikipedia» 2021). Die Wetterdaten von MeteoSchweiz (MeteoSchweiz 2021) konnten aufgrund der Datenmenge nur als einzelne Parametergruppen heruntergeladen werden. Die einzelnen Datengruppen von MeteoSchweiz wurden jeweils in ein Pandas Dataframe geladen, bereinigt, Datenquellen ergänzt, die Ortsdaten der einzelnen Wetterstationen von WGS84 nach CH1903+ LV95 projiziert und wiederum als CSV abgespeichert. Alle Daten von MeteoSchweiz wurden dann in ein Dataframe zusammengeführt.

Die Wetterdaten von MeteoOberwallis (Schnidrig 2021) wurden je Station heruntergeladen, von SQL zu CSV transformiert und danach in Dataframes geladen, welche nach einer Bereinigung, Umwandlung US Imperial nach metrischen System, verschiedenen Ergänzungen und Projektion von WGS84 nach CH1903+ (PROJ contributors 2021) auch in einem Dataframe zusammengeführt wurden. Schliesslich wurden alle Wetterdaten der 2 Datenprovider in ein einziges Dataframe zusammengeführt und als CSV gespeichert. Die grosse Datenmenge erforderte eine Verkleinerung der Daten, daher wurden nur die wichtigsten Wetterparameter sowie Zeit und Standort sowie einige weitere Parameter in einem kleineren Dataset als CSV abgespeichert.

In einem weiteren Jupyter Skript wurden die Wetter und GPS-Daten zusammengeführt. Die Wetterdaten wurden zur Interpolation (falls möglich / nötig) auf Meereshöhe transformiert und dann interpoliert. Dies geschah mit selbst geschriebenen Funktionen. Für jeden GPS Punkt des Rotwildes wurde eine «Inverse Distance Weighting» (IDW) Interpolation (GISGeography 2021) durchgeführt. Danach wurden die Daten auf Meereshöhe wieder auf die eigentliche Höhe rücktransformiert. Für die Interpolation wurde der IDW Algorithmus speziell auf die Daten angepasst und als Funktion in Python implementiert. Nach der Rücktransformation wurden die Daten für den nächsten Schritt als CSV abgespeichert.

Für die Analyse wurden die zusammengeführten und interpolierten GPS und Wetterdaten in ein viertes Jupyter Skript als Pandas Dataframe gelesen. Eine erste, direkte, Analyse fand mittels Plots – Matplotlib (Hunter 2007), LAG Plots sowie Seaborn Autokorrelation (Waskom 2021) statt. Die Plots mittels Matplotlib zeigten, dass die vom GPS-Halsband gemessenen Temperaturen sowie Höhendaten nicht immer stimmen konnten (Höhe über Meer bis zu 8500m, Temperatur – 100°C). Die falschen Höhendaten lieferten dadurch eine viel grössere Distanz bzw. Bewegungsgeschwindigkeit. Darum wurden die Höhendaten, wie oben erwähnt, mittels Swisalti3d (Bundesamt für Topographie 2021) und ArcGIS Pro (2D, 3D & 4D GIS Mapping Software | ArcGIS Pro (Version 2.7) 2021) korrigiert. Zuerst wurde das «Digital Elevation Model» (DEM) des Kantons Wallis von Swisstopo heruntergeladen. Mittels ArcGIS Online Portal wurde aus den Polygonen der Schweizer Gemeinden die Gemeinden oberhalb Visp des Kantons Wallis selektiert, zusammengeführt und gebuffert. Nachdem die einzelnen Kacheln des DEM mit dem Oberwallis Buffer Polygon verschnitten wurden, wurden die Kacheln zu einem DEM_Oberwallis zusammengeführt. Die bearbeiteten GPS-Daten wurden in ArcGIS Pro importiert und als x/y-Data dargestellt. Das DEM wurde als Höhe definiert und die x/y GPS-Daten wurden als Punkteabfrage mit den Höhendaten des DEM abgeglichen. Für Tiere, die die Schweiz verliessen, wurden anschliessend in Python die ursprünglichen GPS-Höhendaten genommen. Danach wurden die vorderen 3 Python Scripts noch einmal durchlaufen.

Die mit dem Sensor gemessene Temperatur wurde in «Subzero», «Cold», «Warm» und «Hot» mittels Buckets klassifiziert. Die Temperatur Klassen wurden mit den Bewegungsdistanzen geplottet.

Da aber die Tiere auch indirekt, das heisst mit zeitlicher Verzögerung auf das Wetter reagieren könnten wurden weitere statistische Methoden in Betracht gezogen. Nach einiger Recherchearbeit über Time-Series (Zeitreihen) Analyse kamen folgende Methoden in Betracht: ADF (Cheung und Lai 1995) und KPSS (Kwiatkowski u. a. 1992) Test, Differentiation (Non-Stationary to Stationary), Seaborn Autocorrelation (Waskom 2021), Statsmodels: Granger Causality Test (Seabold und Perktold 2010) sowie zu Testzwecken Machine Learning (Random Forest Regression) (Pedregosa u. a. 2011a). Zudem machte ich zur besseren Visualisierung und Analyse der Daten LAG Plots (Brownlee 2017), Loess Function Plots (Jacoby 2000), Plots Bewegungsgeschwindigkeit vs. Wetterparameter, Bewegungs-geschwindigkeit vs. Zeit (Mittelwerte von: Jahreszeit 4 Season, Jahreszeit Halbjahr, Jahr, Monat, Tage im Jahr, Stunden am Tag, Tageszeit (Dusk, Dawn, Day, Night), sowie Bewegungsgeschwindigkeit vs. Temperaturklassen. Ich fasste die Daten auch in Gruppen (UTC Date and Time, daytime, Stunden im Tag, UTC Date, Months, Days in year, Jahreszeit Halbjahr, Jahreszeit4season) zusammen, berechnete den Durchschnitt, bzw. wo sinnvoll die Gesamtsumme und rechnete danach die statistischen, oben bereits erwähnten Methoden noch einmal je Gruppe.

Einige Methoden und Code-Blöcke wurden von Stackoverflow (Stackoverflow Community 2021) sowie dem Blog towardsdatascience.com (Towards Data Science Authors 2021) adaptiert.

Detaillierte Methoden und MAP Algebra in Appendix C, Code Appendix G

3.1. Download Daten

GPS: ZHAW WILMA / Dienststelle für Jagd, Fischerei und Wildtiere, Kanton Wallis (via E-Mail). MeteoSchweiz – IDAWEB. Meteo Oberwallis www.meteo-oberwallis.ch via Server (SQL Database). DEM Wallis von Swisstopo / Swisalti3d. ArcGIS Online Portal: Gemeinden CH Polygone

3.2. manuelle Datenbereinigung

Mit Notepad ++ wurden die Daten ein erstes Mal bereinigt (einheitliche Nomenklatur der Datenbanken, löschen von Leerzeilen, Vereinheitlichung der CSV Daten, Separator etc.)

3.3. Datacleaning GPS

Python Jupyter Notebook Skript: 01_Rotwildmonitoring_GPS_DataCleaning_FINAL.ipynb
Datacleaning, Aggregation, Merging, Distanzberechnung pro Tier und Stunde, Bewegungsgeschwindigkeit, Plots, Statistiken → Fehlerhafte Höhendaten, Teilweise Extreme Temperatur Daten des Sensors von GPS-Sender.

3.3.1. Projektion nach CH1903+

Die WGS84 Koordinaten (Polarkoordinaten) wurden mittels PYPROJ (PROJ contributors 2021) nach CH1903+ projiziert um kartesische Koordinaten zu erhalten.

3.3.2. Euclidian Distance

Die euklidische Distanz wurde nach folgender Formel ermittelt:

$$d(p, q) = \sqrt{(p_1 - q_1)^2 + (p_2 - q_2)^2 + (p_3 - q_3)^2}$$

Abbildung 4: Euclidian Distance in 3 dimensional space («Euclidean Distance - Wikipedia» 2021)

Das Pandas Dataframe wurde nach TierID und Zeit geordnet. Der jeweils 1. Eintrag je Gruppe wurde Distanz = 0 gesetzt. Danach wurden die jeweils vorderen Koordinaten (CH1903+) mit der aktuellen Reihe in Variablen gespeichert und es folgte die Berechnung der euklidischen Distanz (Betrag des Vektors) im dreidimensionalen Raum.

3.3.3. Umwandlung der Distanz zu Geschwindigkeit

Die errechneten Distanzen wurden umgerechnet zu m/h. Da $v = s \cdot t$ und $s = \text{Distanz}$ und $t = 1h$ Intervalle ergab sich daraus [m/h]. Um später eventuell auch andere Geschwindigkeitsangaben machen zu können wurden die Geschwindigkeiten auch nach SI Standard [m/s] sowie [km/h] umgerechnet.

3.4. Datacleaning Weather Data

Python Jupyter Notebook Skript: 02_Rotwildmonitoring_Weather_Data_final.ipynb
Die Daten von Meteo Schweiz wurden als Parametergruppen mit je eigener CSV Datei in Pandas Dataframes eingelesen und bereinigt. Die Originaldaten wurden aufbereitet und zur späteren Weiterverwendung als CSV abgespeichert, sowohl für die einzelnen Parametergruppen als auch als zusammengeführtes, vollständiges Dataframe.

3.4.1. Datacleaning Meteo Schweiz

Beseitigen von Daten die nur NaN / kein Wert enthalten, Zusammenführen der einzelnen Parameter, CH1903+ und WGS84 Koordinaten.

3.4.2. Datacleaning MeteoOberwallis

Beseitigen von Daten die nur NaN / kein Wert enthalten, Resampling von Minutenintervall auf Stundenintervall

3.4.3. Datamerging Weather Data

Die Meteo Schweiz Daten werden über die Zeit (UTC) mit den Meteo Oberwallis Daten zusammengeführt, dazu werden gewisse Spalten werden umbenannt und vereinheitlicht.

3.5. Berechnungen und Interpolation

Skript: 03_Rotwildmonitoring_Calculations_final.ipynb

3.5.1. Datamerging

Verbindung von GPS und Wetterdaten

3.5.2. Temperatur Höhenformel ASL und AGL

Die verschiedenen Wetterstationen sind auf verschiedenen Höhen, dadurch kann nicht sauber interpoliert werden. Darum werden alle Temperaturdaten zuerst auf Meereshöhe gerechnet. Dies geschieht mit der simplen Formel (ICAO-Temperaturgradient) («Normatmosphäre – Wikipedia» 2021), («Standardatmosphäre – SystemPhysik» 2021):

$$Temp_ASL = (Hoehe_AGL_m * 0.0065) + Temp_2mAGL_C$$

nach der Interpolation (IDW) für jeden GPS Punkt werden die interpolierten Daten wieder auf die entsprechende Höhe über Meer gerechnet: $Temp_AGL = (-1) * (Hoehe_AGL_m * 0.0065) + Temp_2mASL_C$

3.5.3. Taupunkt Berechnung ASL und AGL

Wie bei der Temperatur wird der Taupunkt zuerst für die Meereshöhe berechnet, danach interpoliert und wieder auf die Höhe über Meer gerechnet. Diese Formel ist nur eine Annäherung:

$$dewpoint_ASL = temp_asl - ((100 - rel_hum_percent)/5)$$

$$dewpoint_AGL = dewpoint_asl - (height_agl * 0.0065)$$

dewpoint ASL müsste bei der nächsten Iteration des Projekts evtl korrigiert werden zu:

$$dewpoint_AGL = dewpoint_asl + ((100 - rel_hum_percent)/5) - (height_agl * 0.0065)$$

3.5.4. Barometrische Höhenformel

$$p_0 = p(h) e^{+\frac{Mg}{R \left(T(h) + a \frac{h}{2} \right)} h}$$

Abbildung 5: Barometrische Höhenformel

«Falls eine höhere Genauigkeit gewünscht ist, aktuelle Lufttemperaturen zur Verfügung stehen und Genauigkeit sowie Kalibrierung des verwendeten Barometers den Aufwand rechtfertigen, sollte die Reduktion stets unter Verwendung der aktuellen Lufttemperatur erfolgen. Als Höhenformel bietet sich die Variante für linearen Temperaturverlauf (isotherm) an. (...) Bei den für Wetterstationen üblicherweise vorkommenden Höhen und Temperaturen sind die Unterschiede jedoch völlig unbedeutend.» (Roedel 2000) sowie («Barometrische Höhenformel –

Wikipedia» 2021) Wie auch bei Temperatur und Taupunkt wurde zuerst der Druck auf Meereshöhe berechnet und erst danach interpoliert, danach wurde der Druck, durch auflösen nach $p(h)$ wieder zurück gerechnet. Bildquelle: («Barometrische Höhenformel – Wikipedia» 2021)

3.5.5. Interpolation: Inverse Distance Weighting (IDW)

$$z_p = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n \left(\frac{z_i}{d_i^p} \right)}{\sum_{i=1}^n \left(\frac{1}{d_i^p} \right)}$$

Da eine flächendeckende Interpolation nach einem ersten Test in ArcGIS Pro eine riesige Datenmenge produzieren würde, wurde als Methode die Implementierung des IDW als Algorithmus in Python massgeschneidert auf die zugrunde liegenden Daten gewählt. Dies ermöglichte die Interpolation von rund 350000 Datenpunkten von jeweils 8 Wetterparametern. (GISGeography 2021). Code siehe Appendix G. Bildquelle: (GISGeography 2021)

Abbildung 6: IDW Formel

3.6. Statistik und Auswertung

Skript: 04_Rotwildmonitoring_Statistics_FINAL

Für die Auswertung wurden folgende Methoden gewählt:

Matplotlib Plots (Hunter 2007), Statistik, Loess Function Plots, LAG Plots, ADF und KPSS Test (Stationary / Non Stationary) Test und Granger Causality Test (Seabold und Perktold 2010), Seaborn Autocorrelation + Heatmaps (Waskom 2021). Zu Testzwecken: Random Forest Regression (ML) (Pedregosa u. a. 2011a). Code siehe Appendix G

4. Resultate

Vollständige Resultate im Appendix E und F.

4.1. Direkte Korrelationen

Figure 7: Temperatur [°C] / v

Figure 8: Taupunkt [°C] / v

Figure 9: Globalstrahlung [W/m2] / v

Figure 10: Luftdruck [hPa] / v

Figure 11: Luftdruckänderung [hPa] / v

Figure 12: Luftfeuchtigkeit [%] / v

Figure 13: Niederschlag [mm] / v

Figure 14: Neuschneehöhe [cm] / v

Figure 15: Windgeschwindigkeit [m/s] / v

Figure 16: Sonnenscheindauer [min/h] / v

Figure 17: Durchschnittliche Bewegungsgeschwindigkeit je Temperaturklasse (Subzero: unter 0°C, Cold: 0°C bis 15°C, Warm: 15°C bis 30°C, Hot 30°C ++)

4.2. Granger Causality Test

Der Granger Causality Test (Y trägt zur Vorhersage von X bei), ergab Resultate (p-value < 5%) bei **GPS_Temp (Lag: 0-12h)**, **interpolierter Temperatur (Lag: 5-12h)**, **Sonnenscheindauer (Lag: 3-5h)**, **Luftdruck (Lag: 1h)**, andere Wetterparameter ergaben keine Granger-Kausalität. Die Resultate sind aber nicht als Kausalität im klassischen Sinne zu interpretieren. Zudem wäre eine genauere Analyse und Interpretation der Resultate nötig.

4.3. Seaborn Autocorrelation

Autocorrelation Heatmap (Tabellen im Appendix). Die Autokorrelation wurde mit dem Log-Differentiated (Stationary) Dataframe durchgeführt. GPS_Temp ergab die beste Autokorrelation von **-0.397666863** vs. Geschwindigkeit (dunkel in der Heatmap). Ausserdem hatten Sunshine, Radiatien Korrelationen um 0.1. Alle anderen Parameter hatten Korrelationen noch näher um 0. Der Wertebereich der Autokorrelation ist [-1, 1] wobei -1 einer starke negative und +1 eine starke positive Korrelation entsprechen. Werte um 0 entsprechen keiner Korrelation.

Abbildung 7: Seaborn Autocorrelation: Log-Differentiated, Stationary Autocorrelation

4.4. Zeitliche Muster:

Figure 18: Durchschnittliche Bewegungsgeschwindigkeit [m/h] je Stunde pro Tag

Figure 19: Durchschnittliche Bewegungsgeschwindigkeit [m/h] je Tageszeit [dawn, day, dusk, night]

In der Nacht ist die Bewegungsgeschwindigkeit höher als am Tag, wobei diese bei Dämmerung langsam abnimmt. Der höhere Wert um 0 Uhr müsste noch näher untersucht werden.

Die durchschnittliche Bewegungsgeschwindigkeit je Tageszeit. Am Tag ist diese wesentlich kleiner als in der Nacht.

Figure 20: Durchschnittliche Bewegungsgeschwindigkeit je Saison [Frühling, Herbst, Sommer, Winter]

Figure 21: Durchschnittliche Bewegungsgeschwindigkeit [m/h] je Monat im Jahr

Im Herbst ist die durchschnittliche Bewegungsgeschwindigkeit am höchsten, im Frühling ist diese auch relativ hoch. Im Winter ist die Bewegungsgeschwindigkeit am kleinsten.

Monatliche, Durchschnittliche Bewegungsgeschwindigkeit. Wie auch bei Figure 20 zeigen sich die Peaks im Mai und im Oktober.

4.5. Zu Testzwecken: ML Random Forest Regression

Die mittlere Bewegungsgeschwindigkeit basierend auf Wetterdaten je Stunde wurde mithilfe von Machine Learning (Random Forest Regression) modelliert. Ohne Hyperparametrisierung und bekannte Korrelation kann das Modell so nicht verbessert werden (R^2 Error minimieren). Dennoch versuchte ich herauszufinden, ob es Wetterparameter gab, welche einen grösseren Anteil als andere, an der Vorhersage der Bewegungsgeschwindigkeit hatten. Auch dort leistete die GPS_Temperatur mit 0.24 den höchsten Beitrag. Plots im Appendix E.

5. Interpretation

5.1. Direkte Korrelationen

Ausser bei Einteilung in Temperaturklassen, konnte eine eindeutige, direkte Korrelation zwischen Wetterdaten und Bewegungsgeschwindigkeit nicht festgestellt werden (Siehe Tabelle Plots Fig 5 – 15). Manche Plots haben eine Gaussche Verteilung, andere eine Tendenz zum Minimum oder Maximum. Dies heisst aber nicht, dass eine Korrelation besteht. Luftfeuchtigkeit z.B. ist fast nie (in unseren Breitengraden) 0%, daher können hier auch keine Werte liegen.

Figure 15: Durchschnittliche Bewegungsgeschwindigkeit je Temperaturklasse (Subzero: unter 0°C, Cold: 0°C bis 15°C, Warm: 15°C bis 30°C, Hot 30°C ++)

Mit der Einteilung in Temperaturklassen konnte eine Aussage gewonnen werden (Siehe Fig. 15). Das Rotwild bewegt sich zwischen 0 bis 15° C am schnellsten bzw. weitesten. Ab 30°C bewegt es sich am langsamsten bzw. am wenigsten weit. Dies wird weiter mit der Seaborn Autokorrelation von -0.397666863 (GPS_Temp vs. Velocity) bestätigt. Auch ist dies kongruent mit den zeitlichen Plots (in der Nacht ist es kälter als am Tag). Ob die Temperatur die Geschwindigkeit verursacht oder ob umgekehrt die zeitlichen Muster die Temperaturen verursachen, kann nicht gesagt werden.

Figure 17: Durchschnittliche Bewegungsgeschwindigkeit [m/h] je Tageszeit [dawn, day, dusk, night]

Die zeitlichen Muster waren eindeutig (mehr Resultate im Appendix): Fig. 17 zeigt, dass das Rotwild bewegt sich in der Dämmerung und in der Nacht schneller/weiter als am Tag. Rotwild ist heutzutage tagaktiv, hat sich aber durch den Einfluss des Menschen angepasst und ist nun mehrheitlich nachtaktiv.

Figure 18: Durchschnittliche Bewegungsgeschwindigkeit je Saison [Frühling, Herbst, Sommer, Winter]

Auch Fig 18 lässt sich durch den Wechsel von den Sommer- zu den Wintereinständen bzw. umgekehrt erklären. Literatur: (Baumann 2019).

5.2. Granger Kausalität mit Verzögerung

Granger Kausalität bedeutet nur, dass eine Abhängigkeit bestehen kann, nicht muss. Die Interpretation der Resultate ist schwierig und erfordert sicherlich in der Zukunft vertiefte Analysen. Ein wichtiger Faktor ist dabei die Entfernung von Trends und Saisonalitäten. Die meisten Wetterdaten wiesen keine Granger Kausalität mit einem p-Wert kleiner 5% auf. Die Parameter **GPS_Temp (Lag: 0-12h)**, **interpolierter Temperatur (Lag: 5-12h)** und **Luftdruck (Lag 1h)** wiesen einen p-Wert kleiner 5% auf. Dies ist kongruent mit den anderen Resultaten. Vollständige Resultate im Appendix E und F.

5.3. Korrelation

Die Seaborn Autokorrelation ergab erst brauchbare Werte nach einer Entfernung der Saisonalität und Trends (Log Differentiation). Auch dieses Resultat (**-0.397666863**) bei GPS_Temp ist kongruent mit den Plots. Dass bei der interpolierten Temperatur eine viel geringere Korrelation herauskam, kann verschiedene Gründe haben: Da der GPS-Temperatursensor eher die gefühlte Temperatur (Windchill + direkte Sonnenstrahlung) und nicht wie die von Stationen gemessene Temperatur (Schatten, 2m über Boden) misst, ist der GPS-Sensor näher an der gefühlten Temperatur als an einer theoretischen Temperatur wie zur einheitlichen Messung des Wetters. Die Temperatur korreliert negativ mit der Bewegungsgeschwindigkeit. Dennoch gilt es zu beachten, dass die Bewegungsgeschwindigkeit mit Minus-Temperaturen abnimmt (siehe Temp Class Plot) und dadurch nicht eine hohe Korrelation erreicht werden kann. Auch ist die IDW Interpolation und Anzahl Messstationen nicht ideal. Ein noch besseres Ergebnis mit dem GPS-Temperatursensor hätte man sicherlich dadurch erzielen können, wenn man 2 unabhängige Sensoren verwendet hätte (Fehler von Sensor, technischer Error, unmögliche Werte v.a. im unter Null-Bereich). Vollständige Resultate im Appendix E und F

6. Fazit und Ausblick

Faktoren wie Zeit, Verhalten oder menschliche Störungen der Tiere haben einen grösseren Einfluss als Wetterdaten. So konnten keine Trends erkannt werden. Ob die Temperatur die Bewegungsgeschwindigkeit beeinflusst oder ob das nachtaktive Verhalten tiefer gemessene Temperaturen ergibt, konnte nicht eruiert werden.

In Zukunft wäre es eventuell sinnvoll, die GPS-Daten mittels Agnes / PPK zu korrigieren, das heisst, der Einfluss von Sonnenwinden bzw. der Sonne nachträglich zu korrigieren. Auch ein redundantes System zur Temperaturmessung wäre hilfreich.

Mögliche Fehlerquellen bei dieser Abschlussarbeit waren:

- Vollständiger GPS-Datensatz war erst nach dem Abschluss des Projekts verfügbar → Fehlende Daten und Kontinuität.
- Interpolation mittels IDW zu ungenau → andere Interpolationsmethoden in Betracht ziehen wie zB. Bayesian Kriging Interpolation.
- Die euklidische Distanz zwischen 2 Messpunkten ist nicht die wahre, zurückgelegte Strecke → als Annäherung der wirklichen Strecke die Rohdaten (5min Intervalle) benutzen und danach Resampling.
- fehlende Wetterdaten → Interpolation oder Machine Learning (Franco, Hernández-Callejo, und Navas-Gracia 2020)
- falsche Wahl der Methoden? → IDW Interpolation ist sicherlich nicht ideal. Die Time Series Analyse beruht oft auf linearer Regression, hier hätte evtl nichtlineare Regression, welche aufwändiger ist, bessere Resultate geliefert.
- Random Forest Regression in Time Series: Hyperparametrisierung konnte nicht gemacht werden, da Korrelation unbekannt. Die Arbeit mit Time Series im Bereich ML hat viele Stolpersteine (Flovik 2021).
- Fehler in der Datenverarbeitung? → gründliche Überprüfung des Codes
- Systemische Fehler → Sensoren, GPS, Datenverarbeitung

In der Zukunft sollten folgende Methoden in Betracht gezogen werden:

- Cross Validation
- Multivariate Time Series Analysis mit Machine Learning Modellen, zB. **Reservoir Computing** («What is Reservoir Computing? — ReservoirPy 0.2.2 documentation» o. J.). Da die Wetterdaten mehrere Parameter haben die zur Bewegungsgeschwindigkeit beitragen (multivariate analysis) und eventuell nonlinear zu den Bewegungsdaten korrelieren, müssen andere Methoden in Betracht gezogen werden (Runge u. a. 2019).

Insgesamt war diese Abschlussarbeit ein sehr spannendes Projekt. Mir wurde die Komplexität von Time Series Analysis und Wetterdaten bewusster. Der bekannte Ausdruck «Korrelation ist nicht Kausalität» kam auch hier zum Tragen.

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8. Appendix

8.1. Appendix A: Daten

8.1.1. GPS Rohdaten Parameter

- TierID: Identität des einzelnen Rothirschs
- No: Anzahl Positionserhebungen seit Besenderung
- CollarID: Halsbandnummer
- UTC_Date: Datumsangabe (nach UTC Zeit)
- UTC_Time: Zeitangabe in UTC
- LMT_Date: Datumsangabe (nach Local Mean Time = MEZ (Winterzeit))
- LMT_Time: Local Mean Time = MEZ (Winterzeit)
- Latitude: Breitengrad [°]
- Longitude: Längengrad [°]
- Height: Höhe über Meer [m]
- DOP: Dilution of precision = Mass für die Genauigkeit der gemessenen GPS-Position
- FixType: Art der gemessenen GPS-Position (je nach Verfügbarkeit der Satelliten)
- Temp: Temperatur gemessen im Halsband [°C]
- timestamp: Zeitstempel aus UTC_Date und UTC_Time
- x: X-Koordinaten → keine Angabe zur Einheit vermutlich CH1903 → darum Konvertierung der WGS84 Daten zu EPSG2056
- y: Y-Koordinaten → keine Angabe zur Einheit vermutlich CH1903 → darum Konvertierung der WGS84 Daten zu EPSG2056
- Einstand_2month: (01.07. - 31.08. = Sommereinstand / 01.01 - 28.02 = Wintereinstand)
- Jahreszeit_4season: Unterteilung der 4 saisonalen Jahreszeiten im Rothirschprojekt (gemäss UTC_Date), welche wie folgt definiert wurden: winter: 16. Nov - 15. Mar, frühling: 16. Mar - 15. Mai, sommer: 16. Mai - 15. Sep, herbst: 16. Sep - 15. Nov
- Jahreszeit_Halbjahr: Unterteilung in saisonale Halbjahre im Rothirschprojekt (gemäss UTC_Date), welche wie folgt definiert wurden: winterhalbjahr: 16. Okt - 15. Apr, sommerhalbjahr: 16. Apr - 15. Okt
- twilight_dawn: Zeitpunkt Morgendämmerung nach Winterzeit (Sonne 6° unter Horizont, Start Civiltwilight)
- sunrise: Zeitpunkt Sonnenaufgang nach Winterzeit
- sunset: Zeitpunkt Sonnenuntergang nach Winterzeit
- twilight_dusk: Zeitpunkt Abenddämmerung nach Winterzeit (Sonne 6° unter Horizont, End Civiltwilight)
- daytime: Tageszeit nach tageszeitlichen Phasen eingeteilt: night: twilight_dusk + 1h bis twilight_dawn - 1h, dawn: twilight_dawn - 1h bis twilight_dawn + 1h, day: twilight_dawn + 1h bis twilight_dusk - 1h, dusk: twilight_dusk - 1h bis twilight_dusk + 1h
- year: Jahr nach UTC_Date
- Projektjahr: Unterteilung des Datensatzes (gemäss UTC_Date) in Projektjahre: 1: 16. Nov. 2017 - 15. Nov. 2018, 2: 16. Nov. 2018 - 15. Nov. 2019, 3: 16. Nov. 2019 - 15. Nov. 2020

Ergänzung Aktivitätsdaten (ACT):

Aktivitätsdaten werden im Halsband in 5min-Intervallen erhoben; pro 5min-Intervall wird jeweils ein Messwert für den Sensor in X-Richtung (ActivityX) und den Sensor in Y-Richtung (ActivityY) generiert. Für die Zusammenführung von GPS- und ACT-Daten werden ActivityX und ActivityY jeweils im Zeitraum 30 min vor bis 30 min nach jeder vollen Stunde wie folgt gemittelt und der stündlichen GPS-Position zugewiesen:

- ActivitySum: (Summe aller ActivityX- und ActivityY-Werte pro Stunde)/2
- Components: Anzahl 5min-Intervalle, welche zur Berechnung von ActivitySum herbeigezogen werden (für eine volle Stunde demnach normalerweise 12 Components)
- ActivityMean: ActivitySum/Components --> ergibt mittleren Aktivitätswert aller 5min-Intervalle pro Stunde

8.1.2. Final Dataframe: Rotwildmonitoring_FINAL.csv

```
<class 'pandas.core.frame.DataFrame'>
```

```
RangIndex: 333993 entries, 0 to 333992
```

```
Data columns (total 85 columns):
```

#	Column	Non-Null Count	Dtype
0	Day	333993 non-null	float64
1	GPS_Abgeschlossen	333993 non-null	object
2	GPS_ActivityMean	333993 non-null	float64
3	GPS_ActivitySum	333993 non-null	float64
4	GPS_CollarID	333993 non-null	int64
5	GPS_Components	333993 non-null	float64
6	GPS_DEM_Height_Difference	333993 non-null	float64
7	GPS_DISTANCE_ABSOLUTE	333993 non-null	float64
8	GPS_DISTANCE_X	333993 non-null	float64
9	GPS_DISTANCE_Y	333993 non-null	float64
10	GPS_DISTANCE_Z	333993 non-null	float64
11	GPS_DOP	333993 non-null	float64
12	GPS_DatenEndeMonat	333993 non-null	object
13	GPS_EPSG2056_lat	333993 non-null	float64
14	GPS_EPSG2056_lon	333993 non-null	float64

15	GPS_Einstand_2month	333993	non-null	object
16	GPS_FixType	333993	non-null	object
17	GPS_Hoehe_AS_L_m	333993	non-null	float64
18	GPS_Hoehe_AS_L_m_DEM	333993	non-null	float64
19	GPS_No	333993	non-null	int64
20	GPS_Start2Datum	333993	non-null	object
21	GPS_Start2Jahr	333993	non-null	object
22	GPS_Start2Monat	333993	non-null	object
23	GPS_StartDatum	333993	non-null	object
24	GPS_StartJahr	333993	non-null	int64
25	GPS_StartMonat	333993	non-null	object
26	GPS_Status	297070	non-null	object
27	GPS_Status2	81774	non-null	object
28	GPS_Stop2Datum	333993	non-null	object
29	GPS_Stop2Jahr	333993	non-null	object
30	GPS_Stop2Monat	333993	non-null	object
31	GPS_StopDatum	333993	non-null	object
32	GPS_StopJahr	333993	non-null	int64
33	GPS_StopMonat	333993	non-null	object
34	GPS_Temp	333976	non-null	float64
35	GPS_Temp_Class	333976	non-null	object
36	GPS_TierID	333993	non-null	object
37	GPS_Tier_Gebiet	333993	non-null	object
38	GPS_Tier_Geschlecht	333993	non-null	object
39	GPS_Tier_Name	333993	non-null	object
40	GPS_Tier_Ohrmarke	333993	non-null	object
41	GPS_Unix_Timestamp	333993	non-null	int64
42	GPS_V_KMproH	333993	non-null	float64
43	GPS_V_MproH	333993	non-null	float64
44	GPS_V_MproS	333993	non-null	float64
45	GPS_WGS84_Breite	333993	non-null	float64
46	GPS_WGS84_Laenge	333993	non-null	float64
47	GPS_sunrise_cleaned	333993	non-null	float64
48	GPS_sunset_cleaned	333993	non-null	float64
49	GPS_timestamp_cleaned	333993	non-null	float64
50	GPS_twilight_dawn_cleaned	333993	non-null	float64
51	GPS_twilight_dusk_cleaned	333993	non-null	float64
52	GPS_x	333993	non-null	int64
53	GPS_y	333993	non-null	int64
54	Hour	333993	non-null	float64
55	INTERPOL_POINT_Foehnindex	65107	non-null	float64
56	INTERPOL_POINT_Globalstrahlung_wm2	210928	non-null	float64
57	INTERPOL_POINT_Luftdruckaenderung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa	210928	non-null	float64
58	INTERPOL_POINT_Neuschnee_Momentanwert_cm	10197	non-null	float64
59	INTERPOL_POINT_Niederschlag_Stundensumme_mm	210928	non-null	float64
60	INTERPOL_POINT_Schneehoehe_Momentanwert_cm	0	non-null	float64
61	INTERPOL_POINT_Windgeschwindigkeit_ms	210928	non-null	float64
62	INTERPOL_POINT_Windrichtung_grad	210928	non-null	float64
63	INTERPOL_POINT_dewpoint_AGL_C	210928	non-null	float64
64	INTERPOL_POINT_dewpoint_AGL_C_CALCULATED	210928	non-null	float64
65	INTERPOL_POINT_dewpoint_AS_L_C	210928	non-null	float64
66	INTERPOL_POINT_pressure_AGL_hPa	210928	non-null	float64
67	INTERPOL_POINT_pressure_AGL_hPa_CALCULATED	210928	non-null	float64
68	INTERPOL_POINT_pressure_asl_hPa	210928	non-null	float64
69	INTERPOL_POINT_rel_Luftfeuchtigkeit_Stundenmittel_prozent	210928	non-null	float64
70	INTERPOL_POINT_sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min	210928	non-null	float64
71	INTERPOL_POINT_temp_AGL_C	210928	non-null	float64
72	INTERPOL_POINT_temp_AGL_C_CALCULATED	210928	non-null	float64
73	INTERPOL_POINT_temp_asl_C	210928	non-null	float64
74	Jahreszeit_4season	333993	non-null	object
75	Jahreszeit_Halbjahr	333993	non-null	object
76	LMT_Date	333993	non-null	object
77	LMT_Time	333993	non-null	object
78	Month	333993	non-null	float64
79	UTC	333993	non-null	object
80	UTC1	333993	non-null	object
81	UTC_Date	333993	non-null	object
82	UTC_Time	333993	non-null	object
83	daytime	333993	non-null	object
84	year	333993	non-null	int64

dtypes: float64(46), int64(8), object(31)
memory usage: 216.6+ MB

8.2. Appendix B: konzeptionelles Datenmodell

Abbildung 8: Konzeptionelles Datenmodell, detaillierte Ansicht in Appendix B

Appendix C: kartografisches Modell / Methoden

8.3. Appendix C; Map Algebra

MAP ALGEBRA: Python Jupyter Notebook: 01_Rotwildmonitoring_GPS_DataCleaning_final_02

MAP ALGEBRA: Python Jupyter Notebook: 02_Rotwildmonitoring_Weather_Data_final 1

MAP ALGEBRA: Python Jupyter Notebook: 02_Rotwildmonitoring_Weather_Data_final 2

MAP ALGEBRA: Python Jupyter Notebook: 03_Rotwildmonitoring_Calculations_final

MAP ALGEBRA: Python Jupyter Notebook: 04_Rotwildmonitoring_Statistics_final

8.4. Appendix D: Libraries

OS– Part of the standard library. This module provides a portable way of using operating system dependent functionality. (Van Rossum und Drake Jr 1995), (Van Rossum 2020)

ipyparallel – Multiprocessing for Python. (IPython 2015)

pandas – is a fast, powerful, flexible and easy to use open source data analysis and manipulation tool. (The pandas development team 2020)

numpy – Arrays (Harris u. a. 2020)

gc – Garbage Collector (Van Rossum 2020)

time – Time Acces and Conversions (Van Rossum 2020)

multiprocess – Process-based Parallelism (Van Rossum 2020)

platform - Access to underlying platform's identifying data (Van Rossum 2020)

geopandas - GeoPandas is an open source project to make working with geospatial data in python easier. (Jordahl 2014)

shapely - (Gillies und others 2007)

pyreproj - Python interface to PROJ4 (cartographic projections and coordinate transformations library) (PROJ contributors 2021)

pyproj - Python interface to PROJ4 (cartographic projections and coordinate transformations library) (PROJ contributors 2021)

collections – Container Datatypes (Van Rossum 2020)

ogr - (GRASS Development Team 2017)

osr - (GRASS Development Team 2017)

osgeo - (GRASS Development Team 2017)

math - (Van Rossum 2020)

itertools - (Van Rossum 2020)

sklearn / scikit learn – Machine Learning Library (Pedregosa u. a. 2011b)

matplotlib - Plots (Hunter 2007)

seaborn - (Waskom 2021)

8.5. Appendix E: Grafiken, Plots

8.5.1. Plots

Abbildung 9: Durchschnittliche Bewegungsgeschwindigkeit pro Tier (Mean und STD)

Abbildung 10: Durchschnittliche Bewegungsgeschwindigkeit pro Tag (blau) vs. Durchschnittliche Interpolierte Temperatur pro Tag (orange)

Abbildung 11: durchschnittliche Bewegungsgeschwindigkeit [m/h] je Tag im Jahr

Abbildung 12: WGS84 Plot GPS Koordinaten

Abbildung 13: CH1903+ Plot projizierte Koordinaten

Abbildung 14: GPS Sensoren: GPS Temp vs. GPS Height

Abbildung 15: GPS Temp Sensor vs Höhe DEM

Abbildung 16: GPS Correlation Heatmap (Raw Data)

Abbildung 17: obviously unsuccessfull Linear Regression

Regression Coefficient -4.18162008
 Mean Square Error: V_MproH 663607.629455
 Regression Score: 0.0012495092146390663

Abbildung 18: Durchschnittliche Bewegungsgeschwindigkeit je Tageszeit

Abbildung 19: Durchschnittliche Bewegungsgeschwindigkeit je Temperaturklasse

Interpolierte Temperatur IDW vs GPS Temperatur

Abbildung 20: Interpolierte Temperatur vs GPS Sensor Temperatur

GPS Höhe vs GPS Temperatur (mit fehlerhaften Daten)

Abbildung 21: GPS Höhe (raw) vs GPS Temperatur (beschnitten bei - 20 °C)

DEM Höhe vs interpolierte Temperatur

Abbildung 22: Höhe DEM vs. interpolierte Temperatur

Abbildung 23: Temperatur [°C] vs Bewegungsgeschwindigkeit [m/h]

Abbildung 24: Taupunkt [°C] vs Bewegungsgeschwindigkeit [m/h]

Abbildung 26: Globalstrahlung [W/m²] vs Bewegungsgeschwindigkeit [m/h]

Abbildung 25: Luftdruck [hPa] vs Bewegungsgeschwindigkeit [m/h]

Abbildung 27: Luftdruckänderung [hPa] vs Bewegungsgeschwindigkeit [m/h]

Abbildung 28: Luftfeuchtigkeit [%] vs Bewegungsgeschwindigkeit [m/h]

Abbildung 29: Niederschlag [mm/h] vs Bewegungsgeschwindigkeit [m/h]

Abbildung 30: Neuschnee Momentanwert [cm] vs. Bewegungsgeschwindigkeit [m/h]

Abbildung 31: Schneehöhe Momentanwert [cm] vs. Bewegungsgeschwindigkeit [m/h]

Abbildung 32: Windgeschwindigkeit [m/s] vs. Bewegungsgeschwindigkeit [m/h]

Abbildung 33: Windrichtung [°] vs. Bewegungsgeschwindigkeit [m/h]

Abbildung 34: Sonnenscheindauer (Strahlung > 120 W/m²) [min/h] vs. Bewegungsgeschwindigkeit [m/h]

8.5.2. Bewegungsgeschwindigkeit und Wetterparameter vs. UTC

Abbildung 35: $x = \text{UTC}$, $y = \text{Bewegungsgeschwindigkeit (rot) und Wetterparameter (blau)}$

8.5.3. Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Monat im Jahr

Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Monat im Jahr

Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Monat im Jahr

Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Monat im Jahr

Durchschnittliche Geschwindigkeit pro Monat

8.5.4. Bar Plots

Durchschnittliche Geschwindigkeit pro Temperaturklasse

Durchschnittliche Geschwindigkeit pro Tageszeit

Durchschnittliche Geschwindigkeit pro Geschlecht

Durchschnittliche Geschwindigkeit pro Gebiet

8.5.5. Lag Plots

Lag Plots plotten $y(t)$ vs. $y(t+1)$

Die Linearen Artefakte sind durch backward/forward fill der fehlenden Daten entstanden und können für die Lag Plots ignoriert werden.

LAG Plot IDW Humidity

LAG Plot IDW Niederschlag

LAG Plot IDW Globalstrahlung

LAG Plot IDW Sonnenscheindauer

LAG Plot IDW Windgeschwindigkeit

LAG Plot IDW Windrichtung

8.5.6. Seaborn Autocorrelation Plots:

8.5.6.1. Raw Data Autocorrelation Heatmap

8.5.6.2. Hourly Mean Autocorrelation Heatmap

8.5.6.3. Differentiated (Stationary) Hourly Mean Autocorrelation Heatmap

8.5.7. Random Forest Regression (Test):

9. Appendix F: Tabellen Resultate

9.1.1.1. Height Difference DEM vs. GPS Height:

Count 334215.000000
mean 43.899491
std 49.941148
min -2857.855039
25% 15.986860
50% 50.990044
75% 57.919454
max 6057.230215

9.1.1.2. Mean and STD per Gender

m: 157.2019695494007 (mean m/h) 823.1222705023221 std m/h 0.0 (min m/h) 31530.696913656906 max m/h
w: 151.8102035794299 (mean m/h) 810.9492737586636 std m/h 0.0 (min m/h) 31530.696913656906 max m/h

Geschlecht	Mean_V_MproH_perGender	STD_V_MproH_perGender	MIN_V_MproH_perGender	MAX_V_MproH_perGender
m	157.201969549401	823.122270502322	0	31530.6969136569
w	151.81020357943	810.949273758664	0	34344.9606135697

9.1.1.3. GPS Temp Stats

count 334192.000000
mean 14.245910
std 6.890536
min -14.000000
25% 9.000000
50% 14.000000
75% 19.000000
max 51.000000

9.1.1.4. Scipy:

DescribeResult(nobs=334192, minmax=(-14.0, 51.0), mean=14.245909537032604, variance=47.47948301521322, skewness=0.17406116213940376, kurtosis=-0.1067917735684989)

9.1.1.5. GPS V_MproH Stats

count 334192.000000
mean 153.644757
std 815.131792
min 0.000000
25% 15.848791
50% 43.590154
75% 125.824855
max 34344.960614

9.1.1.6. Scipy:

DescribeResult(nobs=334192, minmax=(0.0, 34344.960613569725), mean=153.64475724343734, variance=664439.8388699949, skewness=24.63519681237272, kurtosis=746.227556753812)
Granger Causality Test

9.1.1.7. ADF and KPSS Test

number of lags (no zero) 1
ssr based F test: F=17.4053 , p=0.0000 , df_denom=19122, df_num=1
ssr based chi2 test: chi2=17.4080 , p=0.0000 , df=1
likelihood ratio test: chi2=17.4001 , p=0.0000 , df=1
parameter F test: F=17.4053 , p=0.0000 , df_denom=19122, df_num=1

9.1.1.8. ADF und KPSS Test (Stationary / Non Stationary)

GPS_V_MproH

KPSS Statistic: 0.26762234537519375

p-value: 0.1

num lags: 44

Critical Values:

10% : 0.347

5% : 0.463

2.5% : 0.574

1% : 0.739

GPS_Temp

KPSS Statistic: 1.0734141311213057

p-value: 0.01

num lags: 44

Critical Values:

10% : 0.347

5% : 0.463

2.5% : 0.574

1% : 0.739

INTERPOL_POINT_Foehnindex

KPSS Statistic: 4.877432394050653

p-value: 0.01

num lags: 44

Critical Values:

10% : 0.347

5% : 0.463

2.5% : 0.574

1% : 0.739

INTERPOL_POINT_Globalstrahlung_wm2

KPSS Statistic: 0.21731571858665685

p-value: 0.1

num lags: 44

Critical Values:

10% : 0.347

5% : 0.463

2.5% : 0.574

1% : 0.739

INTERPOL_POINT_pressure_AGL_hPa_CALCULATED

KPSS Statistic: 6.653963599199495

p-value: 0.01

num lags: 44

Critical Values:

10% : 0.347

5% : 0.463

2.5% : 0.574

1% : 0.739

INTERPOL_POINT_Luftdruckaenderung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa

KPSS Statistic: 0.3290291422881528

p-value: 0.1

num lags: 44

Critical Values:

10% : 0.347

5% : 0.463

2.5% : 0.574

1% : 0.739

INTERPOL_POINT_temp_AGL_C_CALCULATED

KPSS Statistic: 1.8682227812106973

p-value: 0.01

num lags: 44

Critical Values:

10% : 0.347

5% : 0.463

2.5% : 0.574

1% : 0.739

INTERPOL_POINT_dewpoint_AGL_C_CALCULATED

KPSS Statistic: 3.8967865436668365

p-value: 0.01

num lags: 44

Critical Values:

10% : 0.347

5% : 0.463

2.5% : 0.574

1% : 0.739

INTERPOL_POINT_rel_Luftfeuchtigkeit_Stundenmittel_prozent

KPSS Statistic: 1.053137987925712

p-value: 0.01

num lags: 44

Critical Values:

10% : 0.347

5% : 0.463

2.5% : 0.574

1% : 0.739

INTERPOL_POINT_sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min

KPSS Statistic: 0.801880929884717

p-value: 0.01

num lags: 44

Critical Values:

10% : 0.347

5% : 0.463

2.5% : 0.574

1% : 0.739

9.1.1.9. Granger Causality GPS Temp

GPS_V_MproH_log_diff

ADF Statistic: -7.648233666788947

p-value: 1.8183522268483132e-11

Critical Values:

1%, -3.4307242852745428

Critical Values:

5%, -2.8617054196196627

Critical Values:

10%, -2.566858048572343

KPSS Statistic: 1.073414

p-value: 0.010000

Critical Values:
 10%, 0.347
 Critical Values:
 5%, 0.463
 Critical Values:
 2.5%, 0.574
 Critical Values:
 1%, 0.739

GPS_Temp_log_diff

Granger Causality GPS Temp (Y) to predict GPS_V_MproH (X)

number of lags (no zero) 1
 ssr based F test: F=254.6210, p=0.0000 , df_denom=17449, df_num=1
 ssr based chi2 test: chi2=254.6648, p=0.0000 , df=1
 likelihood ratio test: chi2=252.8246, p=0.0000 , df=1
 parameter F test: F=254.6210, p=0.0000 , df_denom=17449, df_num=1

Granger Causality

number of lags (no zero) 2
 ssr based F test: F=215.0192, p=0.0000 , df_denom=17446, df_num=2
 ssr based chi2 test: chi2=430.1616, p=0.0000 , df=2
 likelihood ratio test: chi2=424.9455, p=0.0000 , df=2
 parameter F test: F=215.0192, p=0.0000 , df_denom=17446, df_num=2

Granger Causality

number of lags (no zero) 3
 ssr based F test: F=200.2096, p=0.0000 , df_denom=17443, df_num=3
 ssr based chi2 test: chi2=600.8700, p=0.0000 , df=3
 likelihood ratio test: chi2=590.7564, p=0.0000 , df=3
 parameter F test: F=200.2096, p=0.0000 , df_denom=17443, df_num=3

Granger Causality

number of lags (no zero) 4
 ssr based F test: F=184.2343, p=0.0000 , df_denom=17440, df_num=4
 ssr based chi2 test: chi2=737.3175, p=0.0000 , df=4
 likelihood ratio test: chi2=722.1650, p=0.0000 , df=4
 parameter F test: F=184.2343, p=0.0000 , df_denom=17440, df_num=4

Granger Causality

number of lags (no zero) 5
 ssr based F test: F=161.9751, p=0.0000 , df_denom=17437, df_num=5
 ssr based chi2 test: chi2=810.3862, p=0.0000 , df=5
 likelihood ratio test: chi2=792.1298, p=0.0000 , df=5
 parameter F test: F=161.9751, p=0.0000 , df_denom=17437, df_num=5

Granger Causality

number of lags (no zero) 6
 ssr based F test: F=142.1981, p=0.0000 , df_denom=17434, df_num=6
 ssr based chi2 test: chi2=853.8248, p=0.0000 , df=6
 likelihood ratio test: chi2=833.5900, p=0.0000 , df=6
 parameter F test: F=142.1981, p=0.0000 , df_denom=17434, df_num=6

Granger Causality

number of lags (no zero) 7
ssr based F test: F=125.1375, p=0.0000 , df_denom=17431, df_num=7
ssr based chi2 test: chi2=876.7166, p=0.0000 , df=7
likelihood ratio test: chi2=855.3990, p=0.0000 , df=7
parameter F test: F=125.1375, p=0.0000 , df_denom=17431, df_num=7

Granger Causality

number of lags (no zero) 8
ssr based F test: F=113.3711, p=0.0000 , df_denom=17428, df_num=8
ssr based chi2 test: chi2=907.8532, p=0.0000 , df=8
likelihood ratio test: chi2=885.0194, p=0.0000 , df=8
parameter F test: F=113.3711, p=0.0000 , df_denom=17428, df_num=8

Granger Causality

number of lags (no zero) 9
ssr based F test: F=103.2710, p=0.0000 , df_denom=17425, df_num=9
ssr based chi2 test: chi2=930.4521, p=0.0000 , df=9
likelihood ratio test: chi2=906.4857, p=0.0000 , df=9
parameter F test: F=103.2710, p=0.0000 , df_denom=17425, df_num=9

Granger Causality

number of lags (no zero) 10
ssr based F test: F=94.4937 , p=0.0000 , df_denom=17422, df_num=10
ssr based chi2 test: chi2=946.0761, p=0.0000 , df=10
likelihood ratio test: chi2=921.3110, p=0.0000 , df=10
parameter F test: F=94.4937 , p=0.0000 , df_denom=17422, df_num=10

Granger Causality

number of lags (no zero) 11
ssr based F test: F=86.3568 , p=0.0000 , df_denom=17419, df_num=11
ssr based chi2 test: chi2=951.1788, p=0.0000 , df=11
likelihood ratio test: chi2=926.1491, p=0.0000 , df=11
parameter F test: F=86.3568 , p=0.0000 , df_denom=17419, df_num=11

Granger Causality

number of lags (no zero) 12
ssr based F test: F=79.7318 , p=0.0000 , df_denom=17416, df_num=12
ssr based chi2 test: chi2=958.1553, p=0.0000 , df=12
likelihood ratio test: chi2=932.7621, p=0.0000 , df=12
parameter F test: F=79.7318 , p=0.0000 , df_denom=17416, df_num=12

9.1.1.10. Granger Causality: INTERPOL_POINT_temp_AGL_C_CALCULATED

GPS_V_MproH_log_diff

INTERPOL_POINT_temp_AGL_C_CALCULATED

ADF Statistic: -11.27730595928231

p-value: 1.485603089929904e-20

Critical Values:

1%, -3.4307242424340445

Critical Values:

5%, -2.861705400687012

Critical Values:

10%, -2.566858038494777

KPSS Statistic: 1.868223

p-value: 0.010000

Critical Values:

10%, 0.347

Critical Values:

5%, 0.463

Critical Values:

2.5%, 0.574

Critical Values:

1%, 0.739

INTERPOL_POINT_temp_AGL_C_CALCULATED_log_diff

Granger Causality INTERPOL_POINT_temp_AGL_C_CALCULATED_log_diff (Y) to predict GPS_V_MproH (X)

number of lags (no zero) 1

ssr based F test: F=2.4084 , p=0.1207 , df_denom=17381, df_num=1
ssr based chi2 test: chi2=2.4089 , p=0.1207 , df=1
likelihood ratio test: chi2=2.4087 , p=0.1207 , df=1
parameter F test: F=2.4084 , p=0.1207 , df_denom=17381, df_num=1

Granger Causality

number of lags (no zero) 2

ssr based F test: F=2.8230 , p=0.0595 , df_denom=17378, df_num=2
ssr based chi2 test: chi2=5.6476 , p=0.0594 , df=2
likelihood ratio test: chi2=5.6467 , p=0.0594 , df=2
parameter F test: F=2.8230 , p=0.0595 , df_denom=17378, df_num=2

Granger Causality

number of lags (no zero) 3

ssr based F test: F=1.9614 , p=0.1174 , df_denom=17375, df_num=3
ssr based chi2 test: chi2=5.8866 , p=0.1173 , df=3
likelihood ratio test: chi2=5.8856 , p=0.1173 , df=3
parameter F test: F=1.9614 , p=0.1174 , df_denom=17375, df_num=3

Granger Causality

number of lags (no zero) 4

ssr based F test: F=1.6837 , p=0.1506 , df_denom=17372, df_num=4
ssr based chi2 test: chi2=6.7385 , p=0.1504 , df=4
likelihood ratio test: chi2=6.7372 , p=0.1504 , df=4
parameter F test: F=1.6837 , p=0.1506 , df_denom=17372, df_num=4

Granger Causality

number of lags (no zero) 5

ssr based F test: F=2.8577 , p=0.0139 , df_denom=17369, df_num=5
ssr based chi2 test: chi2=14.2973 , p=0.0138 , df=5
likelihood ratio test: chi2=14.2915 , p=0.0139 , df=5
parameter F test: F=2.8577 , p=0.0139 , df_denom=17369, df_num=5

Granger Causality

number of lags (no zero) 6

ssr based F test: F=3.0941 , p=0.0050 , df_denom=17366, df_num=6
ssr based chi2 test: chi2=18.5783 , p=0.0049 , df=6
likelihood ratio test: chi2=18.5684 , p=0.0050 , df=6
parameter F test: F=3.0941 , p=0.0050 , df_denom=17366, df_num=6

Granger Causality

number of lags (no zero) 7

ssr based F test: F=2.6551 , p=0.0096 , df_denom=17363, df_num=7
ssr based chi2 test: chi2=18.6016 , p=0.0095 , df=7
likelihood ratio test: chi2=18.5917 , p=0.0096 , df=7
parameter F test: F=2.6551 , p=0.0096 , df_denom=17363, df_num=7

Granger Causality

number of lags (no zero) 8

ssr based F test: F=2.2779 , p=0.0197 , df_denom=17360, df_num=8
ssr based chi2 test: chi2=18.2412 , p=0.0195 , df=8
likelihood ratio test: chi2=18.2317 , p=0.0196 , df=8
parameter F test: F=2.2779 , p=0.0197 , df_denom=17360, df_num=8

Granger Causality

number of lags (no zero) 9

ssr based F test: F=2.2127 , p=0.0185 , df_denom=17357, df_num=9
ssr based chi2 test: chi2=19.9361 , p=0.0183 , df=9
likelihood ratio test: chi2=19.9247 , p=0.0184 , df=9
parameter F test: F=2.2127 , p=0.0185 , df_denom=17357, df_num=9

Granger Causality

number of lags (no zero) 10

ssr based F test: F=2.4513 , p=0.0064 , df_denom=17354, df_num=10
ssr based chi2 test: chi2=24.5431 , p=0.0063 , df=10
likelihood ratio test: chi2=24.5258 , p=0.0063 , df=10
parameter F test: F=2.4513 , p=0.0064 , df_denom=17354, df_num=10

Granger Causality

number of lags (no zero) 11

ssr based F test: F=2.5527 , p=0.0032 , df_denom=17351, df_num=11
ssr based chi2 test: chi2=28.1173 , p=0.0031 , df=11
likelihood ratio test: chi2=28.0946 , p=0.0031 , df=11
parameter F test: F=2.5527 , p=0.0032 , df_denom=17351, df_num=11

Granger Causality

number of lags (no zero) 12

ssr based F test: F=2.3867 , p=0.0045 , df_denom=17348, df_num=12
ssr based chi2 test: chi2=28.6814 , p=0.0044 , df=12
likelihood ratio test: chi2=28.6577 , p=0.0044 , df=12
parameter F test: F=2.3867 , p=0.0045 , df_denom=17348, df_num=12

9.1.1.11. Granger Causality: INTERPOL_POINT_dewpoint_AGL_C_CALCULATED

ADF Statistic: -9.452113406377423
p-value: 4.586750632557894e-16
Critical Values:
1%, -3.4307242852745428
Critical Values:
5%, -2.8617054196196627
Critical Values:
10%, -2.566858048572343

KPSS Statistic: 3.896787
p-value: 0.010000

Critical Values:
 10%, 0.347
 Critical Values:
 5%, 0.463
 Critical Values:
 2.5%, 0.574
 Critical Values:
 1%, 0.739

Granger Causality

number of lags (no zero) 1

ssr based F test: F=0.1936 , p=0.6600 , df_denom=2938, df_num=1
 ssr based chi2 test: chi2=0.1938 , p=0.6598 , df=1
 likelihood ratio test: chi2=0.1938 , p=0.6598 , df=1
 parameter F test: F=0.1936 , p=0.6600 , df_denom=2938, df_num=1

Granger Causality

number of lags (no zero) 2

ssr based F test: F=0.1620 , p=0.8504 , df_denom=2935, df_num=2
 ssr based chi2 test: chi2=0.3246 , p=0.8502 , df=2
 likelihood ratio test: chi2=0.3245 , p=0.8502 , df=2
 parameter F test: F=0.1620 , p=0.8504 , df_denom=2935, df_num=2

Granger Causality

number of lags (no zero) 3

ssr based F test: F=0.1242 , p=0.9458 , df_denom=2932, df_num=3
 ssr based chi2 test: chi2=0.3736 , p=0.9456 , df=3
 likelihood ratio test: chi2=0.3736 , p=0.9456 , df=3
 parameter F test: F=0.1242 , p=0.9458 , df_denom=2932, df_num=3

Granger Causality

number of lags (no zero) 4

ssr based F test: F=0.3967 , p=0.8111 , df_denom=2929, df_num=4
 ssr based chi2 test: chi2=1.5917 , p=0.8103 , df=4
 likelihood ratio test: chi2=1.5913 , p=0.8104 , df=4
 parameter F test: F=0.3967 , p=0.8111 , df_denom=2929, df_num=4

Granger Causality

number of lags (no zero) 5

ssr based F test: F=0.4881 , p=0.7854 , df_denom=2926, df_num=5
 ssr based chi2 test: chi2=2.4496 , p=0.7841 , df=5
 likelihood ratio test: chi2=2.4486 , p=0.7842 , df=5
 parameter F test: F=0.4881 , p=0.7854 , df_denom=2926, df_num=5

Granger Causality

number of lags (no zero) 6

ssr based F test: F=0.7809 , p=0.5848 , df_denom=2923, df_num=6
 ssr based chi2 test: chi2=4.7063 , p=0.5820 , df=6
 likelihood ratio test: chi2=4.7025 , p=0.5825 , df=6
 parameter F test: F=0.7809 , p=0.5848 , df_denom=2923, df_num=6

Granger Causality
number of lags (no zero) 7
ssr based F test: F=0.6747 , p=0.6937 , df_denom=2920, df_num=7
ssr based chi2 test: chi2=4.7470 , p=0.6908 , df=7
likelihood ratio test: chi2=4.7431 , p=0.6913 , df=7
parameter F test: F=0.6747 , p=0.6937 , df_denom=2920, df_num=7

Granger Causality
number of lags (no zero) 8
ssr based F test: F=0.7367 , p=0.6592 , df_denom=2917, df_num=8
ssr based chi2 test: chi2=5.9276 , p=0.6553 , df=8
likelihood ratio test: chi2=5.9217 , p=0.6560 , df=8
parameter F test: F=0.7367 , p=0.6592 , df_denom=2917, df_num=8

Granger Causality
number of lags (no zero) 9
ssr based F test: F=0.6752 , p=0.7321 , df_denom=2914, df_num=9
ssr based chi2 test: chi2=6.1164 , p=0.7282 , df=9
likelihood ratio test: chi2=6.1101 , p=0.7289 , df=9
parameter F test: F=0.6752 , p=0.7321 , df_denom=2914, df_num=9

Granger Causality
number of lags (no zero) 10
ssr based F test: F=0.7421 , p=0.6851 , df_denom=2911, df_num=10
ssr based chi2 test: chi2=7.4748 , p=0.6800 , df=10
likelihood ratio test: chi2=7.4653 , p=0.6809 , df=10
parameter F test: F=0.7421 , p=0.6851 , df_denom=2911, df_num=10

Granger Causality
number of lags (no zero) 11
ssr based F test: F=0.6862 , p=0.7530 , df_denom=2908, df_num=11
ssr based chi2 test: chi2=7.6076 , p=0.7480 , df=11
likelihood ratio test: chi2=7.5978 , p=0.7488 , df=11
parameter F test: F=0.6862 , p=0.7530 , df_denom=2908, df_num=11

Granger Causality
number of lags (no zero) 12
ssr based F test: F=0.7280 , p=0.7252 , df_denom=2905, df_num=12
ssr based chi2 test: chi2=8.8106 , p=0.7190 , df=12
likelihood ratio test: chi2=8.7974 , p=0.7201 , df=12
parameter F test: F=0.7280 , p=0.7252 , df_denom=2905, df_num=12

9.1.1.12. Granger Causality: INTERPOL_POINT_Niederschlag_Stundensumme_mm

INTERPOL_POINT_Niederschlag_Stundensumme_mm [mm]

Pre differentiation: INTERPOL_POINT_Niederschlag_Stundensumme_mm

ADF Statistic: -11.649979311760038
p-value: 2.0484073631091192e-21
Critical Values:
1%, -3.430724221017473
Critical Values:
5%, -2.861705391222312
Critical Values:
10%, -2.566858033456859

KPSS Statistic: 0.923498
p-value: 0.010000
Critical Values:
10%, 0.347
Critical Values:
5%, 0.463
Critical Values:
2.5%, 0.574
Critical Values:
1%, 0.739

Granger Causality
number of lags (no zero) 1
ssr based F test: F=1.0438 , p=0.3070 , df_denom=16873, df_num=1
ssr based chi2 test: chi2=1.0440 , p=0.3069 , df=1
likelihood ratio test: chi2=1.0439 , p=0.3069 , df=1
parameter F test: F=1.0438 , p=0.3070 , df_denom=16873, df_num=1

Granger Causality
number of lags (no zero) 2
ssr based F test: F=0.4446 , p=0.6411 , df_denom=16870, df_num=2
ssr based chi2 test: chi2=0.8895 , p=0.6410 , df=2
likelihood ratio test: chi2=0.8895 , p=0.6410 , df=2
parameter F test: F=0.4446 , p=0.6411 , df_denom=16870, df_num=2

Granger Causality
number of lags (no zero) 3
ssr based F test: F=0.3610 , p=0.7812 , df_denom=16867, df_num=3

ssr based chi2 test: chi2=1.0836 , p=0.7810 , df=3
likelihood ratio test: chi2=1.0835 , p=0.7811 , df=3
parameter F test: F=0.3610 , p=0.7812 , df_denom=16867, df_num=3

Granger Causality

number of lags (no zero) 4

ssr based F test: F=0.8773 , p=0.4765 , df_denom=16864, df_num=4
ssr based chi2 test: chi2=3.5110 , p=0.4762 , df=4
likelihood ratio test: chi2=3.5106 , p=0.4763 , df=4
parameter F test: F=0.8773 , p=0.4765 , df_denom=16864, df_num=4

Granger Causality

number of lags (no zero) 5

ssr based F test: F=1.2769 , p=0.2707 , df_denom=16861, df_num=5
ssr based chi2 test: chi2=6.3884 , p=0.2702 , df=5
likelihood ratio test: chi2=6.3872 , p=0.2703 , df=5
parameter F test: F=1.2769 , p=0.2707 , df_denom=16861, df_num=5

Granger Causality

number of lags (no zero) 6

ssr based F test: F=1.2826 , p=0.2613 , df_denom=16858, df_num=6
ssr based chi2 test: chi2=7.7018 , p=0.2608 , df=6
likelihood ratio test: chi2=7.7000 , p=0.2609 , df=6
parameter F test: F=1.2826 , p=0.2613 , df_denom=16858, df_num=6

Granger Causality

number of lags (no zero) 7

ssr based F test: F=1.1329 , p=0.3388 , df_denom=16855, df_num=7
ssr based chi2 test: chi2=7.9375 , p=0.3381 , df=7
likelihood ratio test: chi2=7.9357 , p=0.3383 , df=7
parameter F test: F=1.1329 , p=0.3388 , df_denom=16855, df_num=7

Granger Causality

number of lags (no zero) 8

ssr based F test: F=1.0395 , p=0.4033 , df_denom=16852, df_num=8
ssr based chi2 test: chi2=8.3242 , p=0.4025 , df=8
likelihood ratio test: chi2=8.3221 , p=0.4027 , df=8
parameter F test: F=1.0395 , p=0.4033 , df_denom=16852, df_num=8

Granger Causality

number of lags (no zero) 9

ssr based F test: F=0.9936 , p=0.4427 , df_denom=16849, df_num=9
ssr based chi2 test: chi2=8.9523 , p=0.4417 , df=9
likelihood ratio test: chi2=8.9499 , p=0.4419 , df=9
parameter F test: F=0.9936 , p=0.4427 , df_denom=16849, df_num=9

Granger Causality

number of lags (no zero) 10

ssr based F test: F=0.9034 , p=0.5289 , df_denom=16846, df_num=10
ssr based chi2 test: chi2=9.0454 , p=0.5278 , df=10
likelihood ratio test: chi2=9.0430 , p=0.5280 , df=10
parameter F test: F=0.9034 , p=0.5289 , df_denom=16846, df_num=10

Granger Causality

number of lags (no zero) 11

ssr based F test: F=1.3068 , p=0.2131 , df_denom=16843, df_num=11
ssr based chi2 test: chi2=14.3945 , p=0.2119 , df=11
likelihood ratio test: chi2=14.3884 , p=0.2122 , df=11
parameter F test: F=1.3068 , p=0.2131 , df_denom=16843, df_num=11

Granger Causality

number of lags (no zero) 12

ssr based F test: F=1.1838 , p=0.2879 , df_denom=16840, df_num=12
ssr based chi2 test: chi2=14.2268 , p=0.2865 , df=12
likelihood ratio test: chi2=14.2208 , p=0.2868 , df=12
parameter F test: F=1.1838 , p=0.2879 , df_denom=16840, df_num=12

9.1.1.13. Granger Causality: INTERPOL_POINT_Windgeschwindigkeit_ms

ADF Statistic: -13.104790625892916
 p-value: 1.681151041331221e-24
 Critical Values:
 1%, -3.430724049773102
 Critical Values:
 5%, -2.8617053155436882
 Critical Values:
 10%, -2.566857993174263

KPSS Statistic: 1.224319
 p-value: 0.010000
 Critical Values:
 10%, 0.347
 Critical Values:
 5%, 0.463
 Critical Values:
 2.5%, 0.574
 Critical Values:
 1%, 0.739

Granger Causality

number of lags (no zero) 1
 ssr based F test: F=0.0040 , p=0.9496 , df_denom=17513, df_num=1
 ssr based chi2 test: chi2=0.0040 , p=0.9496 , df=1
 likelihood ratio test: chi2=0.0040 , p=0.9496 , df=1
 parameter F test: F=0.0040 , p=0.9496 , df_denom=17513, df_num=1

Granger Causality
 number of lags (no zero) 2
 ssr based F test: F=0.7379 , p=0.4781 , df_denom=17510, df_num=2
 ssr based chi2 test: chi2=1.4763 , p=0.4780 , df=2
 likelihood ratio test: chi2=1.4762 , p=0.4780 , df=2
 parameter F test: F=0.7379 , p=0.4781 , df_denom=17510, df_num=2

Granger Causality
 number of lags (no zero) 3
 ssr based F test: F=0.4746 , p=0.7000 , df_denom=17507, df_num=3
 ssr based chi2 test: chi2=1.4244 , p=0.6998 , df=3
 likelihood ratio test: chi2=1.4243 , p=0.6998 , df=3
 parameter F test: F=0.4746 , p=0.7000 , df_denom=17507, df_num=3

Granger Causality
 number of lags (no zero) 4
 ssr based F test: F=0.3092 , p=0.8720 , df_denom=17504, df_num=4
 ssr based chi2 test: chi2=1.2374 , p=0.8719 , df=4
 likelihood ratio test: chi2=1.2374 , p=0.8719 , df=4
 parameter F test: F=0.3092 , p=0.8720 , df_denom=17504, df_num=4

Granger Causality
 number of lags (no zero) 5
 ssr based F test: F=0.8034 , p=0.5470 , df_denom=17501, df_num=5
 ssr based chi2 test: chi2=4.0195 , p=0.5466 , df=5
 likelihood ratio test: chi2=4.0190 , p=0.5467 , df=5
 parameter F test: F=0.8034 , p=0.5470 , df_denom=17501, df_num=5

Granger Causality
 number of lags (no zero) 6
 ssr based F test: F=0.8127 , p=0.5598 , df_denom=17498, df_num=6
 ssr based chi2 test: chi2=4.8798 , p=0.5593 , df=6
 likelihood ratio test: chi2=4.8791 , p=0.5594 , df=6
 parameter F test: F=0.8127 , p=0.5598 , df_denom=17498, df_num=6

Granger Causality
 number of lags (no zero) 7
 ssr based F test: F=0.8812 , p=0.5202 , df_denom=17495, df_num=7
 ssr based chi2 test: chi2=6.1739 , p=0.5196 , df=7
 likelihood ratio test: chi2=6.1728 , p=0.5197 , df=7
 parameter F test: F=0.8812 , p=0.5202 , df_denom=17495, df_num=7

Granger Causality
 number of lags (no zero) 8
 ssr based F test: F=0.7895 , p=0.6119 , df_denom=17492, df_num=8
 ssr based chi2 test: chi2=6.3218 , p=0.6112 , df=8
 likelihood ratio test: chi2=6.3207 , p=0.6114 , df=8
 parameter F test: F=0.7895 , p=0.6119 , df_denom=17492, df_num=8

Granger Causality
 number of lags (no zero) 9
 ssr based F test: F=1.0778 , p=0.3754 , df_denom=17489, df_num=9
 ssr based chi2 test: chi2=9.7104 , p=0.3744 , df=9
 likelihood ratio test: chi2=9.7077 , p=0.3747 , df=9
 parameter F test: F=1.0778 , p=0.3754 , df_denom=17489, df_num=9

Granger Causality
 number of lags (no zero) 10
 ssr based F test: F=0.9894 , p=0.4499 , df_denom=17486, df_num=10
 ssr based chi2 test: chi2=9.9056 , p=0.4488 , df=10

likelihood ratio test: $\chi^2=9.9028$, $p=0.4491$, $df=10$
parameter F test: $F=0.9894$, $p=0.4499$, $df_{denom}=17486$, $df_{num}=10$

Granger Causality

number of lags (no zero) 11

ssr based F test: $F=1.0183$, $p=0.4266$, $df_{denom}=17483$, $df_{num}=11$
ssr based χ^2 test: $\chi^2=11.2163$, $p=0.4253$, $df=11$
likelihood ratio test: $\chi^2=11.2127$, $p=0.4256$, $df=11$
parameter F test: $F=1.0183$, $p=0.4266$, $df_{denom}=17483$, $df_{num}=11$

Granger Causality

number of lags (no zero) 12

ssr based F test: $F=0.9383$, $p=0.5069$, $df_{denom}=17480$, $df_{num}=12$
ssr based χ^2 test: $\chi^2=11.2753$, $p=0.5055$, $df=12$
likelihood ratio test: $\chi^2=11.2717$, $p=0.5058$, $df=12$
parameter F test: $F=0.9383$, $p=0.5069$, $df_{denom}=17480$, $df_{num}=12$

9.1.1.14. Granger Causality INTERPOL_POINT_pressure_AGL_hPa_CALCULATED

ADF Statistic: -11.031735961853679

p-value: 5.645835355416203e-20

Critical Values:

1%, -3.4307241781916824

Critical Values:

5%, -2.861705372296161

Critical Values:

10%, -2.5668580233827525

KPSS Statistic: 6.653964

p-value: 0.010000

Critical Values:

10%, 0.347

Critical Values:

5%, 0.463

Critical Values:

2.5%, 0.574

Critical Values:

1%, 0.739

Granger Causality

number of lags (no zero) 1

ssr based F test: F=5.7759 , p=0.0163 , df_denom=17513, df_num=1

ssr based chi2 test: chi2=5.7768 , p=0.0162 , df=1

likelihood ratio test: chi2=5.7759 , p=0.0162 , df=1

parameter F test: F=5.7759 , p=0.0163 , df_denom=17513, df_num=1

Granger Causality

number of lags (no zero) 2

ssr based F test: F=2.6670 , p=0.0695 , df_denom=17510, df_num=2

ssr based chi2 test: chi2=5.3355 , p=0.0694 , df=2

likelihood ratio test: chi2=5.3347 , p=0.0694 , df=2

parameter F test: F=2.6670 , p=0.0695 , df_denom=17510, df_num=2

Granger Causality

number of lags (no zero) 3

ssr based F test: F=2.0704 , p=0.1018 , df_denom=17507, df_num=3

ssr based chi2 test: chi2=6.2138 , p=0.1017 , df=3

likelihood ratio test: chi2=6.2127 , p=0.1017 , df=3

parameter F test: F=2.0704 , p=0.1018 , df_denom=17507, df_num=3

Granger Causality

number of lags (no zero) 4

ssr based F test: F=1.5174 , p=0.1941 , df_denom=17504, df_num=4

ssr based chi2 test: chi2=6.0727 , p=0.1938 , df=4

likelihood ratio test: chi2=6.0716 , p=0.1939 , df=4

parameter F test: F=1.5174 , p=0.1941 , df_denom=17504, df_num=4

Granger Causality

number of lags (no zero) 5

ssr based F test: F=1.1188 , p=0.3478 , df_denom=17501, df_num=5

ssr based chi2 test: chi2=5.5977 , p=0.3473 , df=5

likelihood ratio test: chi2=5.5968 , p=0.3474 , df=5

parameter F test: F=1.1188 , p=0.3478 , df_denom=17501, df_num=5

Granger Causality

number of lags (no zero) 6

ssr based F test: F=1.2811 , p=0.2620 , df_denom=17498, df_num=6

ssr based chi2 test: chi2=7.6924 , p=0.2615 , df=6

likelihood ratio test: chi2=7.6907 , p=0.2617 , df=6

parameter F test: F=1.2811 , p=0.2620 , df_denom=17498, df_num=6

Granger Causality

number of lags (no zero) 7

ssr based F test: F=1.1207 , p=0.3465 , df_denom=17495, df_num=7

ssr based chi2 test: chi2=7.8518 , p=0.3458 , df=7

likelihood ratio test: chi2=7.8500 , p=0.3460 , df=7

parameter F test: F=1.1207 , p=0.3465 , df_denom=17495, df_num=7

Granger Causality

number of lags (no zero) 8
 ssr based F test: F=1.4114 , p=0.1858 , df_denom=17492, df_num=8
 ssr based chi2 test: chi2=11.3023 , p=0.1851 , df=8
 likelihood ratio test: chi2=11.2987 , p=0.1853 , df=8
 parameter F test: F=1.4114 , p=0.1858 , df_denom=17492, df_num=8

Granger Causality

number of lags (no zero) 9
 ssr based F test: F=1.2925 , p=0.2349 , df_denom=17489, df_num=9
 ssr based chi2 test: chi2=11.6455 , p=0.2340 , df=9
 likelihood ratio test: chi2=11.6416 , p=0.2343 , df=9
 parameter F test: F=1.2925 , p=0.2349 , df_denom=17489, df_num=9

Granger Causality

number of lags (no zero) 10
 ssr based F test: F=1.0720 , p=0.3798 , df_denom=17486, df_num=10
 ssr based chi2 test: chi2=10.7333 , p=0.3787 , df=10
 likelihood ratio test: chi2=10.7300 , p=0.3789 , df=10
 parameter F test: F=1.0720 , p=0.3798 , df_denom=17486, df_num=10

Granger Causality

number of lags (no zero) 11
 ssr based F test: F=1.0265 , p=0.4192 , df_denom=17483, df_num=11
 ssr based chi2 test: chi2=11.3064 , p=0.4180 , df=11
 likelihood ratio test: chi2=11.3027 , p=0.4183 , df=11
 parameter F test: F=1.0265 , p=0.4192 , df_denom=17483, df_num=11

Granger Causality

number of lags (no zero) 12
 ssr based F test: F=0.9778 , p=0.4674 , df_denom=17480, df_num=12
 ssr based chi2 test: chi2=11.7500 , p=0.4660 , df=12
 likelihood ratio test: chi2=11.7461 , p=0.4663 , df=12
 parameter F test: F=0.9778 , p=0.4674 , df_denom=17480, df_num=12

**9.1.1.15. Granger Causality:
 INTERPOL_POINT_Luftdruckaenderung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa**

INTERPOL_POINT_Luftdruckaenderung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa

INTERPOL_POINT_Luftdruckaenderung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa [hPa]

Pre differentiation: INTERPOL_POINT_Luftdruckaenderung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa

ADF Statistic: -13.40624958218986
 p-value: 4.464460255091454e-25
 Critical Values:
 1%, -3.4307242638530675
 Critical Values:
 5%, -2.861705410152796
 Critical Values:
 10%, -2.5668580435332715

KPSS Statistic: 0.329029
 p-value: 0.100000
 Critical Values:
 10%, 0.347
 Critical Values:
 5%, 0.463
 Critical Values:
 2.5%, 0.574
 Critical Values:
 1%, 0.739

Granger Causality
 number of lags (no zero) 1
 ssr based F test: F=0.9968 , p=0.3181 , df_denom=7192, df_num=1
 ssr based chi2 test: chi2=0.9972 , p=0.3180 , df=1
 likelihood ratio test: chi2=0.9972 , p=0.3180 , df=1
 parameter F test: F=0.9968 , p=0.3181 , df_denom=7192, df_num=1

Granger Causality
 number of lags (no zero) 2
 ssr based F test: F=0.6089 , p=0.5440 , df_denom=7189, df_num=2
 ssr based chi2 test: chi2=1.2186 , p=0.5437 , df=2
 likelihood ratio test: chi2=1.2185 , p=0.5438 , df=2
 parameter F test: F=0.6089 , p=0.5440 , df_denom=7189, df_num=2

Granger Causality
 number of lags (no zero) 3
 ssr based F test: F=0.4103 , p=0.7456 , df_denom=7186, df_num=3
 ssr based chi2 test: chi2=1.2321 , p=0.7453 , df=3
 likelihood ratio test: chi2=1.2320 , p=0.7453 , df=3
 parameter F test: F=0.4103 , p=0.7456 , df_denom=7186, df_num=3

Granger Causality
 number of lags (no zero) 4
 ssr based F test: F=0.3139 , p=0.8688 , df_denom=7183, df_num=4
 ssr based chi2 test: chi2=1.2574 , p=0.8686 , df=4
 likelihood ratio test: chi2=1.2572 , p=0.8686 , df=4
 parameter F test: F=0.3139 , p=0.8688 , df_denom=7183, df_num=4

Granger Causality
 number of lags (no zero) 5

ssr based F test: F=0.3790 , p=0.8635 , df_denom=7180, df_num=5
ssr based chi2 test: chi2=1.8979 , p=0.8631 , df=5
likelihood ratio test: chi2=1.8976 , p=0.8631 , df=5
parameter F test: F=0.3790 , p=0.8635 , df_denom=7180, df_num=5

Granger Causality

number of lags (no zero) 6

ssr based F test: F=0.5161 , p=0.7966 , df_denom=7177, df_num=6
ssr based chi2 test: chi2=3.1024 , p=0.7959 , df=6
likelihood ratio test: chi2=3.1017 , p=0.7960 , df=6
parameter F test: F=0.5161 , p=0.7966 , df_denom=7177, df_num=6

Granger Causality

number of lags (no zero) 7

ssr based F test: F=0.6885 , p=0.6820 , df_denom=7174, df_num=7
ssr based chi2 test: chi2=4.8293 , p=0.6808 , df=7
likelihood ratio test: chi2=4.8277 , p=0.6810 , df=7
parameter F test: F=0.6885 , p=0.6820 , df_denom=7174, df_num=7

Granger Causality

number of lags (no zero) 8

ssr based F test: F=0.5837 , p=0.7922 , df_denom=7171, df_num=8
ssr based chi2 test: chi2=4.6803 , p=0.7911 , df=8
likelihood ratio test: chi2=4.6788 , p=0.7913 , df=8
parameter F test: F=0.5837 , p=0.7922 , df_denom=7171, df_num=8

Granger Causality

number of lags (no zero) 9

ssr based F test: F=0.6256 , p=0.7762 , df_denom=7168, df_num=9
ssr based chi2 test: chi2=5.6457 , p=0.7748 , df=9
likelihood ratio test: chi2=5.6435 , p=0.7750 , df=9
parameter F test: F=0.6256 , p=0.7762 , df_denom=7168, df_num=9

Granger Causality

number of lags (no zero) 10

ssr based F test: F=0.6182 , p=0.7996 , df_denom=7165, df_num=10
ssr based chi2 test: chi2=6.2005 , p=0.7981 , df=10
likelihood ratio test: chi2=6.1978 , p=0.7984 , df=10
parameter F test: F=0.6182 , p=0.7996 , df_denom=7165, df_num=10

Granger Causality

number of lags (no zero) 11

ssr based F test: F=0.5783 , p=0.8481 , df_denom=7162, df_num=11
ssr based chi2 test: chi2=6.3815 , p=0.8467 , df=11
likelihood ratio test: chi2=6.3787 , p=0.8469 , df=11
parameter F test: F=0.5783 , p=0.8481 , df_denom=7162, df_num=11

Granger Causality

number of lags (no zero) 12

ssr based F test: F=0.7745 , p=0.6775 , df_denom=7159, df_num=12
ssr based chi2 test: chi2=9.3270 , p=0.6748 , df=12
likelihood ratio test: chi2=9.3210 , p=0.6753 , df=12
parameter F test: F=0.7745 , p=0.6775 , df_denom=7159, df_num=12

9.1.1.16. Granger Causality: INTERPOL_POINT_rel_Luftfeuchtigkeit_Stundenmittel_prozent

ADF Statistic: -10.417768038854492

p-value: 1.736335810202411e-18

Critical Values:

1%, -3.4307240925695

Critical Values:

5%, -2.8617053344568504

Critical Values:

10%, -2.5668580032414554

KPSS Statistic: 1.053138

p-value: 0.010000

Critical Values:

10%, 0.347

Critical Values:

5%, 0.463

Critical Values:

2.5%, 0.574

Critical Values:

1%, 0.739

Granger Causality
number of lags (no zero) 1
ssr based F test: F=2.6164 , p=0.1058 , df_denom=17513, df_num=1
ssr based chi2 test: chi2=2.6168 , p=0.1057 , df=1
likelihood ratio test: chi2=2.6167 , p=0.1057 , df=1
parameter F test: F=2.6164 , p=0.1058 , df_denom=17513, df_num=1

Granger Causality
number of lags (no zero) 2
ssr based F test: F=1.6899 , p=0.1846 , df_denom=17510, df_num=2
ssr based chi2 test: chi2=3.3807 , p=0.1845 , df=2
likelihood ratio test: chi2=3.3804 , p=0.1845 , df=2
parameter F test: F=1.6899 , p=0.1846 , df_denom=17510, df_num=2

Granger Causality
number of lags (no zero) 3
ssr based F test: F=1.8636 , p=0.1334 , df_denom=17507, df_num=3
ssr based chi2 test: chi2=5.5930 , p=0.1332 , df=3
likelihood ratio test: chi2=5.5921 , p=0.1332 , df=3
parameter F test: F=1.8636 , p=0.1334 , df_denom=17507, df_num=3

Granger Causality
number of lags (no zero) 4
ssr based F test: F=1.2778 , p=0.2761 , df_denom=17504, df_num=4
ssr based chi2 test: chi2=5.1137 , p=0.2758 , df=4
likelihood ratio test: chi2=5.1130 , p=0.2759 , df=4
parameter F test: F=1.2778 , p=0.2761 , df_denom=17504, df_num=4

Granger Causality
number of lags (no zero) 5
ssr based F test: F=1.1391 , p=0.3371 , df_denom=17501, df_num=5
ssr based chi2 test: chi2=5.6989 , p=0.3366 , df=5
likelihood ratio test: chi2=5.6980 , p=0.3367 , df=5
parameter F test: F=1.1391 , p=0.3371 , df_denom=17501, df_num=5

Granger Causality
number of lags (no zero) 6
ssr based F test: F=0.9737 , p=0.4412 , df_denom=17498, df_num=6
ssr based chi2 test: chi2=5.8463 , p=0.4406 , df=6
likelihood ratio test: chi2=5.8453 , p=0.4407 , df=6
parameter F test: F=0.9737 , p=0.4412 , df_denom=17498, df_num=6

Granger Causality
number of lags (no zero) 7
ssr based F test: F=0.8370 , p=0.5563 , df_denom=17495, df_num=7
ssr based chi2 test: chi2=5.8641 , p=0.5557 , df=7
likelihood ratio test: chi2=5.8631 , p=0.5558 , df=7
parameter F test: F=0.8370 , p=0.5563 , df_denom=17495, df_num=7

Granger Causality
number of lags (no zero) 8
ssr based F test: F=1.0070 , p=0.4281 , df_denom=17492, df_num=8
ssr based chi2 test: chi2=8.0637 , p=0.4273 , df=8
likelihood ratio test: chi2=8.0619 , p=0.4274 , df=8
parameter F test: F=1.0070 , p=0.4281 , df_denom=17492, df_num=8

Granger Causality
number of lags (no zero) 9
ssr based F test: F=0.9210 , p=0.5053 , df_denom=17489, df_num=9
ssr based chi2 test: chi2=8.2980 , p=0.5044 , df=9
likelihood ratio test: chi2=8.2960 , p=0.5046 , df=9
parameter F test: F=0.9210 , p=0.5053 , df_denom=17489, df_num=9

Granger Causality
number of lags (no zero) 10
ssr based F test: F=0.8320 , p=0.5976 , df_denom=17486, df_num=10

ssr based chi2 test: $\chi^2=8.3303$, $p=0.5966$, $df=10$
 likelihood ratio test: $\chi^2=8.3283$, $p=0.5968$, $df=10$
 parameter F test: $F=0.8320$, $p=0.5976$, $df_denom=17486$, $df_num=10$

Granger Causality

number of lags (no zero) 11

ssr based F test: $F=0.7230$, $p=0.7175$, $df_denom=17483$, $df_num=11$
 ssr based chi2 test: $\chi^2=7.9633$, $p=0.7166$, $df=11$
 likelihood ratio test: $\chi^2=7.9615$, $p=0.7167$, $df=11$
 parameter F test: $F=0.7230$, $p=0.7175$, $df_denom=17483$, $df_num=11$

Granger Causality

number of lags (no zero) 12

ssr based F test: $F=0.6889$, $p=0.7639$, $df_denom=17480$, $df_num=12$
 ssr based chi2 test: $\chi^2=8.2787$, $p=0.7630$, $df=12$
 likelihood ratio test: $\chi^2=8.2768$, $p=0.7631$, $df=12$
 parameter F test: $F=0.6889$, $p=0.7639$, $df_denom=17480$, $df_num=12$

9.1.1.17. Granger Causality: INTERPOL_POINT_sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min

ADF Statistic: -11.47263691701333

p-value: 5.221858396776712e-21

Critical Values:

1%, -3.4307242852745428

Critical Values:

5%, -2.8617054196196627

Critical Values:

10%, -2.566858048572343

KPSS Statistic: 0.801881

p-value: 0.010000

Critical Values:

10%, 0.347

Critical Values:

5%, 0.463

Critical Values:

2.5%, 0.574

Critical Values:

1%, 0.739

Granger Causality

number of lags (no zero) 1

ssr based F test: $F=0.5061$, $p=0.4768$, $df_denom=10419$, $df_num=1$
 ssr based chi2 test: $chi2=0.5063$, $p=0.4768$, $df=1$
 likelihood ratio test: $chi2=0.5063$, $p=0.4768$, $df=1$
 parameter F test: $F=0.5061$, $p=0.4768$, $df_denom=10419$, $df_num=1$

Granger Causality

number of lags (no zero) 2

ssr based F test: $F=1.4537$, $p=0.2337$, $df_denom=10416$, $df_num=2$
 ssr based chi2 test: $chi2=2.9088$, $p=0.2335$, $df=2$
 likelihood ratio test: $chi2=2.9084$, $p=0.2336$, $df=2$
 parameter F test: $F=1.4537$, $p=0.2337$, $df_denom=10416$, $df_num=2$

Granger Causality

number of lags (no zero) 3

ssr based F test: $F=2.8578$, $p=0.0356$, $df_denom=10413$, $df_num=3$
 ssr based chi2 test: $chi2=8.5791$, $p=0.0354$, $df=3$
 likelihood ratio test: $chi2=8.5755$, $p=0.0355$, $df=3$
 parameter F test: $F=2.8578$, $p=0.0356$, $df_denom=10413$, $df_num=3$

Granger Causality

number of lags (no zero) 4

ssr based F test: $F=3.0910$, $p=0.0149$, $df_denom=10410$, $df_num=4$
 ssr based chi2 test: $chi2=12.3747$, $p=0.0148$, $df=4$
 likelihood ratio test: $chi2=12.3673$, $p=0.0148$, $df=4$
 parameter F test: $F=3.0910$, $p=0.0149$, $df_denom=10410$, $df_num=4$

Granger Causality

number of lags (no zero) 5

ssr based F test: $F=3.0570$, $p=0.0092$, $df_denom=10407$, $df_num=5$
 ssr based chi2 test: $chi2=15.3010$, $p=0.0092$, $df=5$
 likelihood ratio test: $chi2=15.2897$, $p=0.0092$, $df=5$
 parameter F test: $F=3.0570$, $p=0.0092$, $df_denom=10407$, $df_num=5$

Granger Causality

number of lags (no zero) 6

ssr based F test: $F=2.6052$, $p=0.0159$, $df_denom=10404$, $df_num=6$
 ssr based chi2 test: $chi2=15.6506$, $p=0.0158$, $df=6$
 likelihood ratio test: $chi2=15.6389$, $p=0.0158$, $df=6$
 parameter F test: $F=2.6052$, $p=0.0159$, $df_denom=10404$, $df_num=6$

Granger Causality

number of lags (no zero) 7

ssr based F test: $F=2.0691$, $p=0.0433$, $df_denom=10401$, $df_num=7$
 ssr based chi2 test: $chi2=14.5044$, $p=0.0429$, $df=7$
 likelihood ratio test: $chi2=14.4943$, $p=0.0431$, $df=7$
 parameter F test: $F=2.0691$, $p=0.0433$, $df_denom=10401$, $df_num=7$

Granger Causality
 number of lags (no zero) 8
 sss based F test: F=1.6567 , p=0.1036 , df_denom=10398, df_num=8
 sss based chi2 test: chi2=13.2754 , p=0.1027 , df=8
 likelihood ratio test: chi2=13.2669 , p=0.1030 , df=8
 parameter F test: F=1.6567 , p=0.1036 , df_denom=10398, df_num=8

Granger Causality
 number of lags (no zero) 9
 sss based F test: F=1.4108 , p=0.1770 , df_denom=10395, df_num=9
 sss based chi2 test: chi2=12.7202 , p=0.1757 , df=9
 likelihood ratio test: chi2=12.7124 , p=0.1761 , df=9
 parameter F test: F=1.4108 , p=0.1770 , df_denom=10395, df_num=9

Granger Causality
 number of lags (no zero) 10
 sss based F test: F=1.4116 , p=0.1679 , df_denom=10392, df_num=10
 sss based chi2 test: chi2=14.1449 , p=0.1665 , df=10
 likelihood ratio test: chi2=14.1353 , p=0.1669 , df=10
 parameter F test: F=1.4116 , p=0.1679 , df_denom=10392, df_num=10

Granger Causality
 number of lags (no zero) 11
 sss based F test: F=1.3522 , p=0.1885 , df_denom=10389, df_num=11
 sss based chi2 test: chi2=14.9076 , p=0.1868 , df=11
 likelihood ratio test: chi2=14.8970 , p=0.1873 , df=11
 parameter F test: F=1.3522 , p=0.1885 , df_denom=10389, df_num=11

Granger Causality
 number of lags (no zero) 12
 sss based F test: F=1.3179 , p=0.2001 , df_denom=10386, df_num=12
 sss based chi2 test: chi2=15.8532 , p=0.1981 , df=12
 likelihood ratio test: chi2=15.8412 , p=0.1986 , df=12
 parameter F test: F=1.3179 , p=0.2001 , df_denom=10386, df_num=12

9.1.1.18. Granger Causality: INTERPOL_POINT_Globalstrahlung_wm2

ADF Statistic: -11.534100962591577
 p-value: 3.7698391886728795e-21
 Critical Values:
 1%, -3.4307242852745428
 Critical Values:
 5%, -2.8617054196196627
 Critical Values:
 10%, -2.566858048572343

KPSS Statistic: 0.217316
 p-value: 0.100000
 Critical Values:
 10%, 0.347
 Critical Values:
 5%, 0.463
 Critical Values:
 2.5%, 0.574
 Critical Values:
 1%, 0.739

INTERPOL_POINT_Globalstrahlung_wm2_log_diff

Granger Causality

number of lags (no zero) 1

ssr based F test: F=0.1244 , p=0.7243 , df_denom=17513, df_num=1
 ssr based chi2 test: chi2=0.1245 , p=0.7243 , df=1
 likelihood ratio test: chi2=0.1245 , p=0.7243 , df=1
 parameter F test: F=0.1244 , p=0.7243 , df_denom=17513, df_num=1

Granger Causality

number of lags (no zero) 2

ssr based F test: F=0.0121 , p=0.9879 , df_denom=17510, df_num=2
 ssr based chi2 test: chi2=0.0243 , p=0.9879 , df=2
 likelihood ratio test: chi2=0.0243 , p=0.9879 , df=2
 parameter F test: F=0.0121 , p=0.9879 , df_denom=17510, df_num=2

Granger Causality

number of lags (no zero) 3

ssr based F test: F=0.2135 , p=0.8871 , df_denom=17507, df_num=3
 ssr based chi2 test: chi2=0.6409 , p=0.8870 , df=3
 likelihood ratio test: chi2=0.6409 , p=0.8870 , df=3
 parameter F test: F=0.2135 , p=0.8871 , df_denom=17507, df_num=3

Granger Causality

number of lags (no zero) 4

ssr based F test: F=0.8591 , p=0.4876 , df_denom=17504, df_num=4
 ssr based chi2 test: chi2=3.4382 , p=0.4873 , df=4
 likelihood ratio test: chi2=3.4379 , p=0.4874 , df=4
 parameter F test: F=0.8591 , p=0.4876 , df_denom=17504, df_num=4

Granger Causality

number of lags (no zero) 5

ssr based F test: F=0.8891 , p=0.4872 , df_denom=17501, df_num=5

ssr based chi2 test: chi2=4.4485 , p=0.4868 , df=5
likelihood ratio test: chi2=4.4479 , p=0.4869 , df=5
parameter F test: F=0.8891 , p=0.4872 , df_denom=17501, df_num=5

Granger Causality

number of lags (no zero) 6

ssr based F test: F=0.7344 , p=0.6218 , df_denom=17498, df_num=6
ssr based chi2 test: chi2=4.4099 , p=0.6214 , df=6
likelihood ratio test: chi2=4.4093 , p=0.6215 , df=6
parameter F test: F=0.7344 , p=0.6218 , df_denom=17498, df_num=6

Granger Causality

number of lags (no zero) 7

ssr based F test: F=0.7260 , p=0.6499 , df_denom=17495, df_num=7
ssr based chi2 test: chi2=5.0865 , p=0.6494 , df=7
likelihood ratio test: chi2=5.0858 , p=0.6495 , df=7
parameter F test: F=0.7260 , p=0.6499 , df_denom=17495, df_num=7

Granger Causality

number of lags (no zero) 8

ssr based F test: F=0.8145 , p=0.5896 , df_denom=17492, df_num=8
ssr based chi2 test: chi2=6.5226 , p=0.5889 , df=8
likelihood ratio test: chi2=6.5214 , p=0.5890 , df=8
parameter F test: F=0.8145 , p=0.5896 , df_denom=17492, df_num=8

Granger Causality

number of lags (no zero) 9

ssr based F test: F=0.7853 , p=0.6300 , df_denom=17489, df_num=9
ssr based chi2 test: chi2=7.0758 , p=0.6292 , df=9
likelihood ratio test: chi2=7.0743 , p=0.6294 , df=9
parameter F test: F=0.7853 , p=0.6300 , df_denom=17489, df_num=9

Granger Causality

number of lags (no zero) 10

ssr based F test: F=1.0091 , p=0.4326 , df_denom=17486, df_num=10
ssr based chi2 test: chi2=10.1035 , p=0.4315 , df=10
likelihood ratio test: chi2=10.1005 , p=0.4317 , df=10
parameter F test: F=1.0091 , p=0.4326 , df_denom=17486, df_num=10

Granger Causality

number of lags (no zero) 11

ssr based F test: F=1.1487 , p=0.3179 , df_denom=17483, df_num=11
ssr based chi2 test: chi2=12.6525 , p=0.3166 , df=11
likelihood ratio test: chi2=12.6480 , p=0.3170 , df=11
parameter F test: F=1.1487 , p=0.3179 , df_denom=17483, df_num=11

Granger Causality

number of lags (no zero) 12

ssr based F test: F=1.1081 , p=0.3479 , df_denom=17480, df_num=12
ssr based chi2 test: chi2=13.3156 , p=0.3465 , df=12
likelihood ratio test: chi2=13.3106 , p=0.3469 , df=12
parameter F test: F=1.1081 , p=0.3479 , df_denom=17480, df_num=12

9.1.1.19. Granger Causality: INTERPOL_POINT_Foehnindex

ADF Statistic: -13.616400934750576
 p-value: 1.8315675131996336e-25
 Critical Values:
 1%, -3.4307242852745428
 Critical Values:
 5%, -2.8617054196196627
 Critical Values:
 10%, -2.566858048572343

KPSS Statistic: 4.877432
 p-value: 0.010000
 Critical Values:
 10%, 0.347
 Critical Values:
 5%, 0.463
 Critical Values:
 2.5%, 0.574
 Critical Values:
 1%, 0.739

INTERPOL_POINT_Foehnindex_log_diff

Granger Causality

number of lags (no zero) 1
 sss based F test: F=0.6985 , p=0.4033 , df_denom=3882, df_num=1
 sss based chi2 test: chi2=0.6990 , p=0.4031 , df=1
 likelihood ratio test: chi2=0.6989 , p=0.4031 , df=1
 parameter F test: F=0.6985 , p=0.4033 , df_denom=3882, df_num=1

Granger Causality
number of lags (no zero) 2
ssr based F test: F=0.5079 , p=0.6018 , df_denom=3879, df_num=2
ssr based chi2 test: chi2=1.0170 , p=0.6014 , df=2
likelihood ratio test: chi2=1.0169 , p=0.6014 , df=2
parameter F test: F=0.5079 , p=0.6018 , df_denom=3879, df_num=2

Granger Causality
number of lags (no zero) 3
ssr based F test: F=2.1601 , p=0.0906 , df_denom=3876, df_num=3
ssr based chi2 test: chi2=6.4921 , p=0.0900 , df=3
likelihood ratio test: chi2=6.4866 , p=0.0902 , df=3
parameter F test: F=2.1601 , p=0.0906 , df_denom=3876, df_num=3

Granger Causality
number of lags (no zero) 4
ssr based F test: F=1.5698 , p=0.1795 , df_denom=3873, df_num=4
ssr based chi2 test: chi2=6.2938 , p=0.1783 , df=4
likelihood ratio test: chi2=6.2887 , p=0.1786 , df=4
parameter F test: F=1.5698 , p=0.1795 , df_denom=3873, df_num=4

Granger Causality
number of lags (no zero) 5
ssr based F test: F=1.2765 , p=0.2710 , df_denom=3870, df_num=5
ssr based chi2 test: chi2=6.4006 , p=0.2692 , df=5
likelihood ratio test: chi2=6.3953 , p=0.2696 , df=5
parameter F test: F=1.2765 , p=0.2710 , df_denom=3870, df_num=5

Granger Causality
number of lags (no zero) 6
ssr based F test: F=1.6297 , p=0.1346 , df_denom=3867, df_num=6
ssr based chi2 test: chi2=9.8113 , p=0.1328 , df=6
likelihood ratio test: chi2=9.7989 , p=0.1334 , df=6
parameter F test: F=1.6297 , p=0.1346 , df_denom=3867, df_num=6

Granger Causality
number of lags (no zero) 7
ssr based F test: F=1.5026 , p=0.1614 , df_denom=3864, df_num=7
ssr based chi2 test: chi2=10.5590 , p=0.1590 , df=7
likelihood ratio test: chi2=10.5446 , p=0.1598 , df=7
parameter F test: F=1.5026 , p=0.1614 , df_denom=3864, df_num=7

Granger Causality
number of lags (no zero) 8
ssr based F test: F=1.4915 , p=0.1547 , df_denom=3861, df_num=8
ssr based chi2 test: chi2=11.9842 , p=0.1519 , df=8
likelihood ratio test: chi2=11.9657 , p=0.1527 , df=8
parameter F test: F=1.4915 , p=0.1547 , df_denom=3861, df_num=8

Granger Causality
number of lags (no zero) 9
ssr based F test: F=1.3916 , p=0.1858 , df_denom=3858, df_num=9
ssr based chi2 test: chi2=12.5862 , p=0.1822 , df=9
likelihood ratio test: chi2=12.5659 , p=0.1833 , df=9
parameter F test: F=1.3916 , p=0.1858 , df_denom=3858, df_num=9

Granger Causality
number of lags (no zero) 10
ssr based F test: F=1.2349 , p=0.2628 , df_denom=3855, df_num=10
ssr based chi2 test: chi2=12.4164 , p=0.2582 , df=10
likelihood ratio test: chi2=12.3966 , p=0.2594 , df=10
parameter F test: F=1.2349 , p=0.2628 , df_denom=3855, df_num=10

Granger Causality
number of lags (no zero) 11
ssr based F test: F=1.2878 , p=0.2245 , df_denom=3852, df_num=11

ssr based chi2 test: $\chi^2=14.2502$, $p=0.2195$, $df=11$
 likelihood ratio test: $\chi^2=14.2241$, $p=0.2208$, $df=11$
 parameter F test: $F=1.2878$, $p=0.2245$, $df_{denom}=3852$, $df_{num}=11$

Granger Causality

number of lags (no zero) 12

ssr based F test: $F=1.2309$, $p=0.2547$, $df_{denom}=3849$, $df_{num}=12$
 ssr based chi2 test: $\chi^2=14.8670$, $p=0.2488$, $df=12$
 likelihood ratio test: $\chi^2=14.8386$, $p=0.2504$, $df=12$
 parameter F test: $F=1.2309$, $p=0.2547$, $df_{denom}=3849$, $df_{num}=12$

9.1.2. Seaborn Autocorrelation

9.1.2.1. GPS Dataframe Seaborn Autocorrelation (Raw Data)

	Temp	ActivitySum	ActivityMean	V_MproH	Month	Hour	Day
Temp	1	-0.038264910058885	-0.037759005954285	-0.035231654738635	0.118186916929462	0.081603482031968	0.123378549
ActivitySum	-0.038264910058885	1	0.999090034320854	0.113894048595653	0.020892594809359	0.026248052301034	0.021495923
ActivityMean	-0.037759005954285	0.999090034320854	1	0.114068371194221	0.020919193891798	0.026336415132022	0.021531214
V_MproH	-0.035231654738635	0.113894048595653	0.114068371194221	1	0.012993754576522	-0.099575435249196	0.008250015
Month	0.118186916929462	0.020892594809359	0.020919193891798	0.012993754576522	1	-0.000293432121297	0.996273468
Hour	0.081603482031968	0.026248052301034	0.026336415132022	-0.099575435249196	-0.000293432121297	1	-0.000314477
Day	0.123378549496804	0.021495922524889	0.021531213715091	0.008250015466181	0.996273467670216	-0.00031447667532	1

9.1.2.2. GPS Dataframe Seaborn Autocorrelation (Differentiated (log) Data)

	GPS_V_MproH	GPS Temp	Temp	Dewpoint
GPS_V_MproH	1	-0.397666863	0.025692706	0.083357363
GPS_Temp	-0.397666863	1	0.014378133	-0.003049442
Temp	0.025692706	0.014378133	1	0.70300958
Dewpoint	0.083357363	-0.003049442	0.70300958	1
Rain	0.101812729	-0.124677103	-0.013659228	0.06775465
Wind	0.086180265	-0.03453105	0.003564656	0.059906325
Pressure	-0.004454267	0.030763771	0.191574779	0.187196593
Pressure Change	0.050922386	-0.003142088	-0.085739157	-0.030880351
Humidity	0.018587489	0.025164964	-0.626552641	-0.186260043
Sunshine	0.103277833	-0.009813476	0.086953146	0.096780725
Radiation	0.104745726	-0.078816945	0.211226347	0.12545376
Foehn	-0.039913245	0.096645735	-0.043330758	0.027227615
	Rain	Wind	Pressure	Pressure Change
GPS_V_MproH	0.101812729	0.086180265	-0.004454267	0.050922386
GPS_Temp	-0.124677103	-0.03453105	0.030763771	-0.003142088
Temp	-0.013659228	0.003564656	0.191574779	-0.085739157
Dewpoint	0.06775465	0.059906325	0.187196593	-0.030880351
Rain	1	-0.046869013	-0.112633181	0.0840705
Wind	-0.046869013	1	0.073175853	-0.053705478
Pressure	-0.112633181	0.073175853	1	-0.034176832
Pressure Change	0.0840705	-0.053705478	-0.034176832	1
Humidity	-0.013806513	-0.062106354	0.09017976	0.091505971
Sunshine	-0.03437552	-0.101369361	0.111242927	-0.128806565
Radiation	-0.118356151	-0.017744601	0.045341573	-0.207850783
Foehn	0.094376119	-0.05051539	0.000285001	0.016138562
	Humidity	Sunshine	Radiation	Foehn
GPS_V_MproH	0.018587489	0.103277833	0.104745726	-0.039913245
GPS_Temp	0.025164964	-0.009813476	-0.078816945	0.096645735

Temp	-0.626552641	0.086953146	0.211226347	-0.043330758
Dewpoint	-0.186260043	0.096780725	0.12545376	0.027227615
Rain	-0.013806513	-0.03437552	-0.118356151	0.094376119
Wind	-0.062106354	-0.101369361	-0.017744601	-0.05051539
Pressure	0.09017976	0.111242927	0.045341573	0.000285001
Pressure Change	0.091505971	-0.128806565	-0.207850783	0.016138562
Humidity	1	-0.065110665	-0.243542038	0.009753271
Sunshine	-0.065110665	1	0.237852039	0.106784352
Radiation	-0.243542038	0.237852039	1	-0.138112795
Foehn	0.009753271	0.106784352	-0.138112795	1

9.2. Appendix G: Code

9.2.1. 01_Rotwildmonitoring_GPS_DataCleaning_FINAL

```
#!/usr/bin/env python
# coding: utf-8

# GPS DATA
# -----
#
#
# Projekt: Rotwildmonitoring Aletsch
#
# CAS Spatial Information Systems ETH

# DataCleaning
# -----
# GPS Daten
# Zeitraum Cleaned: 1.1.2018 bis 31.03.2021 -> Daten Vorhanden 1.1.2018 bis Sept 2019
#
# (@2021: Daten:WILMA ZHAW, Dienststelle für Jagd und Fischerei, Kanton Wallis.
# script & jupyter notebook by Marco Heinzen, Alpine Robotics GmbH, info@alpine-robotics.com, www.alpine-robotics.com)
# (libraries copyright, see individual libraries, creative commons, MIT Licence)

# in case of crash, clear output:
# jupyter nbconvert --clear-output --inplace Rotwildmonitoring_GPS_DataCleaning_final_02.ipynb

# Import Libraries

# In[61]:
print('Import Libraries')
#import ray
#ray.init()
#import modin.pandas as pd
import pandas as pd
print('Pandas imported')
import numpy as np
print('Numpy imported')

print('Import Libraries for geografic transformations')
print('import os \n import geopandas \n import shapely \n import pyreproj \n import pyproj \n import col-
lections \n import ogr, osr \n import osgeo')

import os
import geopandas
import shapely
import pyreproj
import pyproj
import collections
import ogr, osr
import osgeo
print(' -- successfull \n')

print('Import Math and Itertools')
print('import math \n import itertools \n from itertools import islice')
import math
import itertools
from itertools import islice
print(' -- successfull \n')

print('Import Scikit Learn and matplotlib for statistics and plots')
print('import sklearn \n from sklearn import linear_model \n import matplotlib \n import matplotlib.pyplot as
plt \n %matplotlib inline')
import sklearn
from sklearn import linear_model
import matplotlib
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
get_ipython().run_line_magic('matplotlib', 'inline')
print(' -- successfull \n')

# Options to show full pandas dataframe

# In[62]:
print('Options to show full pandas dataframe \n')
#pd.set_option('display.max_rows', None)
pd.set_option('display.max_columns', None)
#pd.set_option('display.width', None)
#pd.set_option('display.max_colwidth', None)

# Import CSV -> if following steps once calculated and written into df_tempclass.csv, skip these

# In[63]:
path_to_input = r'D:\\info\\Downloads\\CAS_ETH_Spatial_Information_Systems\\Rotwildmonitoring\\'
```

```

# In[64]:
path_to_output = r'D:\\info\\Downloads\\CAS_ETH_Spatial_Information_Systems\\Rotwildmonitoring\\output\\'

# In[65]:
print('Import CSV')
path_gps = path_to_input + 'GPS_fixes_1H_bereinigt_with_act_sigb.csv'
path_animals = path_to_input + 'AnimalsTable.csv'
print(' -- successfull \n')
print('Creating Pandas Dataframe:df_gps')
df_gps =pd.DataFrame(pd.read_csv(path_gps, sep=';', low_memory=False))
print(' -- successfull \n')
print('Creating Pandas Dataframe:df_animals')
df_animals =pd.DataFrame(pd.read_csv(path_animals, sep=',', low_memory=False))
print(' -- successfull \n')

# In[66]:
df_gps

# In[67]:
df_gps.UTC_Date.max()

# In[68]:
df_gps.UTC_Date.min()

# In[69]:
df_animals.StartDatum.min()

# In[70]:
df_animals.StartDatum.max()

# In[71]:
df_animals

# 1.1.2018 bis 31.03.2021 laut tabelle
# Daten bevor 1.1.2018 werden ausgeschlossen

# Add/Copy columns to df_gps

# In[72]:
print('truncate: timestamp twilight_dawn sunrise sunset twilight_dusk to YYYYMMDDHHMMSS')
# truncate: timestamp twilight_dawn sunrise sunset twilight_dusk to YYYYMMDDHHMMSS
df_gps['timestamp_cleaned'] = df_gps['timestamp'].copy()
df_gps['twilight_dawn_cleaned'] = df_gps['twilight_dawn'].copy()
df_gps['sunrise_cleaned'] = df_gps['sunrise'].copy()
df_gps['sunset_cleaned'] = df_gps['sunset'].copy()
df_gps['twilight_dusk_cleaned'] = df_gps['twilight_dusk'].copy()

# In[73]:
print('copy wgs84 to new columns epsg2056 for later geographic projection')
# copy wgs84 to new columns epsg2056 for later geographic projection
df_gps['EPSG2056_lat'] = df_gps['latitude'].copy()
df_gps['EPSG2056_lon'] = df_gps['longitude'].copy()
print(' -- successfull \n')

print('create new columns in df_gps and set them to 0')
# create new columns in df and set them to 0
df_gps['DISTANCE_X'] = 0
df_gps['DISTANCE_Y'] = 0
df_gps['DISTANCE_Z'] = 0
df_gps['DISTANCE_ABSOLUTE'] = 0
df_gps['V_KMproH'] = 0
df_gps['V_MproH'] = 0
df_gps['V_MproS'] = 0

df_gps['Temp_Class'] = 'NaN'

print(' -- successfull \n')

# Show Databases

# In[74]:
df_gps

# In[75]:
df_animals

```

```

# In[76]:
df_gps['Temp_Class'] = np.nan

# In[77]:
#Temperature Classification
buckets = [-100, 0, 15, 30, 100]
buckets_name = ['SubZero', 'Cold', 'Warm', 'Hot']
df_gps['Temp_Class'] = pd.cut(df_gps['Temp'], buckets, labels = buckets_name)

# In[78]:
df_gps['Temp_Class'].unique()

# In[79]:
df_gps.loc[df_gps['Temp_Class'] == 'NaN']

# Merge df_gps and df_animals (JOIN BY TierID)

# In[80]:
print('Merge df_gps and df_animals (JOIN BY TierID)')
df = df_gps.merge(df_animals, on='TierID', how='left')
print('-- successfull \n')

# In[81]:
df['Hoehe_ASL_m'] = df['Height'].copy()
del df['Height']

# In[82]:
print('column copies and cleanup of time format')
print('get hour from UTC Time and copy it in new column for later statistical analysis')
df['UTC_Date'] = pd.to_datetime(df['UTC_Date'])
df['UTC_Time'] = pd.to_datetime(df['UTC_Time'])

# get Month from UTC Date and copy it in new column for later statistical analysis
df['Month'] = pd.to_datetime(df['UTC_Date']).dt.month
print('get hour from UTC Time and copy it in new column for later statistical analysis')
# get hour from UTC Time and copy it in new column for later statistical analysis
df['Hour'] = pd.to_datetime(df['UTC_Time']).dt.hour
print('get day from UTC Time and copy it in new column for later statistical analysis')
# get Day from UTC Time and copy it in new column for later statistical analysis
df['Day'] = pd.to_datetime(df['UTC_Date']).dt.dayofyear

print('-- successfull \n')

# In[83]:
df[['twilight_dawn_cleaned', 'sunrise_cleaned', 'sunset_cleaned', 'twilight_dusk_cleaned']]

# In[84]:
print('truncate: timestamp twilight dawn sunrise sunset twilight dusk to YYYYMMDDHHMMSS')
# truncate: timestamp twilight_dawn sunrise sunset twilight_dusk to YYYYMMDDHHMMSS
df['timestamp_cleaned'].replace(to_replace='[^0-9]+', value='', inplace=True, regex=True)
df['twilight_dawn_cleaned'].replace(to_replace='[^0-9]+', value='', inplace=True, regex=True)
df['sunrise_cleaned'].replace(to_replace='[^0-9]+', value='', inplace=True, regex=True)
df['sunset_cleaned'].replace(to_replace='[^0-9]+', value='', inplace=True, regex=True)
df['twilight_dusk_cleaned'].replace(to_replace='[^0-9]+', value='', inplace=True, regex=True)
print('-- successfull \n')

# In[85]:
df['timestamp_cleaned'] = df['timestamp_cleaned'].map(lambda x: str(x)[:4])

# In[86]:
df['timestamp_cleaned'] = df['timestamp_cleaned'] + '0000'

# In[87]:
df[['timestamp_cleaned', 'twilight_dawn_cleaned', 'sunrise_cleaned', 'sunset_cleaned', 'twilight_dusk_cleaned']]

# In[88]:
df['UTC'] = pd.to_datetime(df.timestamp_cleaned)

# In[89]:
df['UTC1'] = df['UTC'].copy()

# In[90]:

```

```

df['UTC1'].min()

# ADJUST TIMEFRAME HERE BELOW
# -----

# --> TO DO IN SECOND ITERATION OF PROJECT \n
# - extend date range by min max of UTC by 01.01.2018 until 31.03.2021
# - extract proper heights by swissalti3d heights -> done

# In[91]:
start_date = '2018-01-01 00:00:00'
end_date = '2021-03-31 23:00:00'
mask = (df['UTC'] > start_date) & (df['UTC'] <= end_date)
df = df.loc[mask]
df

# In[92]:
print('create new columns in df and set them to 0')
# create new columns in df and set them to 0
df['DISTANCE_X'] = 0
df['DISTANCE_Y'] = 0
df['DISTANCE_Z'] = 0
df['DISTANCE_ABSOLUTE'] = 0
df['V_KMproH'] = 0
df['V_MproH'] = 0
df['V_MproS'] = 0
print(' -- successfull \n')

# Write Results in new Database df_tempclass.csv, after crash: once completed the before calculations you can
start your code here (dont forget import libraries at the beginning)

# In[93]:
# write df_new to csv output
print('write df to csv output')
df.to_csv(path_to_output + 'gps_full.csv', index = False)
print(' -- successfull \n')

# --> import in arcgis pro, Wallis DEM (Swissalti3d -> Wallis -> Gemeinden Boundaries -> Join - Polygon Ober-
wallis ab Visp -> Buffer -> Extract Wallis DEM ) -> Extract Heights at Points -> Export Table to
gps_full_heights.csv table -> Import gps_full_heights to Jupyter Notebook

# In[94]:
print('Import CSV')
path_df = path_to_output + 'gps_full_heights.csv'
print(' -- successfull \n')
print('Creating Pandas Dataframe:df')
df = pd.DataFrame(pd.read_csv(path_df, sep=',', low_memory=False))
print(' -- successfull \n')

# Statistics of DF

# In[95]:
df.info()

# In[96]:
df.describe()

# In[97]:
df.Hoehe_AS_L_m.min()

# In[98]:
df.RASTERVALU.min()

# In[99]:
df_temporary1 = df[df['Hoehe_AS_L_m'] <= 0]
df_temporary1

# In[100]:
df_temporary1 = df[df['RASTERVALU'] <= 0]
df_temporary1

# In[101]:
df_temporary2 = df[df['FixType'] == 'GPS-2D']
df_temporary2

```

```

# In[102]:
df_temporary3 = df[df['Hoehe_ASL_m'] >= 3000]
df_temporary3

# In[103]:
df_temporary3 = df[df['RASTERVALU'] >= 3000]
df_temporary3

# In[104]:
df.Hoehe_ASL_m.max()

# In[105]:
df.RASTERVALU.max()

# In[106]:

df.Temp.min()

# In[107]:
df.Temp.max()

# In[108]:
df_temporary4 = df[df['Temp'] >= 45]
df_temporary4

# In[109]:
df_temporary5 = df[df['Temp'] <= -30]
df_temporary5

# In[110]:
df.plot(x="longitude", y="latitude", kind='scatter')
plt.title('GPS Points Rotwildmonitoring')
plt.xlabel('longitude WGS84 [°]')
plt.ylabel('lattitude WGS84 [°]')

plt.savefig(path_to_output + 'gps_points.png', bbox_inches='tight')

# In[111]:
df.plot(x="Temp", y="Hoehe_ASL_m", kind='scatter')
plt.title('GPS Sensors Temp vs Height')
plt.xlabel('Temperatur GPS Sensor [°C]')
plt.ylabel('Hoehe_ASL_m GPS [m]')

plt.savefig(path_to_output + 'gps_sens_temp_vs_height.png', bbox_inches='tight')

# In[112]:
df.plot(x="Temp", y="RASTERVALU", kind='scatter')
plt.title('GPS Sensor Temp vs Height DEM')
plt.xlabel('Temperatur GPS Sensor [°C]')
plt.ylabel('Hoehe_ASL_m DEM [m]')

plt.savefig(path_to_output + 'gps_sen_temp_vs_height_DEM.png', bbox_inches='tight')

# column copies

# In[243]:
print('Create new result dataframes')
df_results_TierID = pd.DataFrame()
df_results_Hour = pd.DataFrame()
df_results_Day = pd.DataFrame()
df_results_Gender = pd.DataFrame()
#results dataframe
df_results_TierID['TierID'] = 0
df_results_TierID['Mean_V_MproS_perDeer'] = 0
df_results_TierID['STD_V_MproS_perDeer'] = 0
df_results_TierID['MIN_V_MproS_perDeer'] = 0
df_results_TierID['MAX_V_MproS_perDeer'] = 0

df_results_Hour['Hour'] = 0
df_results_Hour['Mean_V_MproS_perHour'] = 0
df_results_Hour['STD_V_MproS_perHour'] = 0
df_results_Hour['MIN_V_MproS_perHour'] = 0
df_results_Hour['MAX_V_MproS_perHour'] = 0

df_results_Day['Day'] = 0

```

```

df_results_Day['Mean_V_MproH_perDay'] = 0
df_results_Day['STD_V_MproH_perDay'] = 0
df_results_Day['MIN_V_MproH_perDay'] = 0
df_results_Day['MAX_V_MproH_perDay'] = 0
df_results_Day['Mean_Temp_perDay'] = 0
df_results_Day['STD_Temp_perDay'] = 0
df_results_Day['Min_Temp_perDay'] = 0
df_results_Day['Max_Temp_perDay'] = 0

df_results_Gender['Geschlecht'] = 'x'
df_results_Gender['Mean_V_MproH_perGender'] = 0
df_results_Gender['STD_V_MproH_perGender'] = 0
df_results_Gender['MIN_V_MproH_perGender'] = 0
df_results_Gender['MAX_V_MproH_perGender'] = 0
print(' -- successfull \n')

# In[114]:
df['CollarID'] = df['CollarID_y'].copy()
del df['CollarID_y']
del df['CollarID_x']
del df['timestamp']

del df['twilight_dawn']
del df['sunrise']
del df['sunset']
del df['twilight_dusk']

# In[115]:
df['Hoehe_AS_L_m_DEM'] = df.RASTERVALU.copy()
del df['RASTERVALU']
df

# In[116]:
df['Height_Difference'] = df.Hoehe_AS_L_m.sub(df.Hoehe_AS_L_m_DEM)

# In[117]:
df['Height_Difference'].describe()

# In[118]:
df.Hoehe_AS_L_m_DEM.fillna(df.Hoehe_AS_L_m, inplace=True)

# In[119]:
print('copy wgs84 to new columns epsg2056 for later geographic projection')
# copy wgs84 to new columns epsg2056 for later geographic projection
df['EPSG2056_lat'] = df['latitude'].copy()
df['EPSG2056_lon'] = df['longitude'].copy()
print(' -- successfull \n')
df['WGS84_Breite'] = df['latitude']
df['WGS84_Laenge'] = df['longitude']

del df['latitude']
del df['longitude']

# In[120]:
print('project wgs84 longitude and latitude to EPSG2056 CH1903+ LV95 into two new rows in meters "EPSG2056_X"
and "EPSG2056_Y", copy Height to "EPSG2056_Z" \n')

# Spatial Reference System
inputEPSG = 4326
outputEPSG = 2056
# create coordinate transformation
inSpatialRef = osr.SpatialReference()
inSpatialRef.ImportFromEPSG(inputEPSG)
print(inSpatialRef)
print("\n")
#import spatial reference
outSpatialRef = osr.SpatialReference()
outSpatialRef.ImportFromEPSG(outputEPSG)
print(outSpatialRef)
print("\n")
#coordinate transformation
coordTransform = osr.CoordinateTransformation(inSpatialRef, outSpatialRef)
print(coordTransform)
print(' -- successfull \n')

# In[121]:
print('project WGS84 to EPSG2056')
for row in df.itertuples():
# for loop iterating through rows in df

```

```

# get pointX and PointX from EPSG2056_lat and EPSG2056_lon in row
pointX = row.WGS84_Breite
pointY = row.WGS84_Laenge
# add pointX and pointY as osgeo Point
point = ogr.Geometry(ogr.wkbPoint)
point.AddPoint(pointY, pointX)
# Transform
print("WGS84: ", point)
point.Transform(coordTransform)
# print point in EPSG 4326
print("EPSG2056: ", point)
print("\n")
# convert back tuple back to each row
df.at[row.Index, 'EPSG2056_lat']=point.GetX()
df.at[row.Index, 'EPSG2056_lon']=point.GetY()
print(' -- successfull \n')

# In[122]:
# write df_new to csv output
print('write df to csv output')
df.to_csv(path_to_output + 'gps_epsg.csv', index = False)
print(' -- successfull \n')

# In[123]:
print('Import CSV')
path_df = path_to_output + 'gps_epsg.csv'
print(' -- successfull \n')
print('Creating Pandas Dataframe:df')
df = pd.DataFrame(pd.read_csv(path_df, sep=',', low_memory=False))
print(' -- successfull \n')

# In[124]:
df['UTC'] = pd.to_datetime(df['UTC'], errors='coerce').copy()

# In[125]:
print('column copies and cleanup of time format')
print('get hour from UTC Time and copy it in new column for later statistical analysis')
df['UTC'] = pd.to_datetime(df['UTC'], errors='coerce')
df['UTC1'] = pd.to_datetime(df['UTC1'], errors='coerce')

# In[126]:
df['UTC_Date'] = df['UTC'].dt.date
df['UTC_Time'] = df['UTC'].dt.time

print(' -- successfull \n')

# In[127]:
# get Month from UTC Date and copy it in new column for later statistical analysis
df['Month'] = pd.to_datetime(df['UTC']).dt.month
print('get hour from UTC Time and copy it in new column for later statistical analysis')
# get hour from UTC Time and copy it in new column for later statistical analysis
df['Hour'] = pd.to_datetime(df['UTC']).dt.hour
print('get day from UTC Time and copy it in new column for later statistical analysis')
# get Day from UTC Time and copy it in new column for later statistical analysis
df['Day'] = pd.to_datetime(df['UTC']).dt.dayofyear

print(' -- successfull \n')

# Split Dataframe by TierID

# In[128]:
df = df.set_index('UTC')

# In[129]:
df = df.sort_index()
df

# In[130]:
df = df.reset_index()

# In[131]:
df.index = range(len(df.index))

# In[132]:
df

```

```

# In[133]:
print('Split Dataframe by TierID')
TierIDs = df_animals['TierID'].unique()
TierIDs2 = df_gps['TierID'].unique()
TierIDs3 = df['TierID'].unique()
print(' -- successfull \n')

# In[134]:
print('TierIDs in Animals Dataframe:', len(TierIDs), '\n', TierIDs, '\n')

# In[135]:
print('TierIDs in GPS Dataframe:', len(TierIDs2), '\n', TierIDs2, '\n')

# In[136]:
print('TierIDs in GPS Dataframe:', len(TierIDs3), '\n', TierIDs3, '\n')

# In[137]:
print('there are', abs(len(TierIDs)-len(TierIDs2)), 'animals missing in gps dataframe \n' )

# In[138]:
del df_animals

# In[139]:
df

# In[140]:
print('splitting merged dataframe by TierID - groupby')
#splitting merged dataframe by TierID - groupby
grouped = df.groupby(df.TierID)
df_list_grouped = list(grouped)
df_list_grouped[0][1] #erster Index = je Gruppe von TierID -> Dataframe
print(' -- successfull \n')

# In[141]:
df.loc[df.index == 57991]

# Calculate Distances and Velocity for each TierID

# Problems:
# Points are just every hour -> distances can only be calculated as absolute distance between hourly points ->
this does not represent the real movement in this hour
# ---> deer can move alot in 1 hour but in hourly view just moved a little as long as deer came back to almost
same point in next hour measurement
# ----> possible solution could be to multiply velocity with activity and create vel_act_index which maybe
would better correlate with weather

# In[142]:
#print('Calculate Distances and Velocity for each TierID \n')
# df_list_grouped[0][1] #erster Index = je Gruppe von TierID -> Dataframe
count = len(df['TierID'].unique())
#print('count: ', count)
tick = 0
#print('tick: ', tick)
index=1
currentTierID = df.loc[20321,'TierID']
#print('currentTierID: ', currentTierID)
#print('\n')
#print('\n')
#print('\n')

for tick in range(count):
    df_list_grouped[tick][1].index = range(len(df_list_grouped[tick][1].index))
    for index, row in islice(df_list_grouped[tick][1].iterrows(), 1, None):
        currentTierID = df_list_grouped[tick][1].loc[index,'TierID']
        #print('tick: ', tick)
        #print('index: ', index)
        #print('CurrentID: ', currentTierID)
        ##print('row: ', row)
        #print('\n')
        lat_n = df_list_grouped[tick][1].loc[index,'EPSG2056_lat']
        lon_n = df_list_grouped[tick][1].loc[index,'EPSG2056_lon']
        height_n = df_list_grouped[tick][1].loc[index,'Hoehe_AS_L_m_DEM']
        #print('LATITUDE n: ', lat_n)
        #print('LONGITUDE n: ', lon_n)
        #print('HEIGHT_DEM n: ', height_n)
        lat_n_1 = df_list_grouped[tick][1].loc[index-1,'EPSG2056_lat']
        lon_n_1 = df_list_grouped[tick][1].loc[index-1,'EPSG2056_lon']

```

```

height_n_1 = df_list_grouped[tick][1].loc[index-1, 'Hoehe_AS_L_m_DEM']
#print('LATITUDE n-1: ', lat_n_1)
#print('LONGITUDE n-1: ', lon_n_1)
#print('HEIGHT_DEM n-1: ', height_n_1)

if df_list_grouped[tick][1].loc[index, 'TierID'] != currentTierID:
    #print('NEW TIER_ID')
    #print(currentTierID)
    #print('INDEX: ', index)
    df_list_grouped[tick][1].loc[index, 'DISTANCE_X'] = 0
    #print('DISTANCE_X: ', df_list_grouped[tick][1].loc[index, 'DISTANCE_X'])
    df_list_grouped[tick][1].loc[index, 'DISTANCE_Y'] = 0
    #print('DISTANCE_Y: ', df_list_grouped[tick][1].loc[index, 'DISTANCE_Y'])
    df_list_grouped[tick][1].loc[index, 'DISTANCE_Z'] = 0
    #print('DISTANCE_Z: ', df_list_grouped[tick][1].loc[index, 'DISTANCE_Z'])
    df_list_grouped[tick][1].loc[index, 'DISTANCE_ABSOLUTE'] = 0
    #print('DISTANCE_ABSOLUTE: ', df_list_grouped[tick][1].loc[index, 'DISTANCE_ABSOLUTE'])
    df_list_grouped[tick][1].loc[index, 'V_KMproH'] = 0
    #print('V_KMproH: ', df_list_grouped[tick][1].loc[index, 'V_KMproH'])
    df_list_grouped[tick][1].loc[index, 'V_MproH'] = 0
    #print('V_MproH: ', df_list_grouped[tick][1].loc[index, 'V_MproH'])
    df_list_grouped[tick][1].loc[index, 'V_MproS'] = 0
    #print('V_MproS: ', df_list_grouped[tick][1].loc[index, 'V_MproS'])

elif df_list_grouped[tick][1].loc[index, 'TierID'] == currentTierID:
    #print('SAME TIER_ID')
    #print(currentTierID)
    #print('INDEX: ', index)
    df_list_grouped[tick][1].loc[index, 'DISTANCE_X'] = abs((lat_n)-(lat_n_1))
    #print('DISTANCE_X: ', df_list_grouped[tick][1].loc[index, 'DISTANCE_X'])
    df_list_grouped[tick][1].loc[index, 'DISTANCE_Y'] = abs((lon_n)-(lon_n_1))
    #print('DISTANCE_Y: ', df_list_grouped[tick][1].loc[index, 'DISTANCE_Y'])
    df_list_grouped[tick][1].loc[index, 'DISTANCE_Z'] = abs((height_n)-(height_n_1))
    #print('DISTANCE_Z: ', df_list_grouped[tick][1].loc[index, 'DISTANCE_Z'])
    df_list_grouped[tick][1].loc[index, 'DISTANCE_ABSOLUTE'] =
math.sqrt(pow(df_list_grouped[tick][1].loc[index, 'DISTANCE_X'], 2)+pow(df_list_grouped[tick][1].loc[index, 'DIS-
TANCE_Y'], 2)+pow(df_list_grouped[tick][1].loc[index, 'DISTANCE_Z'], 2))
    #print('DISTANCE_ABSOLUTE: ', df_list_grouped[tick][1].loc[index, 'DISTANCE_ABSOLUTE'])
    df_list_grouped[tick][1].loc[index, 'V_KMproH'] = df_list_grouped[tick][1].loc[index, 'DISTANCE_ABSO-
LUTE'] / 1000
    df_list_grouped[tick][1].loc[index, 'V_MproH'] = df_list_grouped[tick][1].loc[index, 'DISTANCE_ABSO-
LUTE']
    df_list_grouped[tick][1].loc[index, 'V_MproS'] = df_list_grouped[tick][1].loc[index, 'DISTANCE_ABSO-
LUTE'] / 3600
    currentTierID = df_list_grouped[tick][1].loc[index, 'TierID']
    #print(index, 'rows processed \n')
    print('DATAFRAME', tick, 'processed \n')
    tick += 1
#print(' -- successfull \n')

# In[143]:
# write csv files by TierID
print('write csv files by TierID')
count=0
path = "D:\\info\\Downloads\\CAS_ETH_Spatial_Information_Systems\\Rotwildmonitoring\\output"
outfilename = 'outfilename'

#loop to write individual csv files
for tier_ID in TierIDs:
    outfilename = '00' + str(count) + '_' + 'NewTierID_dataframe.csv'
    pathANDfilename = os.path.join(path, outfilename)
    df_list_grouped[count][1].to_csv(pathANDfilename)
    print(outfilename)
    if count == (len(TierIDs2)-1):
        break
    count += 1
print(' -- successfull \n')

# In[144]:
#append splitted dataframes to new dataframe: df_new
print('append splitted dataframes to new dataframe: df_new')
df_new = pd.DataFrame()
count = 0
for tier_ID in TierIDs:
    df_new = df_new.append(df_list_grouped[count][1])
    if count == (len(TierIDs2)-1):
        break
    count += 1
print(' -- successfull \n')
df_new

# In[145]:
del df

```

```

# Statistics of DF

# In[146]:
df_new.info()

# In[147]:
df_new.describe()

# In[148]:
df_new['Height_Difference'] = df_new.Hoehe_ASL_m.sub(df_new.Hoehe_ASL_m_DEM)

# In[149]:
df_new['Height_Difference'].describe()

# In[150]:
df_new.Hoehe_ASL_m_DEM.min()

# In[151]:
df_new_temporary1 = df_new[df_new['Hoehe_ASL_m_DEM'] <= 0]
df_new_temporary1

# In[152]:
df_new_temporary3 = df_new[df_new['Hoehe_ASL_m'] >= 3000]
df_new_temporary3

# In[153]:

df_new.Hoehe_ASL_m_DEM.max()

# In[154]:
df_new.Temp.min()

# In[155]:
df_new.Temp.max()

# In[156]:
df_new_temporary4 = df_new[df_new['Temp'] >= 45]
df_new_temporary4

# In[157]:
df_new_temporary5 = df_new[df_new['Temp'] <= -30]
df_new_temporary5

# In[158]:
df_new.plot(x="EPSG2056_lat", y="EPSG2056_lon", kind='scatter')
plt.title('CH1903+ Coordinates')
plt.xlabel('Latitude [m]')
plt.ylabel('Longitude [m]')

plt.savefig(path_to_output + 'CH1903.png', bbox_inches='tight')

# In[159]:
df_new.plot(x="Temp", y="Hoehe_ASL_m_DEM", kind='scatter')

# In[184]:
df_new.columns.tolist()

# In[185]:
colscorr = [
    'Temp',
    'Jahreszeit_4season',
    'daytime',
    'ActivitySum',
    'ActivityMean',
    'V_MproH',
    'Temp_Class',
    'Geschlecht',
    'Month',
    'Hour',
    'Day']

```

```

# In[186]:
df_corr = df_new[colscorr]
df_corr = df_corr.corr()
df_corr

# In[187]:
# write df_new to csv output
print('write df to csv output')
df_corr.to_csv(path_to_output + 'gps_corr.csv', index = False)
print(' -- successfull \n')

# In[161]:
import seaborn as sns

# In[192]:
sns_plot = sns.heatmap(df_corr,xticklabels=True, yticklabels=True)
sns_plot.figure.savefig(path_to_output + "gps_corr.png", bbox_inches='tight')
sns_plot

# In[163]:
# write df_new to csv output
print('write df_new to csv output')
df_new.to_csv(path_to_output + 'AnimalsGPSExtended.csv', index = False)
print(' -- successfull \n')

# In[193]:
print('Import calculated CSV')
path_extended = path_to_output + 'AnimalsGPSExtended.csv'
print(' -- successfull \n')
print('Creating Pandas Dataframe:df_new')
df_new = pd.DataFrame(pd.read_csv(path_extended, sep=',', low_memory=False))
print(' -- successfull \n')

# In[194]:
df_new_cols = df_new.columns.tolist()

# In[195]:
df_new_cols

# In[196]:
df_new_cols2 =[ 'UTC',
'TierID',
'No',
'Geschlecht',
'Name',
'Ohrmarke',
'Gebiet',
'Temp', 'Temp_Class', 'ActivitySum',
'Components',
'ActivityMean',
'x','y', 'WGS84_Breite',
'WGS84_Laenge', 'EPSG2056_lat',
'EPSG2056_lon', 'Hoehe_ASL_m_DEM', 'Hoehe_ASL_m', 'Height_Difference',
'DISTANCE_X',
'DISTANCE_Y',
'DISTANCE_Z',
'DISTANCE_ABSOLUTE',
'V_KMproH',
'V_MproH',
'V_MproS',
'Einstand_2month',
'Jahreszeit_4season',
'Jahreszeit_Halbjahr',
'daytime',
'UTC1', 'year', 'Month', 'Day', 'Hour',
'timestamp_cleaned',
'twilight_dawn_cleaned',
'sunrise_cleaned',
'sunset_cleaned',
'twilight_dusk_cleaned',
'StartDatum',
'StopDatum',
'StartMonat',
'StartJahr',
'StopMonat',
'StopJahr',
'Status',

```

```

'Start2Datum',
'Stop2Datum',
'Start2Monat',
'Start2Jahr',
'Stopp2Monat',
'Stopp2Jahr',
'Status2',
'DatenEndeMonat',
'Abgeschlossen',
'UTC_Date',
'UTC_Time',
'LMT_Date',
'LMT_Time',
'DOP',
'FixType', 'CollarID'
]

```

```

# In[197]:
df_small = df_new[df_new_cols2]

```

```

# In[198]:
del df_new

```

```

# In[199]:
# write df_new to csv output
print('write df_new to csv output')
df_small.to_csv(path_to_output+'GPS_small.csv', index = False)
print(' -- successfull \n')

```

```

# In[200]:
print('Import calculated CSV')
path_small = path_to_output+'GPS_small.csv'
print(' -- successfull \n')
print('Creating Pandas Dataframe:df_new')
df_small = pd.DataFrame(pd.read_csv(path_small, sep=',', low_memory=False))
print(' -- successfull \n')

```

```

# In[201]:
print('splitting merged dataframe by TierID - groupby')
#splitting merged dataframe by TierID - groupby
grouped = df_small.groupby(df_small.TierID)
df_list_grouped = list(grouped)
df_list_grouped[0][1] #erster Index = je Gruppe von TierID -> Dataframe
print(' -- successfull \n')

```

```

# In[202]:
df_results_TierID = pd.DataFrame()

```

```

# In[203]:
# calculate mean and std by grouped Dataframe TierID
print('calculate mean and std by grouped Dataframe TierID')
TierIDs2 = df_small['TierID'].unique()
count = len(df_small['TierID'].unique())
tick = 0
currentTierID = df_small.loc[0,'TierID']
#loop to write individual csv files
tick = 0
for tick in range(count):
    tier_ID = df_list_grouped[tick][1].TierID.unique()
    df_results_TierID.loc[tick, 'TierID'] = tier_ID
    mean = df_list_grouped[tick][1].V_MproH.mean()
    std = df_list_grouped[tick][1].V_MproH.std()
    minimum = df_list_grouped[tick][1].V_MproH.min()
    maximum = df_list_grouped[tick][1].V_MproH.max()

    print(tier_ID, 'mean: ', mean, 'std: ', std)
    df_results_TierID.loc[tick,'Mean_V_MproH_perDeer'] = mean
    df_results_TierID.loc[tick,'Mean_DISTANCE_ABSOLUTE_perDeer'] = mean
    df_results_TierID.loc[tick,'STD_V_MproH_perDeer'] = std
    df_results_TierID.loc[tick,'STD_DISTANCE_ABSOLUTE_perDeer'] = std
    df_results_TierID.loc[tick,'MIN_V_MproH_perDeer'] = minimum
    df_results_TierID.loc[tick,'MAX_V_MproH_perDeer'] = maximum
    print('Dataframe', tick, 'processed \n')
    if count == (len(TierIDs2)-1):
        break
    tick += 1
print(' -- successfull \n')

```

```

# In[204]:

```

```

df_results_TierID_cols = df_results_TierID.columns.tolist()
df_results_TierID_cols

# In[205]:
df_results_TierID_cols2 = ['TierID','MIN_V_MproH_perDeer','MAX_V_MproH_perDeer','Mean_V_MproH_perDeer',
'STD_V_MproH_perDeer','Mean_DISTANCE_ABSOLUTE_perDeer','STD_DISTANCE_ABSOLUTE_perDeer',]

# In[206]:
df_results_TierID = df_results_TierID[df_results_TierID_cols2]
df_results_TierID

# In[207]:
# write df_new to csv output
print('write df_results_TierID to csv output')
df_results_TierID.to_csv(path_to_output+'statistic_results_TierID.csv', index = False)
print(' -- successfull \n')

# In[180]:
ax = df_results_TierID.plot.bar(y='Mean_V_MproH_perDeer', yerr='STD_V_MproH_perDeer', figsize=(30,8), sub-
plots=True,sharex=True,sharey=True,title='Mean Velocity m/h per Deer', rot=0)
plt.title('Mean MproH per Deer')
plt.xlabel('TierID')
plt.ylabel('Mean and STD [m/h]')
plt.savefig(path_to_output + 'MeanV_MproH_perDeer.png', bbox_inches='tight')

# In[208]:
print('splitting merged dataframe by Hour - groupby')
#splitting merged dataframe by Hour - groupby
grouped2 = df_small.groupby(df_small.Hour)
df_list_grouped2 = list(grouped2)
df_list_grouped2[0][1] #erster Index = je Gruppe von Stunden -> Dataframe
print(' -- successfull \n')
df_list_grouped2[0][1]

# In[209]:
# calculate mean and std by grouped Dataframe Hour
print('calculate mean and std by grouped Dataframe Hour')
count = len(df_small['Hour'].unique())-1
print(count)
#loop to write individual csv files
tick = 0
for tick in range(count):
    print(tick)
    df_results_Hour.loc[tick,'Hour'] = tick
    mean = df_list_grouped2[tick][1].V_MproH.mean()
    std = df_list_grouped2[tick][1].V_MproH.std()
    minimum = df_list_grouped2[tick][1].V_MproH.min()
    maximum = df_list_grouped2[tick][1].V_MproH.max()

    print(tick, 'mean: ', mean, 'std: ', std, 'min: ', minimum, 'max: ', maximum )

    df_results_Hour.loc[tick,'Mean_V_MproH_perHour'] = mean
    df_results_Hour.loc[tick,'STD_V_MproH_perHour'] = std
    df_results_Hour.loc[tick,'MIN_V_MproH_perHour'] = minimum
    df_results_Hour.loc[tick,'MAX_V_MproH_perHour'] = maximum

    print('Dataframe', tick, 'processed \n')
    if tick == count:
        break
    tick += 1
print(' -- successfull \n')

# In[210]:
ax = df_results_Hour.plot.bar(y='Mean_V_MproH_perHour', yerr='STD_V_MproH_perHour', figsize=(30,8), sub-
plots=True,sharex=True,sharey=True,title='Mean Velocity m/h per day hours', rot=0)
plt.title('Mean MproH per Hours')
plt.xlabel('Hour [h]')
plt.ylabel('Mean and STD [m/h]')
plt.savefig(path_to_output + 'MeanV_MproH_perHours.png', bbox_inches='tight')

# In[211]:
df_small

# In[227]:
#optional
print('get day from UTC Time and copy it in new column for later statistical analysis')
# get Day from UTC Time and copy it in new column for later statistical analysis
df_small['Day'] = pd.to_datetime(df_small['UTC']).dt.dayofyear

```

```

print(' -- successfull \n')

# In[232]:
print('splitting merged dataframe by Day - groupby')
#splitting merged dataframe by Hour - groupby
grouped4 = df_small.groupby(df_small.Day)
df_list_day = list(grouped4)
print(' -- successfull \n')
#df_list_day[0][1].Day #erster Index = je Gruppe von TierID -> Dataframe

# In[236]:
year=365
blip=0
for blip in range(year):
    day = df_list_day[blip][1].Day
    days = day[:1].unique()
    df_results_Day.loc[blip, 'Day'] = days[0]
    df_results_Day.loc[blip, 'Mean_V_MproH_perDay'] = df_list_day[blip][1].V_MproH.mean()
    df_results_Day.loc[blip, 'STD_V_MproH_perDay'] = df_list_day[blip][1].V_MproH.std()
    df_results_Day.loc[blip, 'MIN_V_MproH_perDay'] = df_list_day[blip][1].V_MproH.min()
    df_results_Day.loc[blip, 'MAX_V_MproH_perDay'] = df_list_day[blip][1].V_MproH.max()
    df_results_Day.loc[blip, 'Mean_Temp_perDay'] = df_list_day[blip][1].Temp.mean()
    df_results_Day.loc[blip, 'STD_Temp_perDay'] = df_list_day[blip][1].Temp.std()
    df_results_Day.loc[blip, 'Min_Temp_perDay'] = df_list_day[blip][1].Temp.min()
    df_results_Day.loc[blip, 'Max_Temp_perDay'] = df_list_day[blip][1].Temp.max()
    print('Day', blip+1, 'processed \n')
    if blip == 365:
        break
    blip += 1
print(' -- successfull \n')

# In[237]:
df_results_Day

# In[238]:
# write df_new to csv output
print('write df_results_TierID to csv output')
df_results_Day.to_csv(path_to_output+'results_Day.csv', index = False)
print(' -- successfull \n')

# In[ ]:
# In[239]:
ax = df_results_Day.plot('Day', 'Mean_V_MproH_perDay')
df_results_Day.plot('Day', 'Mean_Temp_perDay', figsize=(60,8), title='Mean Velocity [m/h] and Temperature [°C] per
Day', secondary_y=True, ax=ax)
plt.xlabel('Day [d]')
plt.ylabel('Mean V [m/h] and Temperatur [°C]')
plt.savefig(path_to_output + 'MeanVandTempperDay.png', bbox_inches='tight')

# In[240]:
dfs = [rows for , rows in df_small.groupby('Geschlecht')]
mean_m = dfs[0].V_MproH.mean() #m
std_m = dfs[0].V_MproH.std() #m
min_m = dfs[0].V_MproH.min() #m
max_m = dfs[0].V_MproH.max() #m

mean_w = dfs[1].V_MproH.mean() #w
std_w = dfs[1].V_MproH.std() #w
min_w = dfs[1].V_MproH.min() #w
max_w = dfs[1].V_MproH.max() #w

print('m: ', mean_m, '(mean m/h)', std_m, ('std m/h'), min_m, '(min m/h)', max_m, ('max m/h'))
print('w: ', mean_w, '(mean m/h)', std_w, ('std m/h'), min_m, '(min m/h)', max_m, ('max m/h'))

# In[244]:
df_results_Gender.loc[0, 'Geschlecht'] = 'm'
df_results_Gender.loc[0, 'Mean_V_MproH_perGender'] = mean_m
df_results_Gender.loc[0, 'STD_V_MproH_perGender'] = std_m
df_results_Gender.loc[0, 'MIN_V_MproH_perGender'] = min_m
df_results_Gender.loc[0, 'MAX_V_MproH_perGender'] = max_m

df_results_Gender.loc[1, 'Geschlecht'] = 'w'
df_results_Gender.loc[1, 'Mean_V_MproH_perGender'] = mean_w
df_results_Gender.loc[1, 'STD_V_MproH_perGender'] = std_w
df_results_Gender.loc[1, 'MIN_V_MproH_perGender'] = min_w
df_results_Gender.loc[1, 'MAX_V_MproH_perGender'] = max_w

# In[245]:
df_results_Gender

```

```

# In[248]:
# write df_new to csv output
print('write df_results_TierID to csv output')
df_results_Gender.to_csv(path_to_output + 'results_Gender.csv', index = False)
print(' -- successfull \n')

# In[249]:
dfcopy = df_small[['Temp', 'V_MproH']].copy()
dfdropna = dfcopy.dropna()

# In[250]:
dfdropna

# In[252]:
dfdropna = dfdropna.drop(dfdropna[dfdropna.Temp < -40].index)
x_temp = dfdropna[['Temp']].copy()
y_v = dfdropna[['V_MproH']].copy()

print("Number of null values in column 1 : " +
      str(x_temp.isna().sum()))
print("Number of null values in column 2 : " +
      str(y_v.isna().sum()))

#df_new = df_new.drop(df_new[df_new.Temp < -40].index)

# In[257]:
regr = linear_model.LinearRegression()
regr.fit(x_temp, y_v)
print('Regression Coefficient' , regr.coef_)

# The mean square error
meansquare_error = np.mean((regr.predict(x_temp) - y_v)**2)
print('Mean Square Error: ', meansquare_error)
regr_score = regr.score(x_temp, y_v)
print('Regression Score: ', regr_score)
matplotlib.pyplot.plot(x_temp, y_v, 'bo')
plt.title("Linear Regression: Temperatur vs Bewegungsgeschwindigkeit")
plt.xlabel("Temperatur °C")
plt.ylabel("Bewegungsgeschwindigkeit m/h")
plt.savefig(path_to_output + 'LinRegMeanVSTemp.jpg')

# In[259]:
df_daytime_v_mean = df_small.groupby('daytime')['V_MproS'].mean()
ax = df_daytime_v_mean.plot.bar(y='V_MproH', rot=0)
plt.title("Mean Velocity by Daytime")
plt.xlabel("Daytime")
plt.ylabel("Mean Velocity [m/h]")
plt.savefig(path_to_output + 'daytime.jpg')

# In[260]:
df_temp_class = df_small

# In[261]:
df_temp_class

# In[262]:
df_temp_class_v_mean = df_temp_class.groupby('Temp_Class')['V_MproH'].mean()

# In[263]:
df_temp_class_v_mean

# In[264]:
order = ['SubZero', 'Cold', 'Warm', 'Hot']
df_temp_class_v_mean2 = df_temp_class_v_mean.loc[order]

# In[265]:
ax = df_temp_class_v_mean2.plot.bar('Temp_Class', rot=0)
plt.title("Mean Velocity by Temp Class")
plt.xlabel("Temp Classes")
plt.ylabel("Mean Velocity [m/h]")
plt.savefig(path_to_output + 'Tempclass.jpg')

```

```

# In[268]:
dfdropna = df_small.dropna(subset = ['V_MproS', 'Temp'])

# In[269]:
dfdropna = dfdropna[['V_MproH', 'Temp']]
dfdropna = dfdropna[dfdropna.Temp > -30]

dfdropna

# In[270]:
df_small.index = pd.to_datetime(df_small['UTC1'])
df_small

# In[271]:
del df_small['UTC1']

# In[272]:
df_small = df_small.reset_index()

# In[273]:
df_small.index

# In[274]:
y = dfdropna.V_MproH
X = dfdropna.Temp

# In[275]:
mean_x = X.mean()
mean_y = y.mean()
print('Mean Temp', mean_x)
print('Mean Velocity', mean_y)

# In[276]:
mean_x

# In[277]:
mean_y

# In[278]:
dfdropna.Temp.describe()

# In[279]:
dfdropna.V_MproH.describe()

# In[280]:
np.mean(y)

# In[284]:
import scipy

# In[285]:
scipy.stats.describe(X)

# In[286]:
scipy.stats.describe(y)

```

9.2.2. 02_Rotwildmonitoring_Weather_Data_final.ipynb

```
#!/usr/bin/env python
# coding: utf-8

# WEATHER DATA
# -----
#
#
# Projekt: Rotwildmonitoring Aletsch
#
# CAS Spatial Information Systems ETH
#

# Datacleaning
# -----
#
# MeteoSchweiz (IDAWEB)
# -----
#
# Wetterdaten 1.1.2018 bis 31.03.2021
#
# (©2021: script & jupyter notebook by Marco Heinzen, Alpine Robotics GmbH, info@alpine-robotics.com, www.al-
pine-robotics.com)
# (libraries copyright, see individual libraries, creative commons, MIT Licence)

# In[1]:
#Import Libraries
print('Import Libraries')
import pandas as pd
print('Pandas imported')
import numpy as np
print('Numpy imported')
print(' -- successfull \n')

#Import Libraries for geografic transformations
print('Import Libraries for geografic transformations')
print('import os \n import geopandas \n import shapely \n import pyreproj \n import pyproj \n import col-
lections \n import ogr, osr \n import osgeo')
import os
#import geopandas
import shapely
import pyreproj
import pyproj
import collections
import ogr, osr
import osgeo
print(' -- successfull \n')

import io

#Import Math and Itertools
print('Import Math and Itertools')
print('import math \n import itertools \n from itertools import islice')
import math
import itertools
from itertools import islice
print(' -- successfull \n')

#Import Scikit Learn and matplotlib for statistics and plots
print('Import Scikit Learn and matplotlib for statistics and plots')
print('import sklearn \n from sklearn import linear_model \n import matplotlib \n import matplotlib.pyplot as
plt \n %matplotlib inline')
import sklearn
from sklearn import linear_model
import matplotlib
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
get_ipython().run_line_magic('matplotlib', 'inline')
print(' -- successfull \n')

#Options to show full pandas dataframe
print('Options to show full pandas dataframe \n')
#pd.set_option('display.max_rows', None)
#pd.set_option('display.max_columns', None)
#pd.set_option('display.width', None)
#pd.set_option('display.max_colwidth', None)

print('Set display of dataframe to max columns')
pd.set_option('display.max_columns', None)
print(' -- successfull \n')

# In[2]:
```

```

print('project wgs84 longitude and latitude to EPSG2056 CH1903+ LV95 into two new rows in meters "EPSG2056_X"
and "EPSG2056_Y", copy Height to "EPSG2056_Z" \n')

# Spatial Reference System
inputEPSG = 4326
outputEPSG = 2056
# create coordinate transformation
inSpatialRef = osr.SpatialReference()
inSpatialRef.ImportFromEPSG(inputEPSG)
print(inSpatialRef)
print("\n")
#import spatial reference
outSpatialRef = osr.SpatialReference()
outSpatialRef.ImportFromEPSG(outputEPSG)
print(outSpatialRef)
print("\n")
#coordinate transformation
coordTransform = osr.CoordinateTransformation(inSpatialRef, outSpatialRef)
print(coordTransform)
print(' -- successfull \n')

# Import CSV

# In[3]:
path_to_output = r'D:\\info\\Downloads\\CAS_ETH_Spatial_Information_Systems\\Rotwildmonitoring\\output\\'

# In[4]:
path_meteo_ch = 'D:\\info\\Downloads\\CAS_ETH_Spatial_Information_Systems\\Rotwildmonitoring\\MeteoSchweiz\\'

# In[5]:
print('Import CSV')
path_wind_parameter = path_meteo_ch + 'order93782\\WIND_Parameter_Meteo_Schweiz_order_93782.csv'
print(' -- successfull \n')
print('Creating Pandas Dataframe:df_wind')
df_wind_parameters =pd.DataFrame(pd.read_csv(path_wind_parameter, sep=',', low_memory=False))
print(' -- successfull \n')
df_wind_parameters

# In[6]:
print('Import CSV')
path_wind_legend = path_meteo_ch + 'order93782\\WIND_CLEANED_LEGEND_Meteo_Schweiz_order_93782.csv'
print(' -- successfull \n')
print('Creating Pandas Dataframe:df_wind_legend')
df_wind_legend =pd.DataFrame(pd.read_csv(path_wind_legend, sep=',', low_memory=False))
print(' -- successfull \n')
df_wind_legend

# In[7]:
df_wind_legend.merge(df_wind_parameters, left_on='Parameter', right_on='Parameter')

# In[8]:
df_wind_legend['Parameter_fkl010h1'] = 'fkl010h1'
df_wind_legend['Parameter_fkl010h0'] = 'fkl010h0'
df_wind_legend['Parameter_dkl010h0'] = 'dkl010h0'
df_wind_legend['Parameter_wcc006s0'] = 'wcc006s0'
df_wind_legend['Datenquelle_fkl010h1'] = 'NaN'
df_wind_legend['Datenquelle_fkl010h0'] = 'NaN'
df_wind_legend['Datenquelle_dkl010h0'] = 'NaN'
df_wind_legend['Datenquelle_wcc006s0'] = 'NaN'
df_wind_legend['Einheit_fkl010h1'] = 'm/s'
df_wind_legend['Einheit_fkl010h0'] = 'm/s'
df_wind_legend['Einheit_dkl010h0'] = 'Grad'
df_wind_legend['Einheit_wcc006s0'] = 'Code'
df_wind_legend['Beschreibung_fkl010h1'] = 'Boeenspitze (Sekundenboee) Stundenmaximum'
df_wind_legend['Beschreibung_fkl010h0'] = 'Windgeschwindigkeit skalar Stundenmittel'
df_wind_legend['Beschreibung_dkl010h0'] = 'Windrichtung; Stundenmittel'
df_wind_legend['Beschreibung_wcc006s0'] = 'Foehnindex'

# In[9]:
df_wind_legend['Laenge_Minuten'] = df_wind_legend['Laenge_Minuten'].astype(float)
df_wind_legend['Laenge_Grad'] = df_wind_legend['Laenge_Grad'].astype(float)
df_wind_legend['Breite_Minuten'] = df_wind_legend['Breite_Minuten'].astype(float)
df_wind_legend['Breite_Grad'] = df_wind_legend['Breite_Grad'].astype(float)
df_wind_legend['WGS84_Laenge'] = df_wind_legend['Laenge_Grad'].add(df_wind_legend['Laenge_Minuten'].div(60))
df_wind_legend['WGS84_Breite'] = df_wind_legend['Breite_Grad'].add(df_wind_legend['Breite_Minuten'].div(60))

# In[10]:
df_wind_legend['EPSG2056_lat'] = df_wind_legend['WGS84_Breite']
df_wind_legend['EPSG2056_lon'] =df_wind_legend['WGS84_Laenge']

```

```

print('project WGS84 to EPSG2056')
#loop to write individual csv files
index = 0
for index, row in df_wind_legend.iterrows():
# get pointX and PointX from EPSG2056_lat and EPSG2056_long in row
    pointX = df_wind_legend.loc[index,'EPSG2056_lat']
    pointY = df_wind_legend.loc[index,'EPSG2056_lon']
# add pointX and pointY as osgeo Point
    point = ogr.Geometry(ogr.wkbPoint)
    point.AddPoint(pointY, pointX)
# Transform
    print("WGS84: ", point)
    point.Transform(coordTransform)
# print point in EPSG 4326
    print("EPSG2056: ", point)
    print("\n")
# convert back tupel back to each row
    df_wind_legend.loc[index,'EPSG2056_lat'] = point.GetX()
    df_wind_legend.loc[index,'EPSG2056_lon'] = point.GetY()
print(' -- successfull \n')

# In[11]:
del df_wind_legend['EPSG2056_Breite_km']
del df_wind_legend['EPSG2056_Laenge_km']

# In[12]:
for index, row in islice(df_wind_legend.iterrows(), None):
    if df_wind_legend.loc[index,'Parameter'] == 'fk1010h1':
        df_wind_legend.loc[index,'Datenquelle_fk1010h1'] = df_wind_legend.loc[index,'Datenquelle']
        print(df_wind_legend.loc[index,'Datenquelle'])
    elif df_wind_legend.loc[index,'Parameter'] == 'fk1010h0':
        df_wind_legend.loc[index,'Datenquelle_fk1010h0'] = df_wind_legend.loc[index,'Datenquelle']
        print(df_wind_legend.loc[index,'Datenquelle'])
    elif df_wind_legend.loc[index,'Parameter'] == 'dk1010h0':
        df_wind_legend.loc[index,'Datenquelle_dk1010h0'] = df_wind_legend.loc[index,'Datenquelle']
        print(df_wind_legend.loc[index,'Datenquelle'])
    elif df_wind_legend.loc[index,'Parameter'] == 'wcc006s0':
        df_wind_legend.loc[index,'Datenquelle_wcc006s0'] = df_wind_legend.loc[index,'Datenquelle']
        print(df_wind_legend.loc[index,'Datenquelle'])
    else:
        df_wind_legend.loc[index,'Datenquelle_fk1010h1'] = 'NaN'
        df_wind_legend.loc[index,'Datenquelle_fk1010h0'] = 'NaN'
        df_wind_legend.loc[index,'Datenquelle_dk1010h0'] = 'NaN'
        df_wind_legend.loc[index,'Datenquelle_wcc006s0'] = 'NaN'
        print('NaN')

# In[13]:
del df_wind_legend['Parameter']
del df_wind_legend['Datenquelle']

# In[14]:
df_wind_legend['Datenquelle_fk1010h1'] = df_wind_legend.groupby('Station')['Datenquelle_fk1010h1'].ffill()

# In[15]:
dq_1 = 'NaN'
dq_2 = 'NaN'
dq_3 = 'NaN'
dq_4 = 'NaN'
current_station = df_wind_legend.loc[0,'Station']
last_station = df_wind_legend.loc[0,'Station']

for index, row in islice(df_wind_legend.iterrows(), None):
    current_station = df_wind_legend.loc[index,'Station']
    if current_station == last_station:
        if df_wind_legend.loc[index,'Datenquelle_fk1010h1'] != 'NaN':
            dq_1 = df_wind_legend.loc[index,'Datenquelle_fk1010h1']
        elif df_wind_legend.loc[index,'Datenquelle_fk1010h0'] != 'NaN':
            dq_2 = df_wind_legend.loc[index,'Datenquelle_fk1010h0']
        elif df_wind_legend.loc[index,'Datenquelle_dk1010h0'] != 'NaN':
            dq_3 = df_wind_legend.loc[index,'Datenquelle_dk1010h0']
            df_wind_legend.loc[index,'Datenquelle_dk1010h0'] = dq_3
        elif df_wind_legend.loc[index,'Datenquelle_wcc006s0'] != 'NaN':
            dq_4 = df_wind_legend.loc[index,'Datenquelle_wcc006s0']

        df_wind_legend.loc[index,'Datenquelle_fk1010h1'] = dq_1
        df_wind_legend.loc[index,'Datenquelle_fk1010h0'] = dq_2
        df_wind_legend.loc[index,'Datenquelle_dk1010h0'] = dq_3
        df_wind_legend.loc[index,'Datenquelle_wcc006s0'] = dq_4
    else:
        print('New Station')
        dq_1 = df_wind_legend.loc[index,'Datenquelle_fk1010h1']

```

```

df_wind_legend.loc[index, 'Datenquelle_fkl010h1'] = dq_1
print(dq_1, dq_2, dq_3, dq_4)
dq_2='NaN'
dq_3='NaN'
dq_4 = 'NaN'
last_station = df_wind_legend.loc[index, 'Station']

# In[16]:
df_wind_legend = df_wind_legend.drop_duplicates('Station', keep='last')
df_wind_legend

# In[17]:
df_wind_legend.info()

# In[18]:
df_wind_legend_cols = df_wind_legend.columns.tolist()
df_wind_legend_cols

# In[19]:
df_wind_legend_cols2 = ['Station', 'Name', 'WGS84_Laenge', 'WGS84_Breite',
'EPSG2056_lat', 'EPSG2056_lon', 'Hoehe_ASL_m', 'Parameter_fkl010h1', 'Einheit_fkl010h1', 'Beschrei-
bung_fkl010h1', 'Datenquelle_fkl010h1', 'Parameter_fkl010h0', 'Einheit_fkl010h0', 'Beschreibung_fkl010h0', 'Ein-
heit_dkl010h0', 'Datenquelle_fkl010h0', 'Parameter_dkl010h0', 'Beschreibung_dkl010h0', 'Datenquelle_dkl010h0', 'Pa-
rameter_wcc006s0', 'Einheit_wcc006s0', 'Beschreibung_wcc006s0', 'Datenquelle_wcc006s0', 'Laenge_Grad', 'Laenge_Minu-
ten', 'Breite_Grad', 'Breite_Minuten']
df_wind_legend_cols2

# In[20]:
df_wind_legend = df_wind_legend[df_wind_legend_cols2]

# In[21]:

df_wind_legend

# In[22]:
# write df_new to csv output
print('write df to csv output')
df_wind_legend.to_csv(path_to_output + 'MeteoSchweiz_Wind_Legende.csv', index = False)
print('-- successfull \n')

# In[23]:
print('Import CSV')
path_wind_data_foehn = path_meteo_ch + 'order93782\WIND_Foehn_order_93782_data.csv'
print('-- successfull \n')
print('Creating Pandas Dataframe:df_wind_data_foehn')
df_wind_data_foehn =pd.DataFrame(pd.read_csv(path_wind_data_foehn, sep=';', low_memory=False))
print('-- successfull \n')

# In[24]:
df_wind_data_foehn['Timestamp'] = df_wind_data_foehn.Timestamp.astype(str) + '00'

df_wind_data_foehn['year'] = pd.to_numeric(df_wind_data_foehn.Timestamp.astype(str).str[:4])
df_wind_data_foehn['month'] = pd.to_numeric(df_wind_data_foehn.Timestamp.astype(str).str[4:6])
df_wind_data_foehn['day'] = pd.to_numeric(df_wind_data_foehn.Timestamp.astype(str).str[6:8])
df_wind_data_foehn['hour'] = df_wind_data_foehn.Timestamp.astype(str).str[8:10]
df_wind_data_foehn['minutes'] = df_wind_data_foehn.Timestamp.astype(str).str[10:12]
df_wind_data_foehn['seconds'] = df_wind_data_foehn.Timestamp.astype(str).str[12:14]
df_wind_data_foehn['UTC'] = df_wind_data_foehn['day'].astype(str) + '.' +
df_wind_data_foehn['month'].astype(str) + '.' + df_wind_data_foehn['year'].astype(str) + ' ' +
df_wind_data_foehn['hour'].astype(str) + ':' + df_wind_data_foehn['minutes'].astype(str) + ':00'

# In[25]:
df_wind_data_foehn['UTC Date']=pd.to_datetime((df_wind_data_foehn.year*10000+df_wind_data_foehn.month*100+df_wi
nd_data_foehn.day).apply(str),format='%Y%m%d')
df_wind_data_foehn['UTC Time'] = (df_wind_data_foehn.hour+ ':' +df_wind_data_foehn.minutes+ ':' +
df_wind_data_foehn.seconds)
df_wind_data_foehn['UTC Time'] = pd.to_datetime(df_wind_data_foehn['UTC Time'] ,format='%H:%M:%S' )
df_wind_data_foehn['UTC Time'] = pd.Series([val.time() for val in df_wind_data_foehn['UTC Time']])

# In[26]:
df_wind_data_foehn['hour'] = pd.to_numeric(df_wind_data_foehn.Timestamp.astype(str).str[8:10])

# In[27]:
df_wind_data_foehn = df_wind_data_foehn.set_index(pd.DatetimeIndex(df_wind_data_foehn['UTC']))

```

```

# In[28]:
df_wind_data_foehn4 = pd.DataFrame()

# In[29]:
df_wind_data_foehn4['Wert_wcc006s0'] = df_wind_data_foehn['Wert_wcc006s0'].resample('60T').max()
#df_wind_data_foehn4['Foehnindex (wcc006s0)'].value_counts()
df_wind_data_foehn = df_wind_data_foehn[df_wind_data_foehn.index.isin(df_wind_data_foehn4.index)]

# In[30]:
df_wind_data_foehn['Wert_wcc006s0'].value_counts()

# In[31]:
df_wind_data_foehn.info()

# In[32]:
df_wind_data_foehn.dropna(inplace=False)

# In[33]:
df_wind_data_foehn.info()

# In[34]:
#import wind_data
print('Import CSV')
path_wind_data = path_meteo_ch + 'order93782\WIND_DATA_Meteo_Schweiz_order_93782.csv'
print('-- successfull \n')
print('Creating Pandas Dataframe:df_wind_data')
df_wind_data =pd.DataFrame(pd.read_csv(path_wind_data, sep=';', low_memory=False))
print('-- successfull \n')

# In[35]:
df_wind_data['Wert_fkl010h0'] = pd.to_numeric(df_wind_data['Wert_fkl010h0'], downcast="float")
df_wind_data['Wert_dkl010h0'] = pd.to_numeric(df_wind_data['Wert_dkl010h0'], downcast="float")
df_wind_data['Wert_fkl010h1'] = pd.to_numeric(df_wind_data['Wert_fkl010h1'], downcast="float")
df_wind_data['Wert_wcc006s0'] = pd.to_numeric(df_wind_data['Wert_wcc006s0'], downcast="float")

# In[36]:
df_wind_data['Timestamp'] = df_wind_data.Timestamp.astype(str) + '0000'

# In[37]:
df_wind_data['year'] = pd.to_numeric(df_wind_data.Timestamp.astype(str).str[:4])
df_wind_data['month'] = pd.to_numeric(df_wind_data.Timestamp.astype(str).str[4:6])
df_wind_data['day'] = pd.to_numeric(df_wind_data.Timestamp.astype(str).str[6:8])
df_wind_data['hour'] = df_wind_data.Timestamp.astype(str).str[8:10]
df_wind_data['minutes'] = df_wind_data.Timestamp.astype(str).str[10:12]
df_wind_data['seconds'] = df_wind_data.Timestamp.astype(str).str[12:14]

df_wind_data['UTC'] = df_wind_data['day'].astype(str) + '.' + df_wind_data['month'].astype(str) + '.' +
df_wind_data['year'].astype(str) + ' ' + df_wind_data['hour'].astype(str) + ':' +
df_wind_data['minutes'].astype(str) + ':00'

# In[38]:
df_wind_data['UTC_Date'] = pd.to_datetime((df_wind_data.year*10000+df_wind_data.month*100+df_wind_data.day).apply(str), format='%Y%m%d')

# In[39]:
df_wind_data['UTC_Time'] = (df_wind_data.hour+ ':' +df_wind_data.minutes+ ':' +df_wind_data.seconds)
df_wind_data['UTC_Time'] = pd.to_datetime(df_wind_data['UTC_Time'] ,format='%H:%M:%S' )
df_wind_data['UTC_Time'] = pd.Series([val.time() for val in df_wind_data['UTC_Time']])

df_wind_data['UTC_Time']

# In[40]:
df_wind_data['hour'] = pd.to_numeric(df_wind_data.Timestamp.astype(str).str[8:10])
df_wind_data['minutes'] = pd.to_numeric(df_wind_data.Timestamp.astype(str).str[10:12])
df_wind_data['seconds'] = pd.to_numeric(df_wind_data.Timestamp.astype(str).str[12:14])

del df_wind_data['seconds']
del df_wind_data['minutes']

# In[41]:
df_wind_data['UTC'] = pd.to_datetime(df_wind_data['Timestamp'])

```

```

# In[42]:
df_wind_data['UTC'].max()

# In[43]:
print('Options to show full pandas dataframe \n')
#pd.set_option('display.max_rows', None)
#pd.set_option('display.max_columns', None)
#pd.set_option('display.width', None)
#pd.set_option('display.max_colwidth', None)

print('Set display of dataframe to max columns')
pd.set_option('display.max_columns', None)
print(' -- successfull \n')

# In[44]:
df_wind_data

# In[45]:
df_wind_data_foehn

# In[46]:
df_wind_data = df_wind_data.set_index(pd.DatetimeIndex(df_wind_data['UTC']))

# In[47]:
df_wind_data = df_wind_data.append(df_wind_data_foehn)

# In[48]:
df_wind_data['Wert_wcc006s0'].value_counts()

# In[49]:
df_wind_data['Wert_wcc006s0'] = df_wind_data['Wert_wcc006s0'].astype(float)

# In[50]:
df_wind_data = df_wind_data.sort_index()

# In[51]:
df_wind_data['Parameter_fkl010h1'] = 'fkl010h1'
df_wind_data['Einheit_fkl010h1'] = 'm/s'
df_wind_data['Beschreibung_fkl010h1'] = 'Boeenspitze (Sekundenboee) Stundenmaximum'

df_wind_data['Parameter_fkl010h0'] = 'fkl010h0'
df_wind_data['Einheit_fkl010h0'] = 'm/s'
df_wind_data['Beschreibung_fkl010h0'] = 'Windgeschwindigkeit skalar Stundenmittel'

df_wind_data['Parameter_dkl010h0'] = 'dkl010h0'
df_wind_data['Einheit_dkl010h0'] = 'Grad'
df_wind_data['Beschreibung_dkl010h0'] = 'Windrichtung Stundenmittel'

df_wind_data['Parameter_wcc006s0'] = 'wcc006s0'
df_wind_data['Einheit_wcc006s0'] = 'code'
df_wind_data['Beschreibung_wcc006s0'] = 'Foehnindex'

# In[52]:
df_wind_legend

# In[53]:
df_wind_legend2 = pd.DataFrame()
df_wind_legend2 = df_wind_legend[['Station', 'Name', 'WGS84_Laenge', 'WGS84_Brei-
te', 'EPSG2056_lat', 'EPSG2056_lon', 'Hoehe_AS_L_m', 'Datenquelle_fkl010h1', 'Daten-
quelle_fkl010h0', 'Datenquelle_wcc006s0', 'Laenge_Grad', 'Laenge_Minuten', 'Breite_Grad', 'Breite_Minuten']].copy()

# In[54]:
df_wind_legend2

# In[55]:
df_wind_data.info()

# In[56]:
df_wind_data = df_wind_data.merge(df_wind_legend2, left_on='stn', right_on='Station')
df_wind_data

```

```

# In[57]:
wind_cols = df_wind_data.columns.tolist()
wind_cols

# In[58]:
wind_cols = ['UTC', 'Station', 'Timestamp', 'Parameter_fk1010h0', 'Wert_fk1010h0', 'Ein-
heit_fk1010h0', 'Beschreibung_fk1010h0', 'Datenquelle_fk1010h0', 'Parameter_dk1010h0', 'Wert_dk1010h0', 'Ein-
heit_dk1010h0', 'Beschreibung_dk1010h0', 'Datenquelle_dk1010h0', 'Parameter_fk1010h1', 'Wert_fk1010h1', 'Ein-
heit_fk1010h1', 'Beschreibung_fk1010h1', 'Datenquelle_fk1010h1', 'Parameter_wcc006s0', 'Wert_wcc006s0', 'Ein-
heit_wcc006s0', 'Beschreibung_wcc006s0', 'Datenquelle_wcc006s0', 'Name', 'Laenge_Grad', 'Laenge_Mi-
nuten', 'Breite_Grad', 'Breite_Mi-
nuten', 'WGS84_Laenge', 'WGS84_Breite', 'EPSG2056_lat', 'EPSG2056_lon', 'Hoehe_ASL_m', 'UTC_Date', 'UTC_Time', 'year',
'month', 'day', 'hour']
wind_cols

# In[59]:
df_wind_data = df_wind_data[wind_cols]

# In[60]:
df_wind_data

# In[61]:
print('Options to show full pandas dataframe \n')
#pd.set_option('display.max_rows', None)
#pd.set_option('display.max_columns', None)
#pd.set_option('display.width', None)
#pd.set_option('display.max_colwidth', None)

print('Set display of dataframe to max columns')
pd.set_option('display.max_columns', None)
print(' -- successfull \n')

# In[62]:
# write df_new to csv output
print('write df to csv output')
df_wind_data.to_csv(path_to_output + 'MeteoSchweiz_Wind_Data.csv', index = False)
print(' -- successfull \n')

# In[63]:
df_wind_data_small = pd.DataFrame()
df_wind_data_small = df_wind_data.copy()
df_wind_data_small['Windgeschwindigkeit_ms'] = df_wind_data_small['Wert_fk1010h0'].copy()
df_wind_data_small['Windrichtung_grad'] = df_wind_data_small['Wert_dk1010h0'].copy()

# In[64]:
df_wind_data_small['Foehnindex'] = df_wind_data_small['Wert_wcc006s0'].astype(float).copy()

# In[65]:
wind_small_cols = ['UTC', 'Timestamp', 'Windgeschwindigkeit ms', 'Windrichtung grad', 'Foehnindex', 'Sta-
tion', 'Name', 'WGS84_Laenge', 'WGS84_Breite', 'EPSG2056_lat', 'EPSG2056_lon', 'Hoehe_ASL_m']
df_wind_data_small = df_wind_data_small[wind_small_cols]
#df_wind_data_small = df_wind_data_small.dropna()
df_wind_data_small

# In[66]:
# write df_new to csv output
print('write df to csv output')
df_wind_data_small.to_csv(path_to_output + 'MeteoSchweiz_Wind_Data_small.csv', index = False)
print(' -- successfull \n')

# In[67]:
del df_wind_legend
del df_wind_data
del df_wind_data_foehn
del df_wind_data_foehn4

# Lufttemperatur 2 m über Boden; Stundenmittel
# -----

# Import CSV

# In[68]:
#Import CSV
print('Import CSV')
path_temperature_legend = path_meteo_ch + 'order93785\MeteoSchweiz_Stationen_Temperatur_order_93785_legend.csv'
print(' -- successfull \n')

```

```

print('Creating Pandas Dataframe:df_temperature_legend')
df_temperature_legend =pd.DataFrame(pd.read_csv(path_temperature_legend,low_memory=False))
print(' -- successfull \n')

# In[69]:
df_temperature_legend['Parameter_tre200h0'] = df_temperature_legend['Parameter_tre200h0.1'].copy()
del df_temperature_legend['Parameter_tre200h0.1']

# In[70]:
df_temperature_legend

# In[71]:
df_temperature_legend['Laenge_Minuten'] = df_temperature_legend['Laenge_Minuten'].astype(float)
df_temperature_legend['Laenge_Grad'] = df_temperature_legend['Laenge_Grad'].astype(float)
df_temperature_legend['Breite_Minuten'] = df_temperature_legend['Breite_Minuten'].astype(float)
df_temperature_legend['Breite_Grad'] = df_temperature_legend['Breite_Grad'].astype(float)
df_temperature_legend['WGS84_Laenge'] = df_temperature_legend['Laenge_Grad'].add(df_temperature_leg-
end['Laenge_Minuten']).div(60)
df_temperature_legend['WGS84_Breite'] = df_temperature_legend['Breite_Grad'].add(df_temperature_leg-
end['Breite_Minuten']).div(60)

# In[72]:
df_temperature_legend['EPSG2056_lat'] = df_temperature_legend['WGS84_Breite']
df_temperature_legend['EPSG2056_lon'] =df_temperature_legend['WGS84_Laenge']

print('project WGS84 to EPSG2056')
#loop to write individual csv files
index = 0
for index, row in df_temperature_legend.iterrows():
# get pointX and PointX from EPSG2056_lat and EPSG2056_long in row
    pointX = df_temperature_legend.loc[index,'EPSG2056_lat']
    pointY = df_temperature_legend.loc[index,'EPSG2056_lon']
# add pointX and pointY as osgeo Point
    point = ogr.Geometry(ogr.wkbPoint)
    point.AddPoint(pointY, pointX)
# Transform
    print("WGS84: ", point)
    point.Transform(coordTransform)
# print point in EPSG 4326
    print("EPSG2056: ", point)
    print("\n")
# convert back tuple back to each row
    df_temperature_legend.loc[index,'EPSG2056_lat'] = point.GetX()
    df_temperature_legend.loc[index,'EPSG2056_lon'] = point.GetY()
print(' -- successfull \n')

# In[73]:
del df_temperature_legend['EPSG2056_Breite_km']
del df_temperature_legend['EPSG2056_Laenge_km']

# In[74]:
df_temperature_legend

# In[75]:
# write df_new to csv output
print('write df to csv output')
df_temperature_legend.to_csv(path_to_output + 'MeteoSchweiz_Temperatur_Legende.csv', index = False)
print(' -- successfull \n')

# In[76]:
#Import CSV
print('Import CSV')
path_temperature_data = path_meteo_ch + 'order93785\MeteoSchweiz_Data_Temperatur_order_93785_data.csv'
print(' -- successfull \n')
print('Creating Pandas Dataframe:df_temperature_data')
df_temperature_data =pd.DataFrame(pd.read_csv(path_temperature_data, sep=',', low_memory=False))
print(' -- successfull \n')

# In[77]:
df_temperature_data = df_temperature_data.merge(df_temperature_legend, left_on='stn', right_on='Station')
df_temperature_data

# In[78]:
del df_temperature_legend

# In[79]:

```

```

df_temperature_data['Wert_tre200h0'] = df_temperature_data['Wert_tre200h0'].astype(float)

# In[80]:
df_temperature_data['Timestamp'] = df_temperature_data.time.astype(str) + '0000'

df_temperature_data['year'] = pd.to_numeric(df_temperature_data.Timestamp.astype(str).str[:4])
df_temperature_data['month'] = pd.to_numeric(df_temperature_data.Timestamp.astype(str).str[4:6])
df_temperature_data['day'] = pd.to_numeric(df_temperature_data.Timestamp.astype(str).str[6:8])
df_temperature_data['hour'] = df_temperature_data.Timestamp.astype(str).str[8:10]
df_temperature_data['minutes'] = df_temperature_data.Timestamp.astype(str).str[10:12]
df_temperature_data['seconds'] = df_temperature_data.Timestamp.astype(str).str[12:14]

del df_temperature_data['time']
del df_temperature_data['stn']

df_temperature_data

# In[81]:
df_temperature_data['UTC_Date'] = pd.to_datetime((df_temperature_data.year*10000+df_tempera-
ture_data.month*100+df_temperature_data.day).apply(str),format='%Y%m%d')
df_temperature_data['UTC_Time'] = (df_temperature_data.hour+ ':' +df_temperature_data.minutes+ ':' +df_tempera-
ture_data.seconds)
df_temperature_data['UTC_Time'] = pd.to_datetime(df_temperature_data['UTC_Time'] ,format='%H:%M:%S' )
df_temperature_data['UTC_Time'] = pd.Series([val.time() for val in df_temperature_data['UTC_Time']])
df_temperature_data['UTC_Date'] = pd.Series([val.date() for val in df_temperature_data['UTC_Date']])
df_temperature_data['UTC'] = pd.to_datetime(df_temperature_data['Timestamp'], format='%Y%m%d%H%M%S')
df_temperature_data

# In[82]:
df_temperature_data['hour'] = pd.to_numeric(df_temperature_data.Timestamp.astype(str).str[8:10])
df_temperature_data['minutes'] = pd.to_numeric(df_temperature_data.Timestamp.astype(str).str[10:12])
df_temperature_data['seconds'] = pd.to_numeric(df_temperature_data.Timestamp.astype(str).str[12:14])

# In[83]:
df_temperature_data['UTC'].max()

# In[84]:
df_temperature_data['UTC'].min()

# In[85]:
df_temperature_data['UTC_Date'].min()

# In[86]:
df_temperature_data['UTC_Date'].max()

# In[87]:
df_temperature_data = df_temperature_data.set_index(pd.DatetimeIndex(df_temperature_data['UTC']))

# In[88]:
df_temperature_data = df_temperature_data.sort_index()

# In[89]:
df_temperature_cols = df_temperature_data.columns.tolist()
df_temperature_cols

# In[90]:
df_temperature_cols2 = ['UTC','Timestamp','Station','Parameter_tre200h0','Wert_tre200h0','Ein-
heit_tre200h0','Datenquelle_tre200h0','Beschreibung_tre200h0','Name','Laenge_Grad','Laenge_Mi-
nuten','Breite_Grad','Breite_Mi-
nuten','WGS84_Laenge','WGS84_Breite','EPSG2056_lat','EPSG2056_lon','Hoehe_ASL_m','UTC_Date','UTC_Time','year','
month','day','hour','minutes','seconds']
df_temperature_cols2

# In[91]:
df_temperature_data = df_temperature_data[df_temperature_cols2]
df_temperature_data

# In[92]:
del df_temperature_data['minutes']
del df_temperature_data['seconds']

# In[93]:
# write df_new to csv output

```

```

print('write df to csv output')
df_temperature_data.to_csv(path_to_output + 'MeteoSchweiz_Temperatur_Data.csv', index = False)
print(' -- successfull \n')

# In[94]:
df_temperature_data_small = pd.DataFrame()
df_temperature_data_small = df_temperature_data
df_temperature_data_small['Temp_2mAGL_C'] = df_temperature_data_small['Wert_tre200h0']

df_temperature_data_small_cols = ['UTC', 'Timestamp', 'Temp_2mAGL_C', 'Station', 'Name', 'WGS84_Laenge', 'WGS84_Breite', 'EPSG2056_lat', 'EPSG2056_lon', 'Hoehe_ASL_m']
df_temperature_data_small = df_temperature_data_small[df_temperature_data_small_cols]
df_temperature_data_small = df_temperature_data_small.dropna()
df_temperature_data_small

# In[95]:
# write df_new to csv output
print('write df to csv output')
df_temperature_data_small.to_csv(path_to_output + 'MeteoSchweiz_Temp2mAGL_small.csv', index = False)
print(' -- successfull \n')

# In[96]:
del df_temperature_data_small
del df_temperature_data

# Solar Radiation
# -----

# In[97]:
print('Options to show full pandas dataframe \n')
#pd.set_option('display.max_rows', None)
#pd.set_option('display.max_columns', None)
#pd.set_option('display.width', None)
#pd.set_option('display.max_colwidth', None)

print('Set display of dataframe to max columns')
pd.set_option('display.max_columns', None)
print(' -- successfull \n')

# In[98]:
print('Import CSV')
path_solar_radiation_data = path_meteo_ch + 'order93786\MeteoSchweiz_Strahlung_order_93786_Data.csv'
print(' -- successfull \n')

# In[99]:
with open(path_solar_radiation_data, 'r') as input_file:
    data_str = input_file.read()
    data_array = data_str.split('\n\n') # Split on all instances of double new lines
    for i, smaller_data in enumerate(data_array):
        with open(path_meteo_ch + 'order93786\Solar_Radiation\MeteoSchweiz_Strahlung_order_93786_Data[i].csv', 'w') as new_data_file:
            new_data_file.write(smaller_data)

# In[100]:
print('Import CSV')
path_solar_radiation_data = path_meteo_ch + 'order93786\MeteoSchweiz_Strahlung_order_93786_Data'
print(' -- successfull \n')
dataframes = {}
for i in range(17):
    df_var = 'df'+ str(i)
    print(df_var)
    dataframes[df_var] = pd.DataFrame({'Station', 'Timestamp', 'Wert_ods000h0', 'Wert_gre000h0', 'Wert_oli000h0', 'Wert_osr000h0'})
    dataframes[df_var] = pd.DataFrame(pd.read_csv(path_solar_radiation_data+str(i)+'.csv', sep=';', low_memory=False))
    print(dataframes)
    print(' -- successfull \n')

# In[101]:
dataframes.keys()

# In[102]:
df_solar_radiation_data = pd.concat(dataframes, ignore_index=True)

# In[103]:
df_solar_radiation_data

```

```

# In[104]:
# write df_new to csv output
print('write df to csv output')
df_solar_radiation_data.to_csv(path_to_output + 'MeteoSchweiz_Solar_Radiation_Data.csv', index = False)
print(' -- successfull \n')

# In[105]:
print('Import CSV')
path_solar_radiation_legend = path_meteo_ch + 'order93786\MeteoSchweiz_Strahlung_order_93786_legend.csv'
print(' -- successfull \n')
print('Creating Pandas Dataframe:df_solar_radiation_legend')
df_solar_radiation_legend = pd.DataFrame(pd.read_csv(path_solar_radiation_legend, sep=',', low_memory=False))
print(' -- successfull \n')

# In[106]:
df_solar_radiation_legend

# In[107]:
df_solar_radiation_legend['Laenge_Minuten'] = df_solar_radiation_legend['Laenge_Minuten'].astype(float)
df_solar_radiation_legend['Laenge_Grad'] = df_solar_radiation_legend['Laenge_Grad'].astype(float)
df_solar_radiation_legend['Breite_Minuten'] = df_solar_radiation_legend['Breite_Minuten'].astype(float)
df_solar_radiation_legend['Breite_Grad'] = df_solar_radiation_legend['Breite_Grad'].astype(float)
df_solar_radiation_legend['WGS84_Laenge'] = df_solar_radiation_legend['WGS84_Laenge'].add(df_solar_radiation_legend['Laenge_Minuten'].div(60))
df_solar_radiation_legend['WGS84_Breite'] = df_solar_radiation_legend['Breite_Grad'].add(df_solar_radiation_legend['Breite_Minuten'].div(60))

# In[108]:
df_solar_radiation_legend['EPSG2056_lat'] = df_solar_radiation_legend['WGS84_Breite']
df_solar_radiation_legend['EPSG2056_lon'] = df_solar_radiation_legend['WGS84_Laenge']

print('project WGS84 to EPSG2056')
#loop to write individual csv files
index = 0
for index, row in df_solar_radiation_legend.iterrows():
# get pointX and PointX from EPSG2056_lat and EPSG2056_long in row
    pointX = df_solar_radiation_legend.loc[index, 'EPSG2056_lat']
    pointY = df_solar_radiation_legend.loc[index, 'EPSG2056_lon']
# add pointX and pointY as osgeo Point
    point = ogr.Geometry(ogr.wkbPoint)
    point.AddPoint(pointY, pointX)
# Transform
    print("WGS84: ", point)
    point.Transform(coordTransform)
# print point in EPSG 4326
    print("EPSG2056: ", point)
    print("\n")
# convert back tuple back to each row
    df_solar_radiation_legend.loc[index, 'EPSG2056_lat'] = point.GetX()
    df_solar_radiation_legend.loc[index, 'EPSG2056_lon'] = point.GetY()
print(' -- successfull \n')

# In[109]:
del df_solar_radiation_legend['EPSG2056_Breite_km']
del df_solar_radiation_legend['EPSG2056_Laenge_km']

# In[110]:
df_solar_radiation_legend['Datenquelle_ods000h0'] = 'NaN'
df_solar_radiation_legend['Datenquelle_oli000h0'] = 'NaN'
df_solar_radiation_legend['Datenquelle_gre000h0'] = 'NaN'
df_solar_radiation_legend['Datenquelle_osr000h0'] = 'NaN'

# In[111]:
df_solar_radiation_legend

# In[112]:
for index, row in islice(df_solar_radiation_legend.iterrows(), None):
    if df_solar_radiation_legend.loc[index, 'Parameter'] == 'ods000h0':
        df_solar_radiation_legend.loc[index, 'Datenquelle_ods000h0'] = df_solar_radiation_legend.loc[index, 'Datenquelle']
        print(df_solar_radiation_legend.loc[index, 'Datenquelle'])
    elif df_solar_radiation_legend.loc[index, 'Parameter'] == 'oli000h0':
        df_solar_radiation_legend.loc[index, 'Datenquelle_oli000h0'] = df_solar_radiation_legend.loc[index, 'Datenquelle']
        print(df_solar_radiation_legend.loc[index, 'Datenquelle'])
    elif df_solar_radiation_legend.loc[index, 'Parameter'] == 'gre000h0':
        df_solar_radiation_legend.loc[index, 'Datenquelle_gre000h0'] = df_solar_radiation_legend.loc[index, 'Datenquelle']
        print(df_solar_radiation_legend.loc[index, 'Datenquelle'])

```

```

    print(df_solar_radiation_legend.loc[index, 'Datenquelle'])
elif df_solar_radiation_legend.loc[index, 'Parameter'] == 'osr000h0':
    df_solar_radiation_legend.loc[index, 'Datenquelle_osr000h0'] = df_solar_radiation_legend.loc[index, 'Datenquelle']
    print(df_solar_radiation_legend.loc[index, 'Datenquelle'])
else:
    df_solar_radiation_legend.loc[index, 'Datenquelle_ods000h0'] = 'NaN'
    df_solar_radiation_legend.loc[index, 'Datenquelle_oli000h0'] = 'NaN'
    df_solar_radiation_legend.loc[index, 'Datenquelle_gre000h0'] = 'NaN'
    df_solar_radiation_legend.loc[index, 'Datenquelle_osr000h0'] = 'NaN'
    print('NaN')

# In[113]:
df_solar_radiation_legend

# In[114]:
df_solar_radiation_legend['Datenquelle_osr000h0'] = df_solar_radiation_legend.groupby('Station')['Datenquelle_osr000h0'].ffill()

# In[115]:
df_solar_radiation_legend['Beschreibung_osr000h0'] = 'Kurzweilig reflektierte Strahlung Stundenmittel'
df_solar_radiation_legend['Beschreibung_gre000h0'] = 'Globalstrahlung Stundenmittel'
df_solar_radiation_legend['Beschreibung_oli000h0'] = 'Langwellige Einstrahlung Stundenmittel'
df_solar_radiation_legend['Beschreibung_ods000h0'] = 'Diffusstrahlung Stundenmittel'
df_solar_radiation_legend['Einheit_osr000h0'] = 'W/m2'
df_solar_radiation_legend['Einheit_gre000h0'] = 'W/m2'
df_solar_radiation_legend['Einheit_oli000h0'] = 'W/m2'
df_solar_radiation_legend['Einheit_ods000h0'] = 'W/m2'

df_solar_radiation_legend['Parameter_osr000h0'] = 'osr000h0'
df_solar_radiation_legend['Parameter_gre000h0'] = 'gre000h0'
df_solar_radiation_legend['Parameter_oli000h0'] = 'oli000h0'
df_solar_radiation_legend['Parameter_ods000h0'] = 'ods000h0'

# In[116]:
dq_1 = 'NaN'
dq_2 = 'NaN'
dq_3 = 'NaN'
dq_4 = 'NaN'

current_station = df_solar_radiation_legend.loc[0, 'Station']
last_station = df_solar_radiation_legend.loc[0, 'Station']

for index, row in islice(df_solar_radiation_legend.iterrows(), None):
    current_station = df_solar_radiation_legend.loc[index, 'Station']
    if current_station == last_station:
        if df_solar_radiation_legend.loc[index, 'Datenquelle_osr000h0'] != 'NaN':
            dq_1 = df_solar_radiation_legend.loc[index, 'Datenquelle_osr000h0']
        elif df_solar_radiation_legend.loc[index, 'Datenquelle_gre000h0'] != 'NaN':
            dq_2 = df_solar_radiation_legend.loc[index, 'Datenquelle_gre000h0']
        elif df_solar_radiation_legend.loc[index, 'Datenquelle_oli000h0'] != 'NaN':
            dq_3 = df_solar_radiation_legend.loc[index, 'Datenquelle_oli000h0']
        elif df_solar_radiation_legend.loc[index, 'Datenquelle_ods000h0'] != 'NaN':
            dq_4 = df_solar_radiation_legend.loc[index, 'Datenquelle_ods000h0']

        df_solar_radiation_legend.loc[index, 'Datenquelle_osr000h0'] = dq_1
        df_solar_radiation_legend.loc[index, 'Datenquelle_gre000h0'] = dq_2
        df_solar_radiation_legend.loc[index, 'Datenquelle_oli000h0'] = dq_3
        df_solar_radiation_legend.loc[index, 'Datenquelle_ods000h0'] = dq_4

    else:
        print('New Station')
        dq_1 = df_solar_radiation_legend.loc[index, 'Datenquelle_osr000h0']
        df_solar_radiation_legend.loc[index, 'Datenquelle_osr000h0'] = dq_1
        beschreibung_1 = df_solar_radiation_legend.loc[index, 'Beschreibung']
        print(dq_1, dq_2, dq_3, dq_4)
        dq_2 = 'NaN'
        dq_3 = 'NaN'
        dq_4 = 'NaN'
        last_station = df_solar_radiation_legend.loc[index, 'Station']

# In[117]:
df_solar_radiation_legend = df_solar_radiation_legend.drop_duplicates('Station', keep='last')
df_solar_radiation_legend

# In[118]:
del df_solar_radiation_legend['Parameter']
del df_solar_radiation_legend['Datenquelle']
del df_solar_radiation_legend['Beschreibung']
del df_solar_radiation_legend['Einheit']

```

```

# In[119]:
df_solar_radiation_legend

# In[120]:
# write df_new to csv output
print('write df to csv output')
df_solar_radiation_legend.to_csv(path_to_output + 'MeteoSchweiz_Solar_Radiation_Legende.csv', index = False)
print(' -- successfull \n')

# In[121]:
df_solar_radiation_data = df_solar_radiation_data.merge(df_solar_radiation_legend, left_on='Station',
right_on='Station')
df_solar_radiation_data

# In[122]:
del path_solar_radiation_legend

# In[123]:
df_solar_radiation_data['Wert_osr000h0'] = df_solar_radiation_data['Wert_osr000h0'].astype(float)
df_solar_radiation_data['Wert_gre000h0'] = df_solar_radiation_data['Wert_gre000h0'].astype(float)
df_solar_radiation_data['Wert_oli000h0'] = df_solar_radiation_data['Wert_oli000h0'].astype(float)
df_solar_radiation_data['Wert_ods000h0'] = df_solar_radiation_data['Wert_ods000h0'].astype(float)

# In[124]:
df_solar_radiation_data['Timestamp'] = df_solar_radiation_data.Timestamp.astype(str) + '0000'

df_solar_radiation_data['year'] = pd.to_numeric(df_solar_radiation_data.Timestamp.astype(str).str[:4])
df_solar_radiation_data['month'] = pd.to_numeric(df_solar_radiation_data.Timestamp.astype(str).str[4:6])
df_solar_radiation_data['day'] = pd.to_numeric(df_solar_radiation_data.Timestamp.astype(str).str[6:8])
df_solar_radiation_data['hour'] = df_solar_radiation_data.Timestamp.astype(str).str[8:10]
df_solar_radiation_data['minutes'] = df_solar_radiation_data.Timestamp.astype(str).str[10:12]
df_solar_radiation_data['seconds'] = df_solar_radiation_data.Timestamp.astype(str).str[12:14]

df_solar_radiation_data

# In[125]:
df_solar_radiation_data['UTC_Date'] = pd.to_datetime((df_solar_radiation_data.year*10000+df_solar_radiation_data.month*100+df_solar_radiation_data.day).apply(str),format='%Y%m%d')
df_solar_radiation_data['UTC_Time'] = (df_solar_radiation_data.hour+ ':' +df_solar_radiation_data.minutes+ ':' +df_solar_radiation_data.seconds)
df_solar_radiation_data['UTC_Time'] = pd.to_datetime(df_solar_radiation_data['UTC_Time'] ,format='%H:%M:%S' )
df_solar_radiation_data['UTC_Time'] = pd.Series([val.time() for val in df_solar_radiation_data['UTC_Time']])
df_solar_radiation_data['UTC_Date'] = pd.Series([val.date() for val in df_solar_radiation_data['UTC_Date']])
df_solar_radiation_data['UTC'] = pd.to_datetime(df_solar_radiation_data['Timestamp'], format='%Y%m%d%H%M%S')
df_solar_radiation_data

# In[126]:
df_solar_radiation_data['hour'] = pd.to_numeric(df_solar_radiation_data.Timestamp.astype(str).str[8:10])
df_solar_radiation_data['minutes'] = pd.to_numeric(df_solar_radiation_data.Timestamp.astype(str).str[10:12])
df_solar_radiation_data['seconds'] = pd.to_numeric(df_solar_radiation_data.Timestamp.astype(str).str[12:14])

# In[127]:
df_solar_radiation_data['UTC'].max()

# In[128]:

df_solar_radiation_data['UTC'].min()

# In[129]:
df_solar_radiation_data['UTC_Date'].min()

# In[130]:
df_solar_radiation_data['UTC_Date'].max()

# In[131]:
df_solar_radiation_data = df_solar_radiation_data.set_index(pd.DatetimeIndex(df_solar_radiation_data['UTC']))

# In[132]:
df_solar_radiation_data = df_solar_radiation_data.sort_index()

# In[133]:

```

```
df_solar_radiation_data
```

```
# In[134]:
solar_cols = df_solar_radiation_data.columns.tolist()
solar_cols
```

```
# In[135]:
solar_cols = ['Station', 'Timestamp', 'UTC', 'Parameter_osr000h0', 'Wert_osr000h0', 'Ein-
heit_osr000h0', 'Datenquelle_osr000h0', 'Beschreibung_osr000h0', 'Parameter_gre000h0', 'Wert_gre000h0', 'Ein-
heit_gre000h0', 'Datenquelle_gre000h0', 'Beschreibung_gre000h0', 'Parameter_oli000h0', 'Wert_oli000h0', 'Ein-
heit_oli000h0', 'Datenquelle_oli000h0', 'Beschreibung_oli000h0', 'Parameter_ods000h0', 'Wert_ods000h0', 'Ein-
heit_ods000h0', 'Datenquelle_ods000h0', 'Beschreibung_ods000h0', 'Name', 'Laenge_Grad', 'Laenge_Mi-
nuten', 'Breite_Grad', 'Breite_Mi-
nuten', 'WGS84_Laenge', 'WGS84_Breite', 'EPSG2056_lat', 'EPSG2056_lon', 'Hoehe_ASL_m', 'UTC_Date', 'UTC_Time', 'year', '
month', 'day', 'hour', 'minutes', 'seconds', ]
solar_cols
```

```
# In[136]:
df_solar_radiation_data = df_solar_radiation_data[solar_cols]
```

```
# In[137]:
df_solar_radiation_data
```

```
# In[138]:
del df_solar_radiation_data['minutes']
del df_solar_radiation_data['seconds']
```

```
# In[139]:
```

```
df_solar_radiation_data
```

```
# In[140]:
# write df_new to csv output
print('write df to csv output')
df_solar_radiation_data.to_csv(path_to_output + 'MeteoSchweiz_Solar_Radiation_Data.csv', index = False)
print(' -- successfull \n')
```

```
# In[141]:
df_solar_radiation_data_small = pd.DataFrame()
df_solar_radiation_data_small = df_solar_radiation_data
df_solar_radiation_data_small['Globalstrahlung_wm2'] = df_solar_radiation_data_small['Wert_gre000h0']
```

```
solar_radiation_data_small_cols = ['UTC', 'Timestamp', 'Globalstrahlung_wm2', 'Sta-
tion', 'Name', 'WGS84_Laenge', 'WGS84_Breite', 'EPSG2056_lat', 'EPSG2056_lon', 'Hoehe_ASL_m']
df_solar_radiation_data_small = df_solar_radiation_data_small[solar_radiation_data_small_cols]
df_solar_radiation_data_small = df_solar_radiation_data_small.dropna()
df_solar_radiation_data_small
```

```
# In[142]:
# write df_new to csv output
print('write df to csv output')
df_solar_radiation_data_small.to_csv(path_to_output + 'MeteoSchweiz_solar_radiation_Data_small.csv', index =
False)
print(' -- successfull \n')
```

```
# In[143]:
del df_solar_radiation_data_small
del df_solar_radiation_data
```

```
# Sonnenscheindauer
# -----
```

```
#
# Parameter, Einheit, Beschreibung
# sre000h0, min, Sonnenscheindauer Stundensumme
# su2000d0, h, Sonnenscheindauer Tagessumme
```

```
# In[144]:
print('Options to show full pandas dataframe \n')
#pd.set_option('display.max_rows', None)
#pd.set_option('display.max_columns', None)
#pd.set_option('display.width', None)
#pd.set_option('display.max_colwidth', None)

print('Set display of dataframe to max columns')
```

```

pd.set_option('display.max_columns', None)
print(' -- successfull \n')

# In[145]:
print('Import CSV')
path_sonnenscheindauer_legend = path_meteo_ch + 'order93787\MeteoSchweiz_Sonnenscheindauer_order_93787_le-
gend.csv'
print(' -- successfull \n')
print('Creating Pandas Dataframe:df_sonnenscheindauer_legend')
df_sonnenscheindauer_legend =pd.DataFrame(pd.read_csv(path_sonnenscheindauer_legend, sep=',', low_me-
mory=False))
print(' -- successfull \n')

# In[146]:
df_sonnenscheindauer_legend['Laenge_Minuten'] = df_sonnenscheindauer_legend['Laenge_Minuten'].astype(float)
df_sonnenscheindauer_legend['Laenge_Grad'] = df_sonnenscheindauer_legend['Laenge_Grad'].astype(float)
df_sonnenscheindauer_legend['Breite_Minuten'] = df_sonnenscheindauer_legend['Breite_Minuten'].astype(float)
df_sonnenscheindauer_legend['Breite_Grad'] = df_sonnenscheindauer_legend['Breite_Grad'].astype(float)
df_sonnenscheindauer_legend['WGS84_Laenge'] = df_sonnenscheindauer_legend['Laenge_Grad'].add(df_sonnenschein-
dauer_legend['Laenge_Minuten'].div(60))
df_sonnenscheindauer_legend['WGS84_Breite'] = df_sonnenscheindauer_legend['Breite_Grad'].add(df_sonnenschein-
dauer_legend['Breite_Minuten'].div(60))

# In[147]:
df_sonnenscheindauer_legend['EPSG2056_lat'] = df_sonnenscheindauer_legend['WGS84_Breite']
df_sonnenscheindauer_legend['EPSG2056_lon'] = df_sonnenscheindauer_legend['WGS84_Laenge']

print('project WGS84 to EPSG2056')
#loop to write individual csv files
index = 0
for index, row in df_sonnenscheindauer_legend.iterrows():
# get pointX and PointX from EPSG2056_lat and EPSG2056_long in row
pointX = df_sonnenscheindauer_legend.loc[index,'EPSG2056_lat']
pointY = df_sonnenscheindauer_legend.loc[index,'EPSG2056_lon']
# add pointX and pointY as osgeo Point
point = ogr.Geometry(ogr.wkbPoint)
point.AddPoint(pointY, pointX)
# Transform
print("WGS84: ", point)
point.Transform(coordTransform)
# print point in EPSG 4326
print("EPSG2056: ", point)
print("\n")
# convert back tupel back to each row
df_sonnenscheindauer_legend.loc[index,'EPSG2056_lat'] = point.GetX()
df_sonnenscheindauer_legend.loc[index,'EPSG2056_lon'] = point.GetY()
print(' -- successfull \n')

# In[148]:
del df_sonnenscheindauer_legend['EPSG2056_Breite_km']
del df_sonnenscheindauer_legend['EPSG2056_Laenge_km']

# In[149]:
df_sonnenscheindauer_legend['Datenquelle_sre000h0'] = 'MeteoSchweiz'
df_sonnenscheindauer_legend['Datenquelle_su2000d0'] = 'MeteoSchweiz'

# In[150]:
df_sonnenscheindauer_legend['Parameter_sre000h0'] = 'sre000h0'
df_sonnenscheindauer_legend['Parameter_su2000d0'] = 'su2000d0'
df_sonnenscheindauer_legend['Beschreibung_sre000h0'] = 'Sonnenscheindauer Stundensumme'
df_sonnenscheindauer_legend['Beschreibung_su2000d0'] = 'Sonnenscheindauer Tagessumme'
df_sonnenscheindauer_legend['Einheit_sre000h0'] = 'min'
df_sonnenscheindauer_legend['Einheit_su2000d0'] = 'h'

# In[151]:
df_sonnenscheindauer_legend = df_sonnenscheindauer_legend.drop_duplicates('Station', keep='last')
df_sonnenscheindauer_legend

# In[152]:
del df_sonnenscheindauer_legend['Parameter']
del df_sonnenscheindauer_legend['Datenquelle']

# In[153]:
df_sonnenscheindauer_legend

# In[154]:
# write df_new to csv output

```

```

print('write df to csv output')
df_sonnenscheindauer_legend.to_csv(path_to_output + 'MeteoSchweiz_Sonnenscheindauer_Legende.csv', index =
False)
print(' -- successfull \n')

# In[155]:
print('Import CSV')
path_sonnenscheindauer_data = path_meteo_ch + 'order93787\MeteoSchweiz_Sonnenscheindauer_order_93787_data.csv'
print(' -- successfull \n')

# In[156]:
with open(path_sonnenscheindauer_data,'r') as input_file:
    data_str = input_file.read()
    data_array = data_str.split('\n\n') # Split on all instances of double new lines
    for i, smaller_data in enumerate(data_array):
        with open(path_meteo_ch + 'order93787\MeteoSchweiz_Sonnenscheindauer_order_93787_data{i}.csv','w') as
new_data_file:
            new_data_file.write(smaller_data)

# In[157]:
print('Import CSV')
path_sonnenscheindauer_data = path_meteo_ch + 'order93787\MeteoSchweiz_Sonnenscheindauer_order_93787_data'
print(' -- successfull \n')
dataframes_sun = {}
for a in range(10):
    df_var_sun = 'df'+ str(a)
    print(df_var_sun)
    dataframes_sun[df_var_sun] = pd.DataFrame({'Station','Timestamp','Wert_sre000h0','Wert_su2000d0'})
    dataframes_sun[df_var_sun] = pd.DataFrame(pd.read_csv(path_sonnenscheindauer_data+str(a)+'.csv', sep=';',
low_memory=False))
    print(dataframes_sun)
    print(' -- successfull \n')

# In[158]:
dataframes_sun.keys()

# In[159]:
df_sonnenscheindauer_data = pd.concat(dataframes_sun,ignore_index=True)

# In[160]:
df_sonnenscheindauer_data['Wert_sre000h0'] = df_sonnenscheindauer_data['Parameter_sre000h0']
df_sonnenscheindauer_data['Wert_su2000d0'] = df_sonnenscheindauer_data['Parameter_su2000d0']
#df_sonnenscheindauer_data['Parameter_sre000h0'] = 'sre000h0'
#df_sonnenscheindauer_data['Parameter_su2000d0'] = 'su2000d0'
del df_sonnenscheindauer_data['Parameter_sre000h0']
del df_sonnenscheindauer_data['Parameter_su2000d0']

# In[161]:
df_sonnenscheindauer_data

# In[162]:
# write df_new to csv output
print('write df to csv output')
df_sonnenscheindauer_data.to_csv(path_to_output + 'MeteoSchweiz_Sonnenscheindauer_Data.csv', index = False)
print(' -- successfull \n')

# In[163]:
print('Import CSV')
path_sonnenscheindauer_data = path_to_output + 'MeteoSchweiz_Sonnenscheindauer_Data.csv'
print(' -- successfull \n')
print('Creating Pandas Dataframe:df_sonnenscheindauer_data')
df_sonnenscheindauer_data =pd.DataFrame(pd.read_csv(path_sonnenscheindauer_data, sep=',', low_memory=False))
print(' -- successfull \n')

# In[164]:
for index, row in islice(df_sonnenscheindauer_data.iterrows(), None):
    if len(str(df_sonnenscheindauer_data.loc[index,'Timestamp'])) == 8:
        df_sonnenscheindauer_data.loc[index,'Timestamp'] = str(df_sonnenscheindauer_data.loc[in-
dex,'Timestamp']) + '230000'
    elif len(str(df_sonnenscheindauer_data.loc[index,'Timestamp'])) == 10:
        df_sonnenscheindauer_data.loc[index,'Timestamp'] = str(df_sonnenscheindauer_data.loc[index,'Ti-
mestamp']) + '0000'

# In[165]:
df_sonnenscheindauer_data['year'] = pd.to_numeric(df_sonnenscheindauer_data.Timestamp.astype(str).str[:4])
df_sonnenscheindauer_data['month'] = pd.to_numeric(df_sonnenscheindauer_data.Timestamp.astype(str).str[4:6])

```

```

df_sonnenscheindauer_data['day'] = pd.to_numeric(df_sonnenscheindauer_data.Timestamp.astype(str).str[6:8])

# In[166]:
df_sonnenscheindauer_data['hour'] = df_sonnenscheindauer_data.Timestamp.astype(str).str[8:10]
df_sonnenscheindauer_data['minutes'] = df_sonnenscheindauer_data.Timestamp.astype(str).str[10:12]
df_sonnenscheindauer_data['seconds'] = df_sonnenscheindauer_data.Timestamp.astype(str).str[12:14]

# In[167]:
df_sonnenscheindauer_data['UTC_Date'] = pd.to_datetime((df_sonnenscheindauer_data.year*10000+df_sonnenschein-
dauer_data.month*100+df_sonnenscheindauer_data.day).apply(str),format='%Y%m%d')
df_sonnenscheindauer_data['UTC_Date'] = pd.Series([val.date() for val in df_sonnenschein-
dauer_data['UTC_Date']])

# In[168]:
df_sonnenscheindauer_data['UTC_Time'] = (df_sonnenscheindauer_data.hour+ ':' +df_sonnenscheindauer_data.minu-
tes+ ':' +df_sonnenscheindauer_data.seconds)
df_sonnenscheindauer_data['UTC_Time'] = pd.to_datetime(df_sonnenscheindauer_data['UTC_Time'] ,for-
mat='%H:%M:%S' )
df_sonnenscheindauer_data['UTC_Time'] = pd.Series([val.time() for val in df_sonnenschein-
dauer_data['UTC_Time']])
df_sonnenscheindauer_data['UTC'] = pd.to_datetime(df_sonnenscheindauer_data['Timestamp'], for-
mat='%Y%m%d%H%M%S')
df_sonnenscheindauer_data

# In[169]:
df_sonnenscheindauer_data['hour'] = pd.to_numeric(df_sonnenscheindauer_data.Timestamp.astype(str).str[8:10])
df_sonnenscheindauer_data['minutes'] = pd.to_numeric(df_sonnenscheindauer_data.Timestamp.as-
type(str).str[10:12])
df_sonnenscheindauer_data['seconds'] = pd.to_numeric(df_sonnenscheindauer_data.Timestamp.as-
type(str).str[12:14])

# In[170]:
df_sonnenscheindauer_data['UTC'].max()

# In[171]:
df_sonnenscheindauer_data['UTC'].min()

# In[172]:
df_sonnenscheindauer_data['UTC_Date'].min()

# In[173]:
df_sonnenscheindauer_data['UTC_Date'].max()

# In[174]:
df_sonnenscheindauer_legend

# In[175]:
df_sonnenscheindauer_data = df_sonnenscheindauer_data.merge(df_sonnenscheindauer_legend, left_on='Station',
right_on='Station')
df_sonnenscheindauer_data

# In[176]:
del df_sonnenscheindauer_legend

# In[177]:
sun_cols = df_sonnenscheindauer_data.columns.tolist()
sun_cols

# In[178]:
sun_cols = ['Station','Timestamp','UTC','Parameter_sre000h0','Wert_sre000h0','Einheit_sre000h0','Daten-
quelle_sre000h0','Beschreibung_sre000h0','Parameter_su2000d0','Wert_su2000d0','Einheit_su2000d0','Daten-
quelle_su2000d0','Beschreibung_su2000d0','Name','Laenge_Grad','Laenge_Minuten','Breite_Grad','Breite_Minu-
ten','WGS84_Laenge','WGS84_Brei-
te','EPSG2056_lat','EPSG2056_lon','Hoehe_AS_L_m','UTC_Date','UTC_Time','year','month','day','hour','minu-
tes','seconds',]
sun_cols

# In[179]:
df_sonnenscheindauer_data = df_sonnenscheindauer_data[sun_cols]

# In[180]:
del df_sonnenscheindauer_data['minutes']

```

```

del df_sonnenscheindauer_data['seconds']

# In[181]:
df_sonnenscheindauer_data

# In[182]:
for index, row in islice(df_sonnenscheindauer_data.iterrows(), None):
    a = df_sonnenscheindauer_data.loc[index, 'Wert_sre000h0']
    if a == '-':
        df_sonnenscheindauer_data.loc[index, 'Wert_sre000h0'] = np.nan
    elif a == 'NaN':
        df_sonnenscheindauer_data.loc[index, 'Wert_sre000h0'] = np.nan

# In[183]:
df_sonnenscheindauer_data = df_sonnenscheindauer_data.set_index(pd.DatetimeIndex(df_sonnenschein-
dauer_data['UTC']))

# In[184]:
df_sonnenscheindauer_data = df_sonnenscheindauer_data.sort_index()

# In[185]:
df_sonnenscheindauer_data['Wert_sre000h0'] = df_sonnenscheindauer_data['Wert_sre000h0'].astype(float)

# In[186]:
# write df_new to csv output
print('write df to csv output')
df_sonnenscheindauer_data.to_csv(path_to_output + 'MeteoSchweiz_Sonnenscheindauer_Data.csv', index = False)
print(' -- successfull \n')

# In[187]:

df_sonnenscheindauer_data_small = pd.DataFrame()
df_sonnenscheindauer_data_small = df_sonnenscheindauer_data
df_sonnenscheindauer_data_small['sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min'] = df_sonnenschein-
dauer_data_small['Wert_sre000h0']

sonnenscheindauer_data_small_cols = ['UTC', 'Timestamp', 'sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min', 'Sta-
tion', 'Name', 'WGS84_Laenge', 'WGS84_Breite', 'EPSG2056_lat', 'EPSG2056_lon', 'Hoehe_ASL_m']
df_sonnenscheindauer_data_small = df_sonnenscheindauer_data_small[sonnenscheindauer_data_small_cols]
df_sonnenscheindauer_data_small = df_sonnenscheindauer_data_small.dropna()
df_sonnenscheindauer_data_small

# In[188]:
# write df_new to csv output
print('write df to csv output')
df_sonnenscheindauer_data_small.to_csv(path_to_output + 'MeteoSchweiz_sonnenscheindauer_Data_small.csv', index
= False)
print(' -- successfull \n')

# In[189]:
del df_sonnenscheindauer_data_small
del df_sonnenscheindauer_data

# Schnee
# -----

# Parameter          Einheit          Beschreibung
# hns000hs           cm              Neuschneehöhe; stündlicher Momentanwert
# hto000hs           cm              Schneehöhe; stündlicher Momentanwert
#
#

# In[190]:
print('Options to show full pandas dataframe \n')
#pd.set_option('display.max_rows', None)
#pd.set_option('display.max_columns', None)
#pd.set_option('display.width', None)
#pd.set_option('display.max_colwidth', None)

print('Set display of dataframe to max columns')
pd.set_option('display.max_columns', None)
print(' -- successfull \n')

# In[191]:
print('Import CSV')

```

```

path_schnee_legend = path_meteo_ch + 'order93793\Meteo_Schweiz_Schnee_order_93793_legend.csv'
print(' -- successfull \n')
print('Creating Pandas Dataframe:df_schnee_legend')
df_schnee_legend =pd.DataFrame(pd.read_csv(path_schnee_legend, sep=',', low_memory=False))
print(' -- successfull \n')

# In[192]:
df_schnee_legend['Laenge_Minuten'] = df_schnee_legend['Laenge_Minuten'].astype(float)
df_schnee_legend['Laenge_Grad'] = df_schnee_legend['Laenge_Grad'].astype(float)
df_schnee_legend['Breite_Minuten'] = df_schnee_legend['Breite_Minuten'].astype(float)
df_schnee_legend['Breite_Grad'] = df_schnee_legend['Breite_Grad'].astype(float)
df_schnee_legend['WGS84_Laenge'] = df_schnee_legend['Laenge_Grad'].add(df_schnee_legend['Laenge_Minuten'].div(60))
df_schnee_legend['WGS84_Breite'] = df_schnee_legend['Breite_Grad'].add(df_schnee_legend['Breite_Minuten'].div(60))

# In[193]:
del df_schnee_legend['EPSG2056_Breite_km']
del df_schnee_legend['EPSG2056_Laenge_km']

# In[194]:
df_schnee_legend['EPSG2056_lat'] = df_schnee_legend['WGS84_Breite']
df_schnee_legend['EPSG2056_lon'] = df_schnee_legend['WGS84_Laenge']

print('project WGS84 to EPSG2056')
#loop to write individual csv files
index = 0
for index, row in df_schnee_legend.iterrows():
# get pointX and PointX from EPSG2056_lat and EPSG2056_long in row
    pointX = df_schnee_legend.loc[index,'EPSG2056_lat']
    pointY = df_schnee_legend.loc[index,'EPSG2056_lon']
# add pointX and pointY as osgeo Point
    point = ogr.Geometry(ogr.wkbPoint)
    point.AddPoint(pointY, pointX)
# Transform
    print("WGS84: ", point)
    point.Transform(coordTransform)
# print point in EPSG 4326
    print("EPSG2056: ", point)
    print("\n")
# convert back tuple back to each row
    df_schnee_legend.loc[index,'EPSG2056_lat'] = point.GetX()
    df_schnee_legend.loc[index,'EPSG2056_lon'] = point.GetY()
print(' -- successfull \n')

# In[195]:
dq_1 = 'NaN'
dq_2 = 'NaN'
df_schnee_legend['Datenquelle_hns000hs'] = 'NaN'
df_schnee_legend['Datenquelle_hnt000hs'] = 'NaN'

current_station = df_schnee_legend.loc[0,'Station']
last_station = df_schnee_legend.loc[0,'Station']

for index, row in islice(df_schnee_legend.iterrows(), None):
    current_station = df_schnee_legend.loc[index,'Station']
    if current_station == last_station:
        if df_schnee_legend.loc[index,'Parameter'] == 'hns000hs':
            dq_1 = df_schnee_legend.loc[index,'Datenquelle']
        elif df_schnee_legend.loc[index,'Parameter'] == 'hnt000hs':
            dq_2 = df_schnee_legend.loc[index,'Datenquelle']

    df_schnee_legend.loc[index,'Datenquelle_osr000h0'] = dq_1
    df_schnee_legend.loc[index,'Datenquelle_gre000h0'] = dq_2

else:
    print('New Station')
    if df_schnee_legend.loc[index,'Parameter'] == 'hns000hs':
        dq_1 = df_schnee_legend.loc[index,'Datenquelle']
    elif df_schnee_legend.loc[index,'Parameter'] == 'hnt000hs':
        dq_2 = df_schnee_legend.loc[index,'Datenquelle']
    print(dq_1,dq_2)
    dq_2='NaN'
    dq_3='NaN'
    dq_4 = 'NaN'
    last_station = df_schnee_legend.loc[index,'Station']

# In[196]:
df_schnee_legend['Parameter_hns000hs'] = 'hns000hs'
df_schnee_legend['Parameter_hnt000hs'] = 'hnt000hs'

```

```

df_schnee_legend['Beschreibung_hns000hs'] = 'Neuschneehöhe stündlicher Momentanwert'
df_schnee_legend['Beschreibung_hnto000hs'] = 'Schneehöhe stündlicher Momentanwert'
df_schnee_legend['Einheit_hns000hs'] = 'cm'
df_schnee_legend['Einheit_hnto000hs'] = 'cm'

# In[197]:
del df_schnee_legend['Parameter']

# In[198]:
df_schnee_legend = df_schnee_legend.drop_duplicates('Station', keep='last')
df_schnee_legend

# In[199]:
# write df_new to csv output
print('write df to csv output')
df_schnee_legend.to_csv(path_to_output + 'MeteoSchweiz_Schnee_Legende.csv', index = False)
print(' -- successfull \n')

# In[200]:
print('Import CSV')
path_schnee_data = path_meteo_ch + 'order93793\Meteo_Schweiz_Schnee_order_93793_data.csv'
print(' -- successfull \n')

# In[201]:
with open(path_schnee_data, 'r') as input_file:
    data_str = input_file.read()
    data_array = data_str.split('\n\n') # Split on all instances of double new lines
    for i, smaller_data in enumerate(data_array):
        with open(path_meteo_ch + 'order93787\MeteoSchweiz_Schnee_order_93787_data{i}.csv', 'w') as
new_data_file:
            new_data_file.write(smaller_data)

# In[202]:
print('Import CSV')
path_schnee_data = path_meteo_ch + 'order93787\MeteoSchweiz_Schnee_order_93787_data'
print(' -- successfull \n')
dataframes_snow = {}
for a in range(11):
    df_var_snow = 'df'+ str(a)
    print(df_var_snow)
    dataframes_snow[df_var_snow] = pd.DataFrame({'Station', 'Timestamp', 'Wert_hns000hs', 'Wert_hnto000hs'})
    dataframes_snow[df_var_snow] = pd.DataFrame(pd.read_csv(path_schnee_data+str(a)+'.csv', sep=';',
low_memory=False))
    print(dataframes_snow)
    print(' -- successfull \n')

# In[203]:
dataframes_snow.keys()

# In[204]:
df_schnee_data = pd.concat(dataframes_snow, ignore_index=True)

# In[205]:
df_schnee_data

# In[206]:
# write df_new to csv output
print('write df to csv output')
df_schnee_data.to_csv(path_to_output + 'MeteoSchweiz_Schnee_Data.csv', index = False)
print(' -- successfull \n')

# In[207]:
print('Import CSV')
path_schnee_data = path_to_output + 'MeteoSchweiz_Schnee_Data.csv'
print(' -- successfull \n')
print('Creating Pandas Dataframe:df_schnee_data')
df_schnee_data =pd.DataFrame(pd.read_csv(path_schnee_data, sep=',', low_memory=False))
print(' -- successfull \n')

# In[208]:
df_schnee_data['Timestamp'] = df_schnee_data['Timestamp'].apply(str)
df_schnee_data

# In[209]:

```

```

df_schnee_data['Timestamp'] = df_schnee_data['Timestamp'].str.pad(width=14, side='right', fillchar='0')

# In[210]:
df_schnee_data['year'] = pd.to_numeric(df_schnee_data.Timestamp.astype(str).str[:4])
df_schnee_data['month'] = pd.to_numeric(df_schnee_data.Timestamp.astype(str).str[4:6])
df_schnee_data['day'] = pd.to_numeric(df_schnee_data.Timestamp.astype(str).str[6:8])

# In[211]:

df_schnee_data['hour'] = df_schnee_data.Timestamp.astype(str).str[8:10]
df_schnee_data['minutes'] = df_schnee_data.Timestamp.astype(str).str[10:12]
df_schnee_data['seconds'] = df_schnee_data.Timestamp.astype(str).str[12:14]

# In[212]:
df_schnee_data['UTC_Date'] =
pd.to_datetime((df_schnee_data.year*10000+df_schnee_data.month*100+df_schnee_data.day).apply(str), format='%Y%m%d')
df_schnee_data['UTC_Date'] = pd.Series([val.date() for val in df_schnee_data['UTC_Date']])

# In[213]:
df_schnee_data['UTC_Time'] = (df_schnee_data.hour+ ':' +df_schnee_data.minutes+ ':' +df_schnee_data.seconds)
df_schnee_data['UTC_Time'] = pd.to_datetime(df_schnee_data['UTC_Time'], format='%H:%M:%S')
df_schnee_data['UTC_Time'] = pd.Series([val.time() for val in df_schnee_data['UTC_Time']])
df_schnee_data['UTC'] = pd.to_datetime(df_schnee_data['Timestamp'], format='%Y%m%d%H%M%S')
df_schnee_data

# In[214]:
df_schnee_data['hour'] = pd.to_numeric(df_schnee_data.Timestamp.astype(str).str[8:10])
df_schnee_data['minutes'] = pd.to_numeric(df_schnee_data.Timestamp.astype(str).str[10:12])
df_schnee_data['seconds'] = pd.to_numeric(df_schnee_data.Timestamp.astype(str).str[12:14])

# In[215]:
df_schnee_data['UTC'].max()

# In[216]:
df_schnee_data['UTC'].min()

# In[217]:
df_schnee_data['UTC_Date'].min()

# In[218]:
df_schnee_data['UTC_Date'].max()

# In[219]:
df_schnee_data = df_schnee_data.merge(df_schnee_legend, left_on='Station', right_on='Station')
df_schnee_data

# In[220]:
del df_schnee_legend

# In[221]:
df_schnee_data = df_schnee_data.dropna(subset=['Wert_hns000hs', 'Wert_hnt000hs'], how='all')

# In[222]:
snow_cols = df_schnee_data.columns.tolist()
snow_cols

# In[223]:
snow_cols = ['Station', 'Timestamp', 'UTC', 'Wert_hns000hs', 'Einheit_hns000hs', 'Datenquelle_hns000hs',
'Beschreibung_hns000hs', 'Wert_hnt000hs', 'Einheit_hnt000hs', 'Datenquelle_hnt000hs', 'Name', 'Laenge_Grad', 'Laenge_Minuten', 'Breite_Grad', 'Breite_Minuten', 'WGS84_Laenge', 'WGS84_Breite', 'EPSG2056_lat', 'EPSG2056_lon', 'Hoehe_ASL_m', 'UTC_Date', 'UTC_Time', 'year', 'month', 'day', 'hour', 'minutes', 'seconds', ]
snow_cols

# In[224]:
df_schnee_data = df_schnee_data[snow_cols]

# In[225]:

```

```

del df_schnee_data['minutes']
del df_schnee_data['seconds']

# In[226]:
df_schnee_data

# In[227]:
df_schnee_data = df_schnee_data.set_index(pd.DatetimeIndex(df_schnee_data['UTC']))

# In[228]:
df_schnee_data = df_schnee_data.sort_index()

# In[229]:
df_schnee_data

# In[230]:
# write df_new to csv output
print('write df to csv output')
df_schnee_data.to_csv(path_to_output + 'MeteoSchweiz_Schnee_Data.csv', index = False)
print(' -- successfull \n')

# In[231]:
df_schnee_data_small = pd.DataFrame()
df_schnee_data_small = df_schnee_data
df_schnee_data_small['Neuschnee_Momentanwert_cm'] = df_schnee_data_small['Wert_hns000hs']
df_schnee_data_small['Schnee_Momentanwert_cm'] = df_schnee_data_small['Wert_hto000hs']

schnee_data_small_cols = ['UTC', 'Timestamp', 'Neuschnee_Momentanwert_cm', 'Schnee_Momentanwert_cm', 'Sta-
tion', 'Name', 'WGS84_Laenge', 'WGS84_Breite', 'EPSG2056_lat', 'EPSG2056_lon', 'Hoehe_ASL_m']
df_schnee_data_small = df_schnee_data_small[schnee_data_small_cols]
df_schnee_data_small = df_schnee_data_small.dropna()
df_schnee_data_small

# In[232]:
# write df_new to csv output
print('write df to csv output')
df_schnee_data_small.to_csv(path_to_output + 'MeteoSchweiz_schnee_Data_small.csv', index = False)
print(' -- successfull \n')

# In[233]:
del df_schnee_data_small
del df_schnee_data

# Niederschlag
# -----

# Parameter
# -----
# Einheit, Beschreibung
# rre150h0, mm, Niederschlag Stundensumme

# In[234]:
print('Options to show full pandas dataframe \n')
pd.set_option('display.max_rows', None)
pd.set_option('display.max_columns', None)
pd.set_option('display.width', None)
pd.set_option('display.max_colwidth', None)

print('Set display of dataframe to max columns')
pd.set_option('display.max_columns', None)
print(' -- successfull \n')

# In[235]:
print('Import CSV')
path_niederschlag_legend = path_meteo_ch + 'order93795\MeteoSchweiz_order_93795_legend.csv'
print(' -- successfull \n')
print('Creating Pandas Dataframe:df_niederschlag_legend')
df_niederschlag_legend = pd.DataFrame(pd.read_csv(path_niederschlag_legend, sep=',', low_memory=False))
print(' -- successfull \n')

# In[236]:
df_niederschlag_legend['Laenge_Minuten'] = df_niederschlag_legend['Laenge_Minuten'].astype(float)
df_niederschlag_legend['Laenge_Grad'] = df_niederschlag_legend['Laenge_Grad'].astype(float)
df_niederschlag_legend['Breite_Minuten'] = df_niederschlag_legend['Breite_Minuten'].astype(float)
df_niederschlag_legend['Breite_Grad'] = df_niederschlag_legend['Breite_Grad'].astype(float)

```

```

df_niederschlag_legend['WGS84_Laenge'] = df_niederschlag_legend['Laenge_Grad'].add(df_niederschlag_legend['Laenge_Minuten'].div(60))
df_niederschlag_legend['WGS84_Breite'] = df_niederschlag_legend['Breite_Grad'].add(df_niederschlag_legend['Breite_Minuten'].div(60))

# In[237]:
df_niederschlag_legend['EPSG2056_lat'] = df_niederschlag_legend['WGS84_Breite']
df_niederschlag_legend['EPSG2056_lon'] = df_niederschlag_legend['WGS84_Laenge']

print('project WGS84 to EPSG2056')
#loop to write individual csv files
index = 0
for index, row in df_niederschlag_legend.iterrows():
# get pointX and PointX from EPSG2056_lat and EPSG2056_long in row
    pointX = df_niederschlag_legend.loc[index,'EPSG2056_lat']
    pointY = df_niederschlag_legend.loc[index,'EPSG2056_lon']
# add pointX and pointY as osgeo Point
    point = ogr.Geometry(ogr.wkbPoint)
    point.AddPoint(pointY, pointX)
# Transform
    print("WGS84: ", point)
    point.Transform(coordTransform)
# print point in EPSG 4326
    print("EPSG2056: ", point)
    print("\n")
# convert back tuple back to each row
    df_niederschlag_legend.loc[index,'EPSG2056_lat'] = point.GetX()
    df_niederschlag_legend.loc[index,'EPSG2056_lon'] = point.GetY()
print(' -- successfull \n')

# In[238]:
del df_niederschlag_legend['EPSG2056_Breite_km']
del df_niederschlag_legend['EPSG2056_Laenge_km']

# In[239]:
df_niederschlag_legend['Parameter_rre150h0'] = 'rre150h0'
df_niederschlag_legend['Beschreibung_rre150h0'] = 'Niederschlag Stundensumme'
df_niederschlag_legend['Einheit_rre150h0'] = 'mm'

# In[240]:
df_niederschlag_legend = df_niederschlag_legend.drop_duplicates('Station', keep='last')
df_niederschlag_legend

# In[241]:
# write df_new to csv output
print('write df to csv output')
df_niederschlag_legend.to_csv(r'D:\\info\\Downloads\\CAS_ETH_Spatial_Information_Systems\\Rotwildmonitoring\\output\\MeteoSchweiz_Niederschlag_Legende.csv', index = False)
print(' -- successfull \n')

# In[242]:
print('Import CSV')
path_niederschlag_data = path_meteo_ch + 'order93795\MeteoSchweiz_order_93795_data.csv'
print(' -- successfull \n')

# In[243]:
with open(path_niederschlag_data,'r') as input_file:
    data_str = input_file.read()
    data_array = data_str.split('\n\n') # Split on all instances of double new lines
    for i, smaller_data in enumerate(data_array):
        with open(path_meteo_ch + 'order93795\MeteoSchweiz_order_93795_data{i}.csv','w') as new_data_file:
            new_data_file.write(smaller_data)

# In[244]:
print('Import CSV')
path_niederschlag_data = path_meteo_ch + 'order93795\MeteoSchweiz_order_93795_data'
print(' -- successfull \n')
df_var_niederschlag = 'NaN'
dataframes_niederschlag = {}
for b in range(19):
    df_var_niederschlag = 'df'+ str(b)
    print(df_var_niederschlag)
    dataframes_niederschlag[df_var_niederschlag] = pd.DataFrame({'Station','Timestamp','Wert_hns000hs','Wert_hto000hs'})
    dataframes_niederschlag[df_var_niederschlag] = pd.DataFrame(pd.read_csv(path_niederschlag_data+str(b)+'.csv', sep=';', low_memory=False))
    print(dataframes_niederschlag)
    print(' -- successfull \n')

```

```

# In[245]:
dataframes_niederschlag.keys()

# In[246]:
df_niederschlag_data = pd.concat(dataframes_niederschlag,ignore_index=True)

# In[247]:
df_niederschlag_data

# In[248]:
# write df_new to csv output
print('write df to csv output')
df_niederschlag_data.to_csv(path_to_output + 'MeteoSchweiz_Niederschlag_Data.csv', index = False)
print(' -- successfull \n')

# In[249]:
print('Import CSV')
path_niederschlag_data =path_to_output + 'MeteoSchweiz_Niederschlag_Data.csv'
print(' -- successfull \n')
print('Creating Pandas Dataframe:df_schnee_data')
df_niederschlag_data =pd.DataFrame(pd.read_csv(path_niederschlag_data, sep=',', low_memory=False))
print(' -- successfull \n')

# In[250]:
df_niederschlag_data['Timestamp'] = df_niederschlag_data['Timestamp'].apply(str)
df_niederschlag_data

# In[251]:
df_niederschlag_data['Timestamp'] = df_niederschlag_data['Timestamp'].str.pad(width=14, side='right', fill-
char='0')

# In[252]:
df_niederschlag_data['year'] = pd.to_numeric(df_niederschlag_data.Timestamp.astype(str).str[:4])
df_niederschlag_data['month'] = pd.to_numeric(df_niederschlag_data.Timestamp.astype(str).str[4:6])
df_niederschlag_data['day'] = pd.to_numeric(df_niederschlag_data.Timestamp.astype(str).str[6:8])

# In[253]:
df_niederschlag_data['hour'] = df_niederschlag_data.Timestamp.astype(str).str[8:10]
df_niederschlag_data['minutes'] = df_niederschlag_data.Timestamp.astype(str).str[10:12]
df_niederschlag_data['seconds'] = df_niederschlag_data.Timestamp.astype(str).str[12:14]

# In[254]:
df_niederschlag_data['UTC_Date'] = pd.to_datetime((df_niederschlag_data.year*10000+df_nieder-
schlag_data.month*100+df_niederschlag_data.day).apply(str),format='%Y%m%d')
df_niederschlag_data['UTC_Date'] = pd.Series([val.date() for val in df_niederschlag_data['UTC_Date']])

# In[255]:
df_niederschlag_data['UTC_Time'] = (df_niederschlag_data.hour+ ':' +df_niederschlag_data.minutes+ ':' +df_nie-
derschlag_data.seconds)
df_niederschlag_data['UTC_Time'] = pd.to_datetime(df_niederschlag_data['UTC_Time'] ,format='%H:%M:%S' )
df_niederschlag_data['UTC_Time'] = pd.Series([val.time() for val in df_niederschlag_data['UTC_Time']])
df_niederschlag_data['UTC'] = pd.to_datetime(df_niederschlag_data['Timestamp'], format='%Y%m%d%H%M%S')
df_niederschlag_data

# In[256]:
df_niederschlag_data['hour'] = pd.to_numeric(df_niederschlag_data.Timestamp.astype(str).str[8:10])
df_niederschlag_data['minutes'] = pd.to_numeric(df_niederschlag_data.Timestamp.astype(str).str[10:12])
df_niederschlag_data['seconds'] = pd.to_numeric(df_niederschlag_data.Timestamp.astype(str).str[12:14])

# In[257]:
df_niederschlag_data['UTC'].max()

# In[258]:
df_niederschlag_data['UTC'].min()

# In[259]:
df_niederschlag_data['UTC_Date'].min()

# In[260]:
df_niederschlag_data['UTC_Date'].max()

```

```

# In[261]:
df_niederschlag_legend

# In[262]:
# write df_new to csv output
print('write df to csv output')
df_niederschlag_legend.to_csv(path_to_output + 'MeteoSchweiz_Niederschlag_Legende.csv', index = False)
print(' -- successfull \n')

# In[263]:
df_niederschlag_data = df_niederschlag_data.merge(df_niederschlag_legend, left_on='Station', right_on='Station')
df_niederschlag_data

# In[264]:
del df_niederschlag_legend

# In[265]:
df_niederschlag_data = df_niederschlag_data.dropna(subset=['Wert_rre150h0'], how='all')

# In[266]:
niederschlag_cols = df_niederschlag_data.columns.tolist()
niederschlag_cols

# In[267]:
niederschlag_cols = ['Station', 'Timestamp', 'UTC', 'Parameter_rre150h0', 'Wert_rre150h0', 'Einheit_rre150h0', 'Datenquelle_rre150h0', 'Beschreibung_rre150h0', 'Name', 'Laenge_Grad', 'Laenge_Minuten', 'Breite_Grad', 'Breite_Minuten', 'WGS84_Laenge', 'WGS84_Breite', 'EPSG2056_lat', 'EPSG2056_lon', 'Hoehe_ASL_m', 'UTC_Date', 'UTC_Time', 'year', 'month', 'day', 'hour', 'minutes', 'seconds',]
niederschlag_cols

# In[268]:
df_niederschlag_data = df_niederschlag_data[niederschlag_cols]

# In[269]:
del df_niederschlag_data['minutes']
del df_niederschlag_data['seconds']

# In[270]:
df_niederschlag_data

# In[271]:
df_niederschlag_data = df_niederschlag_data.set_index(pd.DatetimeIndex(df_niederschlag_data['UTC']))

# In[272]:
df_niederschlag_data = df_niederschlag_data.sort_index()

# In[273]:
df_niederschlag_data

# In[274]:
# write df_new to csv output
print('write df to csv output')
df_niederschlag_data.to_csv(path_to_output + 'MeteoSchweiz_Niederschlag_Data.csv', index = False)
print(' -- successfull \n')

# In[275]:
df_niederschlag_data_small = pd.DataFrame()
df_niederschlag_data_small = df_niederschlag_data
df_niederschlag_data_small['Niederschlag_Stundensumme_mm'] = df_niederschlag_data_small['Wert_rre150h0']

niederschlag_data_small_cols = ['UTC', 'Timestamp', 'Niederschlag_Stundensumme_mm', 'Station', 'Name', 'WGS84_Laenge', 'WGS84_Breite', 'EPSG2056_lat', 'EPSG2056_lon', 'Hoehe_ASL_m']
df_niederschlag_data_small = df_niederschlag_data_small[niederschlag_data_small_cols]
df_niederschlag_data_small = df_niederschlag_data_small.dropna()
df_niederschlag_data_small

# In[276]:
# write df_new to csv output
print('write df to csv output')

```

```

df_niederschlag_data_small.to_csv(path_to_output + 'MeteoSchweiz_niederschlag_Data_small.csv', index = False)
print(' -- successfull \n')

# In[277]:
del df_niederschlag_data_small
del df_niederschlag_data

# Luftfeuchtigkeit
# -----

# Parameter
# -----
#           Einheit                               Beschreibung
# ure200h0  %                                     Relative Luftfeuchtigkeit 2 m über Boden Stundenmittel
# ure200hs  %                                     Relative Luftfeuchtigkeit 2 m über Boden stündlicher Momentanwert
# tde200hs  C                                     Taupunkt 2 m über Boden; stündlicher Momentanwert
# ure200ha  %                                     Relative Luftfeuchtigkeit 2 m über Boden Standardabweichung
#

# In[278]:
print('Import CSV')
path_luftfeuchtigkeit_legend = path_meteo_ch + 'order93798\MeteoSchweiz_order_93798_legend.csv'
print(' -- successfull \n')
print('Creating Pandas Dataframe:df_luftfeuchtigkeit_legend')
df_luftfeuchtigkeit_legend =pd.DataFrame(pd.read_csv(path_luftfeuchtigkeit_legend, sep=',', low_memory=False))
print(' -- successfull \n')

# In[279]:
df_luftfeuchtigkeit_legend['Laenge_Minuten'] = df_luftfeuchtigkeit_legend['Laenge_Minuten'].astype(float)
df_luftfeuchtigkeit_legend['Laenge_Grad'] = df_luftfeuchtigkeit_legend['Laenge_Grad'].astype(float)
df_luftfeuchtigkeit_legend['Breite_Minuten'] = df_luftfeuchtigkeit_legend['Breite_Minuten'].astype(float)
df_luftfeuchtigkeit_legend['Breite_Grad'] = df_luftfeuchtigkeit_legend['Breite_Grad'].astype(float)
df_luftfeuchtigkeit_legend['WGS84_Laenge'] = df_luftfeuchtigkeit_legend['Laenge_Grad'].add(df_luftfeuchtigkeit_legend['Laenge_Minuten'].div(60))
df_luftfeuchtigkeit_legend['WGS84_Breite'] = df_luftfeuchtigkeit_legend['Breite_Grad'].add(df_luftfeuchtigkeit_legend['Breite_Minuten'].div(60))

# In[280]:
df_luftfeuchtigkeit_legend['EPSG2056_lat'] = df_luftfeuchtigkeit_legend['WGS84_Breite']
df_luftfeuchtigkeit_legend['EPSG2056_lon'] = df_luftfeuchtigkeit_legend['WGS84_Laenge']

print('project WGS84 to EPSG2056')
#loop to write individual csv files
index = 0
for index, row in df_luftfeuchtigkeit_legend.iterrows():
# get pointX and PointX from EPSG2056_lat and EPSG2056_long in row
    pointX = df_luftfeuchtigkeit_legend.loc[index, 'EPSG2056_lat']
    pointY = df_luftfeuchtigkeit_legend.loc[index, 'EPSG2056_lon']
# add pointX and pointY as osgeo Point
    point = ogr.Geometry(ogr.wkbPoint)
    point.AddPoint(pointY, pointX)
# Transform
    print("WGS84: ", point)
    point.Transform(coordTransform)
# print point in EPSG 4326
    print("EPSG2056: ", point)
    print("\n")
# convert back tuple back to each row
    df_luftfeuchtigkeit_legend.loc[index, 'EPSG2056_lat'] = point.GetX()
    df_luftfeuchtigkeit_legend.loc[index, 'EPSG2056_lon'] = point.GetY()
print(' -- successfull \n')

# In[281]:
del df_luftfeuchtigkeit_legend['EPSG2056_Breite_km']
del df_luftfeuchtigkeit_legend['EPSG2056_Laenge_km']

# In[282]:
df_luftfeuchtigkeit_legend['Parameter_ure200h0'] = 'ure200h0'
df_luftfeuchtigkeit_legend['Parameter_ure200hs'] = 'ure200hs'
df_luftfeuchtigkeit_legend['Parameter_tde200hs'] = 'tde200hs'
df_luftfeuchtigkeit_legend['Parameter_ure200ha'] = 'ure200ha'
df_luftfeuchtigkeit_legend['Datenquelle_ure200h0'] = 'NaN'
df_luftfeuchtigkeit_legend['Datenquelle_ure200hs'] = 'NaN'
df_luftfeuchtigkeit_legend['Datenquelle_tde200hs'] = 'NaN'
df_luftfeuchtigkeit_legend['Datenquelle_ure200ha'] = 'NaN'
df_luftfeuchtigkeit_legend['Einheit_ure200h0'] = '%'
df_luftfeuchtigkeit_legend['Einheit_ure200hs'] = '%'
df_luftfeuchtigkeit_legend['Einheit_tde200hs'] = 'C'
df_luftfeuchtigkeit_legend['Einheit_ure200ha'] = '%'
df_luftfeuchtigkeit_legend['Beschreibung_ure200h0'] = 'Relative Luftfeuchtigkeit 2 m über Boden Stundenmittel'

```

```

df_luftfeuchtigkeit_legend['Beschreibung_ure200hs'] ='Relative Luftfeuchtigkeit 2 m über Boden stündlicher Mo-
mentanwert'
df_luftfeuchtigkeit_legend['Beschreibung_tde200hs'] ='Taupunkt 2 m über Boden; stündlicher Momentanwert'
df_luftfeuchtigkeit_legend['Beschreibung_ure200ha'] ='Relative Luftfeuchtigkeit 2 m über Boden Standardabweichung'

# In[283]:
df_luftfeuchtigkeit_legend

# In[284]:
for index, row in islice(df_luftfeuchtigkeit_legend.iterrows(), None):
    if df_luftfeuchtigkeit_legend.loc[index, 'Parameter'] == 'ure200h0':
        df_luftfeuchtigkeit_legend.loc[index, 'Datenquelle_ure200h0'] = df_luftfeuchtigkeit_legend.loc[index, 'Datenquelle']
        print(df_luftfeuchtigkeit_legend.loc[index, 'Datenquelle'])
    elif df_luftfeuchtigkeit_legend.loc[index, 'Parameter'] == 'ure200hs':
        df_luftfeuchtigkeit_legend.loc[index, 'Datenquelle_ure200hs'] = df_luftfeuchtigkeit_legend.loc[index, 'Datenquelle']
        print(df_luftfeuchtigkeit_legend.loc[index, 'Datenquelle'])
    elif df_luftfeuchtigkeit_legend.loc[index, 'Parameter'] == 'tde200hs':
        df_luftfeuchtigkeit_legend.loc[index, 'Datenquelle_tde200hs'] = df_luftfeuchtigkeit_legend.loc[index, 'Datenquelle']
        print(df_luftfeuchtigkeit_legend.loc[index, 'Datenquelle'])
    elif df_luftfeuchtigkeit_legend.loc[index, 'Parameter'] == 'ure200ha':
        df_luftfeuchtigkeit_legend.loc[index, 'Datenquelle_ure200ha'] = df_luftfeuchtigkeit_legend.loc[index, 'Datenquelle']
        print(df_luftfeuchtigkeit_legend.loc[index, 'Datenquelle'])
    else:
        df_luftfeuchtigkeit_legend.loc[index, 'Datenquelle_ure200h0'] = 'NaN'
        df_luftfeuchtigkeit_legend.loc[index, 'Datenquelle_ure200hs'] = 'NaN'
        df_luftfeuchtigkeit_legend.loc[index, 'Datenquelle_tde200hs'] = 'NaN'
        df_luftfeuchtigkeit_legend.loc[index, 'Datenquelle_ure200ha'] = 'NaN'
        print('NaN')

# In[285]:
del df_luftfeuchtigkeit_legend['Parameter']
del df_luftfeuchtigkeit_legend['Datenquelle']

# In[286]:
df_luftfeuchtigkeit_legend

# In[287]:
df_luftfeuchtigkeit_legend['Datenquelle_ure200h0'] = df_luftfeuchtigkeit_legend.groupby('Station')['Daten-
quelle_ure200h0'].ffill()

# In[288]:
dq_1 = 'NaN'
dq_2 = 'NaN'
dq_3 = 'NaN'
dq_4 = 'NaN'
current_station = df_luftfeuchtigkeit_legend.loc[0, 'Station']
last_station = df_luftfeuchtigkeit_legend.loc[0, 'Station']

for index, row in islice(df_luftfeuchtigkeit_legend.iterrows(), None):
    current_station = df_luftfeuchtigkeit_legend.loc[index, 'Station']
    if current_station == last_station:
        if df_luftfeuchtigkeit_legend.loc[index, 'Datenquelle_ure200h0'] != 'NaN':
            dq_1 = df_luftfeuchtigkeit_legend.loc[index, 'Datenquelle_ure200h0']
        elif df_luftfeuchtigkeit_legend.loc[index, 'Datenquelle_ure200hs'] != 'NaN':
            dq_2 = df_luftfeuchtigkeit_legend.loc[index, 'Datenquelle_ure200hs']
        elif df_luftfeuchtigkeit_legend.loc[index, 'Datenquelle_tde200hs'] != 'NaN':
            dq_3 = df_luftfeuchtigkeit_legend.loc[index, 'Datenquelle_tde200hs']
        elif df_luftfeuchtigkeit_legend.loc[index, 'Datenquelle_ure200ha'] != 'NaN':
            dq_4 = df_luftfeuchtigkeit_legend.loc[index, 'Datenquelle_ure200ha']

        df_luftfeuchtigkeit_legend.loc[index, 'Datenquelle_ure200h0'] = dq_1
        df_luftfeuchtigkeit_legend.loc[index, 'Datenquelle_ure200hs'] = dq_2
        df_luftfeuchtigkeit_legend.loc[index, 'Datenquelle_tde200hs'] = dq_3
        df_luftfeuchtigkeit_legend.loc[index, 'Datenquelle_ure200ha'] = dq_4
    else:
        print('New Station')
        dq_1 = df_luftfeuchtigkeit_legend.loc[index, 'Datenquelle_ure200h0']
        df_luftfeuchtigkeit_legend.loc[index, 'Datenquelle_ure200h0'] = dq_1
        print(dq_1, dq_2, dq_3, dq_4)
        dq_2 = 'NaN'
        dq_3 = 'NaN'
        dq_4 = 'NaN'
    last_station = df_luftfeuchtigkeit_legend.loc[index, 'Station']

# In[289]:

```

```

df_luftfeuchtigkeit_legend = df_luftfeuchtigkeit_legend.drop_duplicates('Station', keep='last')
df_luftfeuchtigkeit_legend

# In[290]:
# write df_new to csv output
print('write df to csv output')
df_luftfeuchtigkeit_legend.to_csv(path_to_output + 'MeteoSchweiz_Luftfeuchtigkeit_Legende.csv', index = False)
print(' -- successfull \n')

# In[291]:
print('Import CSV')
path_luftfeuchtigkeit_data = path_meteo_ch + 'order93798\MeteoSchweiz_order_93798_data.csv'
print(' -- successfull \n')

# In[292]:
with open(path_luftfeuchtigkeit_data, 'r') as input_file:
    data_str = input_file.read()
    data_array = data_str.split('\n\n') # Split on all instances of double new lines
    for i, smaller_data in enumerate(data_array):
        with open(path_meteo_ch + 'order93798\MeteoSchweiz_order_93798_data{0}.csv'.format(i), 'w') as new_data_file:
            new_data_file.write(smaller_data)

# In[293]:
print('Import CSV')
path_luftfeuchtigkeit_data = path_meteo_ch + 'order93798\MeteoSchweiz_order_93798_data'
print(' -- successfull \n')
df_var_luftfeuchtigkeit = 'NaN'
dataframes_luftfeuchtigkeit = {}
for c in range(20):
    df_var_luftfeuchtigkeit = 'df'+ str(c)
    print(df_var_luftfeuchtigkeit)
    dataframes_luftfeuchtigkeit[df_var_luftfeuchtigkeit] = pd.DataFrame({'Station', 'Timestamp'})
    dataframes_luftfeuchtigkeit[df_var_luftfeuchtigkeit] = pd.DataFrame(pd.read_csv(path_luftfeuchtigkeit_data+str(c)+'.csv', sep=';', low_memory=False))
    print(dataframes_luftfeuchtigkeit)
    print(' -- successfull \n')

# In[294]:
dataframes_luftfeuchtigkeit.keys()

# In[295]:
df_luftfeuchtigkeit_data = pd.concat(dataframes_luftfeuchtigkeit, ignore_index=True)

# In[296]:
df_luftfeuchtigkeit_data['Wert_ure200h0'] = df_luftfeuchtigkeit_data['Wert_ure200h0'].astype(float)

# In[297]:
#check if there are any non number characters like '-'
# non number characters were removed manually in csv
try:
    df_luftfeuchtigkeit_data['Wert_ure200h0'] = pd.to_numeric(df_luftfeuchtigkeit_data['Wert_ure200h0'])
except ValueError:
    # I want to register on my log the message received on ORIGINAL VALUE
    mask = pd.to_numeric(df_luftfeuchtigkeit_data['Wert_ure200h0'].fillna(np.nan), errors='coerce').isna()
    L = df_luftfeuchtigkeit_data.loc[mask, 'Wert_ure200h0'].tolist()
    for val in L:
        print(f"Not converted values are: {val}")
        log.exception(f"Not converted values are: {val}")

# In[298]:
df_luftfeuchtigkeit_data['Wert_ure200h0'] = df_luftfeuchtigkeit_data['Wert_ure200h0'].astype(float)

# In[299]:
df_luftfeuchtigkeit_data['Wert_ure200hs'] = df_luftfeuchtigkeit_data['Wert_ure200hs'].astype(float)
df_luftfeuchtigkeit_data['Wert_tde200hs'] = df_luftfeuchtigkeit_data['Wert_tde200hs'].astype(float)
df_luftfeuchtigkeit_data['Wert_ure200ha'] = df_luftfeuchtigkeit_data['Wert_ure200ha'].astype(float)

# In[300]:
df_luftfeuchtigkeit_data

# In[301]:
# write df_new to csv output
print('write df to csv output')
df_luftfeuchtigkeit_data.to_csv(path_to_output + 'MeteoSchweiz_Luftfeuchtigkeit_Data.csv', index = False)
print(' -- successfull \n')

```

```

# In[302]:
print('Import CSV')
path_luftfeuchtigkeit_data = path_to_output + 'MeteoSchweiz_Luftfeuchtigkeit_Data.csv'
print('-- successfull \n')
print('Creating Pandas Dataframe:df_luftfeuchtigkeit_data')
df_luftfeuchtigkeit_data =pd.DataFrame(pd.read_csv(path_luftfeuchtigkeit_data, sep=',', low_memory=False))
print('-- successfull \n')

# In[303]:
df_luftfeuchtigkeit_data['Timestamp'] = df_luftfeuchtigkeit_data['Timestamp'].apply(str)
df_luftfeuchtigkeit_data

# In[304]:
df_luftfeuchtigkeit_data['Timestamp'] = df_luftfeuchtigkeit_data['Timestamp'].str.pad(width=14, side='right',
fillchar='0')

# In[305]:
df_luftfeuchtigkeit_data['year'] = pd.to_numeric(df_luftfeuchtigkeit_data.Timestamp.astype(str).str[:4])
df_luftfeuchtigkeit_data['month'] = pd.to_numeric(df_luftfeuchtigkeit_data.Timestamp.astype(str).str[4:6])
df_luftfeuchtigkeit_data['day'] = pd.to_numeric(df_luftfeuchtigkeit_data.Timestamp.astype(str).str[6:8])

# In[306]:
df_luftfeuchtigkeit_data['hour'] = df_luftfeuchtigkeit_data.Timestamp.astype(str).str[8:10]
df_luftfeuchtigkeit_data['minutes'] = df_luftfeuchtigkeit_data.Timestamp.astype(str).str[10:12]
df_luftfeuchtigkeit_data['seconds'] = df_luftfeuchtigkeit_data.Timestamp.astype(str).str[12:14]

# In[307]:
df_luftfeuchtigkeit_data['UTC_Date'] = pd.to_datetime((df_luftfeuchtigkeit_data.year*10000+df_luftfeuchtig-
keit_data.month*100+df_luftfeuchtigkeit_data.day).apply(str),format='%Y%m%d')
df_luftfeuchtigkeit_data['UTC_Date'] = pd.Series([val.date() for val in df_luftfeuchtigkeit_data['UTC_Date']])

# In[308]:
df_luftfeuchtigkeit_data['UTC_Time'] = (df_luftfeuchtigkeit_data.hour+ ':' +df_luftfeuchtigkeit_data.minutes+
 ':' +df_luftfeuchtigkeit_data.seconds)
df_luftfeuchtigkeit_data['UTC_Time'] = pd.to_datetime(df_luftfeuchtigkeit_data['UTC_Time'] ,format='%H:%M:%S' )
df_luftfeuchtigkeit_data['UTC_Time'] = pd.Series([val.time() for val in df_luftfeuchtigkeit_data['UTC_Time']])
df_luftfeuchtigkeit_data['UTC'] = pd.to_datetime(df_luftfeuchtigkeit_data['Timestamp'], format='%Y%m%d%H%M%S')
df_luftfeuchtigkeit_data

# In[309]:
df_luftfeuchtigkeit_data['hour'] = pd.to_numeric(df_luftfeuchtigkeit_data.Timestamp.astype(str).str[8:10])
df_luftfeuchtigkeit_data['minutes'] = pd.to_numeric(df_luftfeuchtigkeit_data.Timestamp.astype(str).str[10:12])
df_luftfeuchtigkeit_data['seconds'] = pd.to_numeric(df_luftfeuchtigkeit_data.Timestamp.astype(str).str[12:14])

# In[310]:
df_luftfeuchtigkeit_data['UTC'].max()

# In[311]:
df_luftfeuchtigkeit_data['UTC'].min()

# In[312]:
df_luftfeuchtigkeit_data['UTC_Date'].min()

# In[313]:
df_luftfeuchtigkeit_data['UTC_Date'].max()

# In[314]:
df_luftfeuchtigkeit_data = df_luftfeuchtigkeit_data.merge(df_luftfeuchtigkeit_legend, left_on='Station',
right_on='Station')
df_luftfeuchtigkeit_data

# In[315]:
del df_luftfeuchtigkeit_legend

# In[316]:
df_luftfeuchtigkeit_data = df_luftfeuchtigkeit_data.dropna(sub-
set=['Wert_ure200h0','Wert_ure200hs','Wert_tde200hs','Wert_ure200ha'], how='all')

# In[317]:

```

```

luftfeuchtigkeit_cols = df_luftfeuchtigkeit_data.columns.tolist()
luftfeuchtigkeit_cols

# In[318]:
luftfeuchtigkeit2_cols = ['Station','Timestamp','UTC','Parameter_ure200h0','Wert_ure200h0','Ein-
heit_ure200h0','Datenquelle_ure200h0','Beschreibung_ure200h0','Parameter_ure200hs','Wert_ure200hs','Ein-
heit_ure200hs','Datenquelle_ure200hs','Beschreibung_ure200hs','Parameter_tde200hs','Wert_tde200hs','Ein-
heit_tde200hs','Datenquelle_tde200hs','Beschreibung_tde200hs','Parameter_ure200ha','Wert_ure200ha','Ein-
heit_ure200ha','Datenquelle_ure200ha','Beschreibung_ure200ha','Name','Laenge_Grad','Laenge_Minu-
ten','Breite_Grad','Breite_Minuten','WGS84_Laenge','WGS84_Brei-
te','EPSG2056_lat','EPSG2056_lon','Hoehe_ASL_m','UTC_Date','UTC_Time','year','month','day','hour']
luftfeuchtigkeit2_cols

# In[319]:
del df_luftfeuchtigkeit_data['minutes']
del df_luftfeuchtigkeit_data['seconds']

# In[320]:
df_luftfeuchtigkeit_data = df_luftfeuchtigkeit_data[luftfeuchtigkeit2_cols]

# In[321]:
df_luftfeuchtigkeit_data

# In[322]:
df_luftfeuchtigkeit_data.info()

# In[323]:
df_luftfeuchtigkeit_data = df_luftfeuchtigkeit_data.set_index(pd.DatetimeIndex(df_luftfeuchtig-
keit_data['UTC']))

# In[324]:
df_luftfeuchtigkeit_data = df_luftfeuchtigkeit_data.sort_index()

# In[325]:
df_luftfeuchtigkeit_data

# In[326]:
# write df_new to csv output
print('write df to csv output')
df_luftfeuchtigkeit_data.to_csv(path_to_output + 'MeteoSchweiz_Luftfeuchtigkeit_Data.csv', index = False)
print(' -- successfull \n')

# In[327]:
df_luftfeuchtigkeit_data_small = pd.DataFrame()
df_luftfeuchtigkeit_data_small = df_luftfeuchtigkeit_data
df_luftfeuchtigkeit_data_small['rel_Luftfeuchtigkeit_Stundenmittel_prozent'] = df_luftfeuchtig-
keit_data_small['Wert_ure200h0']
df_luftfeuchtigkeit_data_small['Taupunkt_Momentanwert_celsius'] = df_luftfeuchtig-
keit_data_small['Wert_tde200hs']

luftfeuchtigkeit_data_small_cols = ['UTC','Timestamp','rel_Luftfeuchtigkeit_Stundenmittel_prozent','Tau-
punkt_Momentanwert_celsius','Station','Name','WGS84_Laenge','WGS84_Brei-
te','EPSG2056_lat','EPSG2056_lon','Hoehe_ASL_m']
df_luftfeuchtigkeit_data_small = df_luftfeuchtigkeit_data_small[luftfeuchtigkeit_data_small_cols]
df_luftfeuchtigkeit_data_small = df_luftfeuchtigkeit_data_small.dropna()
df_luftfeuchtigkeit_data_small

# In[328]:
# write df_new to csv output
print('write df to csv output')
df_luftfeuchtigkeit_data_small.to_csv(path_to_output + 'MeteoSchweiz_luftfeuchtigkeit_Data_small.csv', index =
False)
print(' -- successfull \n')

# In[329]:
del df_luftfeuchtigkeit_data_small
del df_luftfeuchtigkeit_data

# Luftdruck
# -----

# Parameter
# -----
#           Einheit           Beschreibung

```

```

# prestah0 hPa Luftdruck auf Barometerhöhe (QFE); Stundenmittel
# prestahs hPa Luftdruck auf Barometerhöhe (QFE): stündlicher Momentanwert
# prestahd hPa Luftdruckänderung seit der letzten Stunde
#
#
# In[330]:
print('Import CSV')
path_druck_legend = path_meteo_ch + 'order93800\MeteoSchweiz_order_93800_legend.csv'
print(' -- successfull \n')
print('Creating Pandas Dataframe:df_druck_legend')
df_druck_legend =pd.DataFrame(pd.read_csv(path_druck_legend, sep=',', low_memory=False))
print(' -- successfull \n')

# In[331]:
df_druck_legend['Laenge_Minuten'] = df_druck_legend['Laenge_Minuten'].astype(float)
df_druck_legend['Laenge_Grad'] = df_druck_legend['Laenge_Grad'].astype(float)
df_druck_legend['Breite_Minuten'] = df_druck_legend['Breite_Minuten'].astype(float)
df_druck_legend['Breite_Grad'] = df_druck_legend['Breite_Grad'].astype(float)
df_druck_legend['WGS84_Laenge'] = df_druck_legend['Laenge_Grad'].add(df_druck_legend['Laenge_Minuten'].div(60))
df_druck_legend['WGS84_Breite'] = df_druck_legend['Breite_Grad'].add(df_druck_legend['Breite_Minuten'].div(60))

# In[332]:
df_druck_legend['EPSG2056_lat'] = df_druck_legend['WGS84_Breite']
df_druck_legend['EPSG2056_lon'] = df_druck_legend['WGS84_Laenge']

print('project WGS84 to EPSG2056')
#loop to write individual csv files
index = 0
for index, row in df_druck_legend.iterrows():
# get pointX and PointX from EPSG2056_lat and EPSG2056_long in row
pointX = df_druck_legend.loc[index, 'EPSG2056_lat']
pointY = df_druck_legend.loc[index, 'EPSG2056_lon']
# add pointX and pointY as osgeo Point
point = ogr.Geometry(ogr.wkbPoint)
point.AddPoint(pointY, pointX)
# Transform
print("WGS84: ", point)
point.Transform(coordTransform)
# print point in EPSG 4326
print("EPSG2056: ", point)
print("\n")
# convert back tupel back to each row
df_druck_legend.loc[index, 'EPSG2056_lat'] = point.GetX()
df_druck_legend.loc[index, 'EPSG2056_lon'] = point.GetY()
print(' -- successfull \n')

# In[333]:
df_druck_legend['Parameter_prestah0'] = 'prestah0'
df_druck_legend['Parameter_prestahs'] = 'prestahs'
df_druck_legend['Parameter_prestahd'] = 'prestahd'
df_druck_legend['Datenquelle_prestah0'] = 'NaN'
df_druck_legend['Datenquelle_prestahs'] = 'NaN'
df_druck_legend['Datenquelle_prestahd'] = 'NaN'
df_druck_legend['Einheit_prestah0'] = 'hPa'
df_druck_legend['Einheit_prestahs'] = 'hPa'
df_druck_legend['Einheit_prestahd'] = 'hPa'
df_druck_legend['Beschreibung_prestah0'] = 'Luftdruck auf Barometerhöhe (QFE) Stundenmittel'
df_druck_legend['Beschreibung_prestahs'] = 'Luftdruck auf Barometerhöhe (QFE) stündlicher Momentanwert'
df_druck_legend['Beschreibung_prestahd'] = 'Luftdruckänderung seit der letzten Stunde'

# In[334]:
df_druck_legend

# In[335]:
for index, row in islice(df_druck_legend.iterrows(), None):
if df_druck_legend.loc[index, 'Parameter'] == 'prestah0':
df_druck_legend.loc[index, 'Datenquelle_prestah0'] = df_druck_legend.loc[index, 'Datenquelle']
print(df_druck_legend.loc[index, 'Datenquelle'])
elif df_druck_legend.loc[index, 'Parameter'] == 'prestahs':
df_druck_legend.loc[index, 'Datenquelle_prestahs'] = df_druck_legend.loc[index, 'Datenquelle']
print(df_druck_legend.loc[index, 'Datenquelle'])
elif df_druck_legend.loc[index, 'Parameter'] == 'prestahd':
df_druck_legend.loc[index, 'Datenquelle_prestahd'] = df_druck_legend.loc[index, 'Datenquelle']
print(df_druck_legend.loc[index, 'Datenquelle'])
else:
df_druck_legend.loc[index, 'Datenquelle_prestah0'] = 'NaN'
df_druck_legend.loc[index, 'Datenquelle_prestahs'] = 'NaN'
df_druck_legend.loc[index, 'Datenquelle_prestahd'] = 'NaN'
print('NaN')

```

```

# In[336]:
del df_druck_legend['Parameter']
del df_druck_legend['Datenquelle']

# In[337]:
df_druck_legend

# In[338]:
df_druck_legend['Datenquelle_prestah0'] = df_druck_legend.groupby('Station')['Datenquelle_prestah0'].ffill()

# In[339]:
dq_1 = 'NaN'
dq_2 = 'NaN'
dq_3 = 'NaN'
current_station = df_druck_legend.loc[0,'Station']
last_station = df_druck_legend.loc[0,'Station']

for index, row in islice(df_druck_legend.iterrows(), None):
    current_station = df_druck_legend.loc[index,'Station']
    if current_station == last_station:
        if df_druck_legend.loc[index,'Datenquelle_prestah0'] != 'NaN':
            dq_1 = df_druck_legend.loc[index,'Datenquelle_prestah0']
        elif df_druck_legend.loc[index,'Datenquelle_prestahs'] != 'NaN':
            dq_2 = df_druck_legend.loc[index,'Datenquelle_prestahs']
        elif df_druck_legend.loc[index,'Datenquelle_prestahd'] != 'NaN':
            dq_3 = df_druck_legend.loc[index,'Datenquelle_prestahd']
        df_druck_legend.loc[index,'Datenquelle_prestah0'] = dq_1
        df_druck_legend.loc[index,'Datenquelle_prestahs'] = dq_2
        df_druck_legend.loc[index,'Datenquelle_prestahd'] = dq_3
    else:
        print('New Station')
        dq_1 = df_druck_legend.loc[index,'Datenquelle_prestah0']
        df_druck_legend.loc[index,'Datenquelle_prestah0'] = dq_1
        print(dq_1,dq_2,dq_3)
        dq_2='NaN'
        dq_3='NaN'
    last_station = df_druck_legend.loc[index,'Station']

# In[340]:
del df_druck_legend['EPSG2056_Breite_km']
del df_druck_legend['EPSG2056_Laenge_km']

# In[341]:
df_druck_legend = df_druck_legend.drop_duplicates('Station', keep='last')
df_druck_legend

# In[342]:
# write df_new to csv output
print('write df to csv output')
df_druck_legend.to_csv(path_to_output + 'MeteoSchweiz_Druck_Legende.csv', index = False)
print(' -- successfull \n')

# In[343]:
print('Import CSV')
path_druck_data = path_meteo_ch + 'order93800\MeteoSchweiz_order_93800_data.csv'
print(' -- successfull \n')

# In[344]:
with open(path_druck_data,'r') as input_file:
    data_str = input_file.read()
    data_array = data_str.split('\n\n') # Split on all instances of double new lines
    for i, smaller_data in enumerate(data_array):
        with open(path_meteo_ch + 'order93800\MeteoSchweiz_order_93800_data{i}.csv','w') as new_data_file:
            new_data_file.write(smaller_data)

# In[345]:
print('Import CSV')
path_druck_data = path_meteo_ch + 'order93800\MeteoSchweiz_order_93800_data'
print(' -- successfull \n')
df_var_druck = 'NaN'
dataframes_druck = {}
for d in range(6):
    df_var_druck = 'df'+ str(d)
    print(df_var_druck)
    dataframes_druck[df_var_druck] = pd.DataFrame({'Station','Timestamp'})
    dataframes_druck[df_var_druck] = pd.DataFrame(pd.read_csv(path_druck_data+str(d)+'.csv', sep=';', low_memory=False))
    print(dataframes_druck)

```

```

print(' -- successfull \n')

# In[346]:
dataframes_druck.keys()

# In[347]:
df_druck_data = pd.concat(dataframes_druck,ignore_index=True)

# In[348]:
df_druck_data

# In[349]:
# write df_new to csv output
print('write df to csv output')
df_druck_data.to_csv(path_to_output + 'MeteoSchweiz_Druck_Data.csv', index = False)
print(' -- successfull \n')

# In[350]:
print('Import CSV')
path_druck_data = path_to_output + 'MeteoSchweiz_Druck_Data.csv'
print(' -- successfull \n')
print('Creating Pandas Dataframe:df_druck_data')
df_druck_data =pd.DataFrame(pd.read_csv(path_druck_data, sep=',', low_memory=False))
print(' -- successfull \n')

# In[351]:
df_druck_data['Timestamp'] = df_druck_data['Timestamp'].apply(str)
df_druck_data

# In[352]:
df_druck_data['Timestamp'] = df_druck_data['Timestamp'].str.pad(width=14, side='right', fillchar='0')

# In[353]:
df_druck_data['year'] = pd.to_numeric(df_druck_data.Timestamp.astype(str).str[:4])
df_druck_data['month'] = pd.to_numeric(df_druck_data.Timestamp.astype(str).str[4:6])
df_druck_data['day'] = pd.to_numeric(df_druck_data.Timestamp.astype(str).str[6:8])

# In[354]:
df_druck_data['hour'] = df_druck_data.Timestamp.astype(str).str[8:10]
df_druck_data['minutes'] = df_druck_data.Timestamp.astype(str).str[10:12]
df_druck_data['seconds'] = df_druck_data.Timestamp.astype(str).str[12:14]

# In[355]:
df_druck_data['UTC_Date'] =
pd.to_datetime((df_druck_data.year*10000+df_druck_data.month*100+df_druck_data.day).apply(str),format='%Y%m%d')
df_druck_data['UTC_Date'] = pd.Series([val.date() for val in df_druck_data['UTC_Date']])

# In[356]:
df_druck_data['UTC_Time'] = (df_druck_data.hour+ ':' +df_druck_data.minutes+ ':' +df_druck_data.seconds)
df_druck_data['UTC_Time'] = pd.to_datetime(df_druck_data['UTC_Time'] ,format='%H:%M:%S' )
df_druck_data['UTC_Time'] = pd.Series([val.time() for val in df_druck_data['UTC_Time']])
df_druck_data['UTC'] = pd.to_datetime(df_druck_data['Timestamp'], format='%Y%m%d%H%M%S')
df_druck_data

# In[357]:
df_druck_data['hour'] = pd.to_numeric(df_druck_data.Timestamp.astype(str).str[8:10])
df_druck_data['minutes'] = pd.to_numeric(df_druck_data.Timestamp.astype(str).str[10:12])
df_druck_data['seconds'] = pd.to_numeric(df_druck_data.Timestamp.astype(str).str[12:14])

# In[358]:
df_druck_data['UTC'].max()

# In[359]:
df_druck_data['UTC'].min()

# In[360]:
df_druck_data['UTC_Date'].min()

# In[361]:
df_druck_data['UTC_Date'].max()

```

```

# In[362]:
df_druck_data = df_druck_data.merge(df_druck_legend, left_on='Station', right_on='Station')
df_druck_data

# In[363]:
del df_druck_legend

# In[364]:
df_druck_data = df_druck_data.dropna(subset=['Wert_prestah0', 'Wert_prestahs', 'Wert_prestahd'], how='all')

# In[365]:
df_druck_cols = df_druck_data.columns.tolist()
df_druck_cols

# In[366]:
df_druck_2cols = ['Station', 'Timestamp', 'UTC', 'Wert_prestah0', 'Einheit_prestah0', 'Datenquelle_prestah0', 'Beschreibung_prestah0', 'Parameter_prestah0', 'Wert_prestahs', 'Einheit_prestahs', 'Datenquelle_prestahs', 'Beschreibung_prestahs', 'Parameter_prestahs', 'Wert_prestahd', 'Einheit_prestahd', 'Datenquelle_prestahd', 'Beschreibung_prestahd', 'Parameter_prestahd', 'Name', 'Laenge_Grad', 'Laenge_Minuten', 'Breite_Grad', 'Breite_Minuten', 'WGS84_Laenge', 'WGS84_Breite', 'EPSG2056_lat', 'EPSG2056_lon', 'Hoehe_ASL_m', 'UTC_Date', 'UTC_Time', 'year', 'month', 'day', 'hour', 'minuten', 'seconds']
df_druck_2cols

# In[367]:
df_druck_data = df_druck_data[df_druck_2cols]

# In[368]:
df_druck_data.info()

# In[369]:
df_druck_data = df_druck_data.set_index(pd.DatetimeIndex(df_druck_data['UTC']))

# In[370]:
df_druck_data = df_druck_data.sort_index()

# In[371]:
df_druck_data

# In[372]:
# write df_new to csv output
print('write df to csv output')
df_druck_data.to_csv(path_to_output + 'MeteoSchweiz_Druck_Data.csv', index = False)
print(' -- successfull \n')

# In[373]:
df_druck_data_small = pd.DataFrame()
df_druck_data_small = df_druck_data
df_druck_data_small['Luftdruck_Barometerhoehe_QFE_Stundenmittel_hPa'] = df_druck_data_small['Wert_prestah0']
df_druck_data_small['Luftdruckaenderung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa'] = df_druck_data_small['Wert_prestahd']

druck_data_small_small_cols = ['UTC', 'Timestamp', 'Luftdruck_Barometerhoehe_QFE_Stundenmittel_hPa', 'Luftdruckaenderung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa', 'Station', 'Name', 'WGS84_Laenge', 'WGS84_Breite', 'EPSG2056_lat', 'EPSG2056_lon', 'Hoehe_ASL_m']
df_druck_data_small = df_druck_data_small[druck_data_small_small_cols]
df_druck_data_small = df_druck_data_small.dropna()
df_druck_data_small

# In[374]:
# write df_new to csv output
print('write df to csv output')
df_druck_data_small.to_csv(path_to_output + 'MeteoSchweiz_luftdruck_Data_small.csv', index = False)
print(' -- successfull \n')

# In[375]:
del df_druck_data
del df_druck_data_small

# Meteo Schweiz Data small
# -----

# In[376]:

```

```

print('Import CSV')
path_druck_data_small = path_to_output + 'MeteoSchweiz_luftdruck_Data_small.csv'
print(' -- successfull \n')
print('Creating Pandas Dataframe:df_druck_data_small')
df_druck_data_small =pd.DataFrame(pd.read_csv(path_druck_data_small, sep=',', low_memory=False))
print(' -- successfull \n')

print('Import CSV')
path_luftfeuchtigkeit_data_small = path_to_output + 'MeteoSchweiz_luftfeuchtigkeit_Data_small.csv'
print(' -- successfull \n')
print('Creating Pandas Dataframe:df_luftfeuchtigkeit_data_small')
df_luftfeuchtigkeit_data_small =pd.DataFrame(pd.read_csv(path_luftfeuchtigkeit_data_small, sep=',',
low_memory=False))
print(' -- successfull \n')

print('Import CSV')
path_niederschlag_data_small = path_to_output + 'MeteoSchweiz_niederschlag_Data_small.csv'
print(' -- successfull \n')
print('Creating Pandas Dataframe:df_niederschlag_data_small')
df_niederschlag_data_small =pd.DataFrame(pd.read_csv(path_niederschlag_data_small, sep=',', low_memory=False))
print(' -- successfull \n')

print('Import CSV')
path_schnee_data_small = path_to_output + 'MeteoSchweiz_schnee_Data_small.csv'
print(' -- successfull \n')
print('Creating Pandas Dataframe:df_schnee_data_small')
df_schnee_data_small =pd.DataFrame(pd.read_csv(path_schnee_data_small, sep=',', low_memory=False))
print(' -- successfull \n')

print('Import CSV')
path_sonnenscheindauer_data_small = path_to_output + 'MeteoSchweiz_sonnenscheindauer_Data_small.csv'
print(' -- successfull \n')
print('Creating Pandas Dataframe:df_sonnenscheindauer_data_small')
df_sonnenscheindauer_data_small =pd.DataFrame(pd.read_csv(path_sonnenscheindauer_data_small, sep=',',
low_memory=False))
print(' -- successfull \n')

print('Import CSV')
path_solar_radiation_data_small = path_to_output + 'MeteoSchweiz_solar_radiation_Data_small.csv'
print(' -- successfull \n')
print('Creating Pandas Dataframe:df_solar_radiation_data_small')
df_solar_radiation_data_small =pd.DataFrame(pd.read_csv(path_solar_radiation_data_small, sep=',',
low_memory=False))
print(' -- successfull \n')

print('Import CSV')
path_temperature_data_small = path_to_output + 'MeteoSchweiz_Temp2mAGL_small.csv'
print(' -- successfull \n')
print('Creating Pandas Dataframe:df_temperature_data_small')
df_temperature_data_small =pd.DataFrame(pd.read_csv(path_temperature_data_small, sep=',', low_memory=False))
print(' -- successfull \n')

print('Import CSV')
path_wind_data_small = path_to_output + 'MeteoSchweiz_Wind_Data_small.csv'
print(' -- successfull \n')
print('Creating Pandas Dataframe:df_wind_data_small')
df wind data small =pd.DataFrame(pd.read_csv(path_wind_data_small, sep=',', low_memory=False))
print(' -- successfull \n')

# In[377]:
df_druck_data_small

# In[378]:
df_luftfeuchtigkeit_data_small

# In[379]:
df_niederschlag_data_small

# In[380]:
df_sonnenscheindauer_data_small

# In[381]:

df_solar_radiation_data_small

# In[382]:
df_temperature_data_small

# In[383]:

```

```

df_wind_data_small

# In[384]:
df_schnee_data_small

# In[385]:
df_full_small = pd.DataFrame()

df_schnee_data_small['UTC1'] = df_schnee_data_small['UTC']
df_druck_data_small['UTC1'] = df_druck_data_small['UTC']
df_luftfeuchtigkeit_data_small['UTC1'] = df_luftfeuchtigkeit_data_small['UTC']
df_niederschlag_data_small['UTC1'] = df_niederschlag_data_small['UTC']
df_solar_radiation_data_small['UTC1'] = df_solar_radiation_data_small['UTC']
df_sonnenscheindauer_data_small['UTC1'] = df_sonnenscheindauer_data_small['UTC']
df_temperature_data_small['UTC1'] = df_temperature_data_small['UTC']
df_wind_data_small['UTC1'] = df_wind_data_small['UTC']

df_schnee_data_small.reset_index()
df_druck_data_small.reset_index()
df_luftfeuchtigkeit_data_small.reset_index()
df_niederschlag_data_small.reset_index()
df_solar_radiation_data_small.reset_index()
df_sonnenscheindauer_data_small.reset_index()
df_temperature_data_small.reset_index()
df_wind_data_small.reset_index()

df_schnee_data_small['UTC'] = pd.to_datetime(df_schnee_data_small.UTC)
df_druck_data_small['UTC'] = pd.to_datetime(df_druck_data_small.UTC)
df_luftfeuchtigkeit_data_small['UTC'] = pd.to_datetime(df_luftfeuchtigkeit_data_small.UTC)
df_niederschlag_data_small['UTC'] = pd.to_datetime(df_niederschlag_data_small.UTC)
df_solar_radiation_data_small['UTC'] = pd.to_datetime(df_solar_radiation_data_small.UTC)
df_sonnenscheindauer_data_small['UTC'] = pd.to_datetime(df_sonnenscheindauer_data_small.UTC)
df_temperature_data_small['UTC'] = pd.to_datetime(df_temperature_data_small.UTC)
df_wind_data_small['UTC'] = pd.to_datetime(df_wind_data_small.UTC)

df_schnee_data_small['UTC1'] = pd.to_datetime(df_schnee_data_small.UTC1)
df_druck_data_small['UTC1'] = pd.to_datetime(df_druck_data_small.UTC1)
df_luftfeuchtigkeit_data_small['UTC1'] = pd.to_datetime(df_luftfeuchtigkeit_data_small.UTC1)
df_niederschlag_data_small['UTC1'] = pd.to_datetime(df_niederschlag_data_small.UTC1)
df_solar_radiation_data_small['UTC1'] = pd.to_datetime(df_solar_radiation_data_small.UTC1)
df_sonnenscheindauer_data_small['UTC1'] = pd.to_datetime(df_sonnenscheindauer_data_small.UTC1)
df_temperature_data_small['UTC1'] = pd.to_datetime(df_temperature_data_small.UTC1)
df_wind_data_small['UTC1'] = pd.to_datetime(df_wind_data_small.UTC1)

df_full_small = df_temperature_data_small
df_full_small = pd.merge(df_full_small, df_druck_data_small, how='left',
left_on=['UTC', 'UTC1', 'Timestamp', 'Station', 'Name', 'WGS84_Laenge', 'WGS84_Breite', 'EPSG2056_lat', 'EPSG2056_lon', 'Hoehe_ASL_m'], right_on =
['UTC', 'UTC1', 'Timestamp', 'Station', 'Name', 'WGS84_Laenge', 'WGS84_Breite', 'EPSG2056_lat', 'EPSG2056_lon', 'Hoehe_ASL_m'])
df_full_small = pd.merge(df_full_small, df_luftfeuchtigkeit_data_small, how='left',
left_on=['UTC', 'UTC1', 'Timestamp', 'Station', 'Name', 'WGS84_Laenge', 'WGS84_Breite', 'EPSG2056_lat', 'EPSG2056_lon', 'Hoehe_ASL_m'], right_on =
['UTC', 'UTC1', 'Timestamp', 'Station', 'Name', 'WGS84_Laenge', 'WGS84_Breite', 'EPSG2056_lat', 'EPSG2056_lon', 'Hoehe_ASL_m'])
df_full_small = pd.merge(df_full_small, df_niederschlag_data_small, how='left',
left_on=['UTC', 'UTC1', 'Timestamp', 'Station', 'Name', 'WGS84_Laenge', 'WGS84_Breite', 'EPSG2056_lat', 'EPSG2056_lon', 'Hoehe_ASL_m'], right_on =
['UTC', 'UTC1', 'Timestamp', 'Station', 'Name', 'WGS84_Laenge', 'WGS84_Breite', 'EPSG2056_lat', 'EPSG2056_lon', 'Hoehe_ASL_m'])
df_full_small = pd.merge(df_full_small, df_schnee_data_small, how='left',
left_on=['UTC', 'UTC1', 'Timestamp', 'Station', 'Name', 'WGS84_Laenge', 'WGS84_Breite', 'EPSG2056_lat', 'EPSG2056_lon', 'Hoehe_ASL_m'], right_on =
['UTC', 'UTC1', 'Timestamp', 'Station', 'Name', 'WGS84_Laenge', 'WGS84_Breite', 'EPSG2056_lat', 'EPSG2056_lon', 'Hoehe_ASL_m'])
df_full_small = pd.merge(df_full_small, df_sonnenscheindauer_data_small, how='left',
left_on=['UTC', 'UTC1', 'Timestamp', 'Station', 'Name', 'WGS84_Laenge', 'WGS84_Breite', 'EPSG2056_lat', 'EPSG2056_lon', 'Hoehe_ASL_m'], right_on =
['UTC', 'UTC1', 'Timestamp', 'Station', 'Name', 'WGS84_Laenge', 'WGS84_Breite', 'EPSG2056_lat', 'EPSG2056_lon', 'Hoehe_ASL_m'])
df_full_small = pd.merge(df_full_small, df_wind_data_small, how='left',
left_on=['UTC', 'UTC1', 'Timestamp', 'Station', 'Name', 'WGS84_Laenge', 'WGS84_Breite', 'EPSG2056_lat', 'EPSG2056_lon', 'Hoehe_ASL_m'], right_on =
['UTC', 'UTC1', 'Timestamp', 'Station', 'Name', 'WGS84_Laenge', 'WGS84_Breite', 'EPSG2056_lat', 'EPSG2056_lon', 'Hoehe_ASL_m'])
df_full_small = pd.merge(df_full_small, df_solar_radiation_data_small, how='left',
left_on=['UTC', 'UTC1', 'Timestamp', 'Station', 'Name', 'WGS84_Laenge', 'WGS84_Breite', 'EPSG2056_lat', 'EPSG2056_lon', 'Hoehe_ASL_m'], right_on =
['UTC', 'UTC1', 'Timestamp', 'Station', 'Name', 'WGS84_Laenge', 'WGS84_Breite', 'EPSG2056_lat', 'EPSG2056_lon', 'Hoehe_ASL_m'])

# In[386]:
df_full_small

```

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# In[387]:
print(df_full_small.info())

# In[388]:
df_full_small['UTC1'] = pd.to_datetime(df_full_small['UTC1'])

# In[389]:
df_full_small['UTC'] = pd.to_datetime(df_full_small['UTC'])

# In[390]:
print(df_solar_radiation_data_small.info())

# In[391]:
print(df_sonnenscheindauer_data_small.info())

# In[392]:
df_full_small.set_index('UTC1')

# In[393]:
full_small_cols = df_full_small.columns.tolist()
full_small_cols

# In[394]:
full_small_cols2 = ['Timestamp', 'UTC', 'UTC1',
'Station',
'Name',
'WGS84_Laenge',
'WGS84_Breite',
'EPSG2056_lat',
'EPSG2056_lon',
'Hoehe_ASL_m',
'Temp_2mAGL_C',
'Taupunkt_Momentanwert_celsius',
'rel_Luftfeuchtigkeit_Stundenmittel_prozent',
'Luftdruck_Barometerhoehe_QFE_Stundenmittel_hPa',
'Luftdruckaenderung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa',
'Niederschlag_Stundensumme_mm',
'Neuschnee_Momentanwert_cm',
'Schnee_Momentanwert_cm',
'Windgeschwindigkeit_ms',
'Windrichtung_grad',
'Foehnindex',
'sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min',
'Globalstrahlung_wm2']

# In[395]:
df_full_small = df_full_small[full_small_cols2]

# In[396]:
df_full_small = df_full_small.set_index('UTC1')

# In[397]:
df_full_small

# In[398]:
# write df_new to csv output
print('write df to csv output')
df_full_small.to_csv(path_to_output + 'MeteoSchweiz_Data_small.csv', index = False)
print('-- successfull \n')

# In[399]:
del df_full_small
del df_druck_data_small
del df_luftfeuchtigkeit_data_small
del df_niederschlag_data_small
del df_solar_radiation_data_small
del df_sonnenscheindauer_data_small
del df_temperature_data_small
del df_wind_data_small

# MeteoOberwallis
# -----

```

```

# Datacleaning
# -----
#
# MeteoOberwallis
# -----
#
# copyright: www.meteo-oberwallis.ch
# (©2021: script & jupyter notebook by Marco Heinzen, Alpine Robotics GmbH, info@alpine-robotics.com, www.al-
pine-robotics.com)
# (libraries copyright, see individual libraries, creative commons, MIT Licence)

# In[400]:
df = pd.DataFrame()

# In[401]:
path_meteo_ow = r'D:\\info\\Downloads\\CAS_ETH_Spatial_Information_Systems\\Rotwildmonitoring\\MeteoOberwal-
lis\\output1\\'

# Bellwald
# -----

# In[402]:
print('Import CSV')
path_bellwald_data = path_meteo_ow + '1bellwald.csv'
print(' -- successfull \n')
print('Creating Pandas Dataframe:df_bellwald')
df_bellwald = pd.DataFrame(pd.read_csv(path_bellwald_data, sep=',', low_memory=False))
print(' -- successfull \n')

# In[403]:
print('project wgs84 longitude and latitude to EPSG2056 CH1903+ LV95 into two new rows in meters "EPSG2056_X"
and "EPSG2056_Y", copy Height to "EPSG2056_Z" \n')

# Spatial Reference System
inputEPSG = 4326
outputEPSG = 2056
# create coordinate transformation
inSpatialRef = osr.SpatialReference()
inSpatialRef.ImportFromEPSG(inputEPSG)
print(inSpatialRef)
print("\n")
#import spatial reference
outSpatialRef = osr.SpatialReference()
outSpatialRef.ImportFromEPSG(outputEPSG)
print(outSpatialRef)
print("\n")
#coordinate transformation
coordTransform = osr.CoordinateTransformation(inSpatialRef, outSpatialRef)
print(coordTransform)
print(' -- successfull \n')

# In[404]:
df_bellwald.info()

# In[405]:
df_bellwald['UTC'] = pd.to_datetime(df_bellwald['dateTime'],unit='s')
df_bellwald = df_bellwald.set_index(pd.DatetimeIndex(df_bellwald['UTC']))

start_date = '2018-01-01 00:00:00'
end_date = '2021-03-31 23:00:00'
mask = (df_bellwald['UTC'] > start_date) & (df_bellwald['UTC'] <= end_date)
df_bellwald = df_bellwald.loc[mask]

df_bellwald = df_bellwald.dropna(axis=1, how='all')
df_bellwald = df_bellwald.drop(['usUnits', 'interval', 'inTemp', 'inHumidity', 'extraTempl', 'rxCheckPer-
cent', 'txBatteryStatus', 'consBatteryVoltage'], axis=1)
values = {
    'rainRate': 0,
    'rain': 0,
    'windGust': 0,
    'windSpeed': 0,
    'windSpeed': 0,
    'windSpeed': 0,
}
df_bellwald = df_bellwald.fillna(value=values)

df_bellwald3 = pd.DataFrame()
df_bellwald3['regen_stundensumme_mm'] = df_bellwald['rain'].resample('60T').sum()

#df_bellwald_cols = df_bellwald.columns.tolist()
#df_bellwald_cols

```

```

df_bellwaldcols2 = ['barometer','pressure','altimeter','outTemp','outHumidity','windSpeed','windDir','wind-
Gust','windGustDir','dewpoint','windchill','heatindex','ET']
df_bellwald2 = df_bellwald[df_bellwaldcols2]
df_bellwald2 = df_bellwald2.resample('60T').mean()
df_bellwald = df_bellwald2

df_bellwald['regen_stundensumme_mm'] = df_bellwald3['regen_stundensumme_mm'].copy()

df_bellwald['WGS84_Laenge'] = (8+10/60+1.613/3600)
df_bellwald['WGS84_Breite'] = (46+26/60+26.955/3600)

index = df_bellwald.index[0]

df_bellwald.loc[index,'EPSG2056_lat'] = df_bellwald.loc[index,'WGS84_Breite']
df_bellwald.loc[index,'EPSG2056_lon'] = df_bellwald.loc[index,'WGS84_Laenge']

# get pointX and PointX from EPSG2056_lat and EPSG2056_long in row
pointX = df_bellwald.loc[index,'EPSG2056_lat']
pointY = df_bellwald.loc[index,'EPSG2056_lon']
# add pointX and pointY as osgeo Point
point = ogr.Geometry(ogr.wkbPoint)
point.AddPoint(pointY, pointX)
# Transform
print("WGS84: ", point)
point.Transform(coordTransform)
# print point in EPSG 4326
print("EPSG2056: ", point)
print("\n")
# convert back tuple back to each row
df_bellwald.loc[index,'EPSG2056_lat'] = point.GetX()
df_bellwald.loc[index,'EPSG2056_lon'] = point.GetY()
print(' -- successfull \n')

x = df_bellwald.loc[index,'EPSG2056_lat']
y = df_bellwald.loc[index,'EPSG2056_lon']
df_bellwald['EPSG2056_lat'] = x
df_bellwald['EPSG2056_lon'] = y
df_bellwald['WGS84_Breite'] = pointX
df_bellwald['WGS84_Laenge'] = pointY

df_bellwald['Name'] = 'Bellwald'
df_bellwald['Hoehe_AS_L_m'] = 2061
df_bellwald['Station'] = 'MOBELLW'

df_bellwald = df_bellwald.reset_index()
df_bellwald['UTC1'] = df_bellwald['UTC'].copy()
df_bellwald = df_bellwald.set_index(pd.DatetimeIndex(df_bellwald['UTC1']))

df_bellwald.info()

# In[406]:
df = df.append(df_bellwald)
del df_bellwald

# Binn
# -----

# In[407]:
print('Import CSV')
path_binn_data = path_meteo_ow + 'binn.csv'
print(' -- successfull \n')
print('Creating Pandas Dataframe:df_binn')
df_binn = pd.DataFrame(pd.read_csv(path_binn_data, sep=',', low_memory=False))
print(' -- successfull \n')

# In[408]:
df_binn.info()

# In[409]:
df_binn['UTC'] = pd.to_datetime(df_binn['dateTime'],unit='s')
df_binn = df_binn.set_index(pd.DatetimeIndex(df_binn['UTC']))

start_date = '2018-01-01 00:00:00'
end_date = '2021-03-31 23:00:00'
mask = (df_binn['UTC'] > start_date) & (df_binn['UTC'] <= end_date)
df_binn = df_binn.loc[mask]

df_binn = df_binn.dropna(axis=1, how='all')
df_binn = df_binn.drop(['usUnits','interval','inTemp','inHumidity','extraTemp1','rxCheckPercent','txBatterySta-
tus','consBatteryVoltage'], axis=1)
values = {

```

```

        'rainRate': 0,
        'rain': 0,
        'windGust': 0,
        'windSpeed': 0,
        'windSpeed': 0,
        'windSpeed': 0,
    }
df_binn = df_binn.fillna(value=values)

df_binn3 = pd.DataFrame()
df_binn3['regen_stundensumme_mm'] = df_binn['rain'].resample('60T').sum()

#df_binn_cols = df_binn.columns.tolist()
#df_binn_cols
df_binncols2 = ['barometer', 'pressure', 'altimeter', 'outTemp', 'outHumidity', 'windSpeed', 'windDir', 'wind-
Gust', 'windGustDir', 'dewpoint', 'windchill', 'heatindex', 'ET']
df_binn2 = df_binn[df_binncols2]
df_binn2 = df_binn2.resample('60T').mean()
df_binn = df_binn2

df_binn['regen_stundensumme_mm'] = df_binn3['regen_stundensumme_mm'].copy()

df_binn['WGS84_Laenge'] = (8+10.9/60)
df_binn['WGS84_Breite'] = (46+21.69/60)

index = df_binn.index[0]

df_binn.loc[index, 'EPSG2056_lat'] = df_binn.loc[index, 'WGS84_Breite']
df_binn.loc[index, 'EPSG2056_lon'] = df_binn.loc[index, 'WGS84_Laenge']

# get pointX and PointX from EPSG2056_lat and EPSG2056_long in row
pointX = df_binn.loc[index, 'EPSG2056_lat']
pointY = df_binn.loc[index, 'EPSG2056_lon']
# add pointX and pointY as osgeo Point
point = ogr.Geometry(ogr.wkbPoint)
point.AddPoint(pointY, pointX)
# Transform
print("WGS84: ", point)
point.Transform(coordTransform)
# print point in EPSG 4326
print("EPSG2056: ", point)
print("\n")
# convert back tuple back to eacha row
df_binn.loc[index, 'EPSG2056_lat'] = point.GetX()
df_binn.loc[index, 'EPSG2056_lon'] = point.GetY()
print(' -- successfull \n')

x = df_binn.loc[index, 'EPSG2056_lat']
y = df_binn.loc[index, 'EPSG2056_lon']
df_binn['EPSG2056_lat'] = x
df_binn['EPSG2056_lon'] = y
df_binn['WGS84_Breite'] = pointX
df_binn['WGS84_Laenge'] = pointY

df_binn['Name'] = 'Binn Wilern'
df_binn['Hoehe ASL m'] = 1442
df_binn['Station'] = 'MOBINN'

df_binn = df_binn.reset_index()
df_binn['UTC1'] = df_binn['UTC'].copy()
df_binn = df_binn.set_index(pd.DatetimeIndex(df_binn['UTC1']))

df_binn.info()

# In[410]:
df_binn

# In[411]:
df = df.append(df_binn)
del df_binn

# Bettmeralp
# -----

# In[412]:
print('Import CSV')
path_bettmeralp_data = path_meteo_ow + 'bettmeralp.csv'
print(' -- successfull \n')
print('Creating Pandas DataFrame:df_bettmeralp')
df_bettmeralp = pd.DataFrame(pd.read_csv(path_bettmeralp_data, sep=',', low_memory=False))
print(' -- successfull \n')

```

```

# In[413]:
df_bettmeralp.info()

# In[414]:
df_bettmeralp['UTC'] = pd.to_datetime(df_bettmeralp['dateTime'],unit='s')
df_bettmeralp = df_bettmeralp.set_index(pd.DatetimeIndex(df_bettmeralp['UTC']))

start_date = '2018-01-01 00:00:00'
end_date = '2021-03-31 23:00:00'
mask = (df_bettmeralp['UTC'] > start_date) & (df_bettmeralp['UTC'] <= end_date)
df_bettmeralp = df_bettmeralp.loc[mask]

df_bettmeralp = df_bettmeralp.dropna(axis=1, how='all')
df_bettmeralp = df_bettmeralp.drop(['usUnits','interval','inTemp','inHumidity','extraTemp1','rxCheckPer-
cent','txBatteryStatus','consBatteryVoltage'], axis=1)
values = {
    'rainRate': 0,
    'rain': 0,
    'windGust': 0,
    'windSpeed': 0,
    'windSpeed': 0,
    'windSpeed': 0,
}
df_bettmeralp = df_bettmeralp.fillna(value=values)

df_bettmeralp3 = pd.DataFrame()
df_bettmeralp3['regen_stundensumme_mm'] = df_bettmeralp['rain'].resample('60T').sum()

#df_bettmeralp_cols = df_bettmeralp.columns.tolist()
#df_bettmeralp_cols
df_bettmeralpcols2 = ['barometer','pressure','altimeter','outTemp','outHumidity','windSpeed','windDir','wind-
Gust','windGustDir','dewpoint','windchill','heatindex','ET']
df_bettmeralp2 = df_bettmeralp[df_bettmeralpcols2]
df_bettmeralp2 = df_bettmeralp2.resample('60T').mean()
df_bettmeralp = df_bettmeralp2

df_bettmeralp['regen_stundensumme_mm'] = df_bettmeralp3['regen_stundensumme_mm'].copy()

df_bettmeralp['WGS84_Laenge'] = (8+3.48/60)
df_bettmeralp['WGS84_Breite'] = (46+23.53/60)

index = df_bettmeralp.index[0]

df_bettmeralp.loc[index,'EPSG2056_lat'] = df_bettmeralp.loc[index,'WGS84_Breite']
df_bettmeralp.loc[index,'EPSG2056_lon'] = df_bettmeralp.loc[index,'WGS84_Laenge']

# get pointX and PointX from EPSG2056_lat and EPSG2056_long in row
pointX = df_bettmeralp.loc[index,'EPSG2056_lat']
pointY = df_bettmeralp.loc[index,'EPSG2056_lon']
# add pointX and pointY as osgeo Point
point = ogr.Geometry(ogr.wkbPoint)
point.AddPoint(pointY, pointX)
# Transform
print("WGS84: ", point)
point.Transform(coordTransform)
# print point in EPSG 4326
print("EPSG2056: ", point)
print("\n")
# convert back tuple back to eacha row
df_bettmeralp.loc[index,'EPSG2056_lat'] = point.GetX()
df_bettmeralp.loc[index,'EPSG2056_lon'] = point.GetY()
print(' -- successfull \n')

x = df_bettmeralp.loc[index,'EPSG2056_lat']
y = df_bettmeralp.loc[index,'EPSG2056_lon']
df_bettmeralp['EPSG2056_lat'] = x
df_bettmeralp['EPSG2056_lon'] = y
df_bettmeralp['WGS84_Breite'] = pointX
df_bettmeralp['WGS84_Laenge'] = pointY

df_bettmeralp['Name'] = 'Bettmeralp See'
df_bettmeralp['Station'] = 'MOBETT'
df_bettmeralp['Hoehe_AS_L_m'] = 2030

df_bettmeralp = df_bettmeralp.reset_index()
df_bettmeralp['UTC1'] = df_bettmeralp['UTC'].copy()
df_bettmeralp = df_bettmeralp.set_index(pd.DatetimeIndex(df_bettmeralp['UTC1']))

df_bettmeralp.info()

# In[415]:
df = df.append(df_bettmeralp)
del df_bettmeralp

```

```

# Blitzingen
# -----

# In[416]:
print('Import CSV')
path_blitzingen_data = path_meteo_ow + 'blitzingen.csv'
print(' -- successfull \n')
print('Creating Pandas Dataframe:df_blitzingen')
df_blitzingen = pd.DataFrame(pd.read_csv(path_blitzingen_data, sep=',', low_memory=False))
print(' -- successfull \n')

# In[417]:
df_blitzingen.info()

# In[418]:
df_blitzingen['UTC'] = pd.to_datetime(df_blitzingen['dateTime'],unit='s')
df_blitzingen = df_blitzingen.set_index(pd.DatetimeIndex(df_blitzingen['UTC']))

start_date = '2018-01-01 00:00:00'
end_date = '2021-03-31 23:00:00'
mask = (df_blitzingen['UTC'] > start_date) & (df_blitzingen['UTC'] <= end_date)
df_blitzingen = df_blitzingen.loc[mask]

df_blitzingen = df_blitzingen.dropna(axis=1, how='all')
df_blitzingen = df_blitzingen.drop(['usUnits', 'interval', 'inTemp', 'inHumidity', 'extraTemp1', 'rxCheckPer-
cent', 'txBatteryStatus', 'consBatteryVoltage'], axis=1)
values = {
    'rainRate': 0,
    'rain': 0,
    'windGust': 0,
    'windSpeed': 0,
    'windSpeed': 0,
    'windSpeed': 0,
}
df_blitzingen = df_blitzingen.fillna(value=values)

df_blitzingen3 = pd.DataFrame()
df_blitzingen3['regen_stundensumme_mm'] = df_blitzingen['rain'].resample('60T').sum()

#df_blitzingen_cols = df_blitzingen.columns.tolist()
#df_blitzingen_cols
df_blitzingencols2 = ['barometer', 'pressure', 'altimeter', 'outTemp', 'outHumidity', 'windSpeed', 'windDir', 'wind-
Gust', 'windGustDir', 'dewpoint', 'windchill', 'heatindex', 'ET']
df_blitzingen2 = df_blitzingen[df_blitzingencols2]
df_blitzingen2 = df_blitzingen2.resample('60T').mean()
df_blitzingen = df_blitzingen2

df_blitzingen['regen_stundensumme_mm'] = df_blitzingen3['regen_stundensumme_mm'].copy()

df_blitzingen['WGS84_Laenge'] = (8+12.06/60)
df_blitzingen['WGS84_Breite'] = (46+26.82/60)

index = df_blitzingen.index[0]

df_blitzingen.loc[index, 'EPSG2056_lat'] = df_blitzingen.loc[index, 'WGS84_Breite']
df_blitzingen.loc[index, 'EPSG2056_lon'] = df_blitzingen.loc[index, 'WGS84_Laenge']

# get pointX and PointX from EPSG2056_lat and EPSG2056_long in row
pointX = df_blitzingen.loc[index, 'EPSG2056_lat']
pointY = df_blitzingen.loc[index, 'EPSG2056_lon']
# add pointX and pointY as osgeo Point
point = ogr.Geometry(ogr.wkbPoint)
point.AddPoint(pointY, pointX)
# Transform
print("WGS84: ", point)
point.Transform(coordTransform)
# print point in EPSG 4326
print("EPSG2056: ", point)
print("\n")
# convert back tuple back to eacha row
df_blitzingen.loc[index, 'EPSG2056_lat'] = point.GetX()
df_blitzingen.loc[index, 'EPSG2056_lon'] = point.GetY()
print(' -- successfull \n')

x = df_blitzingen.loc[index, 'EPSG2056_lat']
y = df_blitzingen.loc[index, 'EPSG2056_lon']
df_blitzingen['EPSG2056_lat'] = x
df_blitzingen['EPSG2056_lon'] = y
df_blitzingen['WGS84_Breite'] = pointX
df_blitzingen['WGS84_Laenge'] = pointY

df_blitzingen['Name'] = 'Blitzingen Castle'
df_blitzingen['Station'] = 'MOBLITZINGU'

```

```

df_blitzingen['Hoehe_AS_L_m'] = 1429

df_blitzingen = df_blitzingen.reset_index()
df_blitzingen['UTC1'] = df_blitzingen['UTC'].copy()
df_blitzingen = df_blitzingen.set_index(pd.DatetimeIndex(df_blitzingen['UTC1']))

df_blitzingen.info()

# In[419]:
df = df.append(df_blitzingen)
del df_blitzingen

# Brig
# -----

# In[420]:
print('Import CSV')
path_brig_data = path_meteo_ow + 'brig.csv'
print(' -- successfull \n')
print('Creating Pandas Dataframe:df_brig')
df_brig =pd.DataFrame(pd.read_csv(path_brig_data, sep=',', low_memory=False))
print(' -- successfull \n')

# In[421]:
df_brig.info()

# In[422]:
df_brig['UTC'] = pd.to_datetime(df_brig['dateTime'],unit='s')
df_brig = df_brig.set_index(pd.DatetimeIndex(df_brig['UTC']))

start_date = '2018-01-01 00:00:00'
end_date = '2021-03-31 23:00:00'
mask = (df_brig['UTC'] > start_date) & (df_brig['UTC'] <= end_date)
df_brig = df_brig.loc[mask]

df_brig = df_brig.dropna(axis=1, how='all')
df_brig = df_brig.drop(['usUnits','interval','inTemp','inHumidity','extraTemp1','rxCheckPercent','txBatteryStatus','consBatteryVoltage'], axis=1)
values = {
    'rainRate': 0,
    'rain': 0,
    'windGust': 0,
    'windSpeed': 0,
    'windSpeed': 0,
    'windSpeed': 0,
}
df_brig = df_brig.fillna(value=values)

df_brig3 = pd.DataFrame()
df_brig3['regen_stundensumme_mm'] = df_brig['rain'].resample('60T').sum()

#df_brig_cols = df_brig.columns.tolist()
#df_brig_cols
df_brigcols2 = ['barometer','pressure','altimeter','outTemp','outHumidity','windSpeed','windDir','windGust','windGustDir','dewpoint','windchill','heatindex','ET']
df_brig2 = df_brig[df_brigcols2]
df_brig2 = df_brig2.resample('60T').mean()
df_brig = df_brig2

df_brig['regen_stundensumme_mm'] = df_brig3['regen_stundensumme_mm'].copy()

df_brig['WGS84_Laenge'] = (7+59.40/60)
df_brig['WGS84_Breite'] = (46+18.84/60)

index = df_brig.index[0]

df_brig.loc[index,'EPSG2056_lat'] = df_brig.loc[index,'WGS84_Breite']
df_brig.loc[index,'EPSG2056_lon'] = df_brig.loc[index,'WGS84_Laenge']

# get pointX and PointX from EPSG2056_lat and EPSG2056_long in row
pointX = df_brig.loc[index,'EPSG2056_lat']
pointY = df_brig.loc[index,'EPSG2056_lon']
# add pointX and pointY as osgeo Point
point = ogr.Geometry(ogr.wkbPoint)
point.AddPoint(pointY, pointX)
# Transform
print("WGS84: ", point)
point.Transform(coordTransform)
# print point in EPSG 4326
print("EPSG2056: ", point)
print("\n")

```

```

# convert back tuple back to each row
df_brig.loc[index,'EPSG2056_lat'] = point.GetX()
df_brig.loc[index,'EPSG2056_lon'] = point.GetY()
print(' -- successfull \n')

x = df_brig.loc[index,'EPSG2056_lat']
y = df_brig.loc[index,'EPSG2056_lon']
df_brig['EPSG2056_lat'] = x
df_brig['EPSG2056_lon'] = y
df_brig['WGS84_Breite'] = pointX
df_brig['WGS84_Laenge'] = pointY

df_brig['Name'] = 'Brig Schlosshotel'
df_brig['Station'] = 'MOBRIG'
df_brig['Hoehe_AS_L_m'] = 691

df_brig = df_brig.reset_index()
df_brig['UTC1'] = df_brig['UTC'].copy()
df_brig = df_brig.set_index(pd.DatetimeIndex(df_brig['UTC1']))

df_brig.info()

# In[423]:
df = df.append(df_brig)
del df_brig

# Chaeserstatt
# -----

# In[424]:
print('Import CSV')
path_chaeserstatt_data = path_meteo_ow + 'chaeserstatt.csv'
print(' -- successfull \n')
print('Creating Pandas Dataframe:df_chaeserstatt')
df_chaeserstatt =pd.DataFrame(pd.read_csv(path_chaeserstatt_data, sep=',', low_memory=False))
print(' -- successfull \n')

# In[425]:
df_chaeserstatt.info()

# barometer, pressure,altimeter,outTemp,outHumidity,windSpeed,windDir,windGust,windGustDir,dewpoint,wind-
chill,heatindex,ET,UV,extraTemp1,soilTemp1,soilTemp2,soilTemp3,soilTemp4,leafTemp1,leaf-
Temp2,soilMoist1,soilMoist2,soilMoist3,soilMoist4,leafWet1,leafWet2,sunshine_hours

# In[426]:
df_chaeserstatt['UTC'] = pd.to_datetime(df_chaeserstatt['dateTime'],unit='s')
df_chaeserstatt = df_chaeserstatt.set_index(pd.DatetimeIndex(df_chaeserstatt['UTC']))

start_date = '2018-01-01 00:00:00'
end_date = '2021-03-31 23:00:00'
mask = (df_chaeserstatt['UTC'] > start_date) & (df_chaeserstatt['UTC'] <= end_date)
df_chaeserstatt = df_chaeserstatt.loc[mask]

df_chaeserstatt['sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min'] = df_chaeserstatt['radiation'].copy()
df_chaeserstatt.iloc[(df_chaeserstatt.sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min < 120).values, 32] = np.nan
df_chaeserstatt.iloc[(df_chaeserstatt.sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min >= 120).values, 32] = 1

df_chaeserstatt = df_chaeserstatt.dropna(axis=1, how='all')
df_chaeserstatt = df_chaeserstatt.drop(['usUnits','interval','inTemp','inHumidity','rxCheckPercent','txBat-
teryStatus','consBatteryVoltage'], axis=1)
values = {
    'rainRate': 0,
    'rain': 0,
    'windGust': 0,
    'windSpeed': 0,
    'windSpeed': 0,
    'windSpeed': 0,
}
df_chaeserstatt = df_chaeserstatt.fillna(value=values)

df_chaeserstatt3 = pd.DataFrame()
df_chaeserstatt3['regen_stundensumme_mm'] = df_chaeserstatt['rain'].resample('60T').sum()
df_chaeserstatt3['sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min'] = df_chaeserstatt['sonnenscheindauer_stunden-
summe_min'].resample('60T').sum()

#df_chaeserstatt_cols = df_chaeserstatt.columns.tolist()
#df_chaeserstatt_cols
df_chaeserstattcols2 = ['barometer','pressure','altimeter','outTemp','outHumidity','windSpeed','windDir','wind-
Gust','windGustDir','dewpoint','windchill','heatindex','ET']
df_chaeserstatt2 = df_chaeserstatt[df_chaeserstattcols2]
df_chaeserstatt2 = df_chaeserstatt2.resample('60T').mean()
df_chaeserstatt = df_chaeserstatt2

```

```

df_chaeserstatt['regen_stundensumme_mm'] = df_chaeserstatt3['regen_stundensumme_mm'].copy()
df_chaeserstatt['sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min'] = df_chaeserstatt3['sonnenscheindauer_stunden-
summe_min'].copy()

df_chaeserstatt['WGS84_Laenge'] = (8+10.4/60)
df_chaeserstatt['WGS84_Breite'] = (46+24.49/60)

index = df_chaeserstatt.index[0]

df_chaeserstatt.loc[index, 'EPSG2056_lat'] = df_chaeserstatt.loc[index, 'WGS84_Breite']
df_chaeserstatt.loc[index, 'EPSG2056_lon'] = df_chaeserstatt.loc[index, 'WGS84_Laenge']

# get pointX and PointX from EPSG2056_lat and EPSG2056_long in row
pointX = df_chaeserstatt.loc[index, 'EPSG2056_lat']
pointY = df_chaeserstatt.loc[index, 'EPSG2056_lon']
# add pointX and pointY as osgeo Point
point = ogr.Geometry(ogr.wkbPoint)
point.AddPoint(pointY, pointX)
# Transform
print("WGS84: ", point)
point.Transform(coordTransform)
# print point in EPSG 4326
print("EPSG2056: ", point)
print("\n")
# convert back tuple back to eacha row
df_chaeserstatt.loc[index, 'EPSG2056_lat'] = point.GetX()
df_chaeserstatt.loc[index, 'EPSG2056_lon'] = point.GetY()
print(' -- successfull \n')

x = df_chaeserstatt.loc[index, 'EPSG2056_lat']
y = df_chaeserstatt.loc[index, 'EPSG2056_lon']
df_chaeserstatt['EPSG2056_lat'] = x
df_chaeserstatt['EPSG2056_lon'] = y
df_chaeserstatt['WGS84_Breite'] = pointX
df_chaeserstatt['WGS84_Laenge'] = pointY

df_chaeserstatt['Name'] = 'Ernen Chaeserstatt'
df_chaeserstatt['Station'] = 'MOCHAES'
df_chaeserstatt['Hoehe_AS_L_m'] = 1777

df_chaeserstatt = df_chaeserstatt.reset_index()
df_chaeserstatt['UTC1'] = df_chaeserstatt['UTC'].copy()
df_chaeserstatt = df_chaeserstatt.set_index(pd.DatetimeIndex(df_chaeserstatt['UTC1']))

df_chaeserstatt.info()

# In[427]:
df = df.append(df_chaeserstatt)
del df_chaeserstatt

# Deisch
# -----

# In[428]:
print('Import CSV')
path_deisch_data = path_meteo_ow + 'deisch.csv'
print(' -- successfull \n')
print('Creating Pandas Dataframe:df_deisch')
df_deisch = pd.DataFrame(pd.read_csv(path_deisch_data, sep=',', low_memory=False))
print(' -- successfull \n')

# In[429]:
df_deisch.info()

# In[430]:
df_deisch['UTC'] = pd.to_datetime(df_deisch['dateTime'],unit='s')
df_deisch = df_deisch.set_index(pd.DatetimeIndex(df_deisch['UTC']))

start_date = '2018-01-01 00:00:00'
end_date = '2021-03-31 23:00:00'
mask = (df_deisch['UTC'] > start_date) & (df_deisch['UTC'] <= end_date)
df_deisch = df_deisch.loc[mask]

df_deisch['sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min'] = df_deisch['radiation'].copy()
df_deisch.iloc[(df_deisch.sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min < 120).values, 32] = np.nan
df_deisch.iloc[(df_deisch.sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min >= 120).values, 32] = 1

df_deisch = df_deisch.dropna(axis=1, how='all')
df_deisch = df_deisch.drop(['usUnits', 'interval', 'inTemp', 'inHumidity', 'extraTemp1'], axis=1)
values = {
    'rainRate': 0,

```

```

        'rain': 0,
        'windGust': 0,
        'windSpeed': 0,
        'windSpeed': 0,
        'windSpeed': 0,
    }
df_deisch = df_deisch.fillna(value=values)

df_deisch3 = pd.DataFrame()
df_deisch3['regen_stundensumme_mm'] = df_deisch['rain'].resample('60T').sum()
df_deisch3['sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min'] = df_deisch['sonnenscheindauer_stunden-
summe_min'].resample('60T').sum()

#df_deisch_cols = df_deisch.columns.tolist()
#df_deisch_cols
df_deischcols2 = ['barometer','pressure','altimeter','outTemp','outHumidity','windSpeed','windDir','wind-
Gust','windGustDir','dewpoint','windchill','heatindex','ET']
df_deisch2 = df_deisch[df_deischcols2]
df_deisch2 = df_deisch2.resample('60T').mean()
df_deisch = df_deisch2

df_deisch['regen_stundensumme_mm'] = df_deisch3['regen_stundensumme_mm'].copy()
df_deisch['sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min'] = df_deisch3['sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min'].copy()

df_deisch['WGS84_Laenge'] = (8+6.02/60)
df_deisch['WGS84_Breite'] = (46+22.77/60)

index = df_deisch.index[0]

df_deisch.loc[index,'EPSG2056_lat'] = df_deisch.loc[index,'WGS84_Breite']
df_deisch.loc[index,'EPSG2056_lon'] = df_deisch.loc[index,'WGS84_Laenge']

# get pointX and PointX from EPSG2056_lat and EPSG2056_long in row
pointX = df_deisch.loc[index,'EPSG2056_lat']
pointY = df_deisch.loc[index,'EPSG2056_lon']
# add pointX and pointY as osgeo Point
point = ogr.Geometry(ogr.wkbPoint)
point.AddPoint(pointY, pointX)
# Transform
print("WGS84: ", point)
point.Transform(coordTransform)
# print point in EPSG 4326
print("EPSG2056: ", point)
print("\n")
# convert back tuple back to eacha row
df_deisch.loc[index,'EPSG2056_lat'] = point.GetX()
df_deisch.loc[index,'EPSG2056_lon'] = point.GetY()
print(' -- successfull \n')

x = df_deisch.loc[index,'EPSG2056_lat']
y = df_deisch.loc[index,'EPSG2056_lon']
df_deisch['EPSG2056_lat'] = x
df_deisch['EPSG2056_lon'] = y
df_deisch['WGS84_Breite'] = pointX
df_deisch['WGS84_Laenge'] = pointY

df_deisch['Name'] = 'Grengiols Deisch'
df_deisch['Station'] = 'MODEISCH'
df_deisch['Hoehe_AS_L_m'] = 1030

df_deisch = df_deisch.reset_index()
df_deisch['UTC1'] = df_deisch['UTC'].copy()
df_deisch = df_deisch.set_index(pd.DatetimeIndex(df_deisch['UTC1']))

df_deisch.info()

# In[431]:
df = df.append(df_deisch)
del df_deisch

# Fiesch
# -----

# In[432]:
print('Import CSV')
path_fiesch_data = path_meteo_ow + 'fiesch.csv'
print(' -- successfull \n')
print('Creating Pandas Dataframe:df_fiesch')
df_fiesch =pd.DataFrame(pd.read_csv(path_fiesch_data, sep=',', low_memory=False))
print(' -- successfull \n')

# In[433]:

```

```

df_fiesch.info()

# In[434]:
df_fiesch['UTC'] = pd.to_datetime(df_fiesch['dateTime'],unit='s')
df_fiesch = df_fiesch.set_index(pd.DatetimeIndex(df_fiesch['UTC']))

start_date = '2018-01-01 00:00:00'
end_date = '2021-03-31 23:00:00'
mask = (df_fiesch['UTC'] > start_date) & (df_fiesch['UTC'] <= end_date)
df_fiesch = df_fiesch.loc[mask]

df_fiesch = df_fiesch.dropna(axis=1, how='all')
df_fiesch = df_fiesch.drop(['usUnits', 'interval', 'inTemp', 'inHumidity', 'extraTemp1', 'rxCheckPercent', 'txBat-
teryStatus', 'consBatteryVoltage'], axis=1)
values = {
    'rainRate': 0,
    'rain': 0,
    'windGust': 0,
    'windSpeed': 0,
    'windSpeed': 0,
    'windSpeed': 0,
}
df_fiesch = df_fiesch.fillna(value=values)

df_fiesch3 = pd.DataFrame()
df_fiesch3['regen_stundensumme_mm'] = df_fiesch['rain'].resample('60T').sum()

#df_fiesch_cols = df_fiesch.columns.tolist()
#df_fiesch_cols
df_fieschcols2 = ['barometer', 'pressure', 'altimeter', 'outTemp', 'outHumidity', 'windSpeed', 'windDir', 'wind-
Gust', 'windGustDir', 'dewpoint', 'windchill', 'heatindex', 'ET']
df_fiesch2 = df_fiesch[df_fieschcols2]
df_fiesch2 = df_fiesch2.resample('60T').mean()
df_fiesch = df_fiesch2

df_fiesch['regen_stundensumme_mm'] = df_fiesch3['regen_stundensumme_mm'].copy()

df_fiesch['WGS84_Laenge'] = (8+8.32/60)
df_fiesch['WGS84_Breite'] = (46+24.60/60)

index = df_fiesch.index[0]

df_fiesch.loc[index, 'EPSG2056_lat'] = df_fiesch.loc[index, 'WGS84_Breite']
df_fiesch.loc[index, 'EPSG2056_lon'] = df_fiesch.loc[index, 'WGS84_Laenge']

# get pointX and pointY from EPSG2056_lat and EPSG2056_long in row
pointX = df_fiesch.loc[index, 'EPSG2056_lat']
pointY = df_fiesch.loc[index, 'EPSG2056_lon']
# add pointX and pointY as osgeo Point
point = ogr.Geometry(ogr.wkbPoint)
point.AddPoint(pointY, pointX)
# Transform
print("WGS84: ", point)
point.Transform(coordTransform)
# print point in EPSG 4326
print("EPSG2056: ", point)
print("\n")
# convert back tuple back to each row
df_fiesch.loc[index, 'EPSG2056_lat'] = point.GetX()
df_fiesch.loc[index, 'EPSG2056_lon'] = point.GetY()
print(' -- successfull \n')

x = df_fiesch.loc[index, 'EPSG2056_lat']
y = df_fiesch.loc[index, 'EPSG2056_lon']
df_fiesch['EPSG2056_lat'] = x
df_fiesch['EPSG2056_lon'] = y
df_fiesch['WGS84_Breite'] = pointX
df_fiesch['WGS84_Laenge'] = pointY

df_fiesch['Name'] = 'Fiesch Landeplatz'
df_fiesch['Station'] = 'MOFIESCH'
df_fiesch['Hoehe_AS_L_m'] = 1060

df_fiesch = df_fiesch.reset_index()
df_fiesch['UTC1'] = df_fiesch['UTC'].copy()
df_fiesch = df_fiesch.set_index(pd.DatetimeIndex(df_fiesch['UTC1']))

df_fiesch.info()

# In[435]:
df = df.append(df_fiesch)
del df_fiesch

```

```

# Grimselpass
# -----

# In[436]:
print('Import CSV')
path_grimselpass_data = path_meteo_ow + 'grimselpass.csv'
print(' -- successfull \n')
print('Creating Pandas Dataframe:df_grimselpass')
df_grimselpass = pd.DataFrame(pd.read_csv(path_grimselpass_data, sep=',', low_memory=False))
print(' -- successfull \n')

# In[437]:
df_grimselpass.info()

# In[438]:
df_grimselpass['UTC'] = pd.to_datetime(df_grimselpass['dateTime'],unit='s')
df_grimselpass = df_grimselpass.set_index(pd.DatetimeIndex(df_grimselpass['UTC']))

start_date = '2018-01-01 00:00:00'
end_date = '2021-03-31 23:00:00'
mask = (df_grimselpass['UTC'] > start_date) & (df_grimselpass['UTC'] <= end_date)
df_grimselpass = df_grimselpass.loc[mask]

df_grimselpass['sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min'] = df_grimselpass['radiation'].copy()
df_grimselpass.iloc[(df_grimselpass.sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min < 120).values, 32] = np.nan
df_grimselpass.iloc[(df_grimselpass.sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min >= 120).values, 32] = 1

df_grimselpass = df_grimselpass.dropna(axis=1, how='all')
df_grimselpass = df_grimselpass.drop(['usUnits', 'interval', 'inTemp', 'inHumidity', 'extraTemp1', 'rxCheckPer-
cent', 'txBatteryStatus', 'consBatteryVoltage'], axis=1)
values = {
    'rainRate': 0,
    'rain': 0,
    'windGust': 0,
    'windSpeed': 0,
    'windSpeed': 0,
    'windSpeed': 0,
}
df_grimselpass = df_grimselpass.fillna(value=values)

df_grimselpass3 = pd.DataFrame()
df_grimselpass3['regen_stundensumme_mm'] = df_grimselpass['rain'].resample('60T').sum()
df_grimselpass3['sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min'] = df_grimselpass['sonnenscheindauer_stunden-
summe_min'].resample('60T').sum()

#df_grimselpass_cols = df_grimselpass.columns.tolist()
#df_grimselpass_cols
df_grimselpasscols2 = ['barometer', 'pressure', 'altimeter', 'outTemp', 'outHumidity', 'windSpeed', 'windDir', 'wind-
Gust', 'windGustDir', 'dewpoint', 'windchill', 'heatindex', 'ET']
df_grimselpass2 = df_grimselpass[df_grimselpasscols2]
df_grimselpass2 = df_grimselpass2.resample('60T').mean()
df_grimselpass = df_grimselpass2

df_grimselpass['regen_stundensumme_mm'] = df_grimselpass3['regen_stundensumme_mm'].copy()
df_grimselpass['sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min'] = df_grimselpass3['sonnenscheindauer_stunden-
summe_min'].copy()

df_grimselpass['WGS84_Laenge'] = (8+20.32/60)
df_grimselpass['WGS84_Breite'] = (46+33.71/60)

index = df_grimselpass.index[0]

df_grimselpass.loc[index, 'EPSG2056_lat'] = df_grimselpass.loc[index, 'WGS84_Breite']
df_grimselpass.loc[index, 'EPSG2056_lon'] = df_grimselpass.loc[index, 'WGS84_Laenge']

# get pointX and PointX from EPSG2056_lat and EPSG2056_long in row
pointX = df_grimselpass.loc[index, 'EPSG2056_lat']
pointY = df_grimselpass.loc[index, 'EPSG2056_lon']
# add pointX and pointY as osgeo Point
point = ogr.Geometry(ogr.wkbPoint)
point.AddPoint(pointY, pointX)
# Transform
print("WGS84: ", point)
point.Transform(coordTransform)
# print point in EPSG 4326
print("EPSG2056: ", point)
print("\n")
# convert back tuple back to eacha row
df_grimselpass.loc[index, 'EPSG2056_lat'] = point.GetX()
df_grimselpass.loc[index, 'EPSG2056_lon'] = point.GetY()
print(' -- successfull \n')

```

```

x = df_grimselpass.loc[index, 'EPSG2056_lat']
y = df_grimselpass.loc[index, 'EPSG2056_lon']
df_grimselpass['EPSG2056_lat'] = x
df_grimselpass['EPSG2056_lon'] = y
df_grimselpass['WGS84_Breite'] = pointX
df_grimselpass['WGS84_Laenge'] = pointY

df_grimselpass['Name'] = 'Grimselpass'
df_grimselpass['Station'] = 'MOGRIMSEL'
df_grimselpass['Hoehe_AS_L_m'] = 2158

df_grimselpass = df_grimselpass.reset_index()
df_grimselpass['UTC1'] = df_grimselpass['UTC'].copy()
df_grimselpass = df_grimselpass.set_index(pd.DatetimeIndex(df_grimselpass['UTC1']))

df_grimselpass.info()

# In[439]:
df = df.append(df_grimselpass)
del df_grimselpass

# Naters
# -----

# In[440]:
print('Import CSV')
path_naters_data = path_meteo_ow + 'naters.csv'
print('-- successfull \n')
print('Creating Pandas Dataframe:df_naters')
df_naters = pd.DataFrame(pd.read_csv(path_naters_data, sep=',', low_memory=False))
print('-- successfull \n')

# In[441]:
df_naters.info()

# In[442]:
df_naters['UTC'] = pd.to_datetime(df_naters['dateTime'], unit='s')
df_naters = df_naters.set_index(pd.DatetimeIndex(df_naters['UTC']))

start_date = '2018-01-01 00:00:00'
end_date = '2021-03-31 23:00:00'
mask = (df_naters['UTC'] > start_date) & (df_naters['UTC'] <= end_date)
df_naters = df_naters.loc[mask]

df_naters['sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min'] = df_naters['radiation'].copy()
df_naters.iloc[(df_naters.sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min < 120).values, 32] = np.nan
df_naters.iloc[(df_naters.sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min >= 120).values, 32] = 1

df_naters = df_naters.dropna(axis=1, how='all')
df_naters = df_naters.drop(['usUnits', 'interval', 'inTemp', 'inHumidity', 'extraTemp1', 'rxCheckPercent', 'txBatteryStatus', 'consBatteryVoltage'], axis=1)
values = {
    'rainRate': 0,
    'rain': 0,
    'windGust': 0,
    'windSpeed': 0,
    'windSpeed': 0,
    'windSpeed': 0,
}
df_naters = df_naters.fillna(value=values)

df_naters3 = pd.DataFrame()
df_naters3['regen_stundensumme_mm'] = df_naters['rain'].resample('60T').sum()
df_naters3['sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min'] = df_naters['sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min'].resample('60T').sum()

#df_naters_cols = df_naters.columns.tolist()
#df_naters_cols
df_naterscols2 = ['barometer', 'pressure', 'altimeter', 'outTemp', 'outHumidity', 'windSpeed', 'windDir', 'windGust', 'windGustDir', 'dewpoint', 'windchill', 'heatindex', 'ET']
df_naters2 = df_naters[df_naterscols2]
df_naters2 = df_naters2.resample('60T').mean()
df_naters = df_naters2

df_naters['regen_stundensumme_mm'] = df_naters3['regen_stundensumme_mm'].copy()
df_naters['sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min'] = df_naters3['sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min'].copy()

df_naters['WGS84_Laenge'] = (8+0.22/60)
df_naters['WGS84_Breite'] = (46+19.78/60)

index = df_naters.index[0]

```

```

df_naters.loc[index,'EPSG2056_lat'] = df_naters.loc[index,'WGS84_Breite']
df_naters.loc[index,'EPSG2056_lon'] = df_naters.loc[index,'WGS84_Laenge']

# get pointX and PointX from EPSG2056_lat and EPSG2056_long in row
pointX = df_naters.loc[index,'EPSG2056_lat']
pointY = df_naters.loc[index,'EPSG2056_lon']
# add pointX and pointY as osgeo Point
point = ogr.Geometry(ogr.wkbPoint)
point.AddPoint(pointY, pointX)
# Transform
print("WGS84: ", point)
point.Transform(coordTransform)
# print point in EPSG 4326
print("EPSG2056: ", point)
print("\n")
# convert back tuple back to each row
df_naters.loc[index,'EPSG2056_lat'] = point.GetX()
df_naters.loc[index,'EPSG2056_lon'] = point.GetY()
print(' -- successfull \n')

x = df_naters.loc[index,'EPSG2056_lat']
y = df_naters.loc[index,'EPSG2056_lon']
df_naters['EPSG2056_lat'] = x
df_naters['EPSG2056_lon'] = y
df_naters['WGS84_Breite'] = pointX
df_naters['WGS84_Laenge'] = pointY

df_naters['Name'] = 'Naters'
df_naters['Station'] = 'MONAT'
df_naters['Hoehe_AS_L_m'] = 731

df_naters = df_naters.reset_index()
df_naters['UTC1'] = df_naters['UTC'].copy()
df_naters = df_naters.set_index(pd.DatetimeIndex(df_naters['UTC1']))

df_naters.info()

# In[443]:
df = df.append(df_naters)
del df_naters

# Riederalp
# -----

# In[444]:
print('Import CSV')
path_riederalp_data = path_meteo_ow + 'riederalp.csv'
print(' -- successfull \n')
print('Creating Pandas Dataframe:df_riederalp')
df_riederalp =pd.DataFrame(pd.read_csv(path_riederalp_data, sep=',', low_memory=False))
print(' -- successfull \n')

# In[445]:
df_riederalp.info()

# In[446]:
df_riederalp['UTC'] = pd.to_datetime(df_riederalp['dateTime'],unit='s')
df_riederalp = df_riederalp.set_index(pd.DatetimeIndex(df_riederalp['UTC']))

start_date = '2018-01-01 00:00:00'
end_date = '2021-03-31 23:00:00'
mask = (df_riederalp['UTC'] > start_date) & (df_riederalp['UTC'] <= end_date)
df_riederalp = df_riederalp.loc[mask]

df_riederalp['sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min'] = df_riederalp['radiation'].copy()
df_riederalp.iloc[(df_riederalp.sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min < 120).values, 32] = np.nan
df_riederalp.iloc[(df_riederalp.sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min >= 120).values, 32] = 1

df_riederalp = df_riederalp.dropna(axis=1, how='all')
df_riederalp = df_riederalp.drop(['usUnits', 'interval', 'inTemp', 'inHumidity', 'extraTemp1', 'rxCheckPer-
cent', 'txBatteryStatus', 'consBatteryVoltage'], axis=1)
values = {
    'rainRate': 0,
    'rain': 0,
    'windGust': 0,
    'windSpeed': 0,
    'windSpeed': 0,
    'windSpeed': 0,
}
df_riederalp = df_riederalp.fillna(value=values)

df_riederalp3 = pd.DataFrame()

```

```

df_riederalp3['regen_stundensumme_mm'] = df_riederalp['rain'].resample('60T').sum()
df_riederalp3['sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min'] = df_riederalp['sonnenscheindauer_stunden-
summe_min'].resample('60T').sum()

#df_riederalp_cols = df_riederalp.columns.tolist()
#df_riederalp_cols
df_riederalpcols2 = ['barometer','pressure','altimeter','outTemp','outHumidity','windSpeed','windDir','wind-
Gust','windGustDir','dewpoint','windchill','heatindex','ET']
df_riederalp2 = df_riederalp[df_riederalpcols2]
df_riederalp2 = df_riederalp2.resample('60T').mean()
df_riederalp = df_riederalp2

df_riederalp['regen_stundensumme_mm'] = df_riederalp3['regen_stundensumme_mm'].copy()
df_riederalp['sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min'] = df_riederalp3['sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min'].copy()

df_riederalp['WGS84_Laenge'] = (8+2.16/60)
df_riederalp['WGS84_Breite'] = (46+22.77/60)

index = df_riederalp.index[0]

df_riederalp.loc[index,'EPSG2056_lat'] = df_riederalp.loc[index,'WGS84_Breite']
df_riederalp.loc[index,'EPSG2056_lon'] = df_riederalp.loc[index,'WGS84_Laenge']

# get pointX and PointX from EPSG2056_lat and EPSG2056_long in row
pointX = df_riederalp.loc[index,'EPSG2056_lat']
pointY = df_riederalp.loc[index,'EPSG2056_lon']
# add pointX and pointY as osgeo Point
point = ogr.Geometry(ogr.wkbPoint)
point.AddPoint(pointY, pointX)
# Transform
print("WGS84: ", point)
point.Transform(coordTransform)
# print point in EPSG 4326
print("EPSG2056: ", point)
print("\n")
# convert back tuple back to eacha row
df_riederalp.loc[index,'EPSG2056_lat'] = point.GetX()
df_riederalp.loc[index,'EPSG2056_lon'] = point.GetY()
print(' -- successfull \n')

x = df_riederalp.loc[index,'EPSG2056_lat']
y = df_riederalp.loc[index,'EPSG2056_lon']
df_riederalp['EPSG2056_lat'] = x
df_riederalp['EPSG2056_lon'] = y
df_riederalp['WGS84_Breite'] = pointX
df_riederalp['WGS84_Laenge'] = pointY

df_riederalp['Name'] = 'Riederalp'
df_riederalp['Station'] = 'MORIEDA'
df_riederalp['Hoehe_AS_L_m'] = 1907

df_riederalp = df_riederalp.reset_index()
df_riederalp['UTC1'] = df_riederalp['UTC'].copy()
df_riederalp = df_riederalp.set_index(pd.DatetimeIndex(df_riederalp['UTC1']))

df_riederalp.info()

# In[447]:
df = df.append(df_riederalp)
del df_riederalp

# Riederfurka
# -----

# In[448]:
print('Import CSV')
path_riederfurka_data = path_meteo_ow + 'riederfurka.csv'
print(' -- successfull \n')
print('Creating Pandas Dataframe:df_riederfurka')
df_riederfurka =pd.DataFrame(pd.read_csv(path_riederfurka_data, sep=',', low_memory=False))
print(' -- successfull \n')

# In[449]:
df_riederfurka.info()

# In[450]:
df_riederfurka['UTC'] = pd.to_datetime(df_riederfurka['dateTme'],unit='s')
df_riederfurka = df_riederfurka.set_index(pd.DatetimeIndex(df_riederfurka['UTC']))

start_date = '2018-01-01 00:00:00'
end_date = '2021-03-31 23:00:00'

```

```

mask = (df_riederfurka['UTC'] > start_date) & (df_riederfurka['UTC'] <= end_date)
df_riederfurka = df_riederfurka.loc[mask]

df_riederfurka['sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min'] = df_riederfurka['radiation'].copy()
df_riederfurka.iloc[(df_riederfurka.sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min < 120).values, 32] = np.nan
df_riederfurka.iloc[(df_riederfurka.sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min >= 120).values, 32] = 1

df_riederfurka = df_riederfurka.dropna(axis=1, how='all')
df_riederfurka = df_riederfurka.drop(['usUnits', 'interval', 'inTemp', 'inHumidity', 'extraTemp1', 'rxCheckPer-
cent', 'txBatteryStatus', 'consBatteryVoltage'], axis=1)
values = {
    'rainRate': 0,
    'rain': 0,
    'windGust': 0,
    'windSpeed': 0,
    'windSpeed': 0,
    'windSpeed': 0,
}
df_riederfurka = df_riederfurka.fillna(value=values)

df_riederfurka3 = pd.DataFrame()
df_riederfurka3['regen_stundensumme_mm'] = df_riederfurka['rain'].resample('60T').sum()
df_riederfurka3['sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min'] = df_riederfurka['sonnenscheindauer_stunden-
summe_min'].resample('60T').sum()

#df_riederfurka_cols = df_riederfurka.columns.tolist()
#df_riederfurka_cols
df_riederfurkacols2 = ['barometer', 'pressure', 'altimeter', 'outTemp', 'outHumidity', 'windSpeed', 'windDir', 'wind-
Gust', 'windGustDir', 'dewpoint', 'windchill', 'heatindex', 'ET']
df_riederfurka2 = df_riederfurka[df_riederfurkacols2]
df_riederfurka2 = df_riederfurka2.resample('60T').mean()
df_riederfurka = df_riederfurka2

df_riederfurka['regen_stundensumme_mm'] = df_riederfurka3['regen_stundensumme_mm'].copy()
df_riederfurka['sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min'] = df_riederfurka3['sonnenscheindauer_stunden-
summe_min'].copy()

df_riederfurka['WGS84_Laenge'] = (8+1.05/60)
df_riederfurka['WGS84_Breite'] = (46+22.67/60)

index = df_riederfurka.index[0]

df_riederfurka.loc[index, 'EPSG2056_lat'] = df_riederfurka.loc[index, 'WGS84_Breite']
df_riederfurka.loc[index, 'EPSG2056_lon'] = df_riederfurka.loc[index, 'WGS84_Laenge']

# get pointX and PointX from EPSG2056_lat and EPSG2056_long in row
pointX = df_riederfurka.loc[index, 'EPSG2056_lat']
pointY = df_riederfurka.loc[index, 'EPSG2056_lon']
# add pointX and pointY as osgeo Point
point = ogr.Geometry(ogr.wkbPoint)
point.AddPoint(pointY, pointX)
# Transform
print("WGS84: ", point)
point.Transform(coordTransform)
# print point in EPSG 4326
print("EPSG2056: ", point)
print("\n")
# convert back tuple back to each row
df_riederfurka.loc[index, 'EPSG2056_lat'] = point.GetX()
df_riederfurka.loc[index, 'EPSG2056_lon'] = point.GetY()
print(' -- successfull \n')

x = df_riederfurka.loc[index, 'EPSG2056_lat']
y = df_riederfurka.loc[index, 'EPSG2056_lon']
df_riederfurka['EPSG2056_lat'] = x
df_riederfurka['EPSG2056_lon'] = y
df_riederfurka['WGS84_Breite'] = pointX
df_riederfurka['WGS84_Laenge'] = pointY

df_riederfurka['Name'] = 'Riederfurka'
df_riederfurka['Station'] = 'MORIEDF'
df_riederfurka['Hoehe_AS_L_m'] = 2074

df_riederfurka = df_riederfurka.reset_index()
df_riederfurka['UTC1'] = df_riederfurka['UTC'].copy()
df_riederfurka = df_riederfurka.set_index(pd.DatetimeIndex(df_riederfurka['UTC1']))

df_riederfurka.info()

# In[451]:
df = df.append(df_riederfurka)
del df_riederfurka

```

```

# Simplon
# -----

# In[452]:
print('Import CSV')
path_simplon_data = path_meteo_ow + 'simplon.csv'
print(' -- successfull \n')
print('Creating Pandas Dataframe:df_simplon')
df_simplon =pd.DataFrame(pd.read_csv(path_simplon_data, sep=',', low_memory=False))
print(' -- successfull \n')

# In[453]:
df_simplon.info()

# In[454]:
df_simplon['UTC'] = pd.to_datetime(df_simplon['dateTime'],unit='s')
df_simplon = df_simplon.set_index(pd.DatetimeIndex(df_simplon['UTC']))

start_date = '2018-01-01 00:00:00'
end_date = '2021-03-31 23:00:00'
mask = (df_simplon['UTC'] > start_date) & (df_simplon['UTC'] <= end_date)
df_simplon = df_simplon.loc[mask]

df_simplon['sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min'] = df_simplon['radiation'].copy()
df_simplon.iloc[(df_simplon.sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min < 120).values, 32] = np.nan
df_simplon.iloc[(df_simplon.sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min >= 120).values, 32] = 1

df_simplon = df_simplon.dropna(axis=1, how='all')
df_simplon = df_simplon.drop(['usUnits', 'interval', 'inTemp', 'inHumidity', 'extraTemp1', 'rxCheckPercent', 'txBatteryStatus', 'consBatteryVoltage'], axis=1)
values = {
    'rainRate': 0,
    'rain': 0,
    'windGust': 0,
    'windSpeed': 0,
    'windSpeed': 0,
    'windSpeed': 0,
}
df_simplon = df_simplon.fillna(value=values)

df_simplon3 = pd.DataFrame()
df_simplon3['regen_stundensumme_mm'] = df_simplon['rain'].resample('60T').sum()
df_simplon3['sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min'] = df_simplon['sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min'].resample('60T').sum()

#df_simplon_cols = df_simplon.columns.tolist()
#df_simplon_cols
df_simploncols2 = ['barometer','pressure','altimeter','outTemp','outHumidity','windSpeed','windDir','windGust','windGustDir','dewpoint','windchill','heatindex','ET']
df_simplon2 = df_simplon[df_simploncols2]
df_simplon2 = df_simplon2.resample('60T').mean()
df_simplon = df_simplon2

df_simplon['regen stundensumme mm'] = df_simplon3['regen stundensumme mm'].copy()
df_simplon['sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min'] = df_simplon3['sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min'].copy()

df_simplon['WGS84_Laenge'] = (8+1.49/60)
df_simplon['WGS84_Breite'] = (46+14.77/60)

index = df_simplon.index[0]

df_simplon.loc[index,'EPSG2056_lat'] = df_simplon.loc[index,'WGS84_Breite']
df_simplon.loc[index,'EPSG2056_lon'] = df_simplon.loc[index,'WGS84_Laenge']

# get pointX and PointX from EPSG2056_lat and EPSG2056_long in row
pointX = df_simplon.loc[index,'EPSG2056_lat']
pointY = df_simplon.loc[index,'EPSG2056_lon']
# add pointX and pointY as osgeo Point
point = ogr.Geometry(ogr.wkbPoint)
point.AddPoint(pointY, pointX)
# Transform
print("WGS84: ", point)
point.Transform(coordTransform)
# print point in EPSG 4326
print("EPSG2056: ", point)
print("\n")
# convert back tuple back to eacha row
df_simplon.loc[index,'EPSG2056_lat'] = point.GetX()
df_simplon.loc[index,'EPSG2056_lon'] = point.GetY()
print(' -- successfull \n')

x = df_simplon.loc[index,'EPSG2056_lat']
y = df_simplon.loc[index,'EPSG2056_lon']

```

```

df_simplon['EPSG2056_lat'] = x
df_simplon['EPSG2056_lon'] = y
df_simplon['WGS84_Breite'] = pointX
df_simplon['WGS84_Laenge'] = pointY

df_simplon['Name'] = 'Simplonpass'
df_simplon['Station'] = 'MOSIMP'
df_simplon['Hoehe_AS_L_m'] = 1993

df_simplon = df_simplon.reset_index()
df_simplon['UTC1'] = df_simplon['UTC'].copy()
df_simplon = df_simplon.set_index(pd.DatetimeIndex(df_simplon['UTC1']))

df_simplon.info()

# In[455]:
df = df.append(df_simplon)
del df_simplon

# In[456]:
del df['UTC1']

# Editing Meteo Oberwallis
# -----

# In[457]:
df.reset_index(inplace=True)

# In[458]:
df['UTC']

# In[459]:
df['Timestamp'] = pd.to_datetime(df['UTC'], format='%Y%m%d%H%M%S').astype(str)
df['Timestamp'].replace(to_replace='[^0-9]+', value='', inplace=True, regex=True)

# In[460]:
df['Timestamp']

# In[461]:
df['year'] = pd.to_numeric(df.Timestamp.astype(str).str[:4])
df['month'] = pd.to_numeric(df.Timestamp.astype(str).str[4:6])
df['day'] = pd.to_numeric(df.Timestamp.astype(str).str[6:8])
df['hour'] = df.Timestamp.astype(str).str[8:10]
df['minutes'] = df.Timestamp.astype(str).str[10:12]
df['seconds'] = '00'
df['UTC_Date'] = pd.to_datetime((df.year*10000+df.month*100+df.day).apply(str), format='%Y%m%d')
df['UTC_Date']

# In[462]:
df['UTC_Time'] = (df.hour+ ':' +df.minutes+ ':' +df.seconds)

# In[463]:
df.UTC_Time.min()

# In[464]:
df.UTC_Time.max()

# In[465]:
df['UTC_Date'] = (df.day.astype(str)+ '.' +df.month.astype(str)+ '.' +df.year.astype(str))
df['UTC1'] = df['UTC']

# In[466]:
df = df.set_index(pd.DatetimeIndex(df['UTC1']))

# In[467]:
df.UTC_Date.min()

# UTC_DATE MAX FALSCH !!

# In[468]:
df.UTC_Date.max()

```

```

# In[469]:
df = df.dropna(axis=1,how='all')

# del df['rxCheckPercent']
# del df['txBatteryStatus']
# del df['consBatteryVoltage']
# del df['supplyVoltage']
# del df['referenceVoltage']
#
# #del df['heatingTemp']
# #del df['heatingVoltage']
# #del df['windBatteryStatus']
# #del df['rainBatteryStatus']
# #del df['outTempBatteryStatus']
# #del df['inTempBatteryStatus']

# In[470]:
df['Einheit_outHumidity'] = '%'
df['Wert_outHumidity'] = df['outHumidity']
#del df['inHumidity']
del df['outHumidity']

#df['Einheit_extraHumid1'] = '%'
#df['Wert_extraHumid1'] = df['extraHumid1']
#del df['extraHumid1']

#df['Einheit_extraHumid2'] = '%'
#df['Wert_extraHumid2'] = df['extraHumid2']
#del df['extraHumid2']

df['Parameter_outHumidity'] = 'outHumidity'
#df['Parameter_extraHumid1'] = 'extraHumid1'
#df['Parameter_extraHumid2'] = 'extraHumid2'

df['Beschreibung_outHumidity'] = 'Luftfeuchtigkeit Stundenmittel'
#df['Beschreibung_extraHumid1'] = 'Luftfeuchtigkeit Stundenmittel'
#df['Beschreibung_extraHumid2'] = 'Luftfeuchtigkeit Stundenmittel'

df['Datenquelle_outHumidity'] = 'Meteo Oberwallis'
#df['Datenquelle_extraHumid1'] = 'Meteo Oberwallis'
#df['Datenquelle_extraHumid2'] = 'Meteo Oberwallis'

# 1 inhg to hpa = 33.86389 hpa

# In[471]:
df['Wert_pressure'] = df['pressure'].mul(33.86389)
df['Wert_barometer'] = df['barometer'].mul(33.86389)
df['Wert_altimeter'] = df['altimeter'].mul(33.86389)
del df['pressure']
del df['barometer']
del df['altimeter']

df['Einheit_pressure'] = 'hPa'
df['Einheit_barometer'] = 'hPa'
df['Einheit_altimeter'] = 'hPa'

df['Parameter_pressure'] = 'pressure'
df['Parameter_barometer'] = 'barometer'
df['Parameter_altimeter'] = 'altimeter'

df['Beschreibung_pressure'] = 'Luftdruck Stundenmittel'
df['Beschreibung_barometer'] = 'Barometer Stundenmittel'
df['Beschreibung_altimeter'] = 'Altimeter Stundenmittel'

df['Datenquelle_pressure'] = 'Meteo Oberwallis'
df['Datenquelle_barometer'] = 'Meteo Oberwallis'
df['Datenquelle_altimeter'] = 'Meteo Oberwallis'

# (x°F - 32) × 5/9 = y°C
#

# In[472]:
#del df['inTemp']

df['outTemp'] = df['outTemp'].sub(32)
df['Wert_outTemp'] = df['outTemp'].mul(5/9)
del df['outTemp']

df['dewpoint'] = df['dewpoint'].sub(32)
df['Wert_dewpoint'] = df['dewpoint'].mul(5/9)
del df['dewpoint']

df['windchill'] = df['windchill'].sub(32)
df['Wert_windchill'] = df['windchill'].mul(5/9)

```

```

del df['windchill']

df['Einheit_outTemp'] = 'C'
df['Einheit_dewpoint'] = 'C'
df['Einheit_windchill'] = 'C'

df['Parameter_outTemp'] = 'outTemp'
df['Parameter_dewpoint'] = 'dewpoint'
df['Parameter_windchill'] = 'windchill'

df['Beschreibung_outTemp'] = 'Temperatur Stundenmittel'
df['Beschreibung_dewpoint'] = 'Taupunkt Stundenmittel'
df['Beschreibung_windchill'] = 'Windchill Stundenmittel'

df['Datenquelle_outTemp'] = 'Meteo Oberwallis'
df['Datenquelle_dewpoint'] = 'Meteo Oberwallis'
df['Datenquelle_windchill'] = 'Meteo Oberwallis'

#df['extraTemp1'] = df['extraTemp1'].sub(32)
#df['Wert_extraTemp1'] = df['extraTemp1'].mul(5/9)
#del df['extraTemp1']

#df['extraTemp2'] = df['extraTemp2'].sub(32)
#df['Wert_extraTemp2'] = df['extraTemp2'].mul(5/9)
#del df['extraTemp2']

#df['extraTemp3'] = df['extraTemp3'].sub(32)
#df['Wert_extraTemp3'] = df['extraTemp3'].mul(5/9)
#del df['extraTemp3']

#df['Einheit_extraTemp1'] = 'C'
#df['Einheit_extraTemp2'] = 'C'
#df['Einheit_extraTemp3'] = 'C'

#df['Parameter_extraTemp1'] = 'extraTemp1'
#df['Parameter_extraTemp2'] = 'extraTemp2'
#df['Parameter_extraTemp3'] = 'extraTemp3'

#df['Beschreibung_extraTemp1'] = 'Temperatur Stundenmittel'
#df['Beschreibung_extraTemp2'] = 'Temperatur Stundenmittel'
#df['Beschreibung_extraTemp3'] = 'Temperatur Stundenmittel'

#df['Datenquelle_extraTemp1'] = 'Meteo Oberwallis'
#df['Datenquelle_extraTemp2'] = 'Meteo Oberwallis'
#df['Datenquelle_extraTemp3'] = 'Meteo Oberwallis'

#df['soilTemp1'] = df['soilTemp1'].sub(32)
#df['Wert_soilTemp1'] = df['soilTemp1'].mul(5/9)
#del df['soilTemp1']

#df['soilTemp2'] = df['soilTemp2'].sub(32)
#df['Wert_soilTemp2'] = df['soilTemp2'].mul(5/9)
#del df['soilTemp2']

#df['soilTemp3'] = df['soilTemp3'].sub(32)
#df['Wert_soilTemp3'] = df['soilTemp3'].mul(5/9)
#del df['soilTemp3']

#df['soilTemp4'] = df['soilTemp4'].sub(32)
#df['Wert_soilTemp4'] = df['soilTemp4'].mul(5/9)
#del df['soilTemp4']

#df['Einheit_soilTemp1'] = 'C'
#df['Einheit_soilTemp2'] = 'C'
#df['Einheit_soilTemp3'] = 'C'
#df['Einheit_soilTemp4'] = 'C'

#df['Parameter_soilTemp1'] = 'soilTemp1'
#df['Parameter_soilTemp2'] = 'soilTemp2'
#df['Parameter_soilTemp3'] = 'soilTemp3'
#df['Parameter_soilTemp4'] = 'soilTemp3'

#df['Beschreibung_soilTemp1'] = 'Bodentemperatur Stundenmittel'
#df['Beschreibung_soilTemp2'] = 'Bodentemperatur Stundenmittel'
#df['Beschreibung_soilTemp3'] = 'Bodentemperatur Stundenmittel'
#df['Beschreibung_soilTemp4'] = 'Bodentemperatur Stundenmittel'

#df['Datenquelle_soilTemp1'] = 'Meteo Oberwallis'
#df['Datenquelle_soilTemp2'] = 'Meteo Oberwallis'
#df['Datenquelle_soilTemp3'] = 'Meteo Oberwallis'
#df['Datenquelle_soilTemp4'] = 'Meteo Oberwallis'

#df['leafTemp1'] = df['leafTemp1'].sub(32)
#df['Wert_leafTemp1'] = df['leafTemp1'].mul(5/9)
#del df['leafTemp1']

#df['leafTemp2'] = df['leafTemp2'].sub(32)

```

```

#df['Wert_leafTemp2'] = df['leafTemp2'].mul(5/9)
#del df['leafTemp2']

#df['Einheit_leafTemp1'] = 'C'
#df['Einheit_leafTemp2'] = 'C'

#df['Parameter_leafTemp1'] = 'leafTemp1'
#df['Parameter_leafTemp2'] = 'leafTemp2'

#df['Beschreibung_leafTemp1'] = 'Blatttemperatur Stundenmittel'
#df['Beschreibung_leafTemp2'] = 'Blatttemperatur Stundenmittel'

#df['Datenquelle_leafTemp1'] = 'Meteo Oberwallis'
#df['Datenquelle_leafTemp2'] = 'Meteo Oberwallis'

# In[473]:
df

# In[474]:
df['Wert_regen_stundensumme_mm'] = df['regen_stundensumme_mm'].mul(25.4)
del df['regen_stundensumme_mm']

df['Einheit_regen_stundensumme_mm'] = 'mm/h'

df['Parameter_regen_stundensumme_mm'] = 'rain'

df['Beschreibung_regen_stundensumme_mm'] = 'Niederschlag Stundensumme'

df['Datenquelle_regen_stundensumme_mm'] = 'Meteo Oberwallis'

# Wind
# Wind Chill (Calculated)
# Resolution and Units. . . . . 1°F or 1°C (user-selectable) °C is converted from °F rounded to the nearest 1°C
# Range. . . . . -110° to +135°F (-79° to +57°C)
# Accuracy . . . . . ±2°F (±1°C) (typical)
# Update Interval . . . . . 10 to 12 seconds
# Source . . . . . United States National Weather Service (NWS)/NOAA
# Equation Used . . . . . Osczevski (1995) (adopted by US NWS in 2001)
# Variables Used . . . . . Instant Outside Temperature and 10-min. Avg. Wind Speed
# Current Display Data . . . . . Instant Calculation
# Current Graph Data . . . . . Instant Calculation; Hourly, Daily and Monthly Low
# Historical Graph Data . . . . . Hourly, Daily and Monthly Lows
# Alarm . . . . . Low Threshold from Instant Calculation
# Wind Direction
# Range. . . . . 1 - 360°
# Display Resolution . . . . . 16 points (22.5°) on compass rose, 1° in numeric display
# Accuracy . . . . . ±3°
# Update Interval . . . . . 2.5 to 3 seconds
# Current Display Data . . . . . Instant (user-adjustable offset available)
# Current Graph Data . . . . . Instant; 10-min. Dominant; Hourly, Daily, Monthly Dominant
# Historical Graph Data . . . . . Past 6 10-min. Dominants on compass rose only; Hourly, Daily, Monthly Dominants
# Wind Speed
# Resolution and Units. . . . . 1 mph, 1 km/h, 0.4 m/s, or 1 knot (user-selectable). Measured in mph, other units
# are converted from mph and rounded to nearest 1 km/hr, 0.1 m/s, or 1 knot.
# Range. . . . . 0 to 200 mph, 0 to 173 knots, 0 to 89 m/s, 0 to 322 km/h
# Update Interval . . . . . Instant Reading: 2.5 to 3 seconds, 10-minute Average: 1 minute
# Accuracy . . . . . ±2 mph (2 kts, 3.2 km/h, 0.9 m/s) or ±5%, whichever is greater
# Maximum Cable Length . . . . . 240 feet (73 m) (See note on page 1)
# Current Display Data . . . . . Instant
# Current Graph Data . . . . . Instant; 10-minute and Hourly Average; Hourly High; Daily, Monthly and Yearly
# High with Direction of High
# Historical Graph Data . . . . . 10-min. and Hourly Averages; Hourly Highs; Daily, Monthly and Yearly Highs with
# Direction of Highs
# Alarms . . . . . High Thresholds from Instant Reading and 10-minute Average

# In[475]:
df['Wert_windDir'] = df['windDir']

```

```

del df['windDir']

df['Wert_windSpeed'] = df['windSpeed'].astype(float).div(2.237)
del df['windSpeed']

df['Wert_windGust'] = df['windGust']
del df['windGust']

df['Wert_windGustDir'] = df['windGustDir']
del df['windGustDir']

df['Einheit_windDir'] = 'Grad'
df['Einheit_windSpeed'] = 'm/s'
df['Einheit_windGust'] = 'm/s'
df['Einheit_windGustDir'] = 'Grad'

df['Parameter_windDir'] = 'windDir'
df['Parameter_windSpeed'] = 'windSpeed'
df['Parameter_windGust'] = 'windGust'
df['Parameter_windGustDir'] = 'windGustDir'

df['Beschreibung_windDir'] = 'Windrichtung Stundenmittel'
df['Beschreibung_windSpeed'] = 'Windgeschwindigkeit Stundenmittel'
df['Beschreibung_windGust'] = 'Boee Stundenmittel'
df['Beschreibung_windGustDir'] = 'Boeenrichtung Stundenmittel'

df['Datenquelle_windDir'] = 'Meteo Oberwallis'
df['Datenquelle_windSpeed'] = 'Meteo Oberwallis'
df['Datenquelle_windGust'] = 'Meteo Oberwallis'
df['Datenquelle_windGustDir'] = 'Meteo Oberwallis'

# The heat index (HI) is an index that combines air temperature and relative humidity, in shaded areas, to
# posit a human-perceived equivalent temperature, as how hot it would feel if the humidity were some other value
# in the shade. The result is also known as the "felt air temperature", "apparent temperature", "real feel" or
# "feels like".

# In[476]:
df['Wert_heatindex'] = df['heatindex']
del df['heatindex']

df['Einheit_heatindex'] = 'C'
df['Parameter_heatindex'] = 'heatindex'
df['Beschreibung_heatindex'] = 'Gefuehlte Temperatur HeatIndex'
df['Datenquelle_heatindex'] = 'Meteo Oberwallis'

# Leaf wetness is a meteorological parameter that describes the amount of dew and precipitation left on sur-
# faces. It is used for monitoring leaf moisture for agricultural purposes, such as fungus and disease control,
# for control of irrigation systems, and for detection of fog and dew conditions, and early detection of rainfall

# df['Wert_leafWet1'] = df['leafWet1']
# del df['leafWet1']
#
# df['Einheit_leafWet1'] = '??'
# df['Parameter_leafWet1'] = 'leafWet1'
# df['Beschreibung leafWet1'] = 'Leaf wetness is a meteorological parameter that describes the amount of dew
# and precipitation left on surfaces'
# df['Datenquelle_leafWet1'] = 'Meteo Oberwallis'
#
# df['Wert_leafWet2'] = df['leafWet2']
# del df['leafWet2']
#
# df['Einheit_leafWet2'] = '??'
# df['Parameter_leafWet2'] = 'leafWet1'
# df['Beschreibung_leafWet2'] = 'Leaf wetness is a meteorological parameter that describes the amount of dew
# and precipitation left on surfaces'
# df['Datenquelle_leafWet2'] = 'Meteo Oberwallis'

# Ultra Violet (UV) Radiation Dose (requires UV sensor)
# Resolution and Units. . . . . 0.1 MEDS to 19.9 MEDS; 1 MED
# above 19.9 MEDS
# Range. . . . . 0 to 199 MEDS
# Accuracy . . . . . ±5% of daily total
# Drift . . . . . up to ±2% per year
# Update Interval . . . . . 50 seconds to 1 minute (5
# minutes when dark)
# Current Graph Data . . . . . Latest Daily Total (user resetta-
# ble at any time from Current Screen)
# Historical Graph Data . . . . . Hourly, Daily Totals (user reset
# from Current Screen does not affect these values)
# Alarm . . . . . High Threshold from Daily
# Total
# Alarm Range. . . . . 0 to 19.9 MEDS
# Ultra Violet (UV) Radiation Index (requires UV sensor)
# Resolution and Units. . . . . 0.1 Index
# Range. . . . . 0 to 16 Index

```

```

# Accuracy . . . . . ±5% of full scale (Reference: Yankee UVB-1 at UV index 10 (Extremely High))
# Cosine Response . . . . . ±4% FS (0° to 90° zenith angle)
# Update Interval . . . . . 50 seconds to 1 minute (5 minutes when dark)
# Current Graph Data . . . . . Instant Reading and Hourly Average; Daily, Monthly High
# Historical Graph Data . . . . . Hourly Average, Daily, Monthly Highs
# Alarm . . . . . High Threshold from Instant Calculation

# df['Wert_UV'] = df['UV']
# df['Einheit_UV'] = 'MED'
# del df['UV']
#
# df['Parameter_UV'] = 'UV'
# df['Beschreibung_UV'] = 'UVstrahlung Stundenmittel'
# df['Datenquelle_UV'] = 'Meteo Oberwallis'

# "wenn Solarsensor-Wert > 120W/m2, dann Sonnenschein"

# df['Wert_solarradiation'] = df['radiation']
# df['Einheit_solarradiation'] = 'W/m2'
# del df['radiation']
#
# df['Parameter_solarradiation'] = 'solarradiation'
# df['Beschreibung_solarradiation'] = 'Solarstrahlung Stundenmittel'
# df['Datenquelle_solarradiation'] = 'Meteo Oberwallis'

# df['Wert_soilMoist1'] = df['soilMoist1']
# del df['soilMoist1']
#
# df['Wert_soilMoist2'] = df['soilMoist2']
# del df['soilMoist2']
#
# df['Wert_soilMoist3'] = df['soilMoist3']
# del df['soilMoist3']
#
# df['Wert_soilMoist4'] = df['soilMoist4']
# del df['soilMoist4']
#
# df['Parameter_soilMoist1'] = 'soilMoist1'
# df['Parameter_soilMoist2'] = 'soilMoist2'
# df['Parameter_soilMoist3'] = 'soilMoist3'
# df['Parameter_soilMoist4'] = 'soilMoist4'
#
# df['Einheit_soilMoist1'] = 'centibars (cB)'
# df['Einheit_soilMoist2'] = 'centibars (cB)'
# df['Einheit_soilMoist3'] = 'centibars (cB)'
# df['Einheit_soilMoist4'] = 'centibars (cB)'
#
# df['Beschreibung_soilMoist1'] = 'Bodenfeuchtigkeit Stundenmittel'
# df['Beschreibung_soilMoist2'] = 'Bodenfeuchtigkeit Stundenmittel'
# df['Beschreibung_soilMoist3'] = 'Bodenfeuchtigkeit Stundenmittel'
# df['Beschreibung_soilMoist4'] = 'Bodenfeuchtigkeit Stundenmittel'
#
# df['Datenquelle_soilMoist1'] = 'Meteo Oberwallis'
# df['Datenquelle_soilMoist2'] = 'Meteo Oberwallis'
# df['Datenquelle_soilMoist3'] = 'Meteo Oberwallis'
# df['Datenquelle_soilMoist4'] = 'Meteo Oberwallis'
#
# df['Parameter_sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min'] = 'sunshine_min'
# df['Einheit_sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min'] = 'min'
# df['Beschreibung_sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min'] = 'Sonnenscheindauer Stundensumme'
# df['Datenquelle_sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min'] = 'Meteo Oberwallis'

# In[477]:
df['Wert_ET'] = df['ET'].mul(25.4)
del df['ET']
df['Parameter_ET'] = 'ET'
df['Einheit_ET'] = 'mm/h'
df['Beschreibung_ET'] = 'EvapoTranspiration (ET) Stundenmittel'
df['Datenquelle_ET'] = 'Meteo Oberwallis'

# In[478]:
df['Wert_sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min'] = df['sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min'].copy()
df['Parameter_sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min'] = 'sun_min_h'
df['Einheit_sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min'] = 'min/h'
df['Beschreibung_sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min'] = 'Sonnenscheindauer Stundensumme'
df['Datenquelle_sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min'] = 'Meteo Oberwallis'

# In[479]:
df

```

```

# In[480]:
list1 = df.columns.tolist()
list1

# In[481]:
df['dateTime'] = df['UTC'].view('int64').div(1000000)

# In[482]:
list2 = ['UTC', 'Timestamp', 'Station', 'Name', 'WGS84_Laenge', 'WGS84_Breite',
        'EPSG2056_lat', 'EPSG2056_lon', 'Hoehe ASL m',
        'Parameter_outTemp', 'Wert_outTemp', 'Einheit_outTemp', 'Beschreibung_outTemp', 'Datenquelle_outTemp',
        'Parameter_dewpoint', 'Wert_dewpoint', 'Einheit_dewpoint', 'Beschreibung_dewpoint', 'Datenquelle_dew-
point',
        'Parameter_windchill', 'Wert_windchill', 'Einheit_windchill', 'Beschreibung_windchill', 'Datenquelle_wind-
chill',
        'Parameter_heatindex', 'Wert_heatindex', 'Einheit_heatindex', 'Beschreibung_heatindex', 'Datenquelle_heat-
index',
        'Parameter_ET', 'Wert_ET', 'Einheit_ET', 'Beschreibung_ET', 'Datenquelle_ET',
        'Parameter_sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min', 'Wert_sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min', 'Einheit_son-
nenscheindauer_stundensumme_min', 'Beschreibung_sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min',
        'Parameter_pressure', 'Wert_pressure', 'Einheit_pressure', 'Beschreibung_pressure', 'Datenquelle_pres-
sure',
        'Parameter_barometer', 'Wert_barometer', 'Einheit_barometer', 'Beschreibung_barometer', 'Datenquelle_baro-
meter',
        'Parameter_altimeter', 'Wert_altimeter', 'Einheit_altimeter', 'Beschreibung_altimeter', 'Datenquelle_alti-
meter',
        'Parameter_outHumidity', 'Wert_outHumidity', 'Einheit_outHumidity', 'Beschreibung_outHumidity', 'Daten-
quelle_outHumidity',
        'Parameter_regen_stundensumme_mm', 'Wert_regen_stundensumme_mm', 'Einheit_regen_stundensumme_mm', 'Be-
schreibung_regen_stundensumme_mm', 'Datenquelle_regen_stundensumme_mm',
        'Parameter_windSpeed', 'Wert_windSpeed', 'Einheit_windSpeed', 'Beschreibung_windSpeed', 'Daten-
quelle_windSpeed',
        'Parameter_windDir', 'Wert_windDir', 'Einheit_windDir', 'Beschreibung_windDir', 'Datenquelle_windDir',
        'Parameter_windGust', 'Wert_windGust', 'Einheit_windGust', 'Beschreibung_windGust', 'Datenquelle_wind-
Gust',
        'Parameter_windGustDir', 'Wert_windGustDir', 'Einheit_windGustDir', 'Beschreibung_windGustDir', 'Daten-
quelle_windGustDir',
        'Parameter_sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min', 'sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min', 'Einheit_sonnen-
scheindauer_stundensumme_min', 'Beschreibung_sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min', 'Datenquelle_sonnenschein-
dauer_stundensumme_min',
        'dateTime', 'year', 'month', 'day', 'hour', 'UTC_Date', 'UTC_Time', 'UTC1']
list2

# In[483]:
df = df[list2]

# In[484]:
df

# In[485]:
df = df.sort_index()

# In[486]:
df['UTC'].max()

# In[487]:
df['UTC'].min()

# In[488]:
df['UTC_Date'].min()

# Fehler Konversion Date ?????

# In[489]:
df['UTC_Date'].max()

# In[490]:
# write df_new to csv output
print('write df to csv output')
df.to_csv(path_to_output + 'MeteoOberwallis_Data.csv', index = False)
print(' -- successfull \n')

# In[491]:
del df

```

```

# In[492]:
print('Import CSV')
path_mo_data = path_to_output + 'MeteoOberwallis_Data.csv'
print('-- successfull \n')
print('Creating Pandas Dataframe:df_meteo_oberwallis_data')
df_meteo_oberwallis_data =pd.DataFrame(pd.read_csv(path_mo_data, sep=',', low_memory=False))
print('-- successfull \n')

# In[493]:
df_meteo_oberwallis_data_small = pd.DataFrame()
df_meteo_oberwallis_data_small['UTC'] = df_meteo_oberwallis_data['UTC'].copy()
df_meteo_oberwallis_data_small['Timestamp'] = df_meteo_oberwallis_data['Timestamp'].copy()
df_meteo_oberwallis_data_small['Station'] = df_meteo_oberwallis_data['Station'].copy()
df_meteo_oberwallis_data_small['Name'] = df_meteo_oberwallis_data['Name'].copy()

df_meteo_oberwallis_data_small['WGS84_Breite'] = df_meteo_oberwallis_data['WGS84_Breite'].copy()
df_meteo_oberwallis_data_small['WGS84_Laenge'] = df_meteo_oberwallis_data['WGS84_Laenge'].copy()
df_meteo_oberwallis_data_small['EPSG2056_lat'] = df_meteo_oberwallis_data['EPSG2056_lat'].copy()
df_meteo_oberwallis_data_small['EPSG2056_lon'] = df_meteo_oberwallis_data['EPSG2056_lon'].copy()

df_meteo_oberwallis_data_small['Hoehe_AS_L_m'] = df_meteo_oberwallis_data['Hoehe_AS_L_m'].copy()

df_meteo_oberwallis_data_small['UTC1'] = df_meteo_oberwallis_data['UTC'].copy()
df_meteo_oberwallis_data_small['Temp_2mAGL_C'] = df_meteo_oberwallis_data['Wert_outTemp'].copy()
df_meteo_oberwallis_data_small['Taupunkt_Momentanwert_celsius'] = df_meteo_oberwallis_data['Wert_dew-
point'].copy()
df_meteo_oberwallis_data_small['rel_Luftfeuchtigkeit_Stundenmittel_prozent'] = df_meteo_oberwal-
lis_data['Wert_outHumidity'].copy()

# In[494]:
df_meteo_oberwallis_data_small['Luftdruck_Barometerhoehe_QFE_Stundenmittel_hPa'] = df_meteo_oberwal-
lis_data['Wert_pressure'].copy()
df_meteo_oberwallis_data_small['Niederschlag_Stundensumme_mm'] = df_meteo_oberwallis_data['Wert_regen_stunden-
summe_mm'].copy()
df_meteo_oberwallis_data_small['Windgeschwindigkeit_ms'] = df_meteo_oberwallis_data['Wert_windSpeed'].copy()
df_meteo_oberwallis_data_small['Windrichtung_grad'] = df_meteo_oberwallis_data['Wert_windDir'].copy()
df_meteo_oberwallis_data_small['sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min'] = df_meteo_oberwallis_data['sonnenschein-
dauer_stundensumme_min'].copy()

# In[495]:
df_meteo_oberwallis_data_small2 = pd.DataFrame()
df_meteo_oberwallis_data_small2['UTC'] = df_meteo_oberwallis_data_small['UTC'].copy()
df_meteo_oberwallis_data_small2['Station'] = df_meteo_oberwallis_data_small['Station'].copy()
df_meteo_oberwallis_data_small2['Luftdruck_Barometerhoehe_QFE_Stundenmittel_hPa'] = df_meteo_oberwal-
lis_data_small['Luftdruck_Barometerhoehe_QFE_Stundenmittel_hPa'].copy()
df_meteo_oberwallis_data_small2

# In[496]:
df_meteo_oberwallis_data_small2['Luftdruckaenderung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa'] = np.nan
df_meteo_oberwallis_data_small2['Station1'] = df_meteo_oberwallis_data_small2['Station']

# In[497]:
df_meteo_oberwallis_data_small2 = df_meteo_oberwallis_data_small2.set_index(['Station1','UTC']).sort_index()

# In[498]:
df_meteo_oberwallis_data_small2.index

# In[499]:
df_meteo_oberwallis_data_small2 = df_meteo_oberwallis_data_small2.reset_index()

# In[500]:current_station = df_meteo_oberwallis_data_small2.loc[99999,'Station']
last_station = df_meteo_oberwallis_data_small2.loc[99999,'Station']
press1 = 0.0
press2 = 0.0

# In[501]:
for index, row in islice(df_meteo_oberwallis_data_small2.iterrows(), None):
    current_station = df_meteo_oberwallis_data_small2.loc[index,'Station']
    if current_station == last_station:
        press1 = df_meteo_oberwallis_data_small2.loc[index,'Luftdruck_Barometerhoehe_QFE_Stundenmittel_hPa']
        press2 = df_meteo_oberwallis_data_small2.loc[index-1,'Luftdruck_Barometerhoehe_QFE_Stundenmittel_hPa']
        #print('current=last station',df_meteo_oberwallis_data_small2.loc[index,'Station'], 'press1: ', press1,
'press2: ', press2)

    if math.isnan(press1) or math.isnan(press2):
        df_meteo_oberwallis_data_small2.loc[index,'Luftdruckaenderung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa'] = np.nan
        #print('nan', press1, press2)

```

```

else:
    df_meteo_oberwallis_data_small2.loc[index, 'Luftdruckaenderung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa'] = press1 -
press2
    #print('Luftdruckaenderung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa: ', df_meteo_oberwallis_data_small2.loc[in-
dex, 'Luftdruckaenderung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa'])

else:
    #print('New Station', df_meteo_oberwallis_data_small2.loc[index, 'Station'])
    press1 = df_meteo_oberwallis_data_small2.loc[index, 'Luftdruck_Barometerhoehe_QFE_Stundenmittel_hPa']
    #print('New Station: press1: ', press1)
    if math.isnan(press1):
        df_meteo_oberwallis_data_small2.loc[index, 'Luftdruckaenderung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa'] = np.nan
    else:
        df_meteo_oberwallis_data_small2.loc[index, 'Luftdruckaenderung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa'] = 0
        #print('Luftdruckaenderung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa', df_meteo_oberwallis_data_small2.loc[index, 'Luft-
druckaenderung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa'] )
        last_station = df_meteo_oberwallis_data_small2.loc[index, 'Station']

# In[502]:
df_meteo_oberwallis_data_small2

# In[503]:
df_meteo_oberwallis_data_small2.set_index('UTC')
df_meteo_oberwallis_data_small[['Luftdruckaenderung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa']] = df_meteo_oberwal-
lis_data_small2[['Luftdruckaenderung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa']].copy()

# In[504]:
df_meteo_oberwallis_data_small.info()

# In[505]:
# write df_new to csv output
print('write df to csv output')
df_meteo_oberwallis_data_small.to_csv(path_to_output + 'MeteoOberwallis_Data_small.csv', index = False)
print(' -- successfull \n')

# DATAMERGING - MeteoSchweiz (small) and MeteoOberwallis small
# -----

# In[506]:
print('Import CSV')
path_ms_data = path_to_output + 'MeteoSchweiz_Data_small.csv'
print(' -- successfull \n')
print('Creating Pandas Dataframe:MeteoSchweiz_Data_small')
df_meteo_schweiz_data_small = pd.DataFrame(pd.read_csv(path_ms_data, sep=',', low_memory=False))
print(' -- successfull \n')

# In[507]:
df_meteo_schweiz_data_small.info()

# In[508]:
df_full_small = pd.DataFrame()

# In[509]:
df_full_small = df_meteo_schweiz_data_small.append(df_meteo_oberwallis_data_small)

# In[510]:
df_full_small.info()

# In[511]:
df_full_small['UTC1'] = df_full_small['UTC'].copy()

# In[512]:
df_full_small.set_index('UTC1')

# In[513]:
df_full_small

# In[514]:
df_full_small = df_full_small.reset_index()

# In[515]:
del df_full_small['index']
df_full_small

```

```

# In[516]:
# write df_new to csv output
print('write df to csv output')
df_full_small.to_csv(path_to_output + 'Weather_Data_small.csv', index = False)
print(' -- successfull \n')

# In[517]:
del df_full_small

```

9.2.3. 03_Rotwildmonitoring_Calculations_final.ipynb

```

#!/usr/bin/env python
# coding: utf-8

# In[ ]:
print('Import Libraries')
import os
import ipyparallel as ipp
import ipyparallel

# attach to a running cluster

rc = ipp.Client()
ar = rc[:].apply_async(os.getpid)
pid_map = ar.get_dict()
print('profile:', rc.profile)
print("IDs:", rc.ids) # Print process id numbers
dview = rc[:]

import pandas as pd
print('Pandas imported')
import numpy as np
print('Numpy imported')
print(' -- successfull \n')

#gc.collect() explicitly frees memory space.
import gc

from multiprocessing import set_start_method
set_start_method("spawn")
from multiprocessing import get_context

import time
from multiprocessing import Pool
from multiprocessing.pool import ThreadPool

import multiprocessing as mp
get_ipython().system('python --version')
import platform
print(platform.platform())
print("cpu cores: {0}".format(mp.cpu_count()))
processes = mp.cpu_count()

print('Import Libraries for geografic transformations')
print('import os \n import geopandas \n import shapely \n import pyreproj \n import pyproj \n import col-
lections \n import ogr, osr \n import osgeo')

import geopandas as gpd
import shapely
import pyreproj
import pyproj
import collections
import ogr, osr
import osgeo
from shapely import wkt
print(' -- successfull \n')

print('Import Math and Itertools')
print('import math \n import itertools \n from itertools import islice')
import math
import itertools
from itertools import islice
print(' -- successfull \n')

print('Import Scikit Learn and matplotlib for statistics and plots')
print('import sklearn \n from sklearn import linear_model \n import matplotlib \n import matplotlib.pyplot as
plt \n %matplotlib inline')
import sklearn
from sklearn import linear_model

```

```

import matplotlib
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
get_ipython().run_line_magic('matplotlib', 'inline')
print(' -- successfull \n')

print('Options to show full pandas dataframe \n')
#pd.set_option('display.max_rows', None)
#pd.set_option('display.max_columns', None)
#pd.set_option('display.width', None)
#pd.set_option('display.max_colwidth', None)

print('Set display of dataframe to max columns')
pd.set_option('display.max_columns', None)
print(' -- successfull \n')

# In [ ]:
path_to_output = r'D:\info\Downloads\CAS_ETH_Spatial_Information_Systems\Rotwildmonitoring\output\'

# In [ ]:
df1 = pd.DataFrame()
df2 = pd.DataFrame()

# In [ ]:
get_ipython().run_cell_magic('timeit', '', "\nglobal df1, df2\npath1 = path_to_output +
'Weather_Data_small.csv'\npath2 = path_to_output + 'GPS_small.csv'\nlist_paths = [path1, path2]\n\n# wrap csv
importer in a function that can be mapped\ndef read_csv(path):\n    'converts a filename to a pandas data-
frame'\n    return pd.read_csv(path, low_memory=False)\n\ndef main():\n    # set up your pool\n    with Thread-
Pool(processes) as pool:\n    # or whatever your hardware can support\n\n        # have your pool map the file names
to dataframes\n        df_list = pool.map(read_csv, list_paths)\n        df1 = df_list[0]\n        df2 =
df_list[1]\n    return df1, df2\n\nif __name__ == '__main__':\n    df1, df2 = main()\n    ")

# In [ ]:
df_weather = df1
df_gps = df2
del df1
del df2
gc.collect()

# In [ ]:
df_weather.info()

# In [ ]:
df_gps.info()

# In [ ]:
df_weather['UTC1'] = pd.to_datetime(df_weather['UTC1'])
df_weather['UTC'] = pd.to_datetime(df_weather['UTC'])

# In [ ]:
df_gps['UTC1'] = pd.to_datetime(df_gps['UTC1'])
df_gps['UTC'] = pd.to_datetime(df_gps['UTC'])

# In [ ]:
df_weather['rel_Luftfeuchtigkeit_Stundenmittel_prozent'] = df_weather['rel_Luftfeuchtigkeit_Stundenmittel_pro-
zent'].astype(float)
df_weather['Taupunkt_Momentanwert_celsius'] = df_weather['Taupunkt_Momentanwert_celsius'].astype(float)

# In [ ]:
df_gps.info()

# In [ ]:
df_weather.info()

# In [ ]:
df_weather['Index'] = df_weather['Unnamed: 0'].copy()
del df_weather['Unnamed: 0']

# In [ ]:
df_gps

# In [ ]:
df_weather['Weather_Unix_Timestamp'] = df_weather['UTC'].view('int64')

```

```

df_gps['GPS_Unix_Timestamp'] = df_gps['UTC'].view('int64')

# Temperature_AS_L = (Height * 0.0065) + Temperature_At_Height

# In[ ]:
df_weather['Temp_2mAGL_C']

# In[ ]:
df_weather['Hoehe_AS_L_m']

# In[ ]:
def temp_asl_formula(Hoehe_AGL_m,Temp_2mAGL_C):
    Temp_AS_L = (Hoehe_AGL_m * 0.0065) + Temp_2mAGL_C
    return Temp_AS_L

def temp_agl_formula(Hoehe_AGL_m,Temp_2mASL_C):
    Temp_AGL = (-1) * (Hoehe_AGL_m * 0.0065) + Temp_2mASL_C
    return Temp_AGL

# In[ ]:
df_weather['CALCULATED_temp_asl_C'] = temp_asl_formula(df_weather.Hoehe_AS_L_m,df_weather.Temp_2mAGL_C)
df_weather['CALCULATED_temp_asl_C']

# https://integritext.net/DrKFS/correctiontosealevel.htm
# https://de.wikipedia.org/wiki/Barometrische_H%C3%B6henformel

# Wikipedia:
# Falls eine höhere Genauigkeit gewünscht ist, aktuelle Lufttemperaturen zur Verfügung stehen und Genauigkeit
sowie Kalibrierung des verwendeten Barometers den Aufwand rechtfertigen, sollte die Reduktion stets unter Ver-
wendung der aktuellen Lufttemperatur erfolgen. Als Höhenformel bietet sich die Variante für linearen Tempera-
turverlauf an. Es kann aber ebenso gut die Variante für konstanten Temperaturverlauf verwendet werden, sofern
die auf halber Stationshöhe herrschende aktuelle Temperatur eingesetzt wird:
#
# Diese Variante ist zwar theoretisch etwas weniger genau, da sie die Veränderlichkeit der Temperatur mit der
Höhe ignoriert, während die lineare Variante diese zumindest ansatzweise berücksichtigt. Bei den für Wettersta-
tionen üblicherweise vorkommenden Höhen und Temperaturen sind die Unterschiede jedoch völlig unbedeutend.

# ![barometrische%20h%C3%B6henformel.svg](attachment:barometrische%20h%C3%B6henformel.svg)
# Dabei ist
#
# M die mittlere molare Masse der Atmosphärgase (0,02896 kg mol-1),
# g die Schwerebeschleunigung (9,807 m s-2),
# R die universelle Gaskonstante (8,314 J K-1 mol-1) und
# T die absolute Temperatur.

# In[ ]:
def barometric_formula_pressure_at_sealevel(p_h,height,Temp_at_height):
    p_0 = (p_h*(math.exp((0.02896 * 9.807*height)/(8.314 *((Temp_at_height+273.15) + (0.0065*(height/2)))))))
    #print(p_0)
    return p_0

# In[ ]:
def barometric_formula_convert_AS_L_to_pressure_at_height(p_0,height,Temp_at_height):
    p_h = p_0 / (math.exp((0.02896 * 9.807*height)/(8.314 *((Temp_at_height+273.15) + (0.0065*(height/2))))))
    #print(p_h)
    return p_h

# In[ ]:
df_weather['Hoehe_AS_L_m'] = df_weather.Hoehe_AS_L_m.astype(float)
df_weather['Luftdruck_Barometerhoehe_QFE_Stundenmittel_hPa'] = df_weather.Luftdruck_Barometerhoehe_QFE_Stunden-
mittel_hPa.astype(float)
df_weather['Temp_2mAGL_C'] = df_weather.Temp_2mAGL_C.astype(float)

# In[ ]:
df_weather['CALCULATED_pressure_asl_hPa'] = np.vectorize(barometric_formula_pres-
sure_at_sealevel)(df_weather.Luftdruck_Barometerhoehe_QFE_Stundenmit-
tel_hPa,df_weather.Hoehe_AS_L_m,df_weather.Temp_2mAGL_C)

# https://iridl.ldeo.columbia.edu/dochelp/QA/Basic/dewpoint.html
#
# If you are interested in a simpler calculation that gives an approximation of dew point temperature if you
know the observed temperature and relative humidity, the following formula was proposed in a 2005 article by
Mark G. Lawrence in the Bulletin of the American Meteorological Society:
#
# Td = T - ((100 - RH)/5.)
#

```

```

# where Td is dew point temperature (in degrees Celsius), T is observed temperature (in degrees Celsius), and
RH is relative humidity (in percent). Apparently this relationship is fairly accurate for relative humidity
values above 50%.
#
# More details can be found in the article:
#
# Lawrence, Mark G., 2005: The relationship between relative humidity and the dewpoint temperature in moist
air: A simple conversion and applications. Bull. Amer. Meteor. Soc., 86, 225-233. doi:
http://dx.doi.org/10.1175/BAMS-86-2-225

# In[ ]:

def dewpoint_asl_formula(temp_asl, rel_hum_percent):
    dewpoint_AS_L = temp_asl - ((100 - rel_hum_percent)/5)
    return dewpoint_AS_L

def dewpoint_agl_transpose(dewpoint_asl,height_agl):
    dewpoint_AGL = dewpoint_asl - (height_agl * 0.0065)
    return dewpoint_AGL

# In[ ]:
df_weather['CALCULATED_dewpoint_asl_C'] = np.vectorize(dewpoint_asl_formula)(df_weather.CALCU-
LATED_temp_asl_C,df_weather.rel_Luftfeuchtigkeit_Stundenmittel_prozent)

# In[ ]:
df_weather

# In[ ]:
path1 = path_to_output + 'Weather_Data_small.csv'

# In[ ]:
df_weather.to_csv(path1)

# In[ ]:
df = pd.DataFrame()

# In[ ]:
df = df_gps

# In[ ]:
del df_gps

# In[ ]:
gc.collect()

# In[ ]:
df

# In[ ]:
df['INTERPOL_POINT_temp_asl_C'] = np.nan
df['INTERPOL_POINT_temp_AGL_C'] = np.nan

df['INTERPOL_POINT_dewpoint_AS_L_C'] = np.nan
df['INTERPOL_POINT_dewpoint_AGL_C'] = np.nan

df['INTERPOL_POINT_pressure_asl_hPa'] = np.nan
df['INTERPOL_POINT_pressure_AGL_hPa'] = np.nan

df['INTERPOL_POINT_rel_Luftfeuchtigkeit_Stundenmittel_prozent'] = np.nan
df['INTERPOL_POINT_Luftdruckaenderung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa'] = np.nan
df['INTERPOL_POINT_Niederschlag_Stundensumme_mm'] = np.nan
df['INTERPOL_POINT_Neuschnee_Momentanwert_cm'] = np.nan
df['INTERPOL_POINT_Schneehoehe_Momentanwert_cm'] = np.nan

df['INTERPOL_POINT_Windgeschwindigkeit_ms'] = np.nan
df['INTERPOL_POINT_Windrichtung_grad'] = np.nan
df['INTERPOL_POINT_Foehnindex'] = np.nan

df['INTERPOL_POINT_Globalstrahlung_wm2'] = np.nan
df['INTERPOL_POINT_sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min'] = np.nan

# In[ ]:
df['Weight_BIN'] = np.nan
df['Weight_EGH'] = np.nan
df['Weight_JUN'] = np.nan

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df['Weight_SIM'] = np.nan
df['Weight_SLFBEL'] = np.nan
df['Weight_SLFBOR'] = np.nan
df['Weight_SLFEGH'] = np.nan
df['Weight_SLFGO2'] = np.nan
df['Weight_SLFGO3'] = np.nan
df['Weight_SLFMU2'] = np.nan
df['Weight_SLFOB2'] = np.nan
df['Weight_SLFOB3'] = np.nan
df['Weight_SLFOBW'] = np.nan
df['Weight_SLFSP2'] = np.nan
df['Weight_SLFSP3'] = np.nan
df['Weight_ULR'] = np.nan
df['Weight_VIS'] = np.nan
df['Weight_VSBRB'] = np.nan
df['Weight_WSLVSB'] = np.nan
df['Weight_WSLVSF'] = np.nan
df['Weight_MOBELLW'] = np.nan
df['Weight_MOBETT'] = np.nan
df['Weight_MOBINN'] = np.nan
df['Weight_MOBLITZINGU'] = np.nan
df['Weight_MOBRIG'] = np.nan
df['Weight_MOCHAES'] = np.nan
df['Weight_MODEISCH'] = np.nan
df['Weight_MOFIESCH'] = np.nan
df['Weight_MOGRIMSEL'] = np.nan
df['Weight_MONAT'] = np.nan
df['Weight_MORIEDA'] = np.nan
df['Weight_MORIEDF'] = np.nan
df['Weight_MOSIMP'] = np.nan

# In[ ]:
df['GPS_TierID'] = df['TierID']
del df['TierID']

df['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] = df['timestamp_cleaned']
del df['timestamp_cleaned']

df['GPS_Temp'] = df['Temp']
del df['Temp']

df['GPS_Temp_Class'] = df['Temp_Class']
del df['Temp_Class']

df['GPS_ActivitySum'] = df['ActivitySum']
del df['ActivitySum']

df['GPS_Components'] = df['Components']
del df['Components']

df['GPS_ActivityMean'] = df['ActivityMean']
del df['ActivityMean']

df['GPS_twilight_dawn_cleaned'] = df['twilight_dawn_cleaned']
del df['twilight_dawn_cleaned']

df['GPS_sunrise_cleaned'] = df['sunrise_cleaned']
del df['sunrise_cleaned']

df['GPS_sunset_cleaned'] = df['sunset_cleaned']
del df['sunset_cleaned']

df['GPS_twilight_dusk_cleaned'] = df['twilight_dusk_cleaned']
del df['twilight_dusk_cleaned']

df['GPS_WGS84_Breite'] = df['WGS84_Breite']
del df['WGS84_Breite']

df['GPS_WGS84_Laenge'] = df['WGS84_Laenge']
del df['WGS84_Laenge']

df['GPS_EPSG2056_lat'] = df['EPSG2056_lat']
del df['EPSG2056_lat']

df['GPS_EPSG2056_lon'] = df['EPSG2056_lon']
del df['EPSG2056_lon']

df['GPS_Hoehe_AS_L_m_DEM'] = df['Hoehe_AS_L_m_DEM']
del df['Hoehe_AS_L_m_DEM']

df['GPS_Hoehe_AS_L_m'] = df['Hoehe_AS_L_m']
del df['Hoehe_AS_L_m']

```

```

df['GPS_DISTANCE_X'] = df['DISTANCE_X']
del df['DISTANCE_X']

df['GPS_DISTANCE_Y'] = df['DISTANCE_Y']
del df['DISTANCE_Y']

df['GPS_DISTANCE_Z'] = df['DISTANCE_Z']
del df['DISTANCE_Z']

df['GPS_DISTANCE_ABSOLUTE'] = df['DISTANCE_ABSOLUTE']
del df['DISTANCE_ABSOLUTE']

df['GPS_V_MproS'] = df['V_MproS']
del df['V_MproS']

df['GPS_Tier_Name'] = df['Name']
del df['Name']

df['GPS_CollarID'] = df['CollarID']
del df['CollarID']

df['GPS_No'] = df['No']
del df['No']

df['GPS_Tier_Ohrmarke'] = df['Ohrmarke']
del df['Ohrmarke']

df['GPS_Tier_Gebiet'] = df['Gebiet']
del df['Gebiet']

df['GPS_Tier_Geschlecht'] = df['Geschlecht']
del df['Geschlecht']

df['GPS_DEM_Height_Difference'] = df['Height_Difference']
del df['Height_Difference']

df['GPS_V_KMproH'] = df['V_KMproH']
del df['V_KMproH']
df['GPS_V_MproH'] = df['V_MproH']
del df['V_MproH']

df['GPS_Abgeschlossen'] = df['Abgeschlossen']
del df['Abgeschlossen']
df['GPS_DOP'] = df['DOP']
del df['DOP']
df['GPS_DatenEndeMonat'] = df['DatenEndeMonat']
del df['DatenEndeMonat']
df['GPS_Einstand_2month'] = df['Einstand_2month']
del df['Einstand_2month']
df['GPS_FixType'] = df['FixType']
del df['FixType']

df['GPS_Status'] = df['Status']
del df['Status']
df['GPS_Status2'] = df['Status2']
del df['Status2']
df['GPS_Stop2Datum'] = df['Stop2Datum']
del df['Stop2Datum']

df['GPS_StartDatum'] = df['StartDatum']
del df['StartDatum']
df['GPS_StartMonat'] = df['StartMonat']
del df['StartMonat']
df['GPS_StartJahr'] = df['StartJahr']
del df['StartJahr']

df['GPS_StopJahr'] = df['StopJahr']
del df['StopJahr']

df['GPS_StopMonat'] = df['StopMonat']
del df['StopMonat']
df['GPS_Start2Datum'] = df['Start2Datum']
del df['Start2Datum']
df['GPS_Start2Monat'] = df['Start2Monat']
del df['Start2Monat']

df['GPS_Start2Jahr'] = df['Start2Jahr']
del df['Start2Jahr']
df['GPS_Stop2Monat'] = df['Stopp2Monat']
del df['Stopp2Monat']
df['GPS_Stop2Jahr'] = df['Stopp2Jahr']
del df['Stopp2Jahr']

df['GPS_StopDatum'] = df['StopDatum']
del df['StopDatum']

df['GPS_x'] = df['x']

```

```

del df['x']
df['GPS_y'] = df['y']
del df['y']
df

# In[ ]:
df = df.sort_index(axis=1)
df

# df['GPS_Unix_Timestamp'] = df['Unix_Timestamp']

# In[ ]:
df_cols = df.columns.tolist()

# In[ ]:
df_cols

# In[ ]:
cols = [ 'GPS_TierID', 'GPS_Tier_Geschlecht', 'GPS_Tier_Name', 'GPS_Tier_Ohrmarke', 'GPS_Tier_Gebiet', 'GPS_Ein-
stand_2month',
'GPS_EPSG2056_lat', 'GPS_EPSG2056_lon', 'GPS_x', 'GPS_y', 'GPS_WGS84_Breite', 'GPS_WGS84_Laenge',
'GPS_Hoehe_ASL_m_DEM', 'GPS_Hoehe_ASL_m', 'GPS_DEM_Height_Difference',
'GPS_DISTANCE_ABSOLUTE', 'GPS_DISTANCE_X', 'GPS_DISTANCE_Y', 'GPS_DISTANCE_Z',
'GPS_V_KMproH', 'GPS_V_MproH', 'GPS_V_MproS',

'UTC', 'UTC1', 'GPS_timestamp_cleaned', 'GPS_Unix_Timestamp', 'year', 'Month', 'Day', 'Hour',
'UTC_Date', 'UTC_Time', 'LMT_Date', 'LMT_Time', 'daytime',
'GPS_sunrise_cleaned', 'GPS_sunset_cleaned', 'GPS_twilight_dawn_cleaned', 'GPS_twi-
light_dusk_cleaned', 'Jahreszeit_4season', 'Jahreszeit_Halbjahr',

'GPS_Temp', 'GPS_Temp_Class', 'GPS_ActivityMean', 'GPS_ActivitySum',
'INTERPOL_POINT_Foehnindex',
'INTERPOL_POINT_Globalstrahlung_wm2',
'INTERPOL_POINT_Luftdruckaenderung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa',
'INTERPOL_POINT_Neuschnee_Momentanwert_cm',
'INTERPOL_POINT_Niederschlag_Stundensumme_mm',
'INTERPOL_POINT_Schneehoehe_Momentanwert_cm',
'INTERPOL_POINT_Windgeschwindigkeit_ms',
'INTERPOL_POINT_Windrichtung_grad',
'INTERPOL_POINT_dewpoint_AGL_C',
'INTERPOL_POINT_dewpoint_ASL_C',
'INTERPOL_POINT_pressure_AGL_hPa',
'INTERPOL_POINT_pressure_asl_hPa',
'INTERPOL_POINT_rel_Luftfeuchtigkeit_Stundenmittel_prozent',
'INTERPOL_POINT_sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min',
'INTERPOL_POINT_temp_AGL_C',
'INTERPOL_POINT_temp_asl_C',
'Weight_BIN',
'Weight_EGH',
'Weight_JUN',
'Weight_MOBELLW',
'Weight_MOBETT',
'Weight_MOBINN',
'Weight_MOBLITZINGU',
'Weight_MOBRIG',
'Weight_MOCHAES',
'Weight_MODEISCH',
'Weight_MOFIESCH',
'Weight_MOGRIMSEL',
'Weight_MONAT',
'Weight_MORIEDA',
'Weight_MORIEDF',
'Weight_MOSIMP',
'Weight_SIM',
'Weight_SLFBEL',
'Weight_SLFBOR',
'Weight_SLFEGH',
'Weight_SLFGO2',
'Weight_SLFGO3',
'Weight_SLFMU2',
'Weight_SLFOB2',
'Weight_SLFOB3',
'Weight_SLFOBW',
'Weight_SLFSP2',
'Weight_SLFSP3',
'Weight_ULR',
'Weight_VIS',
'Weight_VSBRB',
'Weight_WSLVSB',
'Weight_WSLVSF',
'GPS_CollarID', 'GPS_No', 'GPS_Components', 'GPS_DOP', 'GPS_FixType', 'GPS_Abgeschlossen', 'GPS_DatenEndeMonat',
'GPS_StartDatum', 'GPS_StartJahr', 'GPS_StartMonat', 'GPS_StopDatum', 'GPS_StopJahr', 'GPS_StopMonat', 'GPS_Status',

```

```

'GPS_Start2Datum','GPS_Start2Jahr','GPS_Start2Monat', 'GPS_Stop2Datum', 'GPS_Stop2Jahr', 'GPS_Stop2Mon-
at','GPS_Status2',

]

# In[ ]:
df = df[cols]
df.info()

# In[ ]:
station_cols = ['Station','Name','EPSG2056_lat','EPSG2056_lon','Hoehe_ASL_m']
df_stations = df_weather[station_cols]

# In[ ]:
df_stations_group = df_stations.groupby(['Station'])
df_stations = df_stations_group.first()

# In[ ]:
df_stations = df_stations.reset_index()

# In[ ]:
df_stations = df_stations.sort_values(by=['Station'])

# In[ ]:
df_stations

# In[ ]:
df

# In[ ]:
def euclidian_distance(x1,x2,y1,y2,z1,z2):
    dist = math.sqrt(math.pow(x1-x2,2)+math.pow(y1-y2,2)+math.pow(z1-z2,2))
    return dist

# In[ ]:
df

# In[ ]:
df_stations

# In[ ]:
df.iloc[[1],[int(61)]]

# In[ ]:
df.iloc[[1],[int(61+10)]]

# In[ ]:
for row in df_stations.itertuples():
    row_station = int(row.Index)
    for row in df.itertuples():
        row_gps = row.Index
        lat1 = df.iat[row_gps,6]
        lon1 = df.iat[row_gps,7]
        height1 = df.iat[row_gps,12]
        lat2 = df_stations.iat[row_station,2]
        lon2 = df_stations.iat[row_station,3]
        height2 = df_stations.iat[row_station,4]
        dist = euclidian_distance(lat1,lat2,lon1,lon2,height1,height2)
        weight = float(1/dist)
        df.iloc[[row_gps],[int(61+row_station)]] = weight

# # codeblock to insert df_weights without weight computation above
#
# path2 = path_to_output + 'Weights.csv'
#
# df_weights = pd.read_csv(path2)
#
# df = df_weights.merge(df, left_on=df_weights.index, right_on=df.index)
#
# df['Weight_BIN'] = df['Weight_BIN_x']
# del df['Weight_BIN_x']

```

```

# df['Weight_EGH'] = df['Weight_EGH_x']
# del df['Weight_EGH_x']
#
# df['Weight_JUN'] = df['Weight_JUN_x']
# del df['Weight_JUN_x']
# df['Weight_SIM'] = df['Weight_SIM_x']
# del df['Weight_SIM_x']
#
# df['Weight_SLFBEL'] = df['Weight_SLFBEL_x']
# del df['Weight_SLFBEL_x']
# df['Weight_SLFBOR'] = df['Weight_SLFBOR_x']
# del df['Weight_SLFBOR_x']
#
# df['Weight_SLFEGH'] = df['Weight_SLFEGH_x']
# del df['Weight_SLFEGH_x']
# df['Weight_SLFGO2'] = df['Weight_SLFGO2_x']
# del df['Weight_SLFGO2_x']
#
# df['Weight_SLFGO3'] = df['Weight_SLFGO3_x']
# del df['Weight_SLFGO3_x']
# df['Weight_SLFMU2'] = df['Weight_SLFMU2_x']
# del df['Weight_SLFMU2_x']
#
# df['Weight_SLFOB2'] = df['Weight_SLFOB2_x']
# del df['Weight_SLFOB2_x']
# df['Weight_SLFOB3'] = df['Weight_SLFOB3_x']
# del df['Weight_SLFOB3_x']
#
# df['Weight_SLFOBW'] = df['Weight_SLFOBW_x']
# del df['Weight_SLFOBW_x']
# df['Weight_SLFSP2'] = df['Weight_SLFSP2_x']
# del df['Weight_SLFSP2_x']
#
# df['Weight_SLFSP3'] = df['Weight_SLFSP3_x']
# del df['Weight_SLFSP3_x']
# df['Weight_ULR'] = df['Weight_ULR_x']
# del df['Weight_ULR_x']
#
# df['Weight_VIS'] = df['Weight_VIS_x']
# del df['Weight_VIS_x']
# df['Weight_VSBRB'] = df['Weight_VSBRB_x']
# del df['Weight_VSBRB_x']
#
# df['Weight_WSLVSB'] = df['Weight_WSLVSB_x']
# del df['Weight_WSLVSB_x']
# df['Weight_WSLVSF'] = df['Weight_WSLVSF_x']
# del df['Weight_WSLVSF_x']
#
# df['Weight_MOBELLW'] = df['Weight_MOBELLW_x']
# del df['Weight_MOBELLW_x']
# df['Weight_MOBETT'] = df['Weight_MOBETT_x']
# del df['Weight_MOBETT_x']
#
# df['Weight_MOBINN'] = df['Weight_MOBINN_x']
# del df['Weight_MOBINN_x']
# df['Weight_MOBLITZINGU'] = df['Weight_MOBLITZINGU_x']
# del df['Weight_MOBLITZINGU_x']
#
# df['Weight_MOBRIG'] = df['Weight_MOBRIG_x']
# del df['Weight_MOBRIG_x']
# df['Weight_MOCHAES'] = df['Weight_MOCHAES_x']
# del df['Weight_MOCHAES_x']
#
# df['Weight_MODEISCH'] = df['Weight_MODEISCH_x']
# del df['Weight_MODEISCH_x']
# df['Weight_MOFIESCH'] = df['Weight_MOFIESCH_x']
# del df['Weight_MOFIESCH_x']
#
# df['Weight_MOGRIMSEL'] = df['Weight_MOGRIMSEL_x']
# del df['Weight_MOGRIMSEL_x']
# df['Weight_MONAT'] = df['Weight_MONAT_x']
# del df['Weight_MONAT_x']
#
# df['Weight_MORIEDA'] = df['Weight_MORIEDA_x']
# del df['Weight_MORIEDA_x']
# df['Weight_MORIEDF'] = df['Weight_MORIEDF_x']
# del df['Weight_MORIEDF_x']
#
# df['Weight_MOSIMP'] = df['Weight_MOSIMP_x']
# del df['Weight_MOSIMP_x']
#
# del df['Weight_BIN_y']
# del df['Weight_EGH_y']
#
# del df['Weight_JUN_y']
# del df['Weight_SIM_y']
#

```

```

# del df['Weight_SLFBEL_y']
# del df['Weight_SLFBOR_y']
#
# del df['Weight_SLFEGH_y']
# del df['Weight_SLFGO2_y']
#
# del df['Weight_SLFGO3_y']
# del df['Weight_SLFMU2_y']
#
# del df['Weight_SLFOB2_y']
# del df['Weight_SLFOB3_y']
#
# del df['Weight_SLFOBW_y']
# del df['Weight_SLFSP2_y']
#
# del df['Weight_SLFSP3_y']
# del df['Weight_ULR_y']
#
# del df['Weight_VIS_y']
# del df['Weight_VSBRB_y']
#
# del df['Weight_WSLVSB_y']
# del df['Weight_WSLVSF_y']
#
# del df['Weight_MOBELLW_y']
# del df['Weight_MOBETT_y']
#
# del df['Weight_MOBINN_y']
# del df['Weight_MOBLITZINGU_y']
#
# del df['Weight_MOBRIG_y']
# del df['Weight_MOCHAES_y']
#
# del df['Weight_MODEISCH_y']
# del df['Weight_MOFIESCH_y']
#
# del df['Weight_MOGRIMSEL_y']
# del df['Weight_MONAT_y']
#
# del df['Weight_MORIEDA_y']
# del df['Weight_MORIEDF_y']
#
# del df['Weight_MOSIMP_y']
#
# del df['key_0']
# del df['Unnamed: 0']

# In[ ]:
df

# In[ ]:

path_gps_weights = path_to_output + 'GPS_Weights_Data.csv'

# In[ ]:
df.to_csv(path_gps_weights)

# In[ ]:
del df_stations

# In[ ]:
gc.collect()

# In[ ]:
df =pd.read_csv(path_gps_weights)

# df['INTERPOL_POINT_Neuschnee_Momentanwert_cm'] = df['INTERPOL_POINT_Neuschnee_Stundensumme_mm'].copy()
# del df['INTERPOL_POINT_Neuschnee_Stundensumme_mm']
# df['INTERPOL_POINT_Schneehoehe_Momentanwert_cm'] = df['INTERPOL_POINT_Schneehoehe_Stundensumme_mm'].copy()
# del df['INTERPOL_POINT_Schneehoehe_Stundensumme_mm']

# In[ ]:
weight_cols= ['Weight_BIN',
'Weight_EGH',
'Weight_JUN',
'Weight_SIM',
'Weight_SLFBEL',
'Weight_SLFBOR',
'Weight_SLFEGH',
'Weight_SLFGO2',
'Weight_SLFGO3',
'Weight_SLFMU2',

```

```

'Weight_SLFOB2',
'Weight_SLFOB3',
'Weight_SLFOBW',
'Weight_SLFSP2',
'Weight_SLFSP3',
'Weight_ULR',
'Weight_VIS',
'Weight_VSBRB',
'Weight_WSLVSB',
'Weight_WSLVSF',
'Weight_MOBELLW',
'Weight_MOBETT',
'Weight_MOBINN',
'Weight_MOBLITZINGU',
'Weight_MOBRIG',
'Weight_MOCHAES',
'Weight_MODEISCH',
'Weight_MOFIESCH',
'Weight_MOGRIMSEL',
'Weight_MONAT',
'Weight_MORIEDA',
'Weight_MORIEDF',
'Weight_MOSIMP',
]

# In[ ]:
df_gps_weights = df[weight_cols]

# In[ ]:
df_gps_weights

# In[ ]:
path2 = path_to_output + 'Weights.csv'

df_gps_weights.to_csv(path2)

# In[ ]:
del df_gps_weights
gc.collect()

# In[ ]:
df_weather

# In[ ]:
idw_cols = [ 'GPS_TierID', 'GPS_Tier_Geschlecht', 'GPS_Tier_Name', 'GPS_Tier_Ohrmarke', 'GPS_Tier_Gebiet',
'GPS_Einstand_2month',
'GPS_EPSG2056_lat', 'GPS_EPSG2056_lon', 'GPS_x', 'GPS_y', 'GPS_WGS84_Breite', 'GPS_WGS84_Laenge',
'GPS_Hoehe_ASL_m_DEM', 'GPS_Hoehe_ASL_m', 'GPS_DEM_Height_Difference',
'GPS_DISTANCE_ABSOLUTE', 'GPS_DISTANCE_X', 'GPS_DISTANCE_Y', 'GPS_DISTANCE_Z',
'GPS_V_KMproH', 'GPS_V_MproH', 'GPS_V_MproS',

'UTC', 'UTC1', 'GPS_timestamp_cleaned', 'GPS_Unix_Timestamp', 'year', 'Month', 'Day', 'Hour',
'UTC_Date', 'UTC_Time', 'LMT_Date', 'LMT_Time', 'daytime',
'GPS_sunrise_cleaned', 'GPS_sunset_cleaned', 'GPS_twilight_dawn_cleaned', 'GPS_twi-
light_dusk_cleaned', 'Jahreszeit_4season', 'Jahreszeit_Halbjahr',

'GPS_Temp', 'GPS_Temp_Class', 'GPS_ActivityMean', 'GPS_ActivitySum',
'INTERPOL_POINT_Foehnindex',
'INTERPOL_POINT_Globalstrahlung_wm2',
'INTERPOL_POINT_Luftdruckaenderung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa',
'INTERPOL_POINT_Neuschnee_Momentanwert_cm',
'INTERPOL_POINT_Niederschlag_Stundensumme_mm',
'INTERPOL_POINT_Schneehoehe_Momentanwert_cm',
'INTERPOL_POINT_Windgeschwindigkeit_ms',
'INTERPOL_POINT_Windrichtung_grad',
'INTERPOL_POINT_dewpoint_AGL_C',
'INTERPOL_POINT_dewpoint_ASL_C',
'INTERPOL_POINT_pressure_AGL_hPa',
'INTERPOL_POINT_pressure_asl_hPa',
'INTERPOL_POINT_rel_Luftfeuchtigkeit_Stundenmittel_prozent',
'INTERPOL_POINT_sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min',
'INTERPOL_POINT_temp_AGL_C',
'INTERPOL_POINT_temp_asl_C',

'Weight_BIN',
'Weight_EGH',
'Weight_JUN',
'Weight_MOBELLW',
'Weight_MOBETT',

```

```
'Weight_MOBINN',
'Weight_MOBLITZINGU',
'Weight_MOBRIG',
'Weight_MOCHAES',
'Weight_MODEISCH',
'Weight_MOFIESCH',
'Weight_MOGRIMSEL',
'Weight_MONAT',
'Weight_MORIEDA',
'Weight_MORIEDF',
'Weight_MOSIMP',
'Weight_SIM',
'Weight_SLFBEL',
'Weight_SLFBOR',
'Weight_SLFEGH',
'Weight_SLFGO2',
'Weight_SLFGO3',
'Weight_SLFMU2',
'Weight_SLFOB2',
'Weight_SLFOB3',
'Weight_SLFOBW',
'Weight_SLFSP2',
'Weight_SLFSP3',
'Weight_ULR',
'Weight_VIS',
'Weight_VSBRB',
'Weight_WSLVSB',
'Weight_WSLVSF',
'GPS_CollarID', 'GPS_No', 'GPS_Components', 'GPS_DOP', 'GPS_FixType', 'GPS_Abgeschlossen', 'GPS_DatenEndeMonat',
'GPS_StartDatum', 'GPS_StartJahr', 'GPS_StartMonat', 'GPS_StopDatum', 'GPS_StopJahr', 'GPS_StopMonat', 'GPS_Status',
'GPS_Start2Datum', 'GPS_Start2Jahr', 'GPS_Start2Monat', 'GPS_Stop2Datum', 'GPS_Stop2Jahr', 'GPS_Stop2Mon-
at', 'GPS_Status2',
```

```
]
```

```
# In[ ]:
df_idw = df[idw_cols]
```

```
# In[ ]:
df_idw
```

```
# In[ ]:
path3 = path_to_output + 'IDW.csv'
```

```
# In[ ]:
df_idw.to_csv(path3)
```

```
# In[ ]:
df_idw = pd.read_csv(path3)
```

```
# In[ ]:
df_idw['Station_BIN'] = 'BIN'
df_idw['Station_EGH'] = 'EGH'
df_idw['Station_JUN'] = 'JUN'
df_idw['Station_SIM'] = 'SIM'
df_idw['Station_SLFBEL'] = 'SLFBEL'
df_idw['Station_SLFBOR'] = 'SLFBOR'
df_idw['Station_SLFEGH'] = 'SLFEGH'
df_idw['Station_SLFGO2'] = 'SLFGO2'
df_idw['Station_SLFGO3'] = 'SLFGO3'
df_idw['Station_SLFMU2'] = 'SLFMU2'
df_idw['Station_SLFOB2'] = 'SLFOB2'
df_idw['Station_SLFOB3'] = 'SLFOB3'
df_idw['Station_SLFOBW'] = 'SLFOBW'
df_idw['Station_SLFSP2'] = 'SLFSP2'
df_idw['Station_SLFSP3'] = 'SLFSP3'
df_idw['Station_ULR'] = 'ULR'
df_idw['Station_VIS'] = 'VIS'
df_idw['Station_VSBRB'] = 'VSBRB'
df_idw['Station_WSLVSB'] = 'WSLVSB'
df_idw['Station_WSLVSF'] = 'WSLVSF'
df_idw['Station_MOBELLW'] = 'MOBELLW'
df_idw['Station_MOBETT'] = 'MOBETT'
df_idw['Station_MOBINN'] = 'MOBINN'
df_idw['Station_MOBLITZINGU'] = 'MOBLITZINGU'
df_idw['Station_MOBRIG'] = 'MOBRIG'
df_idw['Station_MOCHAES'] = 'MOCHAES'
df_idw['Station_MODEISCH'] = 'MODEISCH'
df_idw['Station_MOFIESCH'] = 'MOFIESCH'
df_idw['Station_MOGRIMSEL'] = 'MOGRIMSEL'
```

```
df_idw['Station_MONAT'] = 'MONAT'  
df_idw['Station_MORIEDA'] = 'MORIEDA'  
df_idw['Station_MORIEDF'] = 'MORIEDF'  
df_idw['Station_MOSIMP'] = 'MOSIMP'
```

```
# In [ ]:
```

```
idw_cols2 = df_idw.columns.tolist()
```

```
# In [ ]:
```

```
idw_cols2
```

```
# In [ ]:
```

```
df_idw['VALUE_BIN_Globalstrahlung_wm2'] = np.nan  
df_idw['VALUE_BIN_Luftdruckaenderung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa'] = np.nan  
df_idw['VALUE_BIN_Niederschlag_Stundensumme_mm'] = np.nan  
df_idw['VALUE_BIN_Windgeschwindigkeit_ms'] = np.nan  
df_idw['VALUE_BIN_Windrichtung_grad'] = np.nan  
df_idw['VALUE_BIN_dewpoint_AGL_C'] = np.nan  
df_idw['VALUE_BIN_dewpoint_AS_L_C'] = np.nan  
df_idw['VALUE_BIN_pressure_AGL_hPa'] = np.nan  
df_idw['VALUE_BIN_pressure_asl_hPa'] = np.nan  
df_idw['VALUE_BIN_rel_Luftfeuchtigkeit_Stundenmittel_prozent'] = np.nan  
df_idw['VALUE_BIN_sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min'] = np.nan  
df_idw['VALUE_BIN_temp_AGL_C'] = np.nan  
df_idw['VALUE_BIN_temp_asl_C'] = np.nan  
df_idw['VALUE_BIN_Neuschnee_Momentanwert_cm'] = np.nan  
df_idw['VALUE_BIN_Schneehoehe_Momentanwert_cm'] = np.nan  
df_idw['VALUE_BIN_Foehnindex'] = np.nan
```

```
df_idw['VALUE_EGH_Globalstrahlung_wm2'] = np.nan  
df_idw['VALUE_EGH_Luftdruckaenderung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa'] = np.nan  
df_idw['VALUE_EGH_Niederschlag_Stundensumme_mm'] = np.nan  
df_idw['VALUE_EGH_Windgeschwindigkeit_ms'] = np.nan  
df_idw['VALUE_EGH_Windrichtung_grad'] = np.nan  
df_idw['VALUE_EGH_dewpoint_AGL_C'] = np.nan  
df_idw['VALUE_EGH_dewpoint_AS_L_C'] = np.nan  
df_idw['VALUE_EGH_pressure_AGL_hPa'] = np.nan  
df_idw['VALUE_EGH_pressure_asl_hPa'] = np.nan  
df_idw['VALUE_EGH_rel_Luftfeuchtigkeit_Stundenmittel_prozent'] = np.nan  
df_idw['VALUE_EGH_sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min'] = np.nan  
df_idw['VALUE_EGH_temp_AGL_C'] = np.nan  
df_idw['VALUE_EGH_temp_asl_C'] = np.nan  
df_idw['VALUE_EGH_Neuschnee_Momentanwert_cm'] = np.nan  
df_idw['VALUE_EGH_Schneehoehe_Momentanwert_cm'] = np.nan  
df_idw['VALUE_EGH_Foehnindex'] = np.nan
```

```
df_idw['VALUE_JUN_Globalstrahlung_wm2'] = np.nan  
df_idw['VALUE_JUN_Luftdruckaenderung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa'] = np.nan  
df_idw['VALUE_JUN_Niederschlag_Stundensumme_mm'] = np.nan  
df_idw['VALUE_JUN_Windgeschwindigkeit_ms'] = np.nan  
df_idw['VALUE_JUN_Windrichtung_grad'] = np.nan  
df_idw['VALUE_JUN_dewpoint_AGL_C'] = np.nan  
df_idw['VALUE_JUN_dewpoint_AS_L_C'] = np.nan  
df_idw['VALUE_JUN_pressure_AGL_hPa'] = np.nan  
df_idw['VALUE_JUN_pressure_asl_hPa'] = np.nan  
df_idw['VALUE_JUN_rel_Luftfeuchtigkeit_Stundenmittel_prozent'] = np.nan  
df_idw['VALUE_JUN_sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min'] = np.nan  
df_idw['VALUE_JUN_temp_AGL_C'] = np.nan  
df_idw['VALUE_JUN_temp_asl_C'] = np.nan  
df_idw['VALUE_JUN_Neuschnee_Momentanwert_cm'] = np.nan  
df_idw['VALUE_JUN_Schneehoehe_Momentanwert_cm'] = np.nan  
df_idw['VALUE_JUN_Foehnindex'] = np.nan
```

```
df_idw['VALUE_MOBELLW_Globalstrahlung_wm2'] = np.nan  
df_idw['VALUE_MOBELLW_Luftdruckaenderung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa'] = np.nan  
df_idw['VALUE_MOBELLW_Niederschlag_Stundensumme_mm'] = np.nan  
df_idw['VALUE_MOBELLW_Windgeschwindigkeit_ms'] = np.nan  
df_idw['VALUE_MOBELLW_Windrichtung_grad'] = np.nan  
df_idw['VALUE_MOBELLW_dewpoint_AGL_C'] = np.nan  
df_idw['VALUE_MOBELLW_dewpoint_AS_L_C'] = np.nan  
df_idw['VALUE_MOBELLW_pressure_AGL_hPa'] = np.nan  
df_idw['VALUE_MOBELLW_pressure_asl_hPa'] = np.nan  
df_idw['VALUE_MOBELLW_rel_Luftfeuchtigkeit_Stundenmittel_prozent'] = np.nan  
df_idw['VALUE_MOBELLW_sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min'] = np.nan  
df_idw['VALUE_MOBELLW_temp_AGL_C'] = np.nan  
df_idw['VALUE_MOBELLW_temp_asl_C'] = np.nan
```

```
df_idw['VALUE_MOBELLW_Neuschnee_Momentanwert_cm'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MOBELLW_Schneehoehe_Momentanwert_cm'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MOBELLW_Foehnindex'] = np.nan
```

```
df_idw['VALUE_MOBETT_Globalstrahlung_wm2'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MOBETT_Luftdruckaenderung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MOBETT_Niederschlag_Stundensumme_mm'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MOBETT_Windgeschwindigkeit_ms'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MOBETT_Windrichtung_grad'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MOBETT_dewpoint_AGL_C'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MOBETT_dewpoint_ASL_C'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MOBETT_pressure_AGL_hPa'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MOBETT_pressure_asl_hPa'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MOBETT_rel_Luftfeuchtigkeit_Stundenmittel_prozent'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MOBETT_sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MOBETT_temp_AGL_C'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MOBETT_temp_asl_C'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MOBETT_Neuschnee_Momentanwert_cm'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MOBETT_Schneehoehe_Momentanwert_cm'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MOBETT_Foehnindex'] = np.nan
```

```
df_idw['VALUE_MOBINN_Globalstrahlung_wm2'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MOBINN_Luftdruckaenderung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MOBINN_Niederschlag_Stundensumme_mm'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MOBINN_Windgeschwindigkeit_ms'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MOBINN_Windrichtung_grad'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MOBINN_dewpoint_AGL_C'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MOBINN_dewpoint_ASL_C'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MOBINN_pressure_AGL_hPa'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MOBINN_pressure_asl_hPa'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MOBINN_rel_Luftfeuchtigkeit_Stundenmittel_prozent'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MOBINN_sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MOBINN_temp_AGL_C'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MOBINN_temp_asl_C'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MOBINN_Neuschnee_Momentanwert_cm'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MOBINN_Schneehoehe_Momentanwert_cm'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MOBINN_Foehnindex'] = np.nan
```

```
df_idw['VALUE_MOBLITZINGU_Globalstrahlung_wm2'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MOBLITZINGU_Luftdruckaenderung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MOBLITZINGU_Niederschlag_Stundensumme_mm'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MOBLITZINGU_Windgeschwindigkeit_ms'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MOBLITZINGU_Windrichtung_grad'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MOBLITZINGU_dewpoint_AGL_C'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MOBLITZINGU_dewpoint_ASL_C'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MOBLITZINGU_pressure_AGL_hPa'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MOBLITZINGU_pressure_asl_hPa'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MOBLITZINGU_rel_Luftfeuchtigkeit_Stundenmittel_prozent'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MOBLITZINGU_sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MOBLITZINGU_temp_AGL_C'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MOBLITZINGU_temp_asl_C'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MOBLITZINGU_Neuschnee_Momentanwert_cm'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MOBLITZINGU_Schneehoehe_Momentanwert_cm'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MOBLITZINGU_Foehnindex'] = np.nan
```

```
df_idw['VALUE_MOBRIG_Globalstrahlung_wm2'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MOBRIG_Luftdruckaenderung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MOBRIG_Niederschlag_Stundensumme_mm'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MOBRIG_Windgeschwindigkeit_ms'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MOBRIG_Windrichtung_grad'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MOBRIG_dewpoint_AGL_C'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MOBRIG_dewpoint_ASL_C'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MOBRIG_pressure_AGL_hPa'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MOBRIG_pressure_asl_hPa'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MOBRIG_rel_Luftfeuchtigkeit_Stundenmittel_prozent'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MOBRIG_sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MOBRIG_temp_AGL_C'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MOBRIG_temp_asl_C'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MOBRIG_Neuschnee_Momentanwert_cm'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MOBRIG_Schneehoehe_Momentanwert_cm'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MOBRIG_Foehnindex'] = np.nan
```

```
df_idw['VALUE_MOCHAES_Globalstrahlung_wm2'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MOCHAES_Luftdruckaenderung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MOCHAES_Niederschlag_Stundensumme_mm'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MOCHAES_Windgeschwindigkeit_ms'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MOCHAES_Windrichtung_grad'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MOCHAES_dewpoint_AGL_C'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MOCHAES_dewpoint_ASL_C'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MOCHAES_pressure_AGL_hPa'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MOCHAES_pressure_asl_hPa'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MOCHAES_rel_Luftfeuchtigkeit_Stundenmittel_prozent'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MOCHAES_sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min'] = np.nan
```

```

df_idw['VALUE_MOCHAES_temp_AGL_C'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MOCHAES_temp_asl_C'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MOCHAES_Neuschnee_Momentanwert_cm'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MOCHAES_Schneehoehe_Momentanwert_cm'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MOCHAES_Foehnindex'] = np.nan

df_idw['VALUE_MODEISCH_Globalstrahlung_wm2'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MODEISCH_Luftdruckaenderung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MODEISCH_Niederschlag_Stundensumme_mm'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MODEISCH_Windgeschwindigkeit_ms'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MODEISCH_Windrichtung_grad'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MODEISCH_dewpoint_AGL_C'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MODEISCH_dewpoint_ASL_C'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MODEISCH_pressure_AGL_hPa'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MODEISCH_pressure_asl_hPa'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MODEISCH_rel_Luftfeuchtigkeit_Stundenmittel_prozent'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MODEISCH_sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MODEISCH_temp_AGL_C'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MODEISCH_temp_asl_C'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MODEISCH_Neuschnee_Momentanwert_cm'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MODEISCH_Schneehoehe_Momentanwert_cm'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MODEISCH_Foehnindex'] = np.nan

df_idw['VALUE_MOFIESCH_Globalstrahlung_wm2'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MOFIESCH_Luftdruckaenderung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MOFIESCH_Niederschlag_Stundensumme_mm'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MOFIESCH_Windgeschwindigkeit_ms'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MOFIESCH_Windrichtung_grad'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MOFIESCH_dewpoint_AGL_C'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MOFIESCH_dewpoint_ASL_C'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MOFIESCH_pressure_AGL_hPa'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MOFIESCH_pressure_asl_hPa'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MOFIESCH_rel_Luftfeuchtigkeit_Stundenmittel_prozent'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MOFIESCH_sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MOFIESCH_temp_AGL_C'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MOFIESCH_temp_asl_C'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MOFIESCH_Neuschnee_Momentanwert_cm'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MOFIESCH_Schneehoehe_Momentanwert_cm'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MOFIESCH_Foehnindex'] = np.nan

df_idw['VALUE_MOGRIMSEL_Globalstrahlung_wm2'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MOGRIMSEL_Luftdruckaenderung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MOGRIMSEL_Niederschlag_Stundensumme_mm'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MOGRIMSEL_Windgeschwindigkeit_ms'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MOGRIMSEL_Windrichtung_grad'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MOGRIMSEL_dewpoint_AGL_C'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MOGRIMSEL_dewpoint_ASL_C'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MOGRIMSEL_pressure_AGL_hPa'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MOGRIMSEL_pressure_asl_hPa'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MOGRIMSEL_rel_Luftfeuchtigkeit_Stundenmittel_prozent'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MOGRIMSEL_sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MOGRIMSEL_temp_AGL_C'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MOGRIMSEL_temp_asl_C'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MOGRIMSEL_Neuschnee_Momentanwert_cm'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MOGRIMSEL_Schneehoehe_Momentanwert_cm'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MOGRIMSEL_Foehnindex'] = np.nan

df_idw['VALUE_MONAT_Globalstrahlung_wm2'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MONAT_Luftdruckaenderung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MONAT_Niederschlag_Stundensumme_mm'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MONAT_Windgeschwindigkeit_ms'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MONAT_Windrichtung_grad'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MONAT_dewpoint_AGL_C'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MONAT_dewpoint_ASL_C'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MONAT_pressure_AGL_hPa'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MONAT_pressure_asl_hPa'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MONAT_rel_Luftfeuchtigkeit_Stundenmittel_prozent'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MONAT_sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MONAT_temp_AGL_C'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MONAT_temp_asl_C'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MONAT_Neuschnee_Momentanwert_cm'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MONAT_Schneehoehe_Momentanwert_cm'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MONAT_Foehnindex'] = np.nan

df_idw['VALUE_MORIEDA_Globalstrahlung_wm2'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MORIEDA_Luftdruckaenderung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MORIEDA_Niederschlag_Stundensumme_mm'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MORIEDA_Windgeschwindigkeit_ms'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MORIEDA_Windrichtung_grad'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MORIEDA_dewpoint_AGL_C'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MORIEDA_dewpoint_ASL_C'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MORIEDA_pressure_AGL_hPa'] = np.nan

```

```
df_idw['VALUE_MORIEDA_pressure_asl_hPa'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MORIEDA_rel_Luftfeuchtigkeit_Stundenmittel_prozent'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MORIEDA_sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MORIEDA_temp_AGL_C'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MORIEDA_temp_asl_C'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MORIEDA_Neuschnee_Momentanwert_cm'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MORIEDA_Schneehoehe_Momentanwert_cm'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MORIEDA_Foehnindex'] = np.nan
```

```
df_idw['VALUE_MORIEDF_Globalstrahlung_wm2'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MORIEDF_Luftdruckaenderung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MORIEDF_Niederschlag_Stundensumme_mm'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MORIEDF_Windgeschwindigkeit_ms'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MORIEDF_Windrichtung_grad'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MORIEDF_dewpoint_AGL_C'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MORIEDF_dewpoint_AS_L_C'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MORIEDF_pressure_AGL_hPa'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MORIEDF_pressure_asl_hPa'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MORIEDF_rel_Luftfeuchtigkeit_Stundenmittel_prozent'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MORIEDF_sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MORIEDF_temp_AGL_C'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MORIEDF_temp_asl_C'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MORIEDF_Neuschnee_Momentanwert_cm'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MORIEDF_Schneehoehe_Momentanwert_cm'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MORIEDF_Foehnindex'] = np.nan
```

```
df_idw['VALUE_MOSIMP_Globalstrahlung_wm2'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MOSIMP_Luftdruckaenderung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MOSIMP_Niederschlag_Stundensumme_mm'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MOSIMP_Windgeschwindigkeit_ms'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MOSIMP_Windrichtung_grad'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MOSIMP_dewpoint_AGL_C'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MOSIMP_dewpoint_AS_L_C'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MOSIMP_pressure_AGL_hPa'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MOSIMP_pressure_asl_hPa'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MOSIMP_rel_Luftfeuchtigkeit_Stundenmittel_prozent'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MOSIMP_sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MOSIMP_temp_AGL_C'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MOSIMP_temp_asl_C'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MOSIMP_Neuschnee_Momentanwert_cm'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MOSIMP_Schneehoehe_Momentanwert_cm'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_MOSIMP_Foehnindex'] = np.nan
```

```
df_idw['VALUE_SIM_Globalstrahlung_wm2'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SIM_Luftdruckaenderung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SIM_Niederschlag_Stundensumme_mm'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SIM_Windgeschwindigkeit_ms'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SIM_Windrichtung_grad'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SIM_dewpoint_AGL_C'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SIM_dewpoint_AS_L_C'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SIM_pressure_AGL_hPa'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SIM_pressure_asl_hPa'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SIM_rel_Luftfeuchtigkeit_Stundenmittel_prozent'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SIM_sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SIM temp_AGL_C'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SIM temp_asl_C'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SIM_Neuschnee_Momentanwert_cm'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SIM_Schneehoehe_Momentanwert_cm'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SIM_Foehnindex'] = np.nan
```

```
df_idw['VALUE_SLFBEL_Globalstrahlung_wm2'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFBEL_Luftdruckaenderung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFBEL_Niederschlag_Stundensumme_mm'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFBEL_Windgeschwindigkeit_ms'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFBEL_Windrichtung_grad'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFBEL_dewpoint_AGL_C'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFBEL_dewpoint_AS_L_C'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFBEL_pressure_AGL_hPa'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFBEL_pressure_asl_hPa'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFBEL_rel_Luftfeuchtigkeit_Stundenmittel_prozent'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFBEL_sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFBEL temp_AGL_C'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFBEL temp_asl_C'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFBEL_Neuschnee_Momentanwert_cm'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFBEL_Schneehoehe_Momentanwert_cm'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFBEL_Foehnindex'] = np.nan
```

```
df_idw['VALUE_SLFBOR_Globalstrahlung_wm2'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFBOR_Luftdruckaenderung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFBOR_Niederschlag_Stundensumme_mm'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFBOR_Windgeschwindigkeit_ms'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFBOR_Windrichtung_grad'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFBOR_dewpoint_AGL_C'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFBOR_dewpoint_AS_L_C'] = np.nan
```

```
df_idw['VALUE_SLFBOR_pressure_AGL_hPa'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFBOR_pressure_asl_hPa'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFBOR_rel_Luftfeuchtigkeit_Stundenmittel_prozent'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFBOR_sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFBOR_temp_AGL_C'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFBOR_temp_asl_C'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFBOR_Neuschnee_Momentanwert_cm'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFBOR_Schneehoehe_Momentanwert_cm'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFBOR_Foehnindex'] = np.nan
```

```
df_idw['VALUE_SLFEGH_Globalstrahlung_wm2'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFEGH_Luftdruckaenderung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFEGH_Niederschlag_Stundensumme_mm'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFEGH_Windgeschwindigkeit_ms'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFEGH_Windrichtung_grad'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFEGH_dewpoint_AGL_C'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFEGH_dewpoint_ASL_C'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFEGH_pressure_AGL_hPa'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFEGH_pressure_asl_hPa'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFEGH_rel_Luftfeuchtigkeit_Stundenmittel_prozent'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFEGH_sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFEGH_temp_AGL_C'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFEGH_temp_asl_C'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFEGH_Neuschnee_Momentanwert_cm'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFEGH_Schneehoehe_Momentanwert_cm'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFEGH_Foehnindex'] = np.nan
```

```
df_idw['VALUE_SLFGO2_Globalstrahlung_wm2'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFGO2_Luftdruckaenderung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFGO2_Niederschlag_Stundensumme_mm'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFGO2_Windgeschwindigkeit_ms'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFGO2_Windrichtung_grad'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFGO2_dewpoint_AGL_C'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFGO2_dewpoint_ASL_C'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFGO2_pressure_AGL_hPa'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFGO2_pressure_asl_hPa'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFGO2_rel_Luftfeuchtigkeit_Stundenmittel_prozent'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFGO2_sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFGO2_temp_AGL_C'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFGO2_temp_asl_C'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFGO2_Neuschnee_Momentanwert_cm'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFGO2_Schneehoehe_Momentanwert_cm'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFGO2_Foehnindex'] = np.nan
```

```
df_idw['VALUE_SLFGO3_Globalstrahlung_wm2'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFGO3_Luftdruckaenderung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFGO3_Niederschlag_Stundensumme_mm'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFGO3_Windgeschwindigkeit_ms'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFGO3_Windrichtung_grad'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFGO3_dewpoint_AGL_C'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFGO3_dewpoint_ASL_C'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFGO3_pressure_AGL_hPa'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFGO3_pressure_asl_hPa'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFGO3_rel_Luftfeuchtigkeit_Stundenmittel_prozent'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFGO3_sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFGO3_temp_AGL_C'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFGO3_temp_asl_C'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFGO3_Neuschnee_Momentanwert_cm'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFGO3_Schneehoehe_Momentanwert_cm'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFGO3_Foehnindex'] = np.nan
```

```
df_idw['VALUE_SLFMU2_Globalstrahlung_wm2'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFMU2_Luftdruckaenderung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFMU2_Niederschlag_Stundensumme_mm'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFMU2_Windgeschwindigkeit_ms'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFMU2_Windrichtung_grad'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFMU2_dewpoint_AGL_C'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFMU2_dewpoint_ASL_C'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFMU2_pressure_AGL_hPa'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFMU2_pressure_asl_hPa'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFMU2_rel_Luftfeuchtigkeit_Stundenmittel_prozent'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFMU2_sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFMU2_temp_AGL_C'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFMU2_temp_asl_C'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFMU2_Neuschnee_Momentanwert_cm'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFMU2_Schneehoehe_Momentanwert_cm'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFMU2_Foehnindex'] = np.nan
```

```
df_idw['VALUE_SLFOB2_Globalstrahlung_wm2'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFOB2_Luftdruckaenderung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFOB2_Niederschlag_Stundensumme_mm'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFOB2_Windgeschwindigkeit_ms'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFOB2_Windrichtung_grad'] = np.nan
```

```
df_idw['VALUE_SLFOB2_dewpoint_AGL_C'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFOB2_dewpoint_AS_L_C'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFOB2_pressure_AGL_hPa'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFOB2_pressure_asl_hPa'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFOB2_rel_Luftfeuchtigkeit_Stundenmittel_prozent'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFOB2_sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFOB2_temp_AGL_C'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFOB2_temp_asl_C'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFOB2_Neuschnee_Momentanwert_cm'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFOB2_Schneehoehe_Momentanwert_cm'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFOB2_Foehnindex'] = np.nan
```

```
df_idw['VALUE_SLFOB3_Globalstrahlung_wm2'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFOB3_Luftdruckaenderung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFOB3_Niederschlag_Stundensumme_mm'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFOB3_Windgeschwindigkeit_ms'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFOB3_Windrichtung_grad'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFOB3_dewpoint_AGL_C'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFOB3_dewpoint_AS_L_C'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFOB3_pressure_AGL_hPa'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFOB3_pressure_asl_hPa'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFOB3_rel_Luftfeuchtigkeit_Stundenmittel_prozent'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFOB3_sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFOB3_temp_AGL_C'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFOB3_temp_asl_C'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFOB3_Neuschnee_Momentanwert_cm'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFOB3_Schneehoehe_Momentanwert_cm'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFOB3_Foehnindex'] = np.nan
```

```
df_idw['VALUE_SLFOBW_Globalstrahlung_wm2'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFOBW_Luftdruckaenderung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFOBW_Niederschlag_Stundensumme_mm'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFOBW_Windgeschwindigkeit_ms'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFOBW_Windrichtung_grad'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFOBW_dewpoint_AGL_C'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFOBW_dewpoint_AS_L_C'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFOBW_pressure_AGL_hPa'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFOBW_pressure_asl_hPa'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFOBW_rel_Luftfeuchtigkeit_Stundenmittel_prozent'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFOBW_sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFOBW_temp_AGL_C'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFOBW_temp_asl_C'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFOBW_Neuschnee_Momentanwert_cm'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFOBW_Schneehoehe_Momentanwert_cm'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFOBW_Foehnindex'] = np.nan
```

```
df_idw['VALUE_SLFSP2_Globalstrahlung_wm2'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFSP2_Luftdruckaenderung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFSP2_Niederschlag_Stundensumme_mm'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFSP2_Windgeschwindigkeit_ms'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFSP2_Windrichtung_grad'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFSP2_dewpoint_AGL_C'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFSP2_dewpoint_AS_L_C'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFSP2_pressure_AGL_hPa'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFSP2_pressure_asl_hPa'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFSP2_rel_Luftfeuchtigkeit_Stundenmittel_prozent'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFSP2_sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFSP2_temp_AGL_C'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFSP2_temp_asl_C'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFSP2_Neuschnee_Momentanwert_cm'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFSP2_Schneehoehe_Momentanwert_cm'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFSP2_Foehnindex'] = np.nan
```

```
df_idw['VALUE_SLFSP3_Globalstrahlung_wm2'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFSP3_Luftdruckaenderung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFSP3_Niederschlag_Stundensumme_mm'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFSP3_Windgeschwindigkeit_ms'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFSP3_Windrichtung_grad'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFSP3_dewpoint_AGL_C'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFSP3_dewpoint_AS_L_C'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFSP3_pressure_AGL_hPa'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFSP3_pressure_asl_hPa'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFSP3_rel_Luftfeuchtigkeit_Stundenmittel_prozent'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFSP3_sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFSP3_temp_AGL_C'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFSP3_temp_asl_C'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFSP3_Neuschnee_Momentanwert_cm'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFSP3_Schneehoehe_Momentanwert_cm'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_SLFSP3_Foehnindex'] = np.nan
```

```
df_idw['VALUE_ULR_Globalstrahlung_wm2'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_ULR_Luftdruckaenderung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa'] = np.nan
```

```
df_idw['VALUE_ULR_Niederschlag_Stundensumme_mm'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_ULR_Windgeschwindigkeit_ms'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_ULR_Windrichtung_grad'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_ULR_dewpoint_AGL_C'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_ULR_dewpoint_AS_L_C'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_ULR_pressure_AGL_hPa'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_ULR_pressure_asl_hPa'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_ULR_rel_Luftfeuchtigkeit_Stundenmittel_prozent'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_ULR_sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_ULR_temp_AGL_C'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_ULR_temp_asl_C'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_ULR_Neuschnee_Momentanwert_cm'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_ULR_Schneehoehe_Momentanwert_cm'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_ULR_Foehnindex'] = np.nan
```

```
df_idw['VALUE_VIS_Globalstrahlung_wm2'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_VIS_Luftdruckaenderung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_VIS_Niederschlag_Stundensumme_mm'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_VIS_Windgeschwindigkeit_ms'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_VIS_Windrichtung_grad'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_VIS_dewpoint_AGL_C'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_VIS_dewpoint_AS_L_C'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_VIS_pressure_AGL_hPa'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_VIS_pressure_asl_hPa'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_VIS_rel_Luftfeuchtigkeit_Stundenmittel_prozent'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_VIS_sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_VIS_temp_AGL_C'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_VIS_temp_asl_C'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_VIS_Neuschnee_Momentanwert_cm'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_VIS_Schneehoehe_Momentanwert_cm'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_VIS_Foehnindex'] = np.nan
```

```
df_idw['VALUE_VSBRB_Globalstrahlung_wm2'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_VSBRB_Luftdruckaenderung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_VSBRB_Niederschlag_Stundensumme_mm'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_VSBRB_Windgeschwindigkeit_ms'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_VSBRB_Windrichtung_grad'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_VSBRB_dewpoint_AGL_C'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_VSBRB_dewpoint_AS_L_C'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_VSBRB_pressure_AGL_hPa'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_VSBRB_pressure_asl_hPa'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_VSBRB_rel_Luftfeuchtigkeit_Stundenmittel_prozent'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_VSBRB_sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_VSBRB_temp_AGL_C'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_VSBRB_temp_asl_C'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_VSBRB_Neuschnee_Momentanwert_cm'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_VSBRB_Schneehoehe_Momentanwert_cm'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_VSBRB_Foehnindex'] = np.nan
```

```
df_idw['VALUE_WSLVSB_Globalstrahlung_wm2'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_WSLVSB_Luftdruckaenderung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa'] = np.nan
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df_idw['VALUE_WSLVSB_Windgeschwindigkeit_ms'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_WSLVSB_Windrichtung_grad'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_WSLVSB_dewpoint_AGL_C'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_WSLVSB_dewpoint_AS_L_C'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_WSLVSB_pressure_AGL_hPa'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_WSLVSB_pressure_asl_hPa'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_WSLVSB_rel_Luftfeuchtigkeit_Stundenmittel_prozent'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_WSLVSB_sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_WSLVSB_temp_AGL_C'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_WSLVSB_temp_asl_C'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_WSLVSB_Neuschnee_Momentanwert_cm'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_WSLVSB_Schneehoehe_Momentanwert_cm'] = np.nan
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```

```
df_idw['VALUE_WSLVSF_Globalstrahlung_wm2'] = np.nan
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df_idw['VALUE_WSLVSF_Windgeschwindigkeit_ms'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_WSLVSF_Windrichtung_grad'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_WSLVSF_dewpoint_AGL_C'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_WSLVSF_dewpoint_AS_L_C'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_WSLVSF_pressure_AGL_hPa'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_WSLVSF_pressure_asl_hPa'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_WSLVSF_rel_Luftfeuchtigkeit_Stundenmittel_prozent'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_WSLVSF_sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_WSLVSF_temp_AGL_C'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_WSLVSF_temp_asl_C'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_WSLVSF_Neuschnee_Momentanwert_cm'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_WSLVSF_Schneehoehe_Momentanwert_cm'] = np.nan
df_idw['VALUE_WSLVSF_Foehnindex'] = np.nan
```

```
# In[ ]:
```

```
idw_cols3 = df_idw.columns.tolist()  
idw_cols3
```

```
# In[ ]:
```

```
idw_cols3 = ['GPS_TierID', 'GPS_Tier_Geschlecht', 'GPS_Tier_Name', 'GPS_Tier_Ohrmarke', 'GPS_Tier_Gebiet',  
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'GPS_EPSG2056_lat', 'GPS_EPSG2056_lon', 'GPS_x', 'GPS_y', 'GPS_WGS84_Breite', 'GPS_WGS84_Laenge',  
'GPS_Hoehe_AS_L_m_DEM', 'GPS_Hoehe_AS_L_m', 'GPS_DEM_Height_Difference',  
'GPS_DISTANCE_ABSOLUTE', 'GPS_DISTANCE_X', 'GPS_DISTANCE_Y', 'GPS_DISTANCE_Z',  
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```

```
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'GPS_sunrise_cleaned', 'GPS_sunset_cleaned', 'GPS_twilight_dawn_cleaned', 'GPS_twi-  
light_dusk_cleaned', 'Jahreszeit_4season', 'Jahreszeit_HalbJahr',
```

```
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```

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 'VALUE_MOSIMP_temp_asl_C',
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 'VALUE_SLFGO3_Windrichtung_grad',
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 'VALUE_SLFSP2_Windgeschwindigkeit_ms',
 'VALUE_SLFSP2_Windrichtung_grad',
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 'VALUE_SLFSP2_dewpoint_AS_L_C',
 'VALUE_SLFSP2_pressure_AGL_hPa',
 'VALUE_SLFSP2_pressure_asl_hPa',
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 'VALUE_SLFSP2_temp_AGL_C',
 'VALUE_SLFSP2_temp_asl_C',
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 'VALUE_SLFSP2_Schneehoehe_Momentanwert_cm',
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 'VALUE_SLFSP3_Windgeschwindigkeit_ms',
 'VALUE_SLFSP3_Windrichtung_grad',
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 'VALUE_SLFSP3_dewpoint_AS_L_C',
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 'VALUE_SLFSP3_temp_asl_C',
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 'VALUE_ULR_Windgeschwindigkeit_ms',
 'VALUE_ULR_Windrichtung_grad',
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 'VALUE_ULR_dewpoint_AS_L_C',
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 'VALUE_ULR_pressure_asl_hPa',
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 'VALUE_ULR_temp_asl_C',
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 'VALUE_VIS_Niederschlag_Stundensumme_mm',
 'VALUE_VIS_Windgeschwindigkeit_ms',
 'VALUE_VIS_Windrichtung_grad',
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 'VALUE_VIS_dewpoint_AS_L_C',
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 'VALUE_VIS_pressure_asl_hPa',
 'VALUE_VIS_rel_Luftfeuchtigkeit_Stundenmittel_prozent',
 'VALUE_VIS_sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min',
 'VALUE_VIS_temp_AGL_C',
 'VALUE_VIS_temp_asl_C',
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 'VALUE_VIS_Schneehoehe_Momentanwert_cm',
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 'VALUE_VSBRB_Windgeschwindigkeit_ms',
 'VALUE_VSBRB_Windrichtung_grad',
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 'VALUE_VSBRB_dewpoint_AS_L_C',
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```
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'VALUE_WSLVSB_Windgeschwindigkeit_ms',
'VALUE_WSLVSB_Windrichtung_grad',
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'VALUE_WSLVSB_dewpoint_AS_L_C',
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'VALUE_WSLVSB_sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min',
'VALUE_WSLVSB_temp_AGL_C',
'VALUE_WSLVSB_temp_asl_C',
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'VALUE_WSLVSB_Schneehoehe_Momentanwert_cm',
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'VALUE_WSLVSF_Windrichtung_grad',
'VALUE_WSLVSF_dewpoint_AGL_C',
'VALUE_WSLVSF_dewpoint_AS_L_C',
'VALUE_WSLVSF_pressure_AGL_hPa',
'VALUE_WSLVSF_pressure_asl_hPa',
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'VALUE_WSLVSF_sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min',
'VALUE_WSLVSF_temp_AGL_C',
'VALUE_WSLVSF_temp_asl_C',
'VALUE_WSLVSF_Neuschnee_Momentanwert_cm',
'VALUE_WSLVSF_Schneehoehe_Momentanwert_cm',
'VALUE_WSLVSF_Foehnindex']
```

```
# In[ ]:
```

```
df_idw = df_idw[idw_cols3]
```

```
# In[ ]:
```

```
df_idw
```

```
# In[ ]:
```

```
# In[ ]:
```

```
path_idw = path_to_output + 'DF_IDW.csv'
```

```
# In[ ]:
```

```
df_idw.to_csv(path_idw)
```

```
# print('Import Libraries')
# import os
#
# import pandas as pd
# print('Pandas imported')
# import numpy as np
# print('Numpy imported')
# print(' -- successfull \n')
#
# #gc.collect() explicitly frees memory space.
# import gc
#
# from multiprocessing import set_start_method
# set_start_method("spawn")
# from multiprocessing import get_context
#
# import time
# from multiprocessing import Pool
# from multiprocessing.pool import ThreadPool
#
# import multiprocessing as mp
# !python --version
# import platform
# print(platform.platform())
```

```

# print("cpu cores: {}".format(mp.cpu_count()))
# processes = mp.cpu_count()
#
#
# print('Import Libraries for geografic transformations')
# print('import os \n import geopandas \n import shapely \n import pyreproj \n import pyproj \n import col-
lections \n import ogr, osr \n import osgeo')
#
# import geopandas as gpd
# import shapely
# import pyreproj
# import pyproj
# import collections
# import ogr, osr
# import osgeo
# from shapely import wkt
# print(' -- successfull \n')
#
# print('Import Math and Itertools')
# print('import math \n import itertools \n from itertools import islice')
# import math
# import itertools
# from itertools import islice
# print(' -- successfull \n')
#
#
# print('Import Scikit Learn and matplotlib for statistics and plots')
# print('import sklearn \n from sklearn import linear_model \n import matplotlib \n import matplotlib.pyplot as
plt \n %matplotlib inline')
# import sklearn
# from sklearn import linear_model
# import matplotlib
# import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
# %matplotlib inline
# print(' -- successfull \n')
#
#
# print('Options to show full pandas dataframe \n')
# #pd.set_option('display.max_rows', None)
# #pd.set_option('display.max_columns', None)
# #pd.set_option('display.width', None)
# #pd.set_option('display.max_colwidth', None)
#
# print('Set display of dataframe to max columns')
# pd.set_option('display.max_columns', None)
# print(' -- successfull \n')

# In[ ]:

path_idw= path_to_output + 'DF_IDW.csv'

# In[ ]:

path_weather2 = path_to_output + 'Weather_Data_small.csv'

# In[ ]:

df_idw = pd.read_csv(path_idw)

# In[ ]:

df_weather = pd.read_csv(path_weather2)

# In[ ]:

df_copy = pd.DataFrame()
df_rows_idw = pd.DataFrame()

# df_rows_idw = df_idw

# In[ ]:

df_copy = df_idw

# In[ ]:

```

```

df_idw['UTC1'] = df_idw['UTC']
df_idw.set_index('UTC1')

# df_rows_idw['UTC1'] = df_rows_idw['UTC']
# df_rows_idw.set_index('UTC1')
#

# df_rows_idw['Index'] = df_rows_idw['Unnamed: 0'].copy()
#
# del df_rows_idw['Unnamed: 0']

# In[ ]:

df_weather

# In[ ]:

del df_weather['Unnamed: 0']

# In[ ]:

df_weather = df_weather.set_index('UTC1')

# In[ ]:

for row in df_weather.itertuples():
    Timestamp = row.Timestamp
    station = row.Station
    rel_Luftfeuchtigkeit_Stundenmittel_prozent = row.rel_Luftfeuchtigkeit_Stundenmittel_prozent
    Luftdruckaenderung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa = row.Luftdruckaenderung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa
    Niederschlag_Stundensumme_mm = row.Niederschlag_Stundensumme_mm
    Windgeschwindigkeit_ms = row.Windgeschwindigkeit_ms
    Windgeschwindigkeit_ms = row.Windgeschwindigkeit_ms
    Windrichtung_grad = row.Windrichtung_grad
    Globalstrahlung_wm2 = row.Globalstrahlung_wm2
    sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min = row.sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min
    CALCULATED_temp_asl_C = row.CALCULATED_temp_asl_C
    CALCULATED_pressure_asl_hPa = row.CALCULATED_pressure_asl_hPa
    CALCULATED_dewpoint_asl_C = row.CALCULATED_dewpoint_asl_C
    Taupunkt_Momentanwert_celsius = row.Taupunkt_Momentanwert_celsius
    Luftdruck_Barometerhoehe_QFE_Stundenmittel_hPa = row.Luftdruck_Barometerhoehe_QFE_Stundenmittel_hPa
    Temp_2mAGL_C = row.Temp_2mAGL_C
    Foehnindex = row.Foehnindex
    Schnee_Momentanwert_cm = row.Schnee_Momentanwert_cm
    Neuschnee_Momentanwert_cm = row.Neuschnee_Momentanwert_cm

    df_rows_idw = df_idw.loc[df_idw['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp]
    if df_rows_idw.empty:
        print(station, ' ', Timestamp, ' DataFrame is empty!')
        print(df_rows_idw)
    else:
        #print(df_rows_idw.GPS_timestamp_cleaned)
        print(station)
        if station == 'BIN':
            print('Station selected', station)
            print('Set Columns section by Timestamp: ', Timestamp)
            df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_BIN_Globalstrahlung_wm2'] = Glob-
alstrahlung_wm2
            df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_BIN_Luftdruckaender-
ung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa'] = Luftdruckaenderung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa
            df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_BIN_Niederschlag_Stunden-
summe_mm'] = Niederschlag_Stundensumme_mm
            df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_BIN_Windgeschwindigkeit_ms'] =
Windgeschwindigkeit_ms
            df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_BIN_Windrichtung_grad'] = Wind-
richtung_grad
            df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_BIN_dewpoint_AGL_C'] = Tau-
punkt_Momentanwert_celsius
            df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_BIN_dewpoint_AS_L_C'] = CALCU-
LATED_dewpoint_asl_C
            df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_BIN_pressure_AGL_hPa'] = Luft-
druck_Barometerhoehe_QFE_Stundenmittel_hPa
            df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_BIN_pressure_asl_hPa'] = CALCU-
LATED_pressure_asl_hPa
            df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_BIN_rel_Luftfeuchtigkeit_Stunden-
mittel_prozent'] = rel_Luftfeuchtigkeit_Stundenmittel_prozent

```

```

df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_BIN_sonnenscheindauer_stunden-
summe_min'] = sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_BIN_temp_AGL_C'] = Temp_2mAGL_C
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_BIN_temp_asl_C'] = CALCU-
LATED_temp_asl_C
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_BIN_Schnee_Momentanwert_cm'] =
Schnee_Momentanwert_cm
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_BIN_Neuschnee_Momentanwert_cm'] =
Neuschnee_Momentanwert_cm
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_BIN_Foehnindex'] = Foehnindex
print('-- successfull')
elif station == 'EGH':
    print('Station selected', station)
    print('Set Columns section by Timestamp: ', Timestamp)
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_EGH_Globalstrahlung_wm2'] = Glob-
alstrahlung_wm2
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_EGH_Luftdruckaender-
ung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa'] = Luftdruckaenderung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_EGH_Niederschlag_Stunden-
summe_mm'] = Niederschlag_Stundensumme_mm
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_EGH_Windgeschwindigkeit_ms'] =
Windgeschwindigkeit_ms
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_EGH_Windrichtung_grad'] =
Windrichtung_grad
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_EGH_dewpoint_AGL_C'] = Tau-
punkt_Momentanwert_celsius
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_EGH_dewpoint_ASL_C'] = CALCU-
LATED_dewpoint_asl_C
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_EGH_pressure_AGL_hPa'] = Luft-
druck_Barometerhoehe_QFE_Stundenmittel_hPa
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_EGH_pressure_asl_hPa'] = CALCU-
LATED_pressure_asl_hPa
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_EGH_rel_Luftfeuchtigkeit_Stunden-
mittel_prozent'] = rel_Luftfeuchtigkeit_Stundenmittel_prozent
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_EGH_sonnenscheindauer_stunden-
summe_min'] = sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_EGH_temp_AGL_C'] = Temp_2mAGL_C
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_EGH_temp_asl_C'] = CALCU-
LATED_temp_asl_C
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_EGH_Schnee_Momentanwert_cm'] =
Schnee_Momentanwert_cm
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_EGH_Neuschnee_Momentanwert_cm'] =
Neuschnee_Momentanwert_cm
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_EGH_Foehnindex'] = Foehnindex
print('-- successfull')
elif station == 'JUN':
    print('Station selected', station)
    print('Set Columns section by Timestamp: ', Timestamp)
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_JUN_Globalstrahlung_wm2'] = Glob-
alstrahlung_wm2
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_JUN_Luftdruckaender-
ung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa'] = Luftdruckaenderung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_JUN_Niederschlag_Stunden-
summe_mm'] = Niederschlag_Stundensumme_mm
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_JUN_Windgeschwindigkeit_ms'] =
Windgeschwindigkeit_ms
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_JUN_Windrichtung_grad'] =
Windrichtung_grad
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_JUN_dewpoint_AGL_C'] = Tau-
punkt_Momentanwert_celsius
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_JUN_dewpoint_ASL_C'] = CALCU-
LATED_dewpoint_asl_C
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_JUN_pressure_AGL_hPa'] = Luft-
druck_Barometerhoehe_QFE_Stundenmittel_hPa
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_JUN_pressure_asl_hPa'] = CALCU-
LATED_pressure_asl_hPa
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_JUN_rel_Luftfeuchtigkeit_Stunden-
mittel_prozent'] = rel_Luftfeuchtigkeit_Stundenmittel_prozent
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_JUN_sonnenscheindauer_stunden-
summe_min'] = sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_JUN_temp_AGL_C'] = Temp_2mAGL_C
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_JUN_temp_asl_C'] = CALCU-
LATED_temp_asl_C
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_JUN_Schnee_Momentanwert_cm'] =
Schnee_Momentanwert_cm
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_JUN_Neuschnee_Momentanwert_cm'] =
Neuschnee_Momentanwert_cm
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_JUN_Foehnindex'] = Foehnindex
print('-- successfull')
elif station == 'SIM':
    print('Station selected', station)
    print('Set Columns section by Timestamp: ', Timestamp)
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SIM_Globalstrahlung_wm2'] = Glob-
alstrahlung_wm2
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SIM_Luftdruckaender-
ung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa'] = Luftdruckaenderung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa

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df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SIM_Niederschlag_Stunden-
summe_mm'] = Niederschlag_Stundensumme_mm
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SIM_Windgeschwindigkeit_ms'] =
Windgeschwindigkeit_ms
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SIM_Windrichtung_grad'] =
Windrichtung_grad
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SIM_dewpoint_AGL_C'] = Tau-
punkt_Momentanwert_celsius
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SIM_dewpoint_AS_L_C'] = CALCU-
LATED_dewpoint_asl_C
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SIM_pressure_AGL_hPa'] = Luft-
druck_Barometerhoehe_QFE_Stundenmittel_hPa
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SIM_pressure_asl_hPa'] = CALCU-
LATED_pressure_asl_hPa
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SIM_rel_Luftfeuchtigkeit_Stunden-
mittel_prozent'] = rel_Luftfeuchtigkeit_Stundenmittel_prozent
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SIM_sonnenscheindauer_stunden-
summe_min'] = sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SIM_temp_AGL_C'] = Temp_2mAGL_C
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SIM_temp_asl_C'] = CALCU-
LATED_temp_asl_C
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SIM_Schnee_Momentanwert_cm'] =
Schnee_Momentanwert_cm
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SIM_Neuschnee_Momentanwert_cm'] =
Neuschnee_Momentanwert_cm
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SIM_Foehnindex'] = Foehnindex
print('-- successfull')
elif station == 'SLFBEL':
    print('Station selected', station)
    print('Set Columns section by Timestamp: ', Timestamp)
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLFBEL_Globalstrahlung_wm2'] =
Globalstrahlung_wm2
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLFBEL_Luftdruckaender-
ung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa'] = Luftdruckaenderung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLFBEL_Niederschlag_Stunden-
summe_mm'] = Niederschlag_Stundensumme_mm
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLFBEL_Windgeschwindigkeit_ms'] =
Windgeschwindigkeit_ms
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLFBEL_Windrichtung_grad'] =
Windrichtung_grad
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLFBEL_dewpoint_AGL_C'] = Tau-
punkt_Momentanwert_celsius
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLFBEL_dewpoint_AS_L_C'] = CALCU-
LATED_dewpoint_asl_C
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLFBEL_pressure_AGL_hPa'] = Luft-
druck_Barometerhoehe_QFE_Stundenmittel_hPa
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLFBEL_pressure_asl_hPa'] = CAL-
CULATED_pressure_asl_hPa
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLFBEL_rel_Luft-
feuchtigkeit_Stundenmittel_prozent'] = rel_Luftfeuchtigkeit_Stundenmittel_prozent
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLFBEL_sonnenscheindauer_stunden-
summe_min'] = sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLFBEL_temp_AGL_C'] =
Temp_2mAGL_C
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLFBEL_temp_asl_C'] = CALCU-
LATED_temp_asl_C
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLFBEL_Schnee_Momentanwert_cm'] =
Schnee_Momentanwert_cm
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLFBEL_Neuschnee_Momentan-
wert_cm'] = Neuschnee_Momentanwert_cm
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLFBEL_Foehnindex'] = Foehnindex
print('-- successfull')
elif station == 'SLFBOR':
    print('Station selected', station)
    print('Set Columns section by Timestamp: ', Timestamp)
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLFBOR_Globalstrahlung_wm2'] =
Globalstrahlung_wm2
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLFBOR_Luftdruckaender-
ung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa'] = Luftdruckaenderung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLFBOR_Niederschlag_Stunden-
summe_mm'] = Niederschlag_Stundensumme_mm
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLFBOR_Windgeschwindigkeit_ms'] =
Windgeschwindigkeit_ms
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLFBOR_Windrichtung_grad'] =
Windrichtung_grad
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLFBOR_dewpoint_AGL_C'] = Tau-
punkt_Momentanwert_celsius
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLFBOR_dewpoint_AS_L_C'] = CALCU-
LATED_dewpoint_asl_C
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLFBOR_pressure_AGL_hPa'] = Luft-
druck_Barometerhoehe_QFE_Stundenmittel_hPa
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLFBOR_pressure_asl_hPa'] = CAL-
CULATED_pressure_asl_hPa
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLFBOR_rel_Luft-
feuchtigkeit_Stundenmittel_prozent'] = rel_Luftfeuchtigkeit_Stundenmittel_prozent
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLFBOR_sonnenscheindauer_stunden-
summe_min'] = sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min

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df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLFBOR_temp_AGL_C'] =
Temp_2mAGL_C
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLFBOR_temp_asl_C'] = CALCU-
LATED_temp_asl_C
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLFBOR_Schnee_Momentanwert_cm'] =
Schnee_Momentanwert_cm
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLFBOR_Neuschnee_Momentan-
wert_cm'] = Neuschnee_Momentanwert_cm
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLFBOR_Foehnindex'] = Foehnindex
print('-- successfull')
elif station == 'SLFEGH':
print('Station selected', station)
print('Set Columns section by Timestamp: ', Timestamp)
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLFEGH_Globalstrahlung_wm2'] =
Globalstrahlung_wm2
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLFEGH_Luftdruckaender-
ung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa'] = Luftdruckaenderung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLFEGH_Niederschlag_Stunden-
summe_mm'] = Niederschlag_Stundensumme_mm
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLFEGH_Windgeschwindigkeit_ms'] =
Windgeschwindigkeit_ms
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLFEGH_Windrichtung_grad'] =
Windrichtung_grad
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLFEGH_dewpoint_AGL_C'] = Tau-
punkt_Momentanwert_celsius
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLFEGH_dewpoint_ASL_C'] = CALCU-
LATED_dewpoint_asl_C
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLFEGH_pressure_AGL_hPa'] = Luft-
druck_Barometerhoehe_QFE_Stundenmittel_hPa
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLFEGH_pressure_asl_hPa'] = CAL-
CULATED_pressure_asl_hPa
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLFEGH_rel_Luft-
feuchtigkeit_Stundenmittel_prozent'] = rel_Luftfeuchtigkeit_Stundenmittel_prozent
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLFEGH_sonnenscheindauer_stunden-
summe_min'] = sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLFEGH_temp_AGL_C'] =
Temp_2mAGL_C
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLFEGH_temp_asl_C'] = CALCU-
LATED_temp_asl_C
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLFEGH_Schnee_Momentanwert_cm'] =
Schnee_Momentanwert_cm
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLFEGH_Neuschnee_Momentan-
wert_cm'] = Neuschnee_Momentanwert_cm
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLFEGH_Foehnindex'] = Foehnindex
print('-- successfull')
elif station == 'SLFG02':
print('Station selected', station)
print('Set Columns section by Timestamp: ', Timestamp)
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLFG02_Globalstrahlung_wm2'] =
Globalstrahlung_wm2
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLFG02_Luftdruckaender-
ung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa'] = Luftdruckaenderung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLFG02_Niederschlag_Stunden-
summe_mm'] = Niederschlag_Stundensumme_mm
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLFG02_Windgeschwindigkeit_ms'] =
Windgeschwindigkeit_ms
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLFG02_Windrichtung_grad'] =
Windrichtung_grad
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLFG02_dewpoint_AGL_C'] = Tau-
punkt_Momentanwert_celsius
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLFG02_dewpoint_ASL_C'] = CALCU-
LATED_dewpoint_asl_C
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLFG02_pressure_AGL_hPa'] = Luft-
druck_Barometerhoehe_QFE_Stundenmittel_hPa
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLFG02_pressure_asl_hPa'] = CAL-
CULATED_pressure_asl_hPa
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLFG02_rel_Luft-
feuchtigkeit_Stundenmittel_prozent'] = rel_Luftfeuchtigkeit_Stundenmittel_prozent
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLFG02_sonnenscheindauer_stunden-
summe_min'] = sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLFG02_temp_AGL_C'] =
Temp_2mAGL_C
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLFG02_temp_asl_C'] = CALCU-
LATED_temp_asl_C
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLFG02_Schnee_Momentanwert_cm'] =
Schnee_Momentanwert_cm
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLFG02_Neuschnee_Momentan-
wert_cm'] = Neuschnee_Momentanwert_cm
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLFG02_Foehnindex'] = Foehnindex
print('-- successfull')
elif station == 'SLFG03':
print('Station selected', station)
print('Set Columns section by Timestamp: ', Timestamp)
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLFG03_Globalstrahlung_wm2'] =
Globalstrahlung_wm2
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLFG03_Luftdruckaender-
ung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa'] = Luftdruckaenderung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa

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df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLFGO3_Niederschlag_Stunden-
summe_mm'] = Niederschlag_Stundensumme_mm
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLFGO3_Windgeschwindigkeit_ms'] =
Windgeschwindigkeit_ms
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLFGO3_Windrichtung_grad'] =
Windrichtung_grad
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLFGO3_dewpoint_AGL_C'] = Tau-
punkt_Momentanwert_celsius
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLFGO3_dewpoint_AS_L_C'] = CALCU-
LATED_dewpoint_asl_C
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLFGO3_pressure_AGL_hPa'] = Luft-
druck_Barometerhoehe_QFE_Stundenmittel_hPa
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLFGO3_pressure_asl_hPa'] = CAL-
CULATED_pressure_asl_hPa
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLFGO3_rel_Luft-
feuchtigkeit_Stundenmittel_prozent'] = rel_Luftfeuchtigkeit_Stundenmittel_prozent
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLFGO3_sonnenscheindauer_stunden-
summe_min'] = sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLFGO3_temp_AGL_C'] =
Temp_2mAGL_C
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLFGO3_temp_asl_C'] = CALCU-
LATED_temp_asl_C
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLFGO3_Schnee_Momentanwert_cm'] =
Schnee_Momentanwert_cm
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLFGO3_Neuschnee_Momentan-
wert_cm'] = Neuschnee_Momentanwert_cm
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLFGO3_Foehnindex'] = Foehnindex
print('-- successfull')
elif station == 'SLFMU2':
print('Station selected', station)
print('Set Columns section by Timestamp: ', Timestamp)
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLFMU2_Globalstrahlung_wm2'] =
Globalstrahlung_wm2
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLFMU2_Luftdruckaender-
ung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa'] = Luftdruckaenderung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLFMU2_Niederschlag_Stunden-
summe_mm'] = Niederschlag_Stundensumme_mm
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLFMU2_Windgeschwindigkeit_ms'] =
Windgeschwindigkeit_ms
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLFMU2_Windrichtung_grad'] =
Windrichtung_grad
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLFMU2_dewpoint_AGL_C'] = Tau-
punkt_Momentanwert_celsius
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLFMU2_dewpoint_AS_L_C'] = CALCU-
LATED_dewpoint_asl_C
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLFMU2_pressure_AGL_hPa'] = Luft-
druck_Barometerhoehe_QFE_Stundenmittel_hPa
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLFMU2_pressure_asl_hPa'] = CAL-
CULATED_pressure_asl_hPa
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLFMU2_rel_Luft-
feuchtigkeit_Stundenmittel_prozent'] = rel_Luftfeuchtigkeit_Stundenmittel_prozent
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLFMU2_sonnenscheindauer_stunden-
summe_min'] = sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLFMU2_temp_AGL_C'] =
Temp_2mAGL_C
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLFMU2_temp_asl_C'] = CALCU-
LATED temp asl C
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLFMU2_Schnee_Momentanwert_cm'] =
Schnee_Momentanwert_cm
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLFMU2_Neuschnee_Momentan-
wert_cm'] = Neuschnee_Momentanwert_cm
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLFMU2_Foehnindex'] = Foehnindex
print('-- successfull')
elif station == 'SLFOB2':
print('Station selected', station)
print('Set Columns section by Timestamp: ', Timestamp)
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLFOB2_Globalstrahlung_wm2'] =
Globalstrahlung_wm2
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLFOB2_Luftdruckaender-
ung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa'] = Luftdruckaenderung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLFOB2_Niederschlag_Stunden-
summe_mm'] = Niederschlag_Stundensumme_mm
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLFOB2_Windgeschwindigkeit_ms'] =
Windgeschwindigkeit_ms
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLFOB2_Windrichtung_grad'] =
Windrichtung_grad
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLFOB2_dewpoint_AGL_C'] = Tau-
punkt_Momentanwert_celsius
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLFOB2_dewpoint_AS_L_C'] = CALCU-
LATED_dewpoint_asl_C
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLFOB2_pressure_AGL_hPa'] = Luft-
druck_Barometerhoehe_QFE_Stundenmittel_hPa
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLFOB2_pressure_asl_hPa'] = CAL-
CULATED_pressure_asl_hPa
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLFOB2_rel_Luft-
feuchtigkeit_Stundenmittel_prozent'] = rel_Luftfeuchtigkeit_Stundenmittel_prozent

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df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLF0B2_sonnenscheindauer_stunden-
summe_min'] = sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLF0B2_temp_AGL_C'] =
Temp_2mAGL_C
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLF0B2_temp_asl_C'] = CALCU-
LATED_temp_asl_C
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLF0B2_Schnee_Momentanwert_cm'] =
Schnee_Momentanwert_cm
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLF0B2_Neuschnee_Momentan-
wert_cm'] = Neuschnee_Momentanwert_cm
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLF0B2_Foehnindex'] = Foehnindex
print('-- successfull')
elif station == 'SLF0B3':
print('Station selected', station)
print('Set Columns section by Timestamp: ', Timestamp)
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLF0B3_Globalstrahlung_wm2'] =
Globalstrahlung_wm2
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLF0B3_Luftdruckaender-
ung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa'] = Luftdruckaenderung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLF0B3_Niederschlag_Stunden-
summe_mm'] = Niederschlag_Stundensumme_mm
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLF0B3_Windgeschwindigkeit_ms'] =
Windgeschwindigkeit_ms
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLF0B3_Windrichtung_grad'] =
Windrichtung_grad
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLF0B3_dewpoint_AGL_C'] = Tau-
punkt_Momentanwert_celsius
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLF0B3_dewpoint_ASL_C'] = CALCU-
LATED_dewpoint_asl_C
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLF0B3_pressure_AGL_hPa'] = Luft-
druck_Barometerhoehe_QFE_Stundenmittel_hPa
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLF0B3_pressure_asl_hPa'] = CAL-
CULATED_pressure_asl_hPa
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLF0B3_rel_Luft-
feuchtigkeit_Stundenmittel_prozent'] = rel_Luftfeuchtigkeit_Stundenmittel_prozent
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLF0B3_sonnenscheindauer_stunden-
summe_min'] = sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLF0B3_temp_AGL_C'] =
Temp_2mAGL_C
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLF0B3_temp_asl_C'] = CALCU-
LATED_temp_asl_C
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLF0B3_Schnee_Momentanwert_cm'] =
Schnee_Momentanwert_cm
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLF0B3_Neuschnee_Momentan-
wert_cm'] = Neuschnee_Momentanwert_cm
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLF0B3_Foehnindex'] = Foehnindex
print('-- successfull')
elif station == 'SLF0BW':
print('Station selected', station)
print('Set Columns section by Timestamp: ', Timestamp)
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLF0BW_Globalstrahlung_wm2'] =
Globalstrahlung_wm2
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLF0BW_Luftdruckaender-
ung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa'] = Luftdruckaenderung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLF0BW_Niederschlag_Stunden-
summe_mm'] = Niederschlag_Stundensumme_mm
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLF0BW_Windgeschwindigkeit_ms'] =
Windgeschwindigkeit_ms
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLF0BW_Windrichtung_grad'] =
Windrichtung_grad
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLF0BW_dewpoint_AGL_C'] = Tau-
punkt_Momentanwert_celsius
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLF0BW_dewpoint_ASL_C'] = CALCU-
LATED_dewpoint_asl_C
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLF0BW_pressure_AGL_hPa'] = Luft-
druck_Barometerhoehe_QFE_Stundenmittel_hPa
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLF0BW_pressure_asl_hPa'] = CAL-
CULATED_pressure_asl_hPa
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLF0BW_rel_Luft-
feuchtigkeit_Stundenmittel_prozent'] = rel_Luftfeuchtigkeit_Stundenmittel_prozent
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLF0BW_sonnenscheindauer_stunden-
summe_min'] = sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLF0BW_temp_AGL_C'] =
Temp_2mAGL_C
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLF0BW_temp_asl_C'] = CALCU-
LATED_temp_asl_C
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLF0BW_Schnee_Momentanwert_cm'] =
Schnee_Momentanwert_cm
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLF0BW_Neuschnee_Momentan-
wert_cm'] = Neuschnee_Momentanwert_cm
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLF0BW_Foehnindex'] = Foehnindex
print('-- successfull')
elif station == 'SLFSP2':
print('Station selected', station)
print('Set Columns section by Timestamp: ', Timestamp)
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLFSP2_Globalstrahlung_wm2'] =
Globalstrahlung_wm2

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df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLFSP2_Luftdruckaender-
ung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa'] = Luftdruckaenderung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLFSP2_Niederschlag_Stunden-
summe_mm'] = Niederschlag_Stundensumme_mm
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLFSP2_Windgeschwindigkeit_ms'] =
Windgeschwindigkeit_ms
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLFSP2_Windrichtung_grad'] =
Windrichtung_grad
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLFSP2_dewpoint_AGL_C'] = Tau-
punkt_Momentanwert_celsius
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLFSP2_dewpoint_AS_L_C'] = CALCU-
LATED_dewpoint_asl_C
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLFSP2_pressure_AGL_hPa'] = Luft-
druck_Barometerhoehe_QFE_Stundenmittel_hPa
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLFSP2_pressure_asl_hPa'] = CAL-
CULATED_pressure_asl_hPa
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLFSP2_rel_Luft-
feuchtigkeit_Stundenmittel_prozent'] = rel_Luftfeuchtigkeit_Stundenmittel_prozent
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLFSP2_sonnenscheindauer_stunden-
summe_min'] = sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLFSP2_temp_AGL_C'] =
Temp_2mAGL_C
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLFSP2_temp_asl_C'] = CALCU-
LATED_temp_asl_C
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLFSP2_Schnee_Momentanwert_cm'] =
Schnee_Momentanwert_cm
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLFSP2_Neuschnee_Momentan-
wert_cm'] = Neuschnee_Momentanwert_cm
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLFSP2_Foehnindex'] = Foehnindex
print('-- successfull')
elif station == 'SLFSP3':
    print('Station selected', station)
    print('Set Columns section by Timestamp: ', Timestamp)
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLFSP3_Globalstrahlung_wm2'] =
Globalstrahlung_wm2
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLFSP3_Luftdruckaender-
ung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa'] = Luftdruckaenderung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLFSP3_Niederschlag_Stunden-
summe_mm'] = Niederschlag_Stundensumme_mm
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLFSP3_Windgeschwindigkeit_ms'] =
Windgeschwindigkeit_ms
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLFSP3_Windrichtung_grad'] =
Windrichtung_grad
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLFSP3_dewpoint_AGL_C'] = Tau-
punkt_Momentanwert_celsius
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLFSP3_dewpoint_AS_L_C'] = CALCU-
LATED_dewpoint_asl_C
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLFSP3_pressure_AGL_hPa'] = Luft-
druck_Barometerhoehe_QFE_Stundenmittel_hPa
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLFSP3_pressure_asl_hPa'] = CAL-
CULATED_pressure_asl_hPa
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLFSP3_rel_Luft-
feuchtigkeit_Stundenmittel_prozent'] = rel_Luftfeuchtigkeit_Stundenmittel_prozent
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLFSP3_sonnenscheindauer_stunden-
summe_min'] = sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLFSP3_temp_AGL_C'] =
Temp_2mAGL_C
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLFSP3_temp_asl_C'] = CALCU-
LATED_temp_asl_C
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLFSP3_Schnee_Momentanwert_cm'] =
Schnee_Momentanwert_cm
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLFSP3_Neuschnee_Momentan-
wert_cm'] = Neuschnee_Momentanwert_cm
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_SLFSP3_Foehnindex'] = Foehnindex
print('-- successfull')
elif station == 'ULR':
    print('Station selected', station)
    print('Set Columns section by Timestamp: ', Timestamp)
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_ULR_Globalstrahlung_wm2'] = Glob-
alstrahlung_wm2
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_ULR_Luftdruckaender-
ung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa'] = Luftdruckaenderung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_ULR_Niederschlag_Stunden-
summe_mm'] = Niederschlag_Stundensumme_mm
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_ULR_Windgeschwindigkeit_ms'] =
Windgeschwindigkeit_ms
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_ULR_Windrichtung_grad'] =
Windrichtung_grad
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_ULR_dewpoint_AGL_C'] = Tau-
punkt_Momentanwert_celsius
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_ULR_dewpoint_AS_L_C'] = CALCU-
LATED_dewpoint_asl_C
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_ULR_pressure_AGL_hPa'] = Luft-
druck_Barometerhoehe_QFE_Stundenmittel_hPa
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_ULR_pressure_asl_hPa'] = CALCU-
LATED_pressure_asl_hPa

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df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_ULR_rel_Luftfeuchtigkeit_Stunden-
mittel_prozent'] = rel_Luftfeuchtigkeit_Stundenmittel_prozent
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_ULR_sonnenscheindauer_stunden-
summe_min'] = sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_ULR_temp_AGL_C'] = Temp_2mAGL_C
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_ULR_temp_asl_C'] = CALCU-
LATED_temp_asl_C
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_ULR_Schnee_Momentanwert_cm'] =
Schnee_Momentanwert_cm
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_ULR_Neuschnee_Momentanwert_cm'] =
Neuschnee_Momentanwert_cm
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_ULR_Foehnindex'] = Foehnindex
print('-- successfull')
elif station == 'VIS':
print('Station selected', station)
print('Set Columns section by Timestamp: ', Timestamp)
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_VIS_Globalstrahlung_wm2'] = Glob-
alstrahlung_wm2
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_VIS_Luftdruckaender-
ung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa'] = Luftdruckaenderung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_VIS_Niederschlag_Stunden-
summe_mm'] = Niederschlag_Stundensumme_mm
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_VIS_Windgeschwindigkeit_ms'] =
Windgeschwindigkeit_ms
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_VIS_Windrichtung_grad'] =
Windrichtung_grad
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_VIS_dewpoint_AGL_C'] = Tau-
punkt_Momentanwert_celsius
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_VIS_dewpoint_ASL_C'] = CALCU-
LATED_dewpoint_asl_C
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_VIS_pressure_AGL_hPa'] = Luft-
druck_Barometerhoehe_QFE_Stundenmittel_hPa
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_VIS_pressure_asl_hPa'] = CALCU-
LATED_pressure_asl_hPa
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_VIS_rel_Luftfeuchtigkeit_Stunden-
mittel_prozent'] = rel_Luftfeuchtigkeit_Stundenmittel_prozent
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_VIS_sonnenscheindauer_stunden-
summe_min'] = sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_VIS_temp_AGL_C'] = Temp_2mAGL_C
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_VIS_temp_asl_C'] = CALCU-
LATED_temp_asl_C
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_VIS_Schnee_Momentanwert_cm'] =
Schnee_Momentanwert_cm
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_VIS_Neuschnee_Momentanwert_cm'] =
Neuschnee_Momentanwert_cm
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_VIS_Foehnindex'] = Foehnindex
print('-- successfull')
elif station == 'VSRB':
print('Station selected', station)
print('Set Columns section by Timestamp: ', Timestamp)
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_VSRB_Globalstrahlung_wm2'] =
Globalstrahlung_wm2
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_VSRB_Luftdruckaender-
ung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa'] = Luftdruckaenderung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_VSRB_Niederschlag_Stunden-
summe_mm'] = Niederschlag_Stundensumme_mm
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_VSRB_Windgeschwindigkeit_ms'] =
Windgeschwindigkeit_ms
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_VSRB_Windrichtung_grad'] =
Windrichtung_grad
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_VSRB_dewpoint_AGL_C'] = Tau-
punkt_Momentanwert_celsius
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_VSRB_dewpoint_ASL_C'] = CALCU-
LATED_dewpoint_asl_C
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_VSRB_pressure_AGL_hPa'] = Luft-
druck_Barometerhoehe_QFE_Stundenmittel_hPa
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_VSRB_pressure_asl_hPa'] = CALCU-
LATED_pressure_asl_hPa
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_VSRB_rel_Luftfeuchtigkeit_Stund-
enmittel_prozent'] = rel_Luftfeuchtigkeit_Stundenmittel_prozent
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_VSRB_sonnenscheindauer_stunden-
summe_min'] = sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_VSRB_temp_AGL_C'] = Temp_2mAGL_C
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_VSRB_temp_asl_C'] = CALCU-
LATED_temp_asl_C
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_VSRB_Schnee_Momentanwert_cm'] =
Schnee_Momentanwert_cm
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_VSRB_Neuschnee_Momentanwert_cm']
= Neuschnee_Momentanwert_cm
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_VSRB_Foehnindex'] = Foehnindex
print('-- successfull')
elif station == 'WSLVS':
print('Station selected', station)
print('Set Columns section by Timestamp: ', Timestamp)
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_WSLVSB_Globalstrahlung_wm2'] =
Globalstrahlung_wm2

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df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_WSLVSB_Luftdruckaender-
ung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa'] = Luftdruckaenderung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_WSLVSB_Niederschlag_Stunden-
summe_mm'] = Niederschlag_Stundensumme_mm
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_WSLVSB_Windgeschwindigkeit_ms'] =
Windgeschwindigkeit_ms
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_WSLVSB_Windrichtung_grad'] =
Windrichtung_grad
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_WSLVSB_dewpoint_AGL_C'] = Tau-
punkt_Momentanwert_celsius
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_WSLVSB_dewpoint_AS_L_C'] = CALCU-
LATED_dewpoint_asl_C
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_WSLVSB_pressure_AGL_hPa'] = Luft-
druck_Barometerhoehe_QFE_Stundenmittel_hPa
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_WSLVSB_pressure_asl_hPa'] = CAL-
CULATED_pressure_asl_hPa
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_WSLVSB_rel_Luft-
feuchtigkeit_Stundenmittel_prozent'] = rel_Luftfeuchtigkeit_Stundenmittel_prozent
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_WSLVSB_sonnenscheindauer_stunden-
summe_min'] = sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_WSLVSB_temp_AGL_C'] =
Temp_2mAGL_C
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_WSLVSB_temp_asl_C'] = CALCU-
LATED_temp_asl_C
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_WSLVSB_Schnee_Momentanwert_cm'] =
Schnee_Momentanwert_cm
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_WSLVSB_Neuschnee_Momentan-
wert_cm'] = Neuschnee_Momentanwert_cm
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_WSLVSB_Foehnindex'] = Foehnindex
print('-- successfull')
elif station == 'WSLVSF':
    print('Station selected', station)
    print('Set Columns section by Timestamp: ', Timestamp)
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_WSLVSF_Globalstrahlung_wm2'] =
Globalstrahlung_wm2
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_WSLVSF_Luftdruckaender-
ung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa'] = Luftdruckaenderung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_WSLVSF_Niederschlag_Stunden-
summe_mm'] = Niederschlag_Stundensumme_mm
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_WSLVSF_Windgeschwindigkeit_ms'] =
Windgeschwindigkeit_ms
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_WSLVSF_Windrichtung_grad'] =
Windrichtung_grad
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_WSLVSF_dewpoint_AGL_C'] = Tau-
punkt_Momentanwert_celsius
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_WSLVSF_dewpoint_AS_L_C'] = CALCU-
LATED_dewpoint_asl_C
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_WSLVSF_pressure_AGL_hPa'] = Luft-
druck_Barometerhoehe_QFE_Stundenmittel_hPa
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_WSLVSF_pressure_asl_hPa'] = CAL-
CULATED_pressure_asl_hPa
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_WSLVSF_rel_Luft-
feuchtigkeit_Stundenmittel_prozent'] = rel_Luftfeuchtigkeit_Stundenmittel_prozent
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_WSLVSF_sonnenscheindauer_stunden-
summe_min'] = sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_WSLVSF_temp_AGL_C'] =
Temp_2mAGL_C
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_WSLVSF_temp_asl_C'] = CALCU-
LATED_temp_asl_C
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_WSLVSF_Schnee_Momentanwert_cm'] =
Schnee_Momentanwert_cm
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_WSLVSF_Neuschnee_Momentan-
wert_cm'] = Neuschnee_Momentanwert_cm
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_WSLVSF_Foehnindex'] = Foehnindex
print('-- successfull')
elif station == 'MOBELLW':
    print('Station selected', station)
    print('Set Columns section by Timestamp: ', Timestamp)
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MOBELLW_Globalstrahlung_wm2'] =
Globalstrahlung_wm2
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MOBELLW_Luftdruckaender-
ung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa'] = Luftdruckaenderung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MOBELLW_Niederschlag_Stunden-
summe_mm'] = Niederschlag_Stundensumme_mm
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MOBELLW_Windgeschwindigkeit_ms']
= Windgeschwindigkeit_ms
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MOBELLW_Windrichtung_grad'] =
Windrichtung_grad
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MOBELLW_dewpoint_AGL_C'] = Tau-
punkt_Momentanwert_celsius
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MOBELLW_dewpoint_AS_L_C'] = CALCU-
LATED_dewpoint_asl_C
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MOBELLW_pressure_AGL_hPa'] =
Luftdruck_Barometerhoehe_QFE_Stundenmittel_hPa
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MOBELLW_pressure_asl_hPa'] = CAL-
CULATED_pressure_asl_hPa

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df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MOBELLW_rel_Luft-
feuchtigkeit_Stundenmittel_prozent'] = rel_Luftfeuchtigkeit_Stundenmittel_prozent
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MOBELLW_sonnen-
scheindauer_stundensumme_min'] = sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MOBELLW_temp_AGL_C'] =
Temp_2mAGL_C
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MOBELLW_temp_asl_C'] = CALCU-
LATED_temp_asl_C
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MOBELLW_Schnee_Momentanwert_cm']
= Schnee_Momentanwert_cm
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MOBELLW_Neuschnee_Momentan-
wert_cm'] = Neuschnee_Momentanwert_cm
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MOBELLW_Foehnindex'] = Foehnindex
print('-- successfull')
elif station == 'MOBETT':
    print('Station selected', station)
    print('Set Columns section by Timestamp: ', Timestamp)
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MOBETT_Globalstrahlung_wm2'] =
Globalstrahlung_wm2
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MOBETT_Luftdruckaender-
ung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa'] = Luftdruckaenderung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MOBETT_Niederschlag_Stunden-
summe_mm'] = Niederschlag_Stundensumme_mm
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MOBETT_Windgeschwindigkeit_ms'] =
Windgeschwindigkeit_ms
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MOBETT_Windrichtung_grad'] =
Windrichtung_grad
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MOBETT_dewpoint_AGL_C'] = Tau-
punkt_Momentanwert_celsius
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MOBETT_dewpoint_ASL_C'] = CALCU-
LATED_dewpoint_asl_C
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MOBETT_pressure_AGL_hPa'] = Luft-
druck_Barometerhoehe_QFE_Stundenmittel_hPa
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MOBETT_pressure_asl_hPa'] = CAL-
CULATED_pressure_asl_hPa
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MOBETT_rel_Luft-
feuchtigkeit_Stundenmittel_prozent'] = rel_Luftfeuchtigkeit_Stundenmittel_prozent
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MOBETT_sonnenscheindauer_stunden-
summe_min'] = sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MOBETT_temp_AGL_C'] =
Temp_2mAGL_C
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MOBETT_temp_asl_C'] = CALCU-
LATED_temp_asl_C
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MOBETT_Schnee_Momentanwert_cm'] =
Schnee_Momentanwert_cm
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MOBETT_Neuschnee_Momentan-
wert_cm'] = Neuschnee_Momentanwert_cm
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MOBETT_Foehnindex'] = Foehnindex
print('-- successfull')
elif station == 'MOBINN':
    print('Station selected', station)
    print('Set Columns section by Timestamp: ', Timestamp)
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MOBINN_Globalstrahlung_wm2'] =
Globalstrahlung_wm2
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MOBINN_Luftdruckaender-
ung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa'] = Luftdruckaenderung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MOBINN_Niederschlag_Stunden-
summe_mm'] = Niederschlag_Stundensumme_mm
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MOBINN_Windgeschwindigkeit_ms'] =
Windgeschwindigkeit_ms
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MOBINN_Windrichtung_grad'] =
Windrichtung_grad
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MOBINN_dewpoint_AGL_C'] = Tau-
punkt_Momentanwert_celsius
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MOBINN_dewpoint_ASL_C'] = CALCU-
LATED_dewpoint_asl_C
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MOBINN_pressure_AGL_hPa'] = Luft-
druck_Barometerhoehe_QFE_Stundenmittel_hPa
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MOBINN_pressure_asl_hPa'] = CAL-
CULATED_pressure_asl_hPa
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MOBINN_rel_Luft-
feuchtigkeit_Stundenmittel_prozent'] = rel_Luftfeuchtigkeit_Stundenmittel_prozent
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MOBINN_sonnenscheindauer_stunden-
summe_min'] = sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MOBINN_temp_AGL_C'] =
Temp_2mAGL_C
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MOBINN_temp_asl_C'] = CALCU-
LATED_temp_asl_C
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MOBINN_Schnee_Momentanwert_cm'] =
Schnee_Momentanwert_cm
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MOBINN_Neuschnee_Momentan-
wert_cm'] = Neuschnee_Momentanwert_cm
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MOBINN_Foehnindex'] = Foehnindex
print('-- successfull')
elif station == 'MOBLITZINGU':
    print('Station selected', station)
    print('Set Columns section by Timestamp: ', Timestamp)

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df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MOBLITZINGU_Globalstrahlung_wm2']
= Globalstrahlung_wm2
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MOBLITZINGU_Luftdruckaender-
ung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa'] = Luftdruckaenderung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MOBLITZINGU_Niederschlag_Stunden-
summe_mm'] = Niederschlag_Stundensumme_mm
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MOBLITZ-
INGU_Windgeschwindigkeit_ms'] = Windgeschwindigkeit_ms
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MOBLITZINGU_Windrichtung_grad'] =
Windrichtung_grad
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MOBLITZINGU_dewpoint_AGL_C'] =
Taupunkt_Momentanwert_celsius
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MOBLITZINGU_dewpoint_AS_L_C'] =
CALCULATED_dewpoint_asl_C
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MOBLITZINGU_pressure_AGL_hPa'] =
Luftdruck_Barometerhoehe_QFE_Stundenmittel_hPa
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MOBLITZINGU_pressure_asl_hPa'] =
CALCULATED_pressure_asl_hPa
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MOBLITZINGU_rel_Luft-
feuchtigkeit_Stundenmittel_prozent'] = rel_Luftfeuchtigkeit_Stundenmittel_prozent
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MOBLITZINGU_sonnen-
scheindauer_stundensumme_min'] = sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MOBLITZINGU_temp_AGL_C'] =
Temp_2mAGL_C
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MOBLITZINGU_temp_asl_C'] = CALCU-
LATED_temp_asl_C
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MOBLITZINGU_Schnee_Momentan-
wert_cm'] = Schnee_Momentanwert_cm
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MOBLITZINGU_Neuschnee_Momentan-
wert_cm'] = Neuschnee_Momentanwert_cm
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MOBLITZINGU_Foehnindex'] =
Foehnindex
print('-- successfull')
elif station == 'MOBRIG':
print('Station selected', station)
print('Set Columns section by Timestamp: ', Timestamp)
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MOBRIG_Globalstrahlung_wm2'] =
Globalstrahlung_wm2
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MOBRIG_Luftdruckaender-
ung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa'] = Luftdruckaenderung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MOBRIG_Niederschlag_Stunden-
summe_mm'] = Niederschlag_Stundensumme_mm
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MOBRIG_Windgeschwindigkeit_ms'] =
Windgeschwindigkeit_ms
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MOBRIG_Windrichtung_grad'] =
Windrichtung_grad
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MOBRIG_dewpoint_AGL_C'] = Tau-
punkt_Momentanwert_celsius
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MOBRIG_dewpoint_AS_L_C'] = CALCU-
LATED_dewpoint_asl_C
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MOBRIG_pressure_AGL_hPa'] = Luft-
druck_Barometerhoehe_QFE_Stundenmittel_hPa
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MOBRIG_pressure_asl_hPa'] = CAL-
CULATED_pressure_asl_hPa
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MOBRIG_rel_Luft-
feuchtigkeit_Stundenmittel_prozent'] = rel_Luftfeuchtigkeit_Stundenmittel_prozent
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MOBRIG_sonnenscheindauer_stunden-
summe_min'] = sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MOBRIG_temp_AGL_C'] =
Temp_2mAGL_C
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MOBRIG_temp_asl_C'] = CALCU-
LATED_temp_asl_C
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MOBRIG_Schnee_Momentanwert_cm'] =
Schnee_Momentanwert_cm
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MOBRIG_Neuschnee_Momentan-
wert_cm'] = Neuschnee_Momentanwert_cm
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MOBRIG_Foehnindex'] = Foehnindex
print('-- successfull')
elif station == 'MOCHAES':
print('Station selected', station)
print('Set Columns section by Timestamp: ', Timestamp)
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MOCHAES_Globalstrahlung_wm2'] =
Globalstrahlung_wm2
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MOCHAES_Luftdruckaender-
ung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa'] = Luftdruckaenderung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MOCHAES_Niederschlag_Stunden-
summe_mm'] = Niederschlag_Stundensumme_mm
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MOCHAES_Windgeschwindigkeit_ms']
= Windgeschwindigkeit_ms
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MOCHAES_Windrichtung_grad'] =
Windrichtung_grad
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MOCHAES_dewpoint_AGL_C'] = Tau-
punkt_Momentanwert_celsius
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MOCHAES_dewpoint_AS_L_C'] = CALCU-
LATED_dewpoint_asl_C
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MOCHAES_pressure_AGL_hPa'] =
Luftdruck_Barometerhoehe_QFE_Stundenmittel_hPa

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df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MOCHAES_pressure_asl_hPa'] = CAL-
CULATED_pressure_asl_hPa
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MOCHAES_rel_Luft-
feuchtigkeit_Stundenmittel_prozent'] = rel_Luftfeuchtigkeit_Stundenmittel_prozent
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MOCHAES_sonnen-
scheindauer_stundensumme_min'] = sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MOCHAES_temp_AGL_C'] =
Temp_2mAGL_C
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MOCHAES_temp_asl_C'] = CALCU-
LATED_temp_asl_C
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MOCHAES_Schnee_Momentanwert_cm']
= Schnee_Momentanwert_cm
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MOCHAES_Neuschnee_Momentan-
wert_cm'] = Neuschnee_Momentanwert_cm
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MOCHAES_Foehnindex'] = Foehnindex
print('-- successfull')
elif station == 'MODEISCH':
print('Station selected', station)
print('Set Columns section by Timestamp: ', Timestamp)
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MODEISCH_Globalstrahlung_wm2'] =
Globalstrahlung_wm2
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MODEISCH_Luftdruckaender-
ung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa'] = Luftdruckaenderung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MODEISCH_Niederschlag_Stunden-
summe_mm'] = Niederschlag_Stundensumme_mm
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MODEISCH_Windgeschwindigkeit_ms']
= Windgeschwindigkeit_ms
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MODEISCH_Windrichtung_grad'] =
Windrichtung_grad
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MODEISCH_dewpoint_AGL_C'] = Tau-
punkt_Momentanwert_celsius
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MODEISCH_dewpoint_AS_L_C'] = CAL-
CULATED_dewpoint_asl_C
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MODEISCH_pressure_AGL_hPa'] =
Luftdruck_Barometerhoehe_QFE_Stundenmittel_hPa
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MODEISCH_pressure_asl_hPa'] =
CALCULATED_pressure_asl_hPa
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MODEISCH_rel_Luft-
feuchtigkeit_Stundenmittel_prozent'] = rel_Luftfeuchtigkeit_Stundenmittel_prozent
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MODEISCH_sonnen-
scheindauer_stundensumme_min'] = sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MODEISCH_temp_AGL_C'] =
Temp_2mAGL_C
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MODEISCH_temp_asl_C'] = CALCU-
LATED_temp_asl_C
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MODEISCH_Schnee_Momentanwert_cm']
= Schnee_Momentanwert_cm
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MODEISCH_Neuschnee_Momentan-
wert_cm'] = Neuschnee_Momentanwert_cm
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MODEISCH_Foehnindex'] = Foehnindex
print('-- successfull')
elif station == 'MOFIESCH':
print('Station selected', station)
print('Set Columns section by Timestamp: ', Timestamp)
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MOFIESCH_Globalstrahlung_wm2'] =
Globalstrahlung_wm2
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MOFIESCH_Luftdruckaender-
ung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa'] = Luftdruckaenderung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MOFIESCH_Niederschlag_Stunden-
summe_mm'] = Niederschlag_Stundensumme_mm
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MOFIESCH_Windgeschwindigkeit_ms']
= Windgeschwindigkeit_ms
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MOFIESCH_Windrichtung_grad'] =
Windrichtung_grad
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MOFIESCH_dewpoint_AGL_C'] = Tau-
punkt_Momentanwert_celsius
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MOFIESCH_dewpoint_AS_L_C'] = CAL-
CULATED_dewpoint_asl_C
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MOFIESCH_pressure_AGL_hPa'] =
Luftdruck_Barometerhoehe_QFE_Stundenmittel_hPa
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MOFIESCH_pressure_asl_hPa'] =
CALCULATED_pressure_asl_hPa
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MOFIESCH_rel_Luft-
feuchtigkeit_Stundenmittel_prozent'] = rel_Luftfeuchtigkeit_Stundenmittel_prozent
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MOFIESCH_sonnen-
scheindauer_stundensumme_min'] = sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MOFIESCH_temp_AGL_C'] =
Temp_2mAGL_C
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MOFIESCH_temp_asl_C'] = CALCU-
LATED_temp_asl_C
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MOFIESCH_Schnee_Momentanwert_cm']
= Schnee_Momentanwert_cm
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MOFIESCH_Neuschnee_Momentan-
wert_cm'] = Neuschnee_Momentanwert_cm
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MOFIESCH_Foehnindex'] = Foehnindex

```

```

    print('-- successfull')
elif station == 'MOGRIMSEL':
    print('Station selected', station)
    print('Set Columns section by Timestamp: ', Timestamp)
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MOGRIMSEL_Globalstrahlung_wm2'] =
Globalstrahlung_wm2
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MOGRIMSEL_Luftdruckaender-
ung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa'] = Luftdruckaenderung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MOGRIMSEL_Niederschlag_Stunden-
summe_mm'] = Niederschlag_Stundensumme_mm
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MOGRIM-
SEL_Windgeschwindigkeit_ms'] = Windgeschwindigkeit_ms
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MOGRIMSEL_Windrichtung_grad'] =
Windrichtung_grad
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MOGRIMSEL_dewpoint_AGL_C'] = Tau-
punkt_Momentanwert_celsius
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MOGRIMSEL_dewpoint_AS_L_C'] = CAL-
CULATED_dewpoint_asl_C
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MOGRIMSEL_pressure_AGL_hPa'] =
Luftdruck_Barometerhoehe_QFE_Stundenmittel_hPa
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MOGRIMSEL_pressure_asl_hPa'] =
CALCULATED_pressure_asl_hPa
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MOGRIMSEL_rel_Luft-
feuchtigkeit_Stundenmittel_prozent'] = rel_Luftfeuchtigkeit_Stundenmittel_prozent
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MOGRIMSEL_sonnen-
scheindauer_stundensumme_min'] = sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MOGRIMSEL_temp_AGL_C'] =
Temp_2mAGL_C
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MOGRIMSEL_temp_asl_C'] = CALCU-
LATED_temp_asl_C
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MOGRIMSEL_Schnee_Momentan-
wert_cm'] = Schnee_Momentanwert_cm
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MOGRIMSEL_Neuschnee_Momentan-
wert_cm'] = Neuschnee_Momentanwert_cm
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MOGRIMSEL_Foehnindex'] = Foehnindex
    print('-- successfull')
elif station == 'MONAT':
    print('Station selected', station)
    print('Set Columns section by Timestamp: ', Timestamp)
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MONAT_Globalstrahlung_wm2'] =
Globalstrahlung_wm2
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MONAT_Luftdruckaender-
ung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa'] = Luftdruckaenderung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MONAT_Niederschlag_Stunden-
summe_mm'] = Niederschlag_Stundensumme_mm
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MONAT_Windgeschwindigkeit_ms'] =
Windgeschwindigkeit_ms
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MONAT_Windrichtung_grad'] = Wind-
richtung_grad
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MONAT_dewpoint_AGL_C'] = Tau-
punkt_Momentanwert_celsius
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MONAT_dewpoint_AS_L_C'] = CALCU-
LATED_dewpoint_asl_C
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MONAT_pressure_AGL_hPa'] = Luft-
druck_Barometerhoehe_QFE_Stundenmittel_hPa
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MONAT_pressure_asl_hPa'] = CALCU-
LATED_pressure_asl_hPa
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MONAT_rel_Luftfeuchtigkeit_Stund-
enmittel_prozent'] = rel_Luftfeuchtigkeit_Stundenmittel_prozent
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MONAT_sonnenscheindauer_stunden-
summe_min'] = sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MONAT_temp_AGL_C'] = Temp_2mAGL_C
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MONAT_temp_asl_C'] = CALCU-
LATED_temp_asl_C
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MONAT_Schnee_Momentanwert_cm'] =
Schnee_Momentanwert_cm
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MONAT_Neuschnee_Momentanwert_cm']
= Neuschnee_Momentanwert_cm
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MONAT_Foehnindex'] = Foehnindex
    print('-- successfull')
elif station == 'MORIEDA':
    print('Station selected', station)
    print('Set Columns section by Timestamp: ', Timestamp)
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MORIEDA_Globalstrahlung_wm2'] =
Globalstrahlung_wm2
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MORIEDA_Luftdruckaender-
ung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa'] = Luftdruckaenderung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MORIEDA_Niederschlag_Stunden-
summe_mm'] = Niederschlag_Stundensumme_mm
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MORIEDA_Windgeschwindigkeit_ms']
= Windgeschwindigkeit_ms
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MORIEDA_Windrichtung_grad'] =
Windrichtung_grad
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MORIEDA_dewpoint_AGL_C'] = Tau-
punkt_Momentanwert_celsius

```

```

df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MORIEDA_dewpoint_ASL_C'] = CALCU-
LATED_dewpoint_asl_C
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MORIEDA_pressure_AGL_hPa'] =
Luftdruck_Barometerhoehe_QFE_Stundenmittel_hPa
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MORIEDA_pressure_asl_hPa'] = CAL-
CULATED_pressure_asl_hPa
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MORIEDA_rel_Luft-
feuchtigkeit_Stundenmittel_prozent'] = rel_Luftfeuchtigkeit_Stundenmittel_prozent
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MORIEDA_sonnen-
scheindauer_stundensumme_min'] = sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MORIEDA_temp_AGL_C'] =
Temp_2mAGL_C
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MORIEDA_temp_asl_C'] = CALCU-
LATED_temp_asl_C
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MORIEDA_Schnee_Momentanwert_cm']
= Schnee_Momentanwert_cm
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MORIEDA_Neuschnee_Momentan-
wert_cm'] = Neuschnee_Momentanwert_cm
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MORIEDA_Foehnindex'] = Foehnindex
print('-- successfull')
elif station == 'MORIEDF':
print('Station selected', station)
print('Set Columns section by Timestamp: ', Timestamp)
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MORIEDF_Globalstrahlung_wm2'] =
Globalstrahlung_wm2
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MORIEDF_Luftdruckaender-
ung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa'] = Luftdruckaenderung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MORIEDF_Niederschlag_Stunden-
summe_mm'] = Niederschlag_Stundensumme_mm
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MORIEDF_Windgeschwindigkeit_ms']
= Windgeschwindigkeit_ms
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MORIEDF_Windrichtung_grad'] =
Windrichtung_grad
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MORIEDF_dewpoint_AGL_C'] = Tau-
punkt_Momentanwert_celsius
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MORIEDF_dewpoint_ASL_C'] = CALCU-
LATED_dewpoint_asl_C
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MORIEDF_pressure_AGL_hPa'] =
Luftdruck_Barometerhoehe_QFE_Stundenmittel_hPa
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MORIEDF_pressure_asl_hPa'] = CAL-
CULATED_pressure_asl_hPa
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MORIEDF_rel_Luft-
feuchtigkeit_Stundenmittel_prozent'] = rel_Luftfeuchtigkeit_Stundenmittel_prozent
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MORIEDF_sonnen-
scheindauer_stundensumme_min'] = sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MORIEDF_temp_AGL_C'] =
Temp_2mAGL_C
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MORIEDF_temp_asl_C'] = CALCU-
LATED_temp_asl_C
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MORIEDF_Schnee_Momentanwert_cm']
= Schnee_Momentanwert_cm
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MORIEDF_Neuschnee_Momentan-
wert_cm'] = Neuschnee_Momentanwert_cm
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MORIEDF_Foehnindex'] = Foehnindex
print('-- successfull')
elif station == 'MOSIMP':
print('Station selected', station)
print('Set Columns section by Timestamp: ', Timestamp)
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MOSIMP_Globalstrahlung_wm2'] =
Globalstrahlung_wm2
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MOSIMP_Luftdruckaender-
ung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa'] = Luftdruckaenderung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MOSIMP_Niederschlag_Stunden-
summe_mm'] = Niederschlag_Stundensumme_mm
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MOSIMP_Windgeschwindigkeit_ms'] =
Windgeschwindigkeit_ms
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MOSIMP_Windrichtung_grad'] =
Windrichtung_grad
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MOSIMP_dewpoint_AGL_C'] = Tau-
punkt_Momentanwert_celsius
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MOSIMP_dewpoint_ASL_C'] = CALCU-
LATED_dewpoint_asl_C
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MOSIMP_pressure_AGL_hPa'] = Luft-
druck_Barometerhoehe_QFE_Stundenmittel_hPa
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MOSIMP_pressure_asl_hPa'] = CAL-
CULATED_pressure_asl_hPa
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MOSIMP_rel_Luft-
feuchtigkeit_Stundenmittel_prozent'] = rel_Luftfeuchtigkeit_Stundenmittel_prozent
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MOSIMP_sonnenscheindauer_stunden-
summe_min'] = sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MOSIMP_temp_AGL_C'] =
Temp_2mAGL_C
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MOSIMP_temp_asl_C'] = CALCU-
LATED_temp_asl_C
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MOSIMP_Schnee_Momentanwert_cm'] =
Schnee_Momentanwert_cm

```

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df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MOSIMP_Neuschnee_Momentanwert_cm'] = Neuschnee_Momentanwert_cm
df_copy.loc[df_copy['GPS_timestamp_cleaned'] == Timestamp, 'VALUE_MOSIMP_Foehnindex'] = Foehnindex
print('-- successfull')
else:
    print('Station ist nicht im Verzeichnis!')

# In[ ]:

df_copy

# In[ ]:

df_copy.info()

# In[ ]:

df_copy['UTC1'] = df_copy['UTC']
df_copy = df_copy.set_index('UTC1')
df_copy = df_copy.sort_index()

# In[ ]:

del df_idw
gc.collect()

# In[ ]:

df_copy

# In[ ]:

path5 = path_to_output + 'gps_weather_Data_and_Weights.csv'

# In[ ]:

df_copy.to_csv(path5)

# In[ ]:

df_copy = pd.read_csv(path5)

# In[ ]:

df_copy.columns.get_loc("INTERPOL_POINT_temp_asl_C")

# In[ ]:

df_copy.columns.get_loc("Station_BIN")

# In[ ]:

df_copy.columns.get_loc("VALUE_SLFBEL_temp_asl_C")

# In[ ]:

interp_cols = [col for col in df_copy.columns if 'INTERPOL' in col]
df_interp = df_copy[interp_cols]

# In[ ]:

```

```
df_interpol
```

```
# In[ ]:
```

```
value_cols = [col for col in df_copy.columns if 'VALUE' in col]
weight_cols = [col for col in df_copy.columns if 'Weight' in col]
df_values = df_copy[value_cols + weight_cols]
```

```
# In[ ]:
```

```
df_values = df_values.sort_index(axis=1)
```

```
# In[ ]:
```

```
df_values
```

```
# In[ ]:
```

```
stations_list = df_weather.Station.unique().tolist()
interpol_list = df_interpol.columns.tolist()
parameters_list = []
word = 'INTERPOL_POINT'
for x in interpol_list:
    print(x)
    parameters_list.append(x.replace(word, ""))
parameters_list
```

```
# In[ ]:
```

```
parameter_cols = [col for col in df_values.columns if 'VALUE' in col]
parameter_cols
```

```
# In[ ]:
```

```
weight_cols = [col for col in df_values.columns if 'Weight' in col]
weight_cols
```

```
# In[ ]:
```

```
temporary_df = df_values[parameter_cols + weight_cols]
```

```
# stations_list = stations_list[0:2]
# stations_list
```

```
# In[ ]:
```

```
DF_list = list()
```

```
# In[ ]:
```

```
temporary_df.columns.tolist()
```

```
# In[ ]:
```

```
for x in stations_list:
    for y in parameters_list:
        Station = x
        Parameter = y
        Value = 'VALUE_' + Station + Parameter
        Weight = "Weight_" + Station
        Result = 'Result_' + Station + Parameter
        Weight_Parameter = Weight + Parameter
        print('Station: ', Station, ' Parameter: ', Parameter, ' Value: ', Value, ' Weight: ', Weight, ' Result: ', Result, ' Weight_Parameter: ', Weight_Parameter)

        values = [col for col in df_values.columns if Value in col]
```

```

weights = [col for col in df_values.columns if Weight in col]
temporary_df = df_values[values + weights]

temporary_df[Weight_Parameter] = temporary_df[Weight]
del temporary_df[Weight]
Temp_ASL = []
weights = []

#calculating result by value * weight parameter
temporary_df[Result] = (temporary_df[Value] * temporary_df[Weight_Parameter])
#filling result and weight by 0 where value = nan
temporary_df[Result] = np.where(temporary_df[Value].isnull(),0,temporary_df[Result])
temporary_df[Weight_Parameter] = np.where(temporary_df[Value].isnull(),0,temporary_df[Weight_Parame-
ter])

DF_list.append(temporary_df)

# Station = stations_list[0]
# Parameter = parameters_list[0]
# Value = 'VALUE_' + Station + Parameter
# Weight = "Weight_" + Station
# Result = 'Result_' + Station + Parameter
# Weight_Parameter = Weight + Parameter
# print('Station: ', Station, ' Parameter: ', Parameter, ' Value: ', Value, ' Weight: ', Weight, ' Result: ',
Result, ' Weight_Parameter: ', Weight_Parameter)
#
# values = [col for col in df_Temp_ASL.columns if Value in col]
# weights = [col for col in df_Temp_ASL.columns if Weight in col]
# df_temp_asl_C = df_values[values + weights]
#
# values = [col for col in df_Temp_ASL.columns if Value in col]
# weights = [col for col in df_Temp_ASL.columns if Weight in col]
# df_temp_asl_C = df_values[values + weights]
# df_temp_asl_C[Weight_Parameter] = df_temp_asl_C[Weight]
# del df_temp_asl_C[Weight]
# Temp_ASL = []
# weights = []
#
# #calculating result by value * weight parameter
# df_temp_asl_C[Result] = (df_temp_asl_C[Value] * df_temp_asl_C[Weight_Parameter])
# #filling result and weight by 0 where value = nan
# df_temp_asl_C[Result] = np.where(df_temp_asl_C[Value].isnull(),0,df_temp_asl_C[Result])
# df_temp_asl_C[Weight_Parameter] = np.where(df_temp_asl_C[Value].isnull(),0,df_temp_asl_C[Weight_Parameter])
# df_temp_asl_C

# In[ ]:

df_idw_calc = pd.concat(DF_list, axis=1)

# In[ ]:

df_idw_calc

# In[ ]:

df_idw_calc = pd.concat([df_interpol, df_idw_calc], axis =1)

# In[ ]:

df_idw_calc

# In[ ]:

for column in interpol_list:
    print(column)
    results0 = [col for col in df_idw_calc.columns if parameters_list[interpol_list.index(column)] in col]
    result1 = [s for s in results0 if "Result" in s]
    weights = [s for s in results0 if "Weight" in s]
    df_idw_calc.loc[:,str(column)] = df_idw_calc[result1].sum(axis = 1).div(df_idw_calc[weights].sum(axis = 1))

# In[ ]:

df_idw_calc

# In[ ]:

```

```

df_idw_calc['INTERPOL_POINT_dewpoint_AGL_C_CALCULATED'] = np.vectorize(dewpoint_agl_transpose)(df_idw_calc.INTERPOL_POINT_dewpoint_ASL_C,df_copy.GPS_Hoehe_ASL_m_DEM)
df_idw_calc['INTERPOL_POINT_temp_AGL_C_CALCULATED'] = np.vectorize(temp_agl_formula)(df_copy.GPS_Hoehe_ASL_m_DEM,df_idw_calc.INTERPOL_POINT_temp_asl_C)
df_idw_calc['INTERPOL_POINT_pressure_AGL_hPa_CALCULATED'] = np.vectorize(barometric_formula_convert_ASL_to_pressure_at_height)(df_idw_calc.INTERPOL_POINT_pressure_asl_hPa,df_copy.GPS_Hoehe_ASL_m_DEM,df_idw_calc.INTERPOL_POINT_temp_AGL_C_CALCULATED)

# In[ ]:

df_idw_calc = df_idw_calc.sort_index(axis=1)

# In[ ]:

df_idw_calc

# del df_idw_calc['INTERPOL_POINTS_Globalstrahlung']

# In[ ]:

df_idw_calc

# In[ ]:

path6 = path_to_output + 'IDW_CALCULATED.csv'

# In[ ]:

df_idw_calc.to_csv(path6)

# In[ ]:

interpols = [col for col in df_idw_calc.columns if 'INTERPOL' in col]

# In[ ]:

df_interpol = df_idw_calc[interpols]

# In[ ]:

# In[ ]:

path3 = path_to_output + 'IDW.csv'

# In[ ]:

df_gps = pd.read_csv(path3)

# In[ ]:

colsgps = [ 'GPS_TierID', 'GPS_Tier_Geschlecht', 'GPS_Tier_Name', 'GPS_Tier_Ohrmarke', 'GPS_Tier_Gebiet', 'GPS_Einstand_2month',
'GPS_EPSG2056_lat', 'GPS_EPSG2056_lon', 'GPS_x', 'GPS_y', 'GPS_WGS84_Breite', 'GPS_WGS84_Laenge',
'GPS_Hoehe_ASL_m_DEM', 'GPS_Hoehe_ASL_m', 'GPS_DEM_Height_Difference',
'GPS_DISTANCE_ABSOLUTE', 'GPS_DISTANCE_X', 'GPS_DISTANCE_Y', 'GPS_DISTANCE_Z',
'GPS_V_KMproH', 'GPS_V_MproH', 'GPS_V_MproS',

'UTC', 'UTC1', 'GPS_timestamp_cleaned', 'GPS_Unix_Timestamp', 'year', 'Month', 'Day', 'Hour',
'UTC_Date', 'UTC_Time', 'LMT_Date', 'LMT_Time', 'daytime',
'GPS_sunrise_cleaned', 'GPS_sunset_cleaned', 'GPS_twilight_dawn_cleaned', 'GPS_twilight_dusk_cleaned', 'Jahreszeit_4season', 'Jahreszeit_Halbjahr',

```

```

'GPS_Temp', 'GPS_Temp_Class', 'GPS_ActivityMean', 'GPS_ActivitySum',
'GPS_CollarID', 'GPS_No', 'GPS_Components', 'GPS_DOP', 'GPS_FixType', 'GPS_Abgeschlossen', 'GPS_DatenEndeMonat',
'GPS_StartDatum', 'GPS_StartJahr', 'GPS_StartMonat', 'GPS_StopDatum', 'GPS_StopJahr', 'GPS_StopMonat', 'GPS_Status',
'GPS_Start2Datum', 'GPS_Start2Jahr', 'GPS_Start2Monat', 'GPS_Stop2Datum', 'GPS_Stop2Jahr', 'GPS_Stop2Mon-
at', 'GPS_Status2',

]

# In[ ]:

df_gps = df_gps[colsgps]

# In[ ]:

df_final = pd.concat([df_gps, df_interpol], axis=1)
df_final = df_final.sort_index(axis=1)

# In[ ]:

df_final

# In[ ]:

path7 = path_to_output + 'Rotwildmonitoring_FINAL.csv'

# In[ ]:

df_final.to_csv(path7)

# In[ ]:

# In[ ]:

# In[ ]:

```

9.2.4. 04_Rotwildmonitoring_Statistics_FINAL

```

#!/usr/bin/env python
# coding: utf-8

# open new conda window:
#     type "ipcluster start"

# In[1]:
print('Import Libraries')
import os
import ipyparallel as ipp

# attach to a running cluster

rc = ipp.Client()
ar = rc[:].apply_async(os.getpid)
pid_map = ar.get_dict()
print('profile:', rc.profile)

```

```

print("IDs:", rc.ids) # Print process id numbers
dview = rc[:]

import pandas as pd
print('Pandas imported')
import numpy as np
print('Numpy imported')
print(' -- successfull \n')

#gc.collect() explicitly frees memory space.
import gc

import time
from multiprocessing import Pool
from multiprocessing.pool import ThreadPool

import multiprocessing as mp
get_ipython().system('python --version')
import platform
print(platform.platform())
print("cpu cores: {}".format(mp.cpu_count()))
processes = mp.cpu_count()

print('Import Libraries for geografic transformations')
print('import os \n import geopandas \n import shapely \n import pyreproj \n import pyproj \n import col-
lections \n import ogr, osr \n import osgeo')

import geopandas as gpd
import shapely
import pyreproj
import pyproj
import collections
import ogr, osr
import osgeo
from shapely import wkt
print(' -- successfull \n')

print('Import Math and Itertools')
print('import math \n import itertools \n from itertools import islice')
import math
import itertools
from itertools import islice
print(' -- successfull \n')

print('Import Scikit Learn and matplotlib for statistics and plots')
print('import sklearn \n from sklearn import linear_model \n import matplotlib \n import matplotlib.pyplot as
plt \n %matplotlib inline')
import sklearn
from sklearn import linear_model
import matplotlib
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
get_ipython().run_line_magic('matplotlib', 'inline')
import seaborn as sns
sns.set()
print(' -- successfull \n')

print('Options to show full pandas dataframe \n')
#pd.set_option('display.max_rows', None)
#pd.set_option('display.max_columns', None)
#pd.set_option('display.width', None)
#pd.set_option('display.max_colwidth', None)

print('Set display of dataframe to max columns')
pd.set_option('display.max_columns', None)
print(' -- successfull \n')

# In[2]:
path_to_output = 'D:\\info\\Downloads\\CAS_ETH_Spatial_Information_Systems\\Rotwildmonitoring\\output\\'

# In[3]:
path7 = path_to_output + 'Rotwildmonitoring_FINAL.csv'

# In[4]:
df = pd.read_csv(path7)

# In[5]:
df

# In[6]:

```

```

df = df.reset_index()

# In[7]:
del df['index']
del df['Unnamed: 0']

# In[8]:
df

# In[9]:
df.info()

# Enddatum wurde beschränkt auf 31.12.2019 da bis anhin nur bis zu diesem Datum Bewegungsdaten vorhanden sind

# In[10]:
# to explicitly convert the date column to type DATETIME
df['UTC1'] = pd.to_datetime(df['UTC1'],errors='coerce')
df['UTC'] = pd.to_datetime(df['UTC'],errors='coerce')
df['GPS_StartDatum'] = pd.to_datetime(df['GPS_StartDatum'],errors='coerce')
df['GPS_StopDatum'] = pd.to_datetime(df['GPS_StopDatum'],errors='coerce')
df['GPS_Start2Datum'] = pd.to_datetime(df['GPS_Start2Datum'],errors='coerce')
df['GPS_Stop2Datum'] = pd.to_datetime(df['GPS_Stop2Datum'],errors='coerce')
df['LMT_Date'] = pd.to_datetime(df['LMT_Date'],errors='coerce')
df['LMT_Time'] = pd.to_datetime(df['LMT_Time'],errors='coerce')
df['UTC_Date'] = pd.to_datetime(df['UTC_Date'],errors='coerce')
df['UTC_Time'] = pd.to_datetime(df['UTC_Time'],errors='coerce')

df = df.set_index('UTC1')
df = df.sort_index()

# In[11]:
start_date = '2018-01-01 00:00:00'
end_date = '2019-12-31 23:00:00'
mask = (df['UTC'] > start_date) & (df['UTC'] <= end_date)
df = df.loc[mask]

# In[12]:
df_original_original = df

# In[13]:
df.info()

# In[14]:
df

# In[15]:
fig, axes = plt.subplots(2,1, sharex=True, figsize=(160, 12))
plt.rcParams.update({'xtick.bottom' : False})
df_notna =df[df['GPS_V_MproH'].notna()]
df_isna =df[df['GPS_V_MproH'].isna()]
df_isna.GPS_V_MproH.plot(title='Actual', ax=axes[0], label='Actual', color='red', style=".-")
df_notna.GPS_V_MproH.plot(title='Actual', ax=axes[0], label='Actual', color='green', style=".-")
axes[0].legend(["Missing Data", "Available Data"])

# In[16]:
fig, axes = plt.subplots(2,1, sharex=True, figsize=(160, 12))
plt.rcParams.update({'xtick.bottom' : False})
c =df[df['INTERPOL_POINT_Foehnindex'].notna()]
df_isna =df[df['INTERPOL_POINT_Foehnindex'].isna()]
df_isna.INTERPOL_POINT_Foehnindex.plot(title='Actual', ax=axes[0], label='Actual', color='red', style=".-")
df_notna.INTERPOL_POINT_Foehnindex.plot(title='Actual', ax=axes[0], label='Actual', color='green', style=".-")
axes[0].legend(["Missing Data", "Available Data"])

# In[17]:
fig, axes = plt.subplots(2,1, sharex=True, figsize=(160, 12))
plt.rcParams.update({'xtick.bottom' : False})
df_notna =df[df['INTERPOL_POINT_Globalstrahlung_wm2'].notna()]
df_isna =df[df['INTERPOL_POINT_Globalstrahlung_wm2'].isna()]
df_isna.INTERPOL_POINT_Globalstrahlung_wm2.plot(title='Actual', ax=axes[0], label='Actual', color='red',
style=".-")
df_notna.INTERPOL_POINT_Globalstrahlung_wm2.plot(title='Actual', ax=axes[0], label='Actual', color='green',
style=".-")
axes[0].legend(["Missing Data", "Available Data"])

# In[18]:

```

```

fig, axes = plt.subplots(2,1, sharex=True, figsize=(160, 12))
plt.rcParams.update({'xtick.bottom' : False})
df_notna =df[df['INTERPOL_POINT_Niederschlag_Stundensumme_mm'].notna()]
df_isna =df[df['INTERPOL_POINT_Niederschlag_Stundensumme_mm'].isna()]
df_isna.INTERPOL_POINT_Niederschlag_Stundensumme_mm.plot(title='Actual', ax=axes[0], label='Actual',
color='red', style="-")
df_notna.INTERPOL_POINT_Niederschlag_Stundensumme_mm.plot(title='Actual', ax=axes[0], label='Actual',
color='green', style="-")
axes[0].legend(["Missing Data", "Available Data"])

# In[19]:
fig, axes = plt.subplots(2,1, sharex=True, figsize=(160, 12))
plt.rcParams.update({'xtick.bottom' : False})
df_notna =df[df['INTERPOL_POINT_Windgeschwindigkeit_ms'].notna()]
df_isna =df[df['INTERPOL_POINT_Windgeschwindigkeit_ms'].isna()]
df_isna.INTERPOL_POINT_Windgeschwindigkeit_ms.plot(title='Actual', ax=axes[0], label='Actual', color='red',
style="-")
df_notna.INTERPOL_POINT_Windgeschwindigkeit_ms.plot(title='Actual', ax=axes[0], label='Actual', color='green',
style="-")
axes[0].legend(["Missing Data", "Available Data"])

# In[20]:
fig, axes = plt.subplots(2,1, sharex=True, figsize=(160, 12))
plt.rcParams.update({'xtick.bottom' : False})
df_notna =df[df['INTERPOL_POINT_dewpoint_AGL_C_CALCULATED'].notna()]
df_isna =df[df['INTERPOL_POINT_dewpoint_AGL_C_CALCULATED'].isna()]
df_isna.INTERPOL_POINT_dewpoint_AGL_C_CALCULATED.plot(title='Actual', ax=axes[0], label='Actual', color='red',
style="-")
df_notna.INTERPOL_POINT_dewpoint_AGL_C_CALCULATED.plot(title='Actual', ax=axes[0], label='Actual',
color='green', style="-")
axes[0].legend(["Missing Data", "Available Data"])

# In[21]:
fig, axes = plt.subplots(2,1, sharex=True, figsize=(160, 12))
plt.rcParams.update({'xtick.bottom' : False})
df_notna =df[df['INTERPOL_POINT_pressure_AGL_hPa_CALCULATED'].notna()]
df_isna =df[df['INTERPOL_POINT_pressure_AGL_hPa_CALCULATED'].isna()]
df_isna.INTERPOL_POINT_pressure_AGL_hPa_CALCULATED.plot(title='Actual', ax=axes[0], label='Actual',
color='red', style="-")
df_notna.INTERPOL_POINT_pressure_AGL_hPa_CALCULATED.plot(title='Actual', ax=axes[0], label='Actual',
color='green', style="-")
axes[0].legend(["Missing Data", "Available Data"])

# In[22]:

fig, axes = plt.subplots(2,1, sharex=True, figsize=(160, 12))
plt.rcParams.update({'xtick.bottom' : False})
df_notna =df[df['INTERPOL_POINT_Luftdruckaenderung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa'].notna()]
df_isna =df[df['INTERPOL_POINT_Luftdruckaenderung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa'].isna()]
df_isna.INTERPOL_POINT_Luftdruckaenderung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa.plot(title='Actual', ax=axes[0], label='Actual',
color='red', style="-")
df_notna.INTERPOL_POINT_Luftdruckaenderung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa.plot(title='Actual', ax=axes[0], label='Actual',
color='green', style="-")
axes[0].legend(["Missing Data", "Available Data"])

# In[23]:
fig, axes = plt.subplots(2,1, sharex=True, figsize=(160, 12))
plt.rcParams.update({'xtick.bottom' : False})
df_notna =df[df['INTERPOL_POINT_rel_Luftfeuchtigkeit_Stundenmittel_prozent'].notna()]
df_isna =df[df['INTERPOL_POINT_rel_Luftfeuchtigkeit_Stundenmittel_prozent'].isna()]
df_isna.INTERPOL_POINT_rel_Luftfeuchtigkeit_Stundenmittel_prozent.plot(title='Actual', ax=axes[0], label='Actual',
color='red', style="-")
df_notna.INTERPOL_POINT_rel_Luftfeuchtigkeit_Stundenmittel_prozent.plot(title='Actual', ax=axes[0], label='Actual',
color='green', style="-")
axes[0].legend(["Missing Data", "Available Data"])

# In[24]:
fig, axes = plt.subplots(2,1, sharex=True, figsize=(160, 12))
plt.rcParams.update({'xtick.bottom' : False})
df_notna =df[df['INTERPOL_POINT_sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min'].notna()]
df_isna =df[df['INTERPOL_POINT_sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min'].isna()]
df_isna.INTERPOL_POINT_sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min.plot(title='Actual', ax=axes[0], label='Actual',
color='red', style="-")
df_notna.INTERPOL_POINT_sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min.plot(title='Actual', ax=axes[0], label='Actual',
color='green', style="-")
axes[0].legend(["Missing Data", "Available Data"])

```

```

# In[25]:
fig, axes = plt.subplots(2,1, sharex=True, figsize=(160, 12))
plt.rcParams.update({'xtick.bottom' : False})
df_notna =df[df['INTERPOL_POINT_temp_AGL_C_CALCULATED'].notna()]
df_isna =df[df['INTERPOL_POINT_temp_AGL_C_CALCULATED'].isna()]
df_isna.INTERPOL_POINT_temp_AGL_C_CALCULATED.plot(title='Actual', ax=axes[0], label='Actual', color='red',
style="-")
df_notna.INTERPOL_POINT_temp_AGL_C_CALCULATED.plot(title='Actual', ax=axes[0], label='Actual', color='green',
style="-")
axes[0].legend(["Missing Data", "Available Data"])

# In[26]:
df['Velocity_Activity_Index_mpros_activitysum_mul'] = df.GPS_V_MproS.mul(df.GPS_ActivitySum)
df['Velocity_Activity_Index_mpros_activitysum_mul']

# In[27]:
df['INTERPOL_POINT_dewpoint_AGL_C_CALCULATED'] =df.INTERPOL_POINT_dewpoint_AGL_C_CALCULATED.fillna(method='ffill')
df['INTERPOL_POINT_temp_AGL_C_CALCULATED'] =df.INTERPOL_POINT_temp_AGL_C_CALCULATED.fillna(method='ffill')
df['INTERPOL_POINT_Windgeschwindigkeit_ms'] =df.INTERPOL_POINT_Windgeschwindigkeit_ms.fillna(method='ffill')
df['INTERPOL_POINT_pressure_AGL_hPa_CALCULATED'] =df.INTERPOL_POINT_pressure_AGL_hPa_CALCULATED.fillna(method='ffill')
df['INTERPOL_POINT_rel_Luftfeuchtigkeit_Stundenmittel_prozent'] =df.INTERPOL_POINT_rel_Luftfeuchtigkeit_Stundenmittel_prozent.fillna(method='ffill')

df['INTERPOL_POINT_sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min'] = np.where(df.daytime == 'night', 0, df.INTERPOL_POINT_sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min)
df['INTERPOL_POINT_sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min'] =df.INTERPOL_POINT_sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min.fillna(method='ffill')

# In[28]:
df['INTERPOL_POINT_Globalstrahlung_wm2'] = (df.INTERPOL_POINT_Globalstrahlung_wm2.ffill()+df.INTERPOL_POINT_Globalstrahlung_wm2.bfill())/2

# In[29]:
df['INTERPOL_POINT_Globalstrahlung_wm2']

# In[30]:
df.loc[df.GPS_Tier_Geschlecht == "w", "GPS_Tier_Geschlecht_numerical"] = int(0)
df.loc[df.GPS_Tier_Geschlecht == "m", "GPS_Tier_Geschlecht_numerical"] = int(1)
df["GPS_Tier_Geschlecht_numerical"] = df["GPS_Tier_Geschlecht_numerical"].astype(int)

# In[31]:
df['GPS_Tier_Geschlecht_numerical'].unique()

# In[32]:
df['GPS_Tier_Geschlecht'].unique()

# In[33]:
df['GPS_TierID_numerical'] = pd.factorize(df.GPS_TierID)[0] + 1
df["GPS_TierID_numerical"] = df["GPS_TierID_numerical"].astype(int)
df['GPS_TierID_numerical'].unique()

# In[34]:
df['GPS_TierID'].unique()

# In[35]:
df['GPS_Tier_Gebiet_numerical'] = pd.factorize(df.GPS_Tier_Gebiet)[0] + 1
df["GPS_Tier_Gebiet_numerical"] = df["GPS_Tier_Gebiet_numerical"].astype(int)
df['GPS_Tier_Gebiet_numerical'].unique()

# In[36]:
df['GPS_Tier_Gebiet'].unique()

# In[37]:
buckets = [-100, 0, 15, 30, 100]
buckets_name = ['SubZero', 'Cold', 'Warm', 'Hot']
df['INTERPOL_TEMP_CLASS'] = pd.cut(df.INTERPOL_POINT_temp_AGL_C_CALCULATED, buckets, labels = buckets_name)

# In[38]:
df['INTERPOL_TEMP_CLASS_numerical'] = pd.factorize(df.INTERPOL_TEMP_CLASS)[0] + 1

df.loc[df.INTERPOL_TEMP_CLASS_numerical == np.nan, 'INTERPOL_TEMP_CLASS_numerical'] = np.nan

```

```

df['INTERPOL_TEMP_CLASS_numerical'] = df['INTERPOL_TEMP_CLASS_numerical'].astype(float)
df['INTERPOL_TEMP_CLASS_numerical'].unique()

# In[39]:
df['Interpol_potential_snowfall'] = np.nan

# In[40]:
df.loc[((df['INTERPOL_POINT_temp_AGL_C_CALCULATED'] < df['INTERPOL_POINT_dewpoint_AGL_C_CALCULATED']) &
(df['INTERPOL_POINT_Niederschlag_Stundensumme_mm'] > 5)), 'Interpol_potential_snowfall'] = 1
df.loc[((df['INTERPOL_POINT_temp_AGL_C_CALCULATED'] > df['INTERPOL_POINT_dewpoint_AGL_C_CALCULATED']) |
(df['INTERPOL_POINT_Niederschlag_Stundensumme_mm'] < 5)), 'Interpol_potential_snowfall'] = 0

# In[41]:
df.Interpol_potential_snowfall.describe()

# In[42]:
df.GPS_Temp_Class.describe()

# In[43]:
df.GPS_Temp.fillna(df.INTERPOL_POINT_temp_AGL_C_CALCULATED, inplace=True)

# In[44]:
buckets = [-100, 0, 15, 30, 100]
buckets_name = ['SubZero', 'Cold', 'Warm', 'Hot']
df['GPS_Temp_Class'] = pd.cut(df.GPS_Temp, buckets, labels = buckets_name)

# In[45]:
df['GPS_Temp_Class'].describe()

# In[46]:
df['GPS_Temp_Class_numerical'] = pd.factorize(df.GPS_Temp_Class)[0] + 1
df.loc[df.GPS_Temp_Class_numerical == 0, 'GPS_Temp_Class_numerical'] = np.nan
df['GPS_Temp_Class_numerical'].unique()

# In[47]:
df['GPS_Temp_Class'].unique()

# In[48]:
df['Jahreszeit_4season_numerical'] = pd.factorize(df.Jahreszeit_4season)[0] + 1
df['Jahreszeit_4season_numerical'].unique()

# In[49]:
df['Jahreszeit_Halbjahr_numerical'] = pd.factorize(df.Jahreszeit_Halbjahr)[0] + 1
df['Jahreszeit_Halbjahr_numerical'].unique()

# In[50]:
df['Jahreszeit_Halbjahr'].unique()

# In[51]:
df['daytime_numerical'] = pd.factorize(df.daytime)[0] + 1
df['daytime_numerical'].unique()

# In[52]:
df['daytime'].unique()

# In[53]:
df['daytime_numerical'] = pd.factorize(df.daytime)[0] + 1
df['daytime_numerical'].unique()

# In[54]:
df_mll['INTERPOL_POINT_Schneehoehe_Momentanwert_cm'] = df_mll.INTERPOL_POINT_Schneehoehe_Momentanwert_cm.fillna(0)
df_mll['INTERPOL_POINT_Neuschnee_Momentanwert_cm'] = df_mll.INTERPOL_POINT_Neuschnee_Momentanwert_cm.fillna(0)
df['INTERPOL_POINT_Niederschlag_Stundensumme_mm'] = df.INTERPOL_POINT_Niederschlag_Stundensumme_mm.fillna(0)
df['INTERPOL_POINT_Luftdruckaenderung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa'] = df.INTERPOL_POINT_Luftdruckaenderung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa.fillna(0)
df['INTERPOL_POINT_Foehnindex'] = df.INTERPOL_POINT_Foehnindex.fillna(0)

# In[55]:
df['Temp_Difference_GPS_INTERPOL'] = abs(abs(df.GPS_Temp) - abs(df.INTERPOL_POINT_temp_AGL_C_CALCULATED))

```

```

# In[56]:
df.info()

# In[57]:
df_original = df

# In[58]:
df.columns.tolist()

# In[59]:
colsdfvalues = [
'GPS_Temp',
'GPS_V_MproH',
'INTERPOL_POINT_Foehnindex',
'INTERPOL_POINT_Globalstrahlung_wm2',
'INTERPOL_POINT_Luftdruckaenderung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa',
'INTERPOL_POINT_Niederschlag_Stundensumme_mm',
'INTERPOL_POINT_Windgeschwindigkeit_ms',
'INTERPOL_POINT_dewpoint_AGL_C',
'INTERPOL_POINT_dewpoint_AGL_C_CALCULATED',
'INTERPOL_POINT_pressure_AGL_hPa',
'INTERPOL_POINT_pressure_AGL_hPa_CALCULATED',
'INTERPOL_POINT_rel_Luftfeuchtigkeit_Stundenmittel_prozent',
'INTERPOL_POINT_sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min',
'INTERPOL_POINT_temp_AGL_C',
'INTERPOL_POINT_temp_AGL_C_CALCULATED',
'GPS_Tier_Geschlecht_numerical',
'GPS_TierID_numerical',
'GPS_Tier_Gebiet_numerical',
'GPS_Temp_Class_numerical',
'Jahreszeit_4season_numerical',
'Jahreszeit_Halbjahr_numerical',
'daytime_numerical',

'INTERPOL_TEMP_CLASS_numerical']

# In[60]:
df_ml1 = df[colsdfvalues]

# In[61]:
df_ml1

# In[62]:
colsdfptime = ['UTC','Day',

'Hour',

'Month',

'year']

# In[63]:
df_time = df[colsdfptime]
df_time

# In[64]:
df_original = df

# In[65]:
df = pd.get_dummies(df)

# In[66]:
df = df.sort_index(axis=1)

# In[67]:
df_dummies = df

# Plots (directly (by same hour) Correlation)
# -----

# In[68]:
df.plot(x="INTERPOL_POINT_temp_AGL_C_CALCULATED", y="GPS_Temp", color='r',kind='scatter')
plt.suptitle('Interpolierte Temperatur IDW vs GPS Temperatur', fontsize=18)

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plt.xlabel('Interpolierte Temperatur [°C]', fontsize=14)
plt.ylabel('GPS Temperatur [°C] (beschränkt)', fontsize=14)

plt.savefig(path_to_output + 'Temp_IDW_GPS_Temp.jpg')

# In[69]:
print('GPS_TEMP Minimum:',df.GPS_Temp.min())

# In[70]:
print('GPS_TEMP Maximum:',df.GPS_Temp.max())

# In[71]:
print('INTERPOL_POINT_temp_AGL_C_CALCULATED Minimum: ',df.INTERPOL_POINT_temp_AGL_C_CALCULATED.min())

# In[72]:

print('INTERPOL_POINT_temp_AGL_C_CALCULATED Maximum: ',df.INTERPOL_POINT_temp_AGL_C_CALCULATED.max())

# In[73]:
df.plot(y="GPS_Hoehe_ASL_m", x="GPS_Temp",color='r',kind='scatter')
plt.suptitle('GPS Höhe vs GPS Temperatur (mit fehlerhaften Daten)', fontsize=18)
plt.xlabel('GPS Temperatursensor °C', fontsize=14)
plt.ylabel('GPS Höhe', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + 'GPS_Hoehe_GPS_Temp.jpg')

# In[74]:
df.plot(y="GPS_Hoehe_ASL_m_DEM", x="INTERPOL_POINT_temp_AGL_C_CALCULATED",color='b', kind='scatter')

plt.suptitle('DEM Höhe vs interpolierte Temperatur', fontsize=18)
plt.xlabel('Interpolierte Temperatur [°C]', fontsize=14)
plt.ylabel('GPS Höhe [m]', fontsize=14)

plt.savefig(path_to_output + 'Hoehe_DEM_IDW_Interpol_Temp.jpg')

# In[75]:
df.GPS_Hoehe_ASL_m_DEM.min()

# In[76]:
df.GPS_Hoehe_ASL_m_DEM.max()

# In[77]:
df.GPS_Hoehe_ASL_m.min()

# In[78]:
df.GPS_Hoehe_ASL_m.max()

# In[79]:
df.plot(x="INTERPOL_POINT_temp_AGL_C_CALCULATED", y="GPS_V_MproH",kind='scatter', figsize=(16,8))
plt.suptitle('Temperatur (interpoliert) vs Geschwindigkeit', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Geschwindigkeit [m/h]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('interpolierte Temperatur [°C]', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + 'INTERPOL_POINT_temp_AGL_C_CALCULATED_VS_GPS_V_MproH.jpg')

# In[80]:
df.plot(x="INTERPOL_POINT_dewpoint_AGL_C_CALCULATED", y="GPS_V_MproH",kind='scatter', figsize=(16,8))
plt.suptitle('Taupunkt (interpoliert) vs Geschwindigkeit', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Geschwindigkeit [m/h]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Taupunkt [°C]', fontsize=14)

plt.savefig(path_to_output + 'INTERPOL_POINT_dewpoint_AGL_C_CALCULATED_VS_GPS_V_MproH.jpg')

# In[81]:
df.plot(x="INTERPOL_POINT_Globalstrahlung_wm2", y="GPS_V_MproH",kind='scatter', figsize=(16,8))
plt.suptitle('Globalstrahlung (interpoliert) vs Geschwindigkeit', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Geschwindigkeit [m/h]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Globalstrahlung [W/m^2]', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + 'INTERPOL_POINT_Globalstrahlung_wm2_VS_GPS_V_MproH.jpg')

# In[82]:
df.plot(x="INTERPOL_POINT_pressure_AGL_hPa_CALCULATED", y="GPS_V_MproH",kind='scatter', color='b',fig-
size=(16,8))
plt.suptitle('Luftdruck (interpoliert) vs Geschwindigkeit', fontsize=18)

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plt.ylabel('Geschwindigkeit [m/h]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Luftdruck [hPa]', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + 'INTERPOL_POINT_pressure_AGL_hPa_CALCULATED_VS_GPS_V_MproH.jpg')

# In[83]:
df.plot(x="INTERPOL_POINT_Luftdruckaenderung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa", y="GPS_V_MproH", kind='scatter',
color='b', figsize=(16,8))
plt.suptitle('Luftdruckänderung der letzten Stunde (interpoliert) vs Geschwindigkeit', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Geschwindigkeit [m/h]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Luftdruckänderung [hPa]', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + 'INTERPOL_POINT_Luftdruckaenderung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa_VS_GPS_V_MproH.jpg')

# In[84]:

df.plot(x="INTERPOL_POINT_rel_Luftfeuchtigkeit_Stundenmittel_prozent", y="GPS_V_MproH", kind='scatter', co-
lor='b', figsize=(16,8))
plt.suptitle('Luftfeuchtigkeit der letzten Stunde (interpoliert) vs Geschwindigkeit', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Geschwindigkeit [m/h]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Luftfeuchtigkeit [%]', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + 'INTERPOL_POINT_rel_Luftfeuchtigkeit_Stundenmittel_prozent_VS_GPS_V_MproH.jpg')

# In[85]:
df.plot(x="INTERPOL_POINT_Niederschlag_Stundensumme_mm", y="GPS_V_MproH", kind='scatter', co-
lor='b', figsize=(16,8))
plt.suptitle('Niederschlag Stundensumme (interpoliert) vs Geschwindigkeit', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Geschwindigkeit [m/h]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Niederschlag [mm]', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + 'INTERPOL_POINT_Niederschlag_Stundensumme_mm_VS_GPS_V_MproH.jpg')

# In[86]:
df.plot(x="INTERPOL_POINT_Neuschnee_Momentanwert_cm", y="GPS_V_MproH", kind='scatter', color='b', figsize=(16,8))
plt.suptitle('Neuschnee Momentanwert (interpoliert) vs Geschwindigkeit', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Geschwindigkeit [m/h]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Neuschnee Momentanwert [cm]', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + 'INTERPOL_POINT_Neuschnee_Momentanwert_cm_VS_GPS_V_MproH.jpg')

# In[87]:
df.plot(x="INTERPOL_POINT_Schneehoehe_Momentanwert_cm", y="GPS_V_MproH", kind='scatter', color='b', fig-
size=(16,8))
plt.suptitle('Schneehöhe Momentanwert (interpoliert) vs Geschwindigkeit', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Geschwindigkeit [m/h]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Schneehöhe Momentanwert [cm]', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + 'INTERPOL_POINT_Schneehoehe_Momentanwert_cm_VS_GPS_V_MproH.jpg')

# In[88]:
df.plot(x="INTERPOL_POINT_Windgeschwindigkeit_ms", y="GPS_V_MproH", kind='scatter', color='b', figsize=(16,8))
plt.suptitle('Windgeschwindigkeit (interpoliert) vs Geschwindigkeit', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Geschwindigkeit [m/h]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Windgeschwindigkeit [m/s]', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + 'INTERPOL_POINT_Windgeschwindigkeit_ms_VS_GPS_V_MproH.jpg')

# In[89]:
df.plot(x="INTERPOL_POINT_Windrichtung_grad", y="GPS_V_MproH", kind='scatter', color='b', figsize=(16,8))
plt.suptitle('Windrichtung (interpoliert) vs Geschwindigkeit', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Geschwindigkeit [m/h]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Windrichtung [° Grad]', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + 'INTERPOL_POINT_Windrichtung_grad_VS_GPS_V_MproH.jpg')

# In[90]:
df.plot(x="INTERPOL_POINT_sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min", y="GPS_V_MproH", kind='scatter', co-
lor='b', figsize=(16,8))
plt.suptitle('Sonnenscheindauer (interpoliert) vs Geschwindigkeit', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Geschwindigkeit [m/h]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Sonnenscheindauer [min]', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + 'INTERPOL_POINT_sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min_VS_GPS_V_MproH.jpg')

# In[91]:
df.groupby('UTC1').mean().plot( y="GPS_V_MproH", figsize=(80,5), color='r')
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Stunde', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Geschwindigkeit [m/h]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('UTC', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '01.UTC_mean.jpg')

df.groupby('UTC1').mean().plot( y="INTERPOL_POINT_temp_AGL_C_CALCULATED", figsize=(80,5))
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Stunde', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Temperatur [°C]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('UTC', fontsize=14)

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plt.savefig(path_to_output + '02_UTC_mean.jpg')

df.groupby('UTC1').mean().plot( y="INTERPOL_POINT_dewpoint_AGL_C_CALCULATED", figsize=(80,5))
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Stunde', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Taupunkt [°C]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('UTC', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '03_UTC_mean.jpg')

df.groupby('UTC1').mean().plot( y="INTERPOL_POINT_Globalstrahlung_wm2", figsize=(80,5))
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Stunde', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Globalstrahlung [W/m^2]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('UTC', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '04_UTC_mean.jpg')

df.groupby('UTC1').mean().plot( y="INTERPOL_POINT_pressure_AGL_hPa_CALCULATED", figsize=(80,5))
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Stunde', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Luftdruck [hPa]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('UTC', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '05_UTC_mean.jpg')

df.groupby('UTC1').mean().plot( y="INTERPOL_POINT_Luftdruckaenderung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa", figsize=(80,5))
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Stunde', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Luftdruckänderung der letzten Stunde[hPa]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('UTC', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '06_UTC_mean.jpg')

df.groupby('UTC1').mean().plot( y="INTERPOL_POINT_rel_Luftfeuchtigkeit_Stundenmittel_prozent", figsize=(80,5))
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Stunde', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Luftfeuchtigkeit [%]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('UTC', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '07_UTC_mean.jpg')

df.groupby('UTC1').mean().plot( y="INTERPOL_POINT_Niederschlag_Stundensumme_mm", figsize=(80,5))
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Stunde', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Niederschlag Stundensumme [mm]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('UTC', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '08_UTC_mean.jpg')

df.groupby('UTC1').mean().plot( y="INTERPOL_POINT_Neuschnee_Momentanwert_cm", figsize=(80,5))
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Stunde', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Neuschnee Momentanwert [cm]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('UTC', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '09_UTC_mean.jpg')

df.groupby('UTC1').mean().plot( y="INTERPOL_POINT_Schneehoehe_Momentanwert_cm", figsize=(80,5))
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Stunde', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Schneehöhe Momentanwert [cm]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('UTC', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '10_UTC_mean.jpg')

df.groupby('UTC1').mean().plot( y="INTERPOL_POINT_Windgeschwindigkeit_ms", figsize=(80,5))
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Stunde', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Windgeschwindigkeit [m/s]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('UTC', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '11_UTC_mean.jpg')

df.groupby('UTC1').mean().plot( y="INTERPOL_POINT_Windrichtung_grad", figsize=(80,5))
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Stunde', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Windrichtung [° Grad]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('UTC', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '12_UTC_mean.jpg')

df.groupby('UTC1').mean().plot( y="INTERPOL_POINT_sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min", figsize=(80,5))
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Stunde', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Sonnenscheindauer Stundensumme [min]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('UTC', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '13_UTC_mean.jpg')

# In[92]:

df.groupby('Hour').mean().plot( y="GPS_V_MproH", figsize=(80,5), color='r')
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Tagesstunde', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Geschwindigkeit [m/h]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Stunden', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '01_Hour_mean.jpg')

df.groupby('Hour').mean().plot( y="INTERPOL_POINT_temp_AGL_C_CALCULATED", figsize=(80,5))
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Tagesstunde', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Temperatur [°C]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Stunden', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '02_Hour_mean.jpg')

df.groupby('Hour').mean().plot( y="INTERPOL_POINT_dewpoint_AGL_C_CALCULATED", figsize=(80,5))
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Tagesstunde', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Taupunkt [°C]', fontsize=14)

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plt.xlabel('Stunden', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '03_Hour_mean.jpg')

df.groupby('Hour').mean().plot( y="INTERPOL_POINT_Globalstrahlung_wm2", figsize=(80,5))
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Tagesstunde', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Globalstrahlung [W/m^2]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Stunden', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '04_Hour_mean.jpg')

df.groupby('Hour').mean().plot( y="INTERPOL_POINT_pressure_AGL_hPa_CALCULATED", figsize=(80,5))
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Tagesstunde', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Luftdruck [hPa]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Stunden', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '05_Hour_mean.jpg')

df.groupby('Hour').mean().plot( y="INTERPOL_POINT_Luftdruckaenderung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa", figsize=(80,5))
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Tagesstunde', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Luftdruckänderung der letzten Stunde[hPa]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Stunden', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '06_Hour_mean.jpg')

df.groupby('Hour').mean().plot( y="INTERPOL_POINT_rel_Luftfeuchtigkeit_Stundenmittel_prozent", figsize=(80,5))
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Tagesstunde', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Luftfeuchtigkeit [%]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Stunden', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '07_Hour_mean.jpg')

df.groupby('Hour').mean().plot( y="INTERPOL_POINT_Niederschlag_Stundensumme_mm", figsize=(80,5))
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Tagesstunde', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Niederschlag Stundensumme [mm]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Stunden', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '08_Hour_mean.jpg')

df.groupby('Hour').mean().plot( y="INTERPOL_POINT_Neuschnee_Momentanwert_cm", figsize=(80,5))
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Tagesstunde', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Neuschnee Momentanwert [cm]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Stunden', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '09_Hour_mean.jpg')

df.groupby('Hour').mean().plot( y="INTERPOL_POINT_Schneehoehe_Momentanwert_cm", figsize=(80,5))
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Tagesstunde', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Schneehöhe Momentanwert [cm]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Stunden', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '10_Hour_mean.jpg')

df.groupby('Hour').mean().plot( y="INTERPOL_POINT_Windgeschwindigkeit_ms", figsize=(80,5))
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Tagesstunde', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Windgeschwindigkeit [m/s]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Stunden', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '11_Hour_mean.jpg')

df.groupby('Hour').mean().plot( y="INTERPOL_POINT_Windrichtung_grad", figsize=(80,5))
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Tagesstunde', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Windrichtung [° Grad]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Stunden', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '12_Hour_mean.jpg')

df.groupby('Hour').mean().plot( y="INTERPOL_POINT_sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min", figsize=(80,5))
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Tagesstunde', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Sonnenscheindauer Stundensumme [min]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Stunden', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '13_Hour_mean.jpg')

# In[93]:
df.groupby('Day').mean().plot( y="GPS_V_MproH", figsize=(80,5), color='r')
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Tag im Jahr', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Geschwindigkeit [m/h]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Tag im Jahr', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '01_Day_mean.jpg')

df.groupby('Day').mean().plot( y="INTERPOL_POINT_temp_AGL_C_CALCULATED", figsize=(80,5))
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Tag im Jahr', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Temperatur [°C]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Tag im Jahr', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '02_Day_mean.jpg')

df.groupby('Day').mean().plot( y="INTERPOL_POINT_dewpoint_AGL_C_CALCULATED", figsize=(80,5))
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Tag im Jahr', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Taupunkt [°C]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Tag im Jahr', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '03_Day_mean.jpg')

df.groupby('Day').mean().plot( y="INTERPOL_POINT_Globalstrahlung_wm2", figsize=(80,5))
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Tag im Jahr', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Globalstrahlung [W/m^2]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Tag im Jahr', fontsize=14)

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plt.savefig(path_to_output + '04_Day_mean.jpg')

df.groupby('Day').mean().plot( y="INTERPOL_POINT_pressure_AGL_hPa_CALCULATED", figsize=(80,5))
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Tag im Jahr', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Luftdruck [hPa]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Tag im Jahr', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '05_Day_mean.jpg')

df.groupby('Day').mean().plot( y="INTERPOL_POINT_Luftdruckaenderung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa", figsize=(80,5))
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Tag im Jahr', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Luftdruckänderung der letzten Stunde[hPa]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Tag im Jahr', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '06_Day_mean.jpg')

df.groupby('Day').mean().plot( y="INTERPOL_POINT_rel_Luftfeuchtigkeit_Stundenmittel_prozent", figsize=(80,5))
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Tag im Jahr', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Luftfeuchtigkeit [%]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Tag im Jahr', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '07_Day_mean.jpg')

df.groupby('Day').mean().plot( y="INTERPOL_POINT_Niederschlag_Stundensumme_mm", figsize=(80,5))
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Tag im Jahr', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Niederschlag Stundensumme [mm]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Tag im Jahr', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '08_Day_mean.jpg')

df.groupby('Day').mean().plot( y="INTERPOL_POINT_Neuschnee_Momentanwert_cm", figsize=(80,5))
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Tag im Jahr', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Neuschnee Momentanwert [cm]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Tag im Jahr', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '09_Day_mean.jpg')

df.groupby('Day').mean().plot( y="INTERPOL_POINT_Schneehoehe_Momentanwert_cm", figsize=(80,5))
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Tag im Jahr', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Schneehöhe Momentanwert [cm]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Tag im Jahr', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '10_Day_mean.jpg')

df.groupby('Day').mean().plot( y="INTERPOL_POINT_Windgeschwindigkeit_ms", figsize=(80,5))
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Tag im Jahr', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Windgeschwindigkeit [m/s]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Tag im Jahr', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '11_Day_mean.jpg')

df.groupby('Day').mean().plot( y="INTERPOL_POINT_Windrichtung_grad", figsize=(80,5))
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Tag im Jahr', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Windrichtung [° Grad]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Tag im Jahr', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '12_Day_mean.jpg')

df.groupby('Day').mean().plot( y="INTERPOL_POINT_sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min", figsize=(80,5))
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Tag im Jahr', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Sonnenscheindauer Stundensumme [min]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Tag im Jahr', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '13_Day_mean.jpg')

# In[94]:
df = df_original

# In[95]:
df.groupby('daytime').mean().plot.bar( y="GPS_V_MproH", figsize=(80,5), color='r')
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Tageszeit', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Geschwindigkeit [m/h]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Tageszeit', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '01_daytime_mean.jpg')

df.groupby('daytime').mean().plot.bar( y="INTERPOL_POINT_temp_AGL_C_CALCULATED", figsize=(80,5))
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Tageszeit', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Temperatur [°C]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Tageszeit', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '02_daytime_mean.jpg')

df.groupby('daytime').mean().plot.bar( y="INTERPOL_POINT_dewpoint_AGL_C_CALCULATED", figsize=(80,5))
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Tageszeit', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Taupunkt [°C]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Tageszeit', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '03_daytime_mean.jpg')

df.groupby('daytime').mean().plot.bar( y="INTERPOL_POINT_Globalstrahlung_wm2", figsize=(80,5))
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Tageszeit', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Globalstrahlung [W/m^2]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Tageszeit', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '04_daytime_mean.jpg')

df.groupby('daytime').mean().plot.bar( y="INTERPOL_POINT_pressure_AGL_hPa_CALCULATED", figsize=(80,5))

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plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Tageszeit', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Luftdruck [hPa]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Tageszeit', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '05_daytime_mean.jpg')

df.groupby('daytime').mean().plot.bar( y="INTERPOL_POINT_Luftdruckaenderung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa", fig-
size=(80,5))
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Tageszeit', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Luftdruckänderung der letzten Stunde[hPa]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Tageszeit', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '06_daytime_mean.jpg')

df.groupby('daytime').mean().plot.bar( y="INTERPOL_POINT_rel_Luftfeuchtigkeit_Stundenmittel_prozent", fig-
size=(80,5))
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Tageszeit', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Luftfeuchtigkeit [%]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Tageszeit', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '07_daytime_mean.jpg')

df.groupby('daytime').mean().plot.bar( y="INTERPOL_POINT_Niederschlag_Stundensumme_mm", figsize=(80,5))
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Tageszeit', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Niederschlag Stundensumme [mm]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Tageszeit', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '08_daytime_mean.jpg')

df.groupby('daytime').mean().plot.bar( y="INTERPOL_POINT_Neuschnee_Momentanwert_cm", figsize=(80,5))
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Tageszeit', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Neuschnee Momentanwert [cm]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Tageszeit', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '09_daytime_mean.jpg')

df.groupby('daytime').mean().plot.bar( y="INTERPOL_POINT_Schneehoehe_Momentanwert_cm", figsize=(80,5))
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Tageszeit', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Schneehöhe Momentanwert [cm]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Tageszeit', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '10_daytime_mean.jpg')

df.groupby('daytime').mean().plot.bar( y="INTERPOL_POINT_Windgeschwindigkeit_ms", figsize=(80,5))
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Tageszeit', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Windgeschwindigkeit [m/s]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Tageszeit', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '11_daytime_mean.jpg')

df.groupby('daytime').mean().plot.bar( y="INTERPOL_POINT_Windrichtung_grad", figsize=(80,5))
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Tageszeit', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Windrichtung [° Grad]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Tageszeit', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '12_daytime_mean.jpg')

df.groupby('daytime').mean().plot.bar( y="INTERPOL_POINT_sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min", figsize=(80,5))
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Tageszeit', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Sonnenscheindauer Stundensumme [min]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Tageszeit', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '13_daytime_mean.jpg')

# In[96]:
df.groupby('GPS_Temp_Class').mean().plot.bar( y="GPS_V_MproH", figsize=(12,4), color='r')
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Temperaturklasse', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Geschwindigkeit [m/h]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Temperaturklasse', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '01_GPS_Temp_Class_mean.jpg')

df.groupby('GPS_Temp_Class').mean().plot.bar( y="INTERPOL_POINT_temp_AGL_C_CALCULATED", figsize=(12,4))
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Temperaturklasse', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Temperatur [°C]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Temperaturklasse', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '02_GPS_Temp_Class_mean.jpg')

df.groupby('GPS_Temp_Class').mean().plot.bar( y="INTERPOL_POINT_dewpoint_AGL_C_CALCULATED", figsize=(12,4))
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Temperaturklasse', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Taupunkt [°C]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Temperaturklasse', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '03_GPS_Temp_Class_mean.jpg')

df.groupby('GPS_Temp_Class').mean().plot.bar( y="INTERPOL_POINT_Globalstrahlung_wm2", figsize=(12,4))
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Temperaturklasse', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Globalstrahlung [W/m^2]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Temperaturklasse', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '04_GPS_Temp_Class_mean.jpg')

df.groupby('GPS_Temp_Class').mean().plot.bar( y="INTERPOL_POINT_pressure_AGL_hPa_CALCULATED", figsize=(12,4))
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Temperaturklasse', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Luftdruck [hPa]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Temperaturklasse', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '05_GPS_Temp_Class_mean.jpg')

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df.groupby('GPS_Temp_Class').mean().plot.bar( y="INTERPOL_POINT_Luftdruckaenderung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa",
figsize=(12,4))
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Temperaturklasse', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Luftdruckänderung der letzten Stunde[hPa]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Temperaturklasse', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '06_GPS_Temp_Class_mean.jpg')

df.groupby('GPS_Temp_Class').mean().plot.bar( y="INTERPOL_POINT_rel_Luftfeuchtigkeit_Stundenmittel_prozent",
figsize=(12,4))
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Temperaturklasse', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Luftfeuchtigkeit [%]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Temperaturklasse', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '07_GPS_Temp_Class_mean.jpg')

df.groupby('GPS_Temp_Class').mean().plot.bar( y="INTERPOL_POINT_Niederschlag_Stundensumme_mm", figsize=(12,4))
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Temperaturklasse', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Niederschlag Stundensumme [mm]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Temperaturklasse', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '08_GPS_Temp_Class_mean.jpg')

df.groupby('GPS_Temp_Class').mean().plot.bar( y="INTERPOL_POINT_Neuschnee_Momentanwert_cm", figsize=(12,4))
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Temperaturklasse', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Neuschnee Momentanwert [cm]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Temperaturklasse', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '09_GPS_Temp_Class_mean.jpg')

df.groupby('GPS_Temp_Class').mean().plot.bar( y="INTERPOL_POINT_Schneehoehe_Momentanwert_cm", figsize=(12,4))
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Temperaturklasse', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Schneehöhe Momentanwert [cm]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Temperaturklasse', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '10_GPS_Temp_Class_mean.jpg')

df.groupby('GPS_Temp_Class').mean().plot.bar( y="INTERPOL_POINT_Windgeschwindigkeit_ms", figsize=(12,4))
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Temperaturklasse', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Windgeschwindigkeit [m/s]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Temperaturklasse', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '11_GPS_Temp_Class_mean.jpg')

df.groupby('GPS_Temp_Class').mean().plot.bar( y="INTERPOL_POINT_Windrichtung_grad", figsize=(12,4))
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Temperaturklasse', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Windrichtung [° Grad]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Temperaturklasse', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '12_GPS_Temp_Class_mean.jpg')

df.groupby('GPS_Temp_Class').mean().plot.bar( y="INTERPOL_POINT_sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min", fig-
size=(12,4))
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Temperaturklasse', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Sonnenscheindauer Stundensumme [min]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Temperaturklasse', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '13_GPS_Temp_Class_mean.jpg')

# In[97]:
df.groupby('Month').mean().plot.bar( y="GPS_V_MproH", figsize=(12,4), color='r')
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Monat im Jahr', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Geschwindigkeit [m/h]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Monat', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '01_month_mean.jpg')

df.groupby('Month').mean().plot.bar( y="INTERPOL_POINT_temp_AGL_C_CALCULATED", figsize=(12,4))
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Monat im Jahr', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Temperatur [°C]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Monat', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '02_month_mean.jpg')

df.groupby('Month').mean().plot.bar( y="INTERPOL_POINT_dewpoint_AGL_C_CALCULATED", figsize=(12,4))
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Monat im Jahr', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Taupunkt [°C]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Monat', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '03_month_mean.jpg')

df.groupby('Month').mean().plot.bar( y="INTERPOL_POINT_Globalstrahlung_wm2", figsize=(12,4))
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Monat im Jahr', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Globalstrahlung [W/m^2]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Monat', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '04_month_mean.jpg')

df.groupby('Month').mean().plot.bar( y="INTERPOL_POINT_pressure_AGL_hPa_CALCULATED", figsize=(12,4))
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Monat im Jahr', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Luftdruck [hPa]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Monat', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '05_month_mean.jpg')

df.groupby('Month').mean().plot.bar( y="INTERPOL_POINT_Luftdruckaenderung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa", fig-
size=(12,4))
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Monat im Jahr', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Luftdruckänderung der letzten Stunde [hPa]', fontsize=14)

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plt.xlabel('Monat', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '06_month_mean.jpg')

df.groupby('Month').mean().plot.bar( y="INTERPOL_POINT_rel_Luftfeuchtigkeit_Stundenmittel_prozent", fig-
size=(12,4))
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Monat im Jahr', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Luftfeuchtigkeit [%]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Monat', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '07_month_mean.jpg')

df.groupby('Month').mean().plot.bar( y="INTERPOL_POINT_Niederschlag_Stundensumme_mm", figsize=(12,4))
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Monat im Jahr', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Niederschlag Stundensumme [mm]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Monat', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '08_month_mean.jpg')

df.groupby('Month').mean().plot.bar( y="INTERPOL_POINT_Neuschnee_Momentanwert_cm", figsize=(12,4))
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Monat im Jahr', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Neuschnee Momentanwert [cm]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Monat', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '09_month_mean.jpg')

df.groupby('Month').mean().plot.bar( y="INTERPOL_POINT_Schneehoehe_Momentanwert_cm", figsize=(12,4))
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Monat im Jahr', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Schneehöhe Momentanwert [cm]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Monat', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '10_month_mean.jpg')

df.groupby('Month').mean().plot.bar( y="INTERPOL_POINT_Windgeschwindigkeit_ms", figsize=(12,4))
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Monat im Jahr', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Windgeschwindigkeit [m/s]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Monat', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '11_month_mean.jpg')

df.groupby('Month').mean().plot.bar( y="INTERPOL_POINT_Windrichtung_grad", figsize=(12,4))
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Monat im Jahr', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Windrichtung [° Grad]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Monat', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '12_month_mean.jpg')

df.groupby('Month').mean().plot.bar( y="INTERPOL_POINT_sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min", figsize=(12,4))
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Monat im Jahr', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Sonnenscheindauer Stundensumme [min]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Monat', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '13_month_mean.jpg')

# In[98]:
df.groupby('year').mean().plot.bar( y="GPS_V_MproH", figsize=(12,4), color='r')
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Jahr', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Geschwindigkeit [m/h]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Jahr', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '01_year_mean.jpg')

df.groupby('year').mean().plot.bar( y="INTERPOL_POINT_temp_AGL_C_CALCULATED", figsize=(12,4))
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Jahr', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Temperatur [°C]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Jahr', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '02_year_mean.jpg')

df.groupby('year').mean().plot.bar( y="INTERPOL_POINT_dewpoint_AGL_C_CALCULATED", figsize=(12,4))
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Jahr', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Taupunkt [°C]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Jahr', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '03_year_mean.jpg')

df.groupby('year').mean().plot.bar( y="INTERPOL_POINT_Globalstrahlung_wm2", figsize=(12,4))
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Jahr', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Globalstrahlung [W/m^2]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Jahr', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '04_year_mean.jpg')

df.groupby('year').mean().plot.bar( y="INTERPOL_POINT_pressure_AGL_hPa_CALCULATED", figsize=(12,4))
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Jahr', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Luftdruck [hPa]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Jahr', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '05_year_mean.jpg')

df.groupby('year').mean().plot.bar( y="INTERPOL_POINT_Luftdruckaenderung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa", fig-
size=(12,4))
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Jahr', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Luftdruckänderung der letzten Stunde [hPa]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Jahr', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '06_year_mean.jpg')

df.groupby('year').mean().plot.bar( y="INTERPOL_POINT_rel_Luftfeuchtigkeit_Stundenmittel_prozent", fig-
size=(12,4))

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plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Jahr', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Luftfeuchtigkeit [%]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Jahr', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '07_year_mean.jpg')

df.groupby('year').mean().plot.bar( y="INTERPOL_POINT_Niederschlag_Stundensumme_mm", figsize=(12,4))
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Jahr', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Niederschlag Stundensumme [mm]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Jahr', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '08_year_mean.jpg')

df.groupby('year').mean().plot.bar( y="INTERPOL_POINT_Neuschnee_Momentanwert_cm", figsize=(12,4))
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Jahr', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Neuschnee Momentanwert [cm]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Jahr', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '09_year_mean.jpg')

df.groupby('year').mean().plot.bar( y="INTERPOL_POINT_Schneehoehe_Momentanwert_cm", figsize=(12,4))
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Jahr', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Schneehöhe Momentanwert [cm]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Jahr', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '10_year_mean.jpg')

df.groupby('year').mean().plot.bar( y="INTERPOL_POINT_Windgeschwindigkeit_ms", figsize=(12,4))
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Jahr', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Windgeschwindigkeit [m/s]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Jahr', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '11_year_mean.jpg')

df.groupby('year').mean().plot.bar( y="INTERPOL_POINT_Windrichtung_grad", figsize=(12,4))
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Jahr', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Windrichtung [° Grad]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Jahr', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '12_year_mean.jpg')

df.groupby('year').mean().plot.bar( y="INTERPOL_POINT_sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min", figsize=(12,4))
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Jahr', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Sonnenscheindauer Stundensumme [min]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Jahr', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '13_year_mean.jpg')

# In[99]:
df.groupby('Jahreszeit_Halbjahr').mean().plot.bar( y="GPS_V_MproH", figsize=(12,4), color='r')
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Jahreszeit Halbjahr', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Geschwindigkeit [m/h]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Jahreszeit Halbjahr', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '01_Jahreszeit_Halbjahr_mean.jpg')

df.groupby('Jahreszeit_Halbjahr').mean().plot.bar( y="INTERPOL_POINT_temp_AGL_C_CALCULATED", figsize=(12,4))
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Jahreszeit Halbjahr', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Temperatur [°C]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Jahreszeit Halbjahr', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '02_Jahreszeit_Halbjahr_mean.jpg')

df.groupby('Jahreszeit_Halbjahr').mean().plot.bar( y="INTERPOL_POINT_dewpoint_AGL_C_CALCULATED",
figsize=(12,4))
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Jahreszeit Halbjahr', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Taupunkt [°C]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Jahreszeit Halbjahr', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '03_Jahreszeit_Halbjahr_mean.jpg')

df.groupby('Jahreszeit_Halbjahr').mean().plot.bar( y="INTERPOL_POINT_Globalstrahlung_wm2", figsize=(12,4))
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Jahreszeit Halbjahr', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Globalstrahlung [W/m^2]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Jahreszeit Halbjahr', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '04_Jahreszeit_Halbjahr_mean.jpg')

df.groupby('Jahreszeit_Halbjahr').mean().plot.bar( y="INTERPOL_POINT_pressure_AGL_hPa_CALCULATED",
figsize=(12,4))
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Jahreszeit Halbjahr', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Luftdruck [hPa]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Jahreszeit Halbjahr', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '05_Jahreszeit_Halbjahr_mean.jpg')

df.groupby('Jahreszeit_Halbjahr').mean().plot.bar( y="INTERPOL_POINT_Luftdruckaende-
rung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa", figsize=(12,4))
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Jahreszeit Halbjahr', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Luftdruckänderung der letzten Stunde [hPa]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Jahreszeit Halbjahr', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '06_Jahreszeit_Halbjahr_mean.jpg')

df.groupby('Jahreszeit_Halbjahr').mean().plot.bar( y="INTERPOL_POINT_rel_Luftfeuchtigkeit_Stundenmittel_pro-
zent", figsize=(12,4))

```

```

plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Jahreszeit Halbjahr', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Luftfeuchtigkeit [%]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Jahreszeit Halbjahr', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '07_Jahreszeit_Halbjahr_mean.jpg')

df.groupby('Jahreszeit_Halbjahr').mean().plot.bar( y="INTERPOL_POINT_Niederschlag_Stundensumme_mm",
figsize=(12,4))
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Jahreszeit Halbjahr', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Niederschlag Stundensumme [mm]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Jahreszeit Halbjahr', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '08_Jahreszeit_Halbjahr_mean.jpg')

df.groupby('Jahreszeit_Halbjahr').mean().plot.bar( y="INTERPOL_POINT_Neuschnee_Momentanwert_cm",
figsize=(12,4))
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Jahreszeit Halbjahr', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Neuschnee Momentanwert [cm]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Jahreszeit Halbjahr', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '09_Jahreszeit_Halbjahr_mean.jpg')

df.groupby('Jahreszeit_Halbjahr').mean().plot.bar( y="INTERPOL_POINT_Schneehoehe_Momentanwert_cm",
figsize=(12,4))
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Jahreszeit Halbjahr', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Schneehöhe Momentanwert [cm]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Jahreszeit Halbjahr', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '10_Jahreszeit_Halbjahr_mean.jpg')

df.groupby('Jahreszeit_Halbjahr').mean().plot.bar( y="INTERPOL_POINT_Windgeschwindigkeit_ms", figsize=(12,4))
plt.ylabel('Windgeschwindigkeit [m/s]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Jahreszeit Halbjahr', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '11_Jahreszeit_Halbjahr_mean.jpg')

df.groupby('Jahreszeit_Halbjahr').mean().plot.bar( y="INTERPOL_POINT_Windrichtung_grad", figsize=(12,4))
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Jahreszeit Halbjahr', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Windrichtung [° Grad]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Jahreszeit Halbjahr', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '12_Jahreszeit_Halbjahr_mean.jpg')

df.groupby('Jahreszeit_Halbjahr').mean().plot.bar( y="INTERPOL_POINT_sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min",
figsize=(12,4))
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Jahreszeit Halbjahr', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Sonnenscheindauer Stundensumme [min]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Jahreszeit Halbjahr', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '13_Jahreszeit_Halbjahr_mean.jpg')

# In[100]:
df.groupby('Jahreszeit_4season').mean().plot.bar( y="GPS_V_MproH", figsize=(12,4), color='r')
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Jahreszeit (4season)', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Geschwindigkeit [m/h]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Jahreszeit 4season', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '01_Jahreszeit_4season_mean.jpg')

df.groupby('Jahreszeit_4season').mean().plot.bar( y="INTERPOL_POINT_temp_AGL_C_CALCULATED", figsize=(12,4))
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Jahreszeit (4season)', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Temperatur [°C]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Jahreszeit 4season', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '02_Jahreszeit_4season_mean.jpg')

df.groupby('Jahreszeit_4season').mean().plot.bar( y="INTERPOL_POINT_dewpoint_AGL_C_CALCULATED", figsize=(12,4))
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Jahreszeit (4season)', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Taupunkt [°C]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Jahreszeit 4season', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '03_Jahreszeit_4season_mean.jpg')

df.groupby('Jahreszeit_4season').mean().plot.bar( y="INTERPOL_POINT_Globalstrahlung_wm2", figsize=(12,4))
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Jahreszeit (4season)', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Globalstrahlung [W/m^2]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Jahreszeit 4season', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '04_Jahreszeit_4season_mean.jpg')

df.groupby('Jahreszeit_4season').mean().plot.bar( y="INTERPOL_POINT_pressure_AGL_hPa_CALCULATED", fig-
size=(12,4))
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Jahreszeit (4season)', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Luftdruck [hPa]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Jahreszeit 4season', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '05_Jahreszeit_4season_mean.jpg')

df.groupby('Jahreszeit_4season').mean().plot.bar( y="INTERPOL_POINT_Luftdruckaenderung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa",
figsize=(12,4))
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Jahreszeit (4season)', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Luftdruckänderung der letzten Stunde [hPa]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Jahreszeit 4season', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '06_Jahreszeit_4season_mean.jpg')

df.groupby('Jahreszeit_4season').mean().plot.bar( y="INTERPOL_POINT_rel_Luftfeuchtigkeit_Stundenmittel_pro-
zent", figsize=(12,4))

```

```

plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Jahreszeit (4season)', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Luftfeuchtigkeit [%]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Jahreszeit 4season', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '07_Jahreszeit_4season_mean.jpg')

df.groupby('Jahreszeit_4season').mean().plot.bar( y="INTERPOL_POINT_Niederschlag_Stundensumme_mm",
figsize=(12,4))
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Jahreszeit (4season)', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Niederschlag Stundensumme [mm]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Jahreszeit 4season', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '08_Jahreszeit_4season_mean.jpg')

df.groupby('Jahreszeit_4season').mean().plot.bar( y="INTERPOL_POINT_Neuschnee_Momentanwert_cm", figsize=(12,4))
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Jahreszeit (4season)', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Neuschnee Momentanwert [cm]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Jahreszeit 4season', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '09_Jahreszeit_4season_mean.jpg')

df.groupby('Jahreszeit_4season').mean().plot.bar( y="INTERPOL_POINT_Schneehoehe_Momentanwert_cm",
figsize=(12,4))
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Jahreszeit (4season)', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Schneehöhe Momentanwert [cm]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Jahreszeit 4season', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '10_Jahreszeit_4season_mean.jpg')

df.groupby('Jahreszeit_4season').mean().plot.bar( y="INTERPOL_POINT_Windgeschwindigkeit_ms", figsize=(12,4))
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Jahreszeit (4season)', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Windgeschwindigkeit [m/s]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Jahreszeit 4season', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '11_Jahreszeit_4season_mean.jpg')

df.groupby('Jahreszeit_4season').mean().plot.bar( y="INTERPOL_POINT_Windrichtung_grad", figsize=(12,4))
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Jahreszeit (4season)', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Windrichtung [° Grad]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Jahreszeit 4season', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '12_Jahreszeit_4season_mean.jpg')

df.groupby('Jahreszeit_4season').mean().plot.bar( y="INTERPOL_POINT_sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min",
figsize=(12,4))
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Jahreszeit (4season)', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Sonnenscheindauer Stundensumme [min]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Jahreszeit 4season', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '13_Jahreszeit_4season_mean.jpg')

# In[101]:
df.groupby('GPS_Hoehe_ASL_m_DEM').mean().plot( y="GPS_V_MproH", figsize=(80,5), color='r')
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Höhendaten (DEM)', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Geschwindigkeit [m/h]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Jahreszeit 4season', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '01_GPS_Hoehe_ASL_m_DEM_mean.jpg')

df.groupby('GPS_Hoehe_ASL_m_DEM').mean().plot( y="INTERPOL_POINT_temp_AGL_C_CALCULATED", figsize=(80,5))
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Höhendaten (DEM)', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Temperatur [°C]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Jahreszeit 4season', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '02_GPS_Hoehe_ASL_m_DEM_mean.jpg')

df.groupby('GPS_Hoehe_ASL_m_DEM').mean().plot( y="INTERPOL_POINT_dewpoint_AGL_C_CALCULATED", figsize=(80,5))
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Höhendaten (DEM)', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Taupunkt [°C]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Jahreszeit 4season', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '03_GPS_Hoehe_ASL_m_DEM_mean.jpg')

df.groupby('GPS_Hoehe_ASL_m_DEM').mean().plot( y="INTERPOL_POINT_Globalstrahlung_wm2", figsize=(80,5))
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Höhendaten (DEM)', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Globalstrahlung [W/m^2]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Jahreszeit 4season', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '04_GPS_Hoehe_ASL_m_DEM_mean.jpg')

df.groupby('GPS_Hoehe_ASL_m_DEM').mean().plot( y="INTERPOL_POINT_pressure_AGL_hPa_CALCULATED", figsize=(80,5))
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Höhendaten (DEM)', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Luftdruck [hPa]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Jahreszeit 4season', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '05_GPS_Hoehe_ASL_m_DEM_mean.jpg')

df.groupby('GPS_Hoehe_ASL_m_DEM').mean().plot( y="INTERPOL_POINT_Luftdruckaenderung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa",
figsize=(80,5))
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Höhendaten (DEM)', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Luftdruckänderung der letzten Stunde [hPa]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Jahreszeit 4season', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '06_GPS_Hoehe_ASL_m_DEM_mean.jpg')

df.groupby('GPS_Hoehe_ASL_m_DEM').mean().plot( y="INTERPOL_POINT_rel_Luftfeuchtigkeit_Stundenmittel_prozent",
figsize=(80,5))
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Höhendaten (DEM)', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Luftfeuchtigkeit [%]', fontsize=14)

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plt.xlabel('Jahreszeit 4season', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '07_GPS_Hoehe_AS_L_m_DEM_mean.jpg')

df.groupby('GPS_Hoehe_AS_L_m_DEM').mean().plot(y="INTERPOL_POINT_Niederschlag_Stundensumme_mm", figsize=(80,5))
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Höhendaten (DEM)', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Niederschlag Stundensumme [mm]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Jahreszeit 4season', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '08_GPS_Hoehe_AS_L_m_DEM_mean.jpg')

df.groupby('GPS_Hoehe_AS_L_m_DEM').mean().plot(y="INTERPOL_POINT_Neuschnee_Momentanwert_cm", figsize=(80,5))
plt.ylabel('Neuschnee Momentanwert [cm]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Jahreszeit 4season', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '09_GPS_Hoehe_AS_L_m_DEM_mean.jpg')

df.groupby('GPS_Hoehe_AS_L_m_DEM').mean().plot(y="INTERPOL_POINT_Schneehoehe_Momentanwert_cm", figsize=(80,5))
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Höhendaten (DEM)', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Schneehöhe Momentanwert [cm]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Jahreszeit 4season', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '10_GPS_Hoehe_AS_L_m_DEM_mean.jpg')

df.groupby('GPS_Hoehe_AS_L_m_DEM').mean().plot(y="INTERPOL_POINT_Windgeschwindigkeit_ms", figsize=(80,5))
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Höhendaten (DEM)', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Windgeschwindigkeit [m/s]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Jahreszeit 4season', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '11_GPS_Hoehe_AS_L_m_DEM_mean.jpg')

df.groupby('GPS_Hoehe_AS_L_m_DEM').mean().plot(y="INTERPOL_POINT_Windrichtung_grad", figsize=(80,5))
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Höhendaten (DEM)', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Windrichtung [° Grad]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Jahreszeit 4season', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '12_GPS_Hoehe_AS_L_m_DEM_mean.jpg')

df.groupby('GPS_Hoehe_AS_L_m_DEM').mean().plot(y="INTERPOL_POINT_sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min", fig-
size=(80,5))
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Höhendaten (DEM)', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Sonnenscheindauer Stundensumme [min]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Jahreszeit 4season', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '13_GPS_Hoehe_AS_L_m_DEM_mean.jpg')

# In[102]:
df = df_original

# In[103]:
df.groupby('GPS_TierID').mean().plot.bar(y="GPS_V_MproH", figsize=(35,5), color='r')
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Jahreszeit (4season)', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Geschwindigkeit [m/h]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('GPS TierID', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '01_GPS_TierID_mean.jpg')

df.groupby('GPS_TierID').mean().plot.bar(y="INTERPOL_POINT_temp_AGL_C_CALCULATED", figsize=(35,5))
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Jahreszeit (4season)', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Temperatur [°C]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('GPS TierID', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '02_GPS_TierID_mean.jpg')

df.groupby('GPS_TierID').mean().plot.bar(y="INTERPOL_POINT_dewpoint_AGL_C_CALCULATED", figsize=(35,5))
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Jahreszeit (4season)', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Taupunkt [°C]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('GPS TierID', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '03_GPS_TierID_mean.jpg')

df.groupby('GPS_TierID').mean().plot.bar(y="INTERPOL_POINT_Globalstrahlung_wm2", figsize=(35,5))
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Jahreszeit (4season)', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Globalstrahlung [W/m^2]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('GPS TierID', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '04_GPS_TierID_mean.jpg')

df.groupby('GPS_TierID').mean().plot.bar(y="INTERPOL_POINT_pressure_AGL_hPa_CALCULATED", figsize=(35,5))
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Jahreszeit (4season)', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Luftdruck [hPa]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('GPS TierID', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '05_GPS_TierID_mean.jpg')

df.groupby('GPS_TierID').mean().plot.bar(y="INTERPOL_POINT_Luftdruckaenderung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa", fig-
size=(35,5))
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Jahreszeit (4season)', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Luftdruckänderung der letzten Stunde [hPa]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('GPS TierID', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '06_GPS_TierID_mean.jpg')

df.groupby('GPS_TierID').mean().plot.bar(y="INTERPOL_POINT_rel_Luftfeuchtigkeit_Stundenmittel_prozent", fig-
size=(35,5))
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Jahreszeit (4season)', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Luftfeuchtigkeit [%]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('GPS TierID', fontsize=14)

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plt.savefig(path_to_output + '07_GPS_TierID_mean.jpg')

df.groupby('GPS_TierID').mean().plot.bar( y="INTERPOL_POINT_Niederschlag_Stundensumme_mm", figsize=(35,5))
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Jahreszeit (4season)', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Niederschlag Stundensumme [mm]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('GPS TierID', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '08_GPS_TierID_mean.jpg')

df.groupby('GPS_TierID').mean().plot.bar( y="INTERPOL_POINT_Neuschnee_Momentanwert_cm", figsize=(35,5))
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Jahreszeit (4season)', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Neuschnee Momentanwert [cm]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('GPS TierID', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '09_GPS_TierID_mean.jpg')

df.groupby('GPS_TierID').mean().plot.bar( y="INTERPOL_POINT_Schneehoehe_Momentanwert_cm", figsize=(35,5))
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Jahreszeit (4season)', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Schneehöhe Momentanwert [cm]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('GPS TierID', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '10_GPS_TierID_mean.jpg')

df.groupby('GPS_TierID').mean().plot.bar( y="INTERPOL_POINT_Windgeschwindigkeit_ms", figsize=(35,5))
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Jahreszeit (4season)', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Windgeschwindigkeit [m/s]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('GPS TierID', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '11_GPS_TierID_mean.jpg')

df.groupby('GPS_TierID').mean().plot.bar( y="INTERPOL_POINT_Windrichtung_grad", figsize=(35,5))
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Jahreszeit (4season)', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Windrichtung [° Grad]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('GPS TierID', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '12_GPS_TierID_mean.jpg')

df.groupby('GPS_TierID').mean().plot.bar( y="INTERPOL_POINT_sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min", fig-
size=(35,5))
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Jahreszeit (4season)', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Sonnenscheindauer Stundensumme [min]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('GPS TierID', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '13_GPS_TierID_mean.jpg')

# In[104]:
df.groupby('GPS_Tier_Gebiet').mean().plot.bar( y="GPS_V_MproH", figsize=(35,5), color='r')
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Tier Gebiet', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Geschwindigkeit [m/h]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Tier Gebiet', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '01_GPS_Tier_Gebiet_mean.jpg')

df.groupby('GPS_Tier_Gebiet').mean().plot.bar( y="INTERPOL_POINT_temp_AGL_C_CALCULATED", figsize=(35,5))
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Tier Gebiet', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Temperatur [°C]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Tier Gebiet', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '02_GPS_Tier_Gebiet_mean.jpg')

df.groupby('GPS_Tier_Gebiet').mean().plot.bar( y="INTERPOL_POINT_dewpoint_AGL_C_CALCULATED", figsize=(35,5))
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Tier Gebiet', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Taupunkt [°C]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Tier Gebiet', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '03_GPS_Tier_Gebiet_mean.jpg')

df.groupby('GPS_Tier_Gebiet').mean().plot.bar( y="INTERPOL_POINT_Globalstrahlung_wm2", figsize=(35,5))
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Tier Gebiet', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Globalstrahlung [W/m^2]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Tier Gebiet', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '04_GPS_Tier_Gebiet_mean.jpg')

df.groupby('GPS_Tier_Gebiet').mean().plot.bar( y="INTERPOL_POINT_pressure_AGL_hPa_CALCULATED", figsize=(35,5))
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Tier Gebiet', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Luftdruck [hPa]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Tier Gebiet', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '05_GPS_Tier_Gebiet_mean.jpg')

df.groupby('GPS_Tier_Gebiet').mean().plot.bar( y="INTERPOL_POINT_Luftdruckaenderung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa",
figsize=(35,5))
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Tier Gebiet', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Luftdruckänderung der letzten Stunde [hPa]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Tier Gebiet', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '06_GPS_Tier_Gebiet_mean.jpg')

df.groupby('GPS_Tier_Gebiet').mean().plot.bar( y="INTERPOL_POINT_rel_Luftfeuchtigkeit_Stundenmittel_prozent",
figsize=(35,5))
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Tier Gebiet', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Luftfeuchtigkeit [%]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Tier Gebiet', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '07_GPS_Tier_Gebiet_mean.jpg')

df.groupby('GPS_Tier_Gebiet').mean().plot.bar( y="INTERPOL_POINT_Niederschlag_Stundensumme_mm", figsize=(35,5))
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Tier Gebiet', fontsize=18)

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```

plt.ylabel('Niederschlag Stundensumme [mm]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Tier Gebiet', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '08_GPS_Tier_Gebiet_mean.jpg')

df.groupby('GPS_Tier_Gebiet').mean().plot.bar( y="INTERPOL_POINT_Neuschnee_Momentanwert_cm", figsize=(35,5))
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Tier Gebiet', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Neuschnee Momentanwert [cm]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Tier Gebiet', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '09_GPS_Tier_Gebiet_mean.jpg')

df.groupby('GPS_Tier_Gebiet').mean().plot.bar( y="INTERPOL_POINT_Schneehoehe_Momentanwert_cm", figsize=(35,5))
plt.ylabel('Schneehöhe Momentanwert [cm]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Tier Gebiet', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '10_GPS_Tier_Gebiet_mean.jpg')

df.groupby('GPS_Tier_Gebiet').mean().plot.bar( y="INTERPOL_POINT_Windgeschwindigkeit_ms", figsize=(35,5))
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Tier Gebiet', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Windgeschwindigkeit [m/s]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Tier Gebiet', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '11_GPS_Tier_Gebiet_mean.jpg')

df.groupby('GPS_Tier_Gebiet').mean().plot.bar( y="INTERPOL_POINT_Windrichtung_grad", figsize=(35,5))
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Tier Gebiet', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Windrichtung [° Grad]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Tier Gebiet', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '12_GPS_Tier_Gebiet_mean.jpg')

df.groupby('GPS_Tier_Gebiet').mean().plot.bar( y="INTERPOL_POINT_sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min",
figsize=(35,5))
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Tier Gebiet', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Sonnenscheindauer Stundensumme [min]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Tier Gebiet', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '13_GPS_Tier_Gebiet_mean.jpg')

# In[105]:
df.groupby('GPS_Tier_Geschlecht').mean().plot.bar( y="GPS_V_MproH", figsize=(35,5), color='r')
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Tier Geschlecht', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Geschwindigkeit [m/h]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Tier Geschlecht', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '01_GPS_Tier_Geschlecht_mean.jpg')

df.groupby('GPS_Tier_Geschlecht').mean().plot.bar( y="INTERPOL_POINT_temp_AGL_C_CALCULATED", figsize=(35,5))
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Tier Geschlecht', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Temperatur [°C]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Tier Geschlecht', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '02_GPS_Tier_Geschlecht_mean.jpg')

df.groupby('GPS_Tier_Geschlecht').mean().plot.bar( y="INTERPOL_POINT_dewpoint_AGL_C_CALCULATED", fig-
size=(35,5))
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Tier Geschlecht', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Taupunkt [°C]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Tier Geschlecht', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '03_GPS_Tier_Geschlecht_mean.jpg')

df.groupby('GPS_Tier_Geschlecht').mean().plot.bar( y="INTERPOL_POINT_Globalstrahlung_wm2", figsize=(35,5))
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Tier Geschlecht', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Globalstrahlung [W/m^2]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Tier Geschlecht', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '04_GPS_Tier_Geschlecht_mean.jpg')

df.groupby('GPS_Tier_Geschlecht').mean().plot.bar( y="INTERPOL_POINT_pressure_AGL_hPa_CALCULATED", fig-
size=(35,5))
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Tier Geschlecht', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Luftdruck [hPa]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Tier Geschlecht', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '05_GPS_Tier_Geschlecht_mean.jpg')

df.groupby('GPS_Tier_Geschlecht').mean().plot.bar( y="INTERPOL_POINT_Luftdruckaender-
ung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa", figsize=(35,5))
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Tier Geschlecht', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Luftdruckänderung der letzten Stunde [hPa]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Tier Geschlecht', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '06_GPS_Tier_Geschlecht_mean.jpg')

df.groupby('GPS_Tier_Geschlecht').mean().plot.bar( y="INTERPOL_POINT_rel_Luftfeuchtigkeit_Stundenmittel_pro-
zent", figsize=(35,5))
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Tier Geschlecht', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Luftfeuchtigkeit [%]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Tier Geschlecht', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '07_GPS_Tier_Geschlecht_mean.jpg')

df.groupby('GPS_Tier_Geschlecht').mean().plot.bar( y="INTERPOL_POINT_Niederschlag_Stundensumme_mm",
figsize=(35,5))
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Tier Geschlecht', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Niederschlag Stundensumme [mm]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Tier Geschlecht', fontsize=14)

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plt.savefig(path_to_output + '08_GPS_Tier_Geschlecht_mean.jpg')

df.groupby('GPS_Tier_Geschlecht').mean().plot.bar( y="INTERPOL_POINT_Neuschnee_Momentanwert_cm", fig-
size=(35,5))
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Tier Geschlecht', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Neuschnee Momentanwert [cm]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Tier Geschlecht', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '09_GPS_Tier_Geschlecht_mean.jpg')

df.groupby('GPS_Tier_Geschlecht').mean().plot.bar( y="INTERPOL_POINT_Schneehoehe_Momentanwert_cm", fig-
size=(35,5))
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Tier Geschlecht', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Schneehöhe Momentanwert [cm]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Tier Geschlecht', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '10_GPS_Tier_Geschlecht_mean.jpg')

df.groupby('GPS_Tier_Geschlecht').mean().plot.bar( y="INTERPOL_POINT_Windgeschwindigkeit_ms", figsize=(35,5))
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Tier Geschlecht', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Windgeschwindigkeit [m/s]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Tier Geschlecht', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '11_GPS_Tier_Geschlecht_mean.jpg')

df.groupby('GPS_Tier_Geschlecht').mean().plot.bar( y="INTERPOL_POINT_Windrichtung_grad", figsize=(35,5))
plt.ylabel('Windrichtung [° Grad]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Tier Geschlecht', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '12_GPS_Tier_Geschlecht_mean.jpg')

df.groupby('GPS_Tier_Geschlecht').mean().plot.bar( y="INTERPOL_POINT_sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min",
figsize=(35,5))
plt.suptitle('Durchschnitt Wetterdaten und Geschwindigkeit je Tier Geschlecht', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Sonnenscheindauer Stundensumme [min]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Tier Geschlecht', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + '13_GPS_Tier_Geschlecht_mean.jpg')

# In[106]:
df_daytime_v_mean = df.groupby('daytime')['GPS_V_MproH'].mean()
ax = df_daytime_v_mean.plot.bar(y='GPS_V_MproH', rot=0)
plt.suptitle('Durchschnittliche Geschwindigkeit pro Tageszeit', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Geschwindigkeit [m/h]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Tageszeit', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + 'mean_daytime2.jpg')

# In[107]:
df_daytime_v_mean = df.groupby('GPS_Temp_Class')['GPS_V_MproH'].mean()
ax = df_daytime_v_mean.plot.bar(y='GPS_V_MproH', rot=0)
plt.suptitle('Durchschnittliche Geschwindigkeit pro Temperaturklasse', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Geschwindigkeit [m/h]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Temperaturklasse', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + 'mean_GPS_Temp_Class.jpg')

# In[108]:
df_daytime_v_mean = df.groupby('Month')['GPS_V_MproH'].mean()
ax = df_daytime_v_mean.plot.bar(y='GPS_V_MproH', rot=0, figsize=(12,4))
plt.suptitle('Durchschnittliche Geschwindigkeit pro Monat', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Geschwindigkeit [m/h]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Monat', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + 'mean_Month.jpg')

# In[109]:
df_daytime_v_mean = df.groupby('GPS_Tier_Geschlecht')['GPS_V_MproH'].mean()
ax = df_daytime_v_mean.plot.bar(y='GPS_V_MproH', rot=0)
plt.suptitle('Durchschnittliche Geschwindigkeit pro Geschlecht', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Geschwindigkeit [m/h]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Geschlecht', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + 'mean_GPS_Tier_Geschlecht.jpg')

# In[110]:
df_daytime_v_mean = df.groupby('GPS_Tier_Gebiet')['GPS_V_MproH'].mean()
ax = df_daytime_v_mean.plot.bar(y='GPS_V_MproH', rot=0)
plt.suptitle('Durchschnittliche Geschwindigkeit pro Gebiet', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Geschwindigkeit [m/h]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Gebiet', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + 'mean_GPS_Tier_Gebiet.jpg')

# In[111]:
df_daytime_v_mean = df.groupby('GPS_Tier_Name')['GPS_V_MproH'].mean()
ax = df_daytime_v_mean.plot.bar(y='GPS_V_MproH', rot=0, figsize=(35,5))
plt.suptitle('Durchschnittliche Geschwindigkeit pro Tier', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Geschwindigkeit [m/h]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Tier Name', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + 'mean_GPS_Tier_Name.jpg')

```

```

# In[112]:
df_daytime_v_mean = df.groupby('Jahreszeit_4season')['GPS_V_MproH'].mean()
ax = df_daytime_v_mean.plot.bar(y='GPS_V_MproH', rot=0,figsize=(35,10))
plt.suptitle('Durchschnittliche Geschwindigkeit pro Jahreszeit', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Geschwindigkeit [m/h]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Jahreszeit (4 Seasons)', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + 'mean_Jahreszeit_4season.jpg')

# In[113]:
df_daytime_v_mean = df.groupby('Jahreszeit_Halbjahr')['GPS_V_MproH'].mean()
ax = df_daytime_v_mean.plot.bar(y='GPS_V_MproH', rot=0,figsize=(12,4))
plt.suptitle('Durchschnittliche Geschwindigkeit pro Jahreszeit', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Geschwindigkeit [m/h]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Jahreszeit (Halbjahr)', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + 'mean_Jahreszeit_Halbjahr.jpg')

# In[114]:
df_daytime_v_mean = df.groupby('year')['GPS_V_MproH'].mean()
ax = df_daytime_v_mean.plot.bar(y='GPS_V_MproH', rot=0,figsize=(35,10))
plt.suptitle('Durchschnittliche Geschwindigkeit pro Jahr', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Geschwindigkeit [m/h]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Jahr', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + 'mean_year.jpg')

# In[115]:
df_daytime_v_mean = df.groupby('Day')['GPS_V_MproH'].mean()
ax = df_daytime_v_mean.plot.bar(y='GPS_V_MproH', rot=0,figsize=(365,10))
plt.suptitle('Durchschnittliche Geschwindigkeit pro Tag im Jahr', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Geschwindigkeit [m/h]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Tage', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + 'mean_Day.jpg')

# In[116]:
df_daytime_v_mean = df.groupby('Hour')['GPS_V_MproH'].mean()
ax = df_daytime_v_mean.plot.bar(y='GPS_V_MproH', rot=0,figsize=(24,10))
plt.suptitle('Durchschnittliche Geschwindigkeit pro Stunde im Tag', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Geschwindigkeit [m/h]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Stunden', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + 'mean_Hour.jpg')

# In[117]:
df_cols = df.columns.tolist()

# In[118]:
df_cols

# In[119]:
cols2 = [
'GPS_V_MproH',
'GPS_Temp',
'GPS_Temp_Class_numerical',
'INTERPOL_POINT_temp_AGL_C_CALCULATED',
'INTERPOL_POINT_dewpoint_AGL_C_CALCULATED',
'INTERPOL_POINT_pressure_AGL_hPa_CALCULATED',
'INTERPOL_POINT_Luftdruckaenderung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa',
'INTERPOL_POINT_rel_Luftfeuchtigkeit_Stundenmittel_prozent',
'INTERPOL_POINT_Niederschlag_Stundensumme_mm',
'INTERPOL_POINT_sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min',
'INTERPOL_POINT_Globalstrahlung_wm2',
'INTERPOL_POINT_Windgeschwindigkeit_ms',
'INTERPOL_POINT_Windrichtung_grad',
'GPS_ActivityMean',
'GPS_ActivitySum',
'GPS_Components',
'INTERPOL_POINT_temp_AGL_C',
'INTERPOL_POINT_pressure_AGL_hPa',
'INTERPOL_POINT_dewpoint_AGL_C',
'Jahreszeit_4season_numerical',
'Jahreszeit_Halbjahr_numerical',
'daytime_numerical']

# In[120]:
df_mean = df[cols2]

# In[121]:
df_mean = df_mean.groupby('UTC1').mean()

```

```

# In[122]:
df_mean.plot(x="INTERPOL_POINT_temp_AGL_C_CALCULATED", y="GPS_V_MproH",kind='scatter')
plt.suptitle('Hourly Mean: Geschwindigkeit vs Temperatur', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Geschwindigkeit [m/h]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Temperatur [°C]', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + 'mean_temp_per_hour.jpg')

# In[123]:
df_mean.plot(x="INTERPOL_POINT_pressure_AGL_hPa_CALCULATED", y="GPS_V_MproH",kind='scatter')
plt.suptitle('Hourly Mean: Geschwindigkeit vs Luftdruck', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Geschwindigkeit [m/h]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Luftdruck [hPa]', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + 'mean_pressure_per_hour.jpg')

# In[124]:
df_mean.plot(x="INTERPOL_POINT_Luftdruckaenderung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa", y="GPS_V_MproH",kind='scatter')
plt.suptitle('Hourly Mean: Geschwindigkeit vs Luftdruckänderung', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Geschwindigkeit [m/h]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Luftdruckänderung [hPa]', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + 'mean_pressure_change_per_hour.jpg')

# In[125]:
df_mean.plot(x="INTERPOL_POINT_Globalstrahlung_wm2", y="GPS_V_MproH",kind='scatter')
plt.suptitle('Hourly Mean: Geschwindigkeit vs Globalstrahlung', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('Geschwindigkeit [m/h]', fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel('Globalstrahlung [W/m^2]', fontsize=14)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + 'mean_radiation_per_hour.jpg')

# In[126]:
df.info()

# In[127]:
df.groupby('GPS_TierID_numerical').plot(x="INTERPOL_POINT_temp_AGL_C_CALCULATED", y="GPS_V_MproH",kind='scatter')
plt.savefig(path_to_output + 'lag_plot_GPS_V_MproH_Temp_byTierID.jpg')

# In[128]:
df.groupby('GPS_TierID_numerical').plot(x="INTERPOL_POINT_dewpoint_AGL_C_CALCULATED",
y="GPS_V_MproH",kind='scatter')
plt.savefig(path_to_output + 'lag_plot_GPS_V_MproH_Dewpoint_byTierID.jpg')

# Lag plot
# Lag plots are used to check if a data set or time series is random. Random data should not exhibit any structure in the lag plot. Non-random structure implies that the underlying data are not random.

# In[129]:
df_lag = df_original_original

# In[130]:
from pandas.plotting import lag_plot

# In[131]:
print(df_lag.GPS_V_MproS.describe())

# In[132]:
lag_plot(df_lag.GPS_V_MproS)
plt.suptitle('LAG Plot GPS_V_MproS', fontsize=18)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + 'lag_plot_GPS_V_MproS.jpg')

# In[133]:
print(df_lag.GPS_Temp.describe())

# In[134]:

lag_plot(df_lag.GPS_Temp)
plt.suptitle('LAG Plot GPS_Temp', fontsize=18)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + 'lag_plot_GPS_Temp.jpg')

# In[135]:
print(df_lag.INTERPOL_POINT_temp_AGL_C_CALCULATED.describe())

```

```

# In[136]:
df_lag.plot(x="INTERPOL_POINT_temp_AGL_C_CALCULATED", y="GPS_V_MproH", kind='scatter')
plt.suptitle('Velocity vs IDW Temp', fontsize=18)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + 'IDW_Temp_GPS_V_MproH.jpg')

# In[137]:
lag_plot(df_lag.INTERPOL_POINT_temp_AGL_C_CALCULATED)
plt.suptitle('LAG Plot IDW Temp', fontsize=18)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + 'lag_plot_IDW_Temp.jpg')

# In[138]:
print(df_lag.INTERPOL_POINT_dewpoint_AGL_C_CALCULATED.describe())

# In[139]:
df_lag.plot(x="INTERPOL_POINT_dewpoint_AGL_C_CALCULATED", y="GPS_V_MproH", kind='scatter')
plt.suptitle('Dewpoint vs GPS_MproH', fontsize=18)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + 'lag_plot_GPS_Temp.jpg')

# In[140]:
lag_plot(df_lag.INTERPOL_POINT_dewpoint_AGL_C_CALCULATED)
plt.suptitle('LAG Plot IDW Dewpoint', fontsize=18)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + 'lag_plot_IDW_Dewpoint.jpg')

# In[141]:
lag_plot(df_lag.INTERPOL_POINT_dewpoint_AGL_C_CALCULATED)
plt.suptitle('LAG Plot IDW Dewpoint', fontsize=18)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + 'lag_plot_IDW_Dewpoint.jpg')

# In[142]:
print(df_lag.INTERPOL_POINT_pressure_AGL_hPa_CALCULATED.describe())

# In[143]:
df_lag.plot(x="INTERPOL_POINT_pressure_AGL_hPa_CALCULATED", y="GPS_V_MproS", kind='scatter')
plt.suptitle('Pressure vs Velocity', fontsize=18)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + 'pressure_velocity.jpg')

# In[144]:
lag_plot(df_lag.INTERPOL_POINT_pressure_AGL_hPa_CALCULATED)
plt.suptitle('LAG Plot IDW Pressure', fontsize=18)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + 'lag_plot_pressure.jpg')

# In[145]:
print(df_lag.INTERPOL_POINT_Luftdruckaenderung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa.describe())

# In[146]:
df_lag.plot(x="INTERPOL_POINT_Luftdruckaenderung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa", y="GPS_V_MproS", kind='scatter')
plt.suptitle('Luftdruckaenderung vs Velocity', fontsize=18)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + 'velocity_pressurechange.jpg')

# In[147]:
lag_plot(df_lag.INTERPOL_POINT_Luftdruckaenderung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa)
plt.suptitle('LAG Plot Pressure Change', fontsize=18)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + 'lag_plot_pressureChange.jpg')

# In[148]:
print(df_lag.INTERPOL_POINT_rel_Luftfeuchtigkeit_Stundenmittel_prozent.describe())

# In[149]:
df_lag.plot(x="INTERPOL_POINT_rel_Luftfeuchtigkeit_Stundenmittel_prozent", y="GPS_V_MproH", kind='scatter')

# In[150]:
lag_plot(df_lag.INTERPOL_POINT_rel_Luftfeuchtigkeit_Stundenmittel_prozent)
plt.suptitle('LAG Plot IDW Humidity', fontsize=18)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + 'lag_plot_IDW_Humidity.jpg')

# In[151]:
print(df_lag.INTERPOL_POINT_Niederschlag_Stundensumme_mm.describe())

# In[152]:
df_lag.plot(x="INTERPOL_POINT_Niederschlag_Stundensumme_mm", y="GPS_V_MproS", kind='scatter')

```

```

# In[153]:
lag_plot(df_lag.INTERPOL_POINT_Niederschlag_Stundensumme_mm)
plt.suptitle('LAG Plot IDW Niederschlag', fontsize=18)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + 'lag_plot_IDW_Niederschlag.jpg')

# In[154]:
print(df_lag.INTERPOL_POINT_sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min.describe())

# In[155]:
df_lag.plot(x="INTERPOL_POINT_sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min", y="GPS_V_MproS", kind='scatter')

# In[156]:
lag_plot(df_lag.INTERPOL_POINT_sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min)
plt.suptitle('LAG Plot IDW Sonnenscheindauer', fontsize=18)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + 'lag_plot_IDW_Sonnenscheindauer.jpg')

# In[157]:
print(df_lag.INTERPOL_POINT_Globalstrahlung_wm2.describe())

# In[158]:
df_lag.plot(x="INTERPOL_POINT_Globalstrahlung_wm2", y="GPS_V_MproS", kind='scatter')

# In[159]:
lag_plot(df_lag.INTERPOL_POINT_Globalstrahlung_wm2)
plt.suptitle('LAG Plot IDW Globalstrahlung', fontsize=18)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + 'lag_plot_IDW_Globalstrahlung.jpg')

# In[160]:
print(df_lag.INTERPOL_POINT_Windgeschwindigkeit_ms.describe())

# In[161]:
df_lag.plot(x="INTERPOL_POINT_Windgeschwindigkeit_ms", y="GPS_V_MproS", kind='scatter')

# In[162]:
lag_plot(df_lag.INTERPOL_POINT_Windgeschwindigkeit_ms)
plt.suptitle('LAG Plot IDW Windgeschwindigkeit', fontsize=18)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + 'lag_plot_IDW_Windgeschwindigkeit.jpg')

# In[163]:
print(df_lag.INTERPOL_POINT_Windrichtung_grad.describe())

# In[164]:
df_lag.plot(x="INTERPOL_POINT_Windrichtung_grad", y="GPS_V_MproS", kind='scatter')

# In[165]:
lag_plot(df_lag.INTERPOL_POINT_Windrichtung_grad)
plt.suptitle('LAG Plot IDW Windrichtung', fontsize=18)
plt.savefig(path_to_output + 'lag_plot_IDW_Windrichtung.jpg')

# In[166]:
df.plot(x='UTC', y=['GPS_V_MproH', 'INTERPOL_POINT_temp_AGL_C_CALCULATED'], figsize=(100,10), linewidth=5, font-
size=20)
plt.xlabel('UTC', fontsize=20);
plt.xlabel('Velocity Activity Index', fontsize=20);

# Identifying Trends in Time Series
# There are several ways to think about identifying trends in time series. One popular way is by taking a roll-
ing average, which means that, for each time point, you take the average of the points on either side of it.
Note that the number of points is specified by a window size, which you need to choose.
#
# https://www.datacamp.com/community/tutorials/time-series-analysis-tutorial

# Differencing is super helpful in turning your time series into a stationary time series. You won't get too
much into these here but a stationary time series is one whose statistical properties (such as mean and vari-
ance) don't change over time. These time series are useful because many time series forecasting methods are
based on the assumption that the time series is approximately stationary.

# In[167]:
cols4 = ['GPS_Hoehe_AS_L_m_DEM',
'GPS_V_MproH', 'GPS_Temp',

```

```

'GPS_Temp_Class_numerical',
'INTERPOL_POINT_temp_AGL_C_CALCULATED','INTERPOL_POINT_dewpoint_AGL_C_CALCULATED','INTERPOL_POINT_pres-
sure_AGL_hPa_CALCULATED','INTERPOL_POINT_Luftdruckaenderung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa',
'INTERPOL_POINT_rel_Luftfeuchtigkeit_Stundenmittel_prozent','INTERPOL_POINT_Niederschlag_Stundensumme_mm',
'INTERPOL_POINT_sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min','INTERPOL_POINT_Globalstrahlung_wm2',
'INTERPOL_POINT_Windgeschwindigkeit_ms','INTERPOL_POINT_Windrichtung_grad',

'GPS_ActivityMean','GPS_ActivitySum','GPS_Components',
]

# In[168]:
cols3 = ['GPS_TierID_numerical', 'GPS_Hoehe_AS_L_m_DEM',

'GPS_V_MproH', 'GPS_Temp',
'GPS_Temp_Class_numerical',
'INTERPOL_POINT_temp_AGL_C_CALCULATED','INTERPOL_POINT_dewpoint_AGL_C_CALCULATED','INTERPOL_POINT_pres-
sure_AGL_hPa_CALCULATED','INTERPOL_POINT_Luftdruckaenderung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa',
'INTERPOL_POINT_rel_Luftfeuchtigkeit_Stundenmittel_prozent','INTERPOL_POINT_Niederschlag_Stundensumme_mm',
'INTERPOL_POINT_sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min','INTERPOL_POINT_Globalstrahlung_wm2',
'INTERPOL_POINT_Windgeschwindigkeit_ms','INTERPOL_POINT_Windrichtung_grad','INTERPOL_POINT_Neuschnee_Momentan-
wert_cm','INTERPOL_POINT_Schneehoehe_Momentanwert_cm',
'GPS_Tier_Gebiet_numerical',
'GPS_Tier_Geschlecht_numerical',
'GPS_ActivityMean','GPS_ActivitySum','GPS_Components',
'GPS_Unix_Timestamp','UTC', 'year','Month','Day', 'Hour', 'Jahreszeit_4season_numerical',
'Jahreszeit_Halbjahr_numerical',
'daytime_numerical'
]

# In[169]:
df_mean2 = df.groupby('UTC').mean()
df_mean2 = df_mean2.reset_index()
df_loess = df_mean2[cols3]
df_loess = df_mean2[cols3]
df_mean2

# In[170]:
df_loess.dropna(axis = 0, how = 'all', inplace = True)

# In[171]:
df_loess

# In[172]:
df_loess

# In[173]:
df_loess_5_1 = df_loess.INTERPOL_POINT_temp_AGL_C_CALCULATED.dropna().reset_index()
df_loess_5_2 = df_loess.INTERPOL_POINT_dewpoint_AGL_C_CALCULATED.dropna().reset_index()
df_loess_5_3 = df_loess.INTERPOL_POINT_pressure_AGL_hPa_CALCULATED.dropna().reset_index()
df_loess_5_4 = df_loess.INTERPOL_POINT_Luftdruckaenderung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa.dropna().reset_index()
df_loess_5_5 = df_loess.INTERPOL_POINT_rel_Luftfeuchtigkeit_Stundenmittel_prozent.dropna().reset_index()
df_loess_5_6 = df_loess.INTERPOL_POINT_Niederschlag_Stundensumme_mm.dropna().reset_index()
df_loess_5_7 = df_loess.INTERPOL_POINT_sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min.dropna().reset_index()
df_loess_5_8 = df_loess.INTERPOL_POINT_Globalstrahlung_wm2.dropna().reset_index()
df_loess_5_9 = df_loess.INTERPOL_POINT_Windgeschwindigkeit_ms.dropna().reset_index()
df_loess_5_10 = df_loess.GPS_V_MproH.dropna().reset_index()
df_loess_5_11 = df_loess.GPS_ActivitySum.dropna().reset_index()
df_loess_5_12 = df_loess.INTERPOL_POINT_Neuschnee_Momentanwert_cm.dropna().reset_index()
df_loess_5_13 = df_loess.INTERPOL_POINT_Schneehoehe_Momentanwert_cm.dropna().reset_index()

# In[174]:
from statsmodels.nonparametric.smoothers_lowess import lowess
plt.rcParams.update({'xtick.bottom' : False, 'axes.titlepad':5})

# 2. Loess Smoothing (5%)
df_loess_5_1 = pd.DataFrame(lowess(df_loess_5_1.INTERPOL_POINT_temp_AGL_C_CALCULATED, np.arange(len(df_lo-
ess_5_1.INTERPOL_POINT_temp_AGL_C_CALCULATED))), frac=0.015)[: , 1], index=df_loess_5_1.index, columns=['INTER-
POL_POINT_temp_AGL_C_CALCULATED'])
df_loess_5_2 = pd.DataFrame(lowess(df_loess_5_2.INTERPOL_POINT_dewpoint_AGL_C_CALCULATED, np.arange(len(df_lo-
ess_5_2.INTERPOL_POINT_dewpoint_AGL_C_CALCULATED))), frac=0.015)[: , 1], index=df_loess_5_2.index, columns=['IN-
TERPOL_POINT_dewpoint_AGL_C_CALCULATED'])
df_loess_5_3 = pd.DataFrame(lowess(df_loess_5_3.INTERPOL_POINT_pressure_AGL_hPa_CALCULATED,
np.arange(len(df_loess_5_3.INTERPOL_POINT_pressure_AGL_hPa_CALCULATED))), frac=0.015)[: , 1], index=df_lo-
ess_5_3.index, columns=['INTERPOL_POINT_pressure_AGL_hPa_CALCULATED'])
df_loess_5_5 = pd.DataFrame(lowess(df_loess_5_5.INTERPOL_POINT_rel_Luftfeuchtigkeit_Stundenmittel_prozent,
np.arange(len(df_loess_5_5.INTERPOL_POINT_rel_Luftfeuchtigkeit_Stundenmittel_prozent))), frac=0.015)[: , 1], in-
dex=df_loess_5_5.index, columns=['INTERPOL_POINT_rel_Luftfeuchtigkeit_Stundenmittel_prozent'])
df_loess_5_6 = pd.DataFrame(lowess(df_loess_5_6.INTERPOL_POINT_Niederschlag_Stundensumme_mm,
np.arange(len(df_loess_5_6.INTERPOL_POINT_Niederschlag_Stundensumme_mm))), frac=0.015)[: , 1], index=df_lo-
ess_5_6.index, columns=['INTERPOL_POINT_Niederschlag_Stundensumme_mm'])

```

```

df_loess_5_7 = pd.DataFrame(lowess(df_loess_5_7.INTERPOL_POINT_sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min,
np.arange(len(df_loess_5_7.INTERPOL_POINT_sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min)), frac=0.015)[: , 1], index=df_lo-
ess_5_7.index, columns=['INTERPOL_POINT_sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min'])
df_loess_5_8 = pd.DataFrame(lowess(df_loess_5_8.INTERPOL_POINT_Globalstrahlung_wm2, np.arange(len(df_lo-
ess_5_8.INTERPOL_POINT_Globalstrahlung_wm2)), frac=0.015)[: , 1], index=df_loess_5_8.index, columns=['INTER-
POL_POINT_Globalstrahlung_wm2'])
df_loess_5_9 = pd.DataFrame(lowess(df_loess_5_9.INTERPOL_POINT_Windgeschwindigkeit_ms, np.arange(len(df_lo-
ess_5_9.INTERPOL_POINT_Windgeschwindigkeit_ms)), frac=0.015)[: , 1], index=df_loess_5_9.index, columns=['INTER-
POL_POINT_Windgeschwindigkeit_ms'])
df_loess_5_12 = pd.DataFrame(lowess(df_loess_5_12.INTERPOL_POINT_Neuschnee_Momentanwert_cm,
np.arange(len(df_loess_5_12.INTERPOL_POINT_Neuschnee_Momentanwert_cm)), frac=0.015)[: , 1], index=df_lo-
ess_5_12.index, columns=['INTERPOL_POINT_Neuschnee_Momentanwert_cm'])
df_loess_5_13 = pd.DataFrame(lowess(df_loess_5_13.INTERPOL_POINT_Schneehoehe_Momentanwert_cm,
np.arange(len(df_loess_5_13.INTERPOL_POINT_Schneehoehe_Momentanwert_cm)), frac=0.015)[: , 1], index=df_lo-
ess_5_13.index, columns=['INTERPOL_POINT_Schneehoehe_Momentanwert_cm'])

df_loess_5_10 = pd.DataFrame(lowess(df_loess_5_10.GPS_V_MproH, np.arange(len(df_loess_5_10.GPS_V_MproH)),
frac=0.015)[: , 1], index=df_loess_5_10.index, columns=['GPS_V_MproH'])
df_loess_5_11 = pd.DataFrame(lowess(df_loess_5_11.GPS_ActivitySum, np.arange(len(df_loess_5_11.GPS_Activ-
itySum)), frac=0.015)[: , 1], index=df_loess_5_11.index, columns=['GPS_ActivitySum'])

# In[175]:
df_loess_5_4['INTERPOL_POINT_Luftdruckaenderung'] = df_loess_5_4.INTERPOL_POINT_Luftdruckaender-
ung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa + df_loess_5_3.INTERPOL_POINT_pressure_AGL_hPa_CALCULATED

# In[176]:
df_loess_5_4

# In[177]:
# Plot
fig, axes = plt.subplots(7,1, figsize=(35, 12), sharex=True, dpi=120)
df_loess_5_1['INTERPOL_POINT_temp_AGL_C_CALCULATED'].plot(ax=axes[0], color='r', title='Loess function: INTER-
POL_POINT_temp_AGL_C_CALCULATED Mean per Hour')
df_loess_5_2['INTERPOL_POINT_dewpoint_AGL_C_CALCULATED'].plot(ax=axes[0], color='b', title='Loess function: IN-
TERPOL_POINT_dewpoint_AGL_C_CALCULATED Mean per Hour')
df_loess_5_4['INTERPOL_POINT_Luftdruckaenderung'].plot(ax=axes[1], color='g')
df_loess_5_3['INTERPOL_POINT_pressure_AGL_hPa_CALCULATED'].plot(ax=axes[1], color='k', title='Loess function:
INTERPOL_POINT_pressure_AGL_hPa_CALCULATED und Luftdruckänderung Mean per Hour')
df_loess_5_5['INTERPOL_POINT_rel_Luftfeuchtigkeit_Stundenmittel_prozent'].plot(ax=axes[2], color='k', ti-
tle='Loess function: INTERPOL_POINT_rel_Luftfeuchtigkeit_Stundenmittel_prozent Mean per Hour')
df_loess_5_6['INTERPOL_POINT_Niederschlag_Stundensumme_mm'].plot(ax=axes[3], color='k', title='Loess function:
INTERPOL_POINT_Niederschlag_Stundensumme_mm Mean per Hour')
df_loess_5_7['INTERPOL_POINT_sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min'].plot(ax=axes[4], color='k', title='Loess
function: INTERPOL_POINT_sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min Mean per Hour')
df_loess_5_8['INTERPOL_POINT_Globalstrahlung_wm2'].plot(ax=axes[5], color='k', title='Loess function: INTER-
POL_POINT_Globalstrahlung_wm2 Mean per Hour')
df_loess_5_9['INTERPOL_POINT_Windgeschwindigkeit_ms'].plot(ax=axes[6], color='k', title='Loess function: INTER-
POL_POINT_Windgeschwindigkeit_ms Mean per Hour')
#df_loess_5_12['INTERPOL_POINT_Neuschnee_Momentanwert_cm'].plot(ax=axes[7], color='k', title='Loess function:
INTERPOL_POINT_Neuschnee_Momentanwert_cm Mean per Hour')
#df_loess_5_13['INTERPOL_POINT_Schneehoehe_Momentanwert_cm'].plot(ax=axes[8], color='k', title='Loess function:
INTERPOL_POINT_Schneehoehe_Momentanwert_cm Mean per Hour')

#df_loess_5_V['GPS_V_MproH'].plot(ax=axes[1], title='Loess Smoothed 5%')
#df_loess_15['GPS_V_MproH'].plot(ax=axes[2], title='Loess Smoothed 15%')
#df_loess_5.plot(ax=axes[4], title='Loess 5%')
fig.suptitle('Loess Function 3% Time Series', y=0.95, fontsize=14)
plt.show()
plt.savefig(path_to_output + 'Loess.jpg')

# In[178]:
# Plot
fig, axes = plt.subplots(2,1, figsize=(35, 12), sharex=True, dpi=120)
df_loess_5_10['GPS_V_MproH'].plot(ax=axes[0], color='r', title='Loess function: GPS_V_MproH Mean per Hour')
df_loess_5_11['GPS_ActivitySum'].plot(ax=axes[1], color='b', title='Loess function: GPS_ActivitySum Mean per
Hour')

fig.suptitle('Loess Function 3% Time Series', y=0.95, fontsize=14)
plt.show()
plt.savefig(path_to_output + 'Vel_Activity_Loess.jpg')

# GRANGER CAUSALITY TEST
# -----

# Stationarity Test

# https://medium.com/swlh/using-granger-causality-test-to-know-if-one-time-series-is-impacting-in-predicting-
another-6285b9fd2d1c
#
# https://www.statsmodels.org/stable/index.html
#

```

```

# https://www.analyticsvidhya.com/blog/2018/09/non-stationary-time-series-python/

# In[179]:
df_differentiated = pd.DataFrame()

# In[180]:
df_mean_hour = df[colsdfvalues]
df_mean_hour = df_mean_hour.groupby('UTC1').mean()

# In[181]:
df_mean_hour

# In[182]:
colsdfvalues

# In[183]:
from statsmodels.tsa.stattools import kpss

def kpss_test(df_mean_hour):
    statistic, p_value, n_lags, critical_values = kpss(df_mean_hour.values)

    print(f'KPSS Statistic: {statistic}')
    print(f'p-value: {p_value}')
    print(f'num lags: {n_lags}')
    print('Critical Values:')
    for key, value in critical_values.items():
        print(f'    {key} : {value}')

print('GPS_V_MproH')
kpss_test(df_mean_hour['GPS_V_MproH'])

print('GPS_Temp')
kpss_test(df_mean_hour['GPS_Temp'])

print('INTERPOL_POINT_Foehnindex')
kpss_test(df_mean_hour['INTERPOL_POINT_Foehnindex'])

print('INTERPOL_POINT_Globalstrahlung_wm2')
kpss_test(df_mean_hour['INTERPOL_POINT_Globalstrahlung_wm2'])

print('INTERPOL_POINT_pressure_AGL_hPa_CALCULATED')
kpss_test(df_mean_hour['INTERPOL_POINT_pressure_AGL_hPa_CALCULATED'])

print('INTERPOL_POINT_Luftdruckaenderung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa')
kpss_test(df_mean_hour['INTERPOL_POINT_Luftdruckaenderung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa'])

print('INTERPOL_POINT_temp_AGL_C_CALCULATED')
kpss_test(df_mean_hour['INTERPOL_POINT_temp_AGL_C_CALCULATED'])

print('INTERPOL_POINT_dewpoint_AGL_C_CALCULATED')
kpss_test(df_mean_hour['INTERPOL_POINT_dewpoint_AGL_C_CALCULATED'])

print('INTERPOL_POINT_rel_Luftfeuchtigkeit_Stundenmittel_prozent')
kpss_test(df_mean_hour['INTERPOL_POINT_rel_Luftfeuchtigkeit_Stundenmittel_prozent'])

print('INTERPOL_POINT_sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min')
kpss_test(df_mean_hour['INTERPOL_POINT_sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min'])

# Granger Causality Test (Lag max 12h)
# -----

# In[184]:
import warnings
warnings.filterwarnings("ignore", message="numpy.dtype size changed")
warnings.filterwarnings("ignore", message="numpy.ufunc size changed")

# In[185]:
import pkgutil

# this is the package we are inspecting -- for example 'email' from stdlib
import statsmodels

package = statsmodels
for importer, modname, ispkg in pkgutil.iter_modules(package.__path__):
    print ("Found submodule %s (is a package: %s)" % (modname, ispkg))

# In[186]:
import statsmodels
import statsmodels.tsa as tsa
from statsmodels.tsa.stattools import kpss
import grangercausalitytests

```

```

# GPS_Temp
# -----

# In[187]:
cols = ['GPS_V_MproH',
        'GPS_Temp']

# In[188]:
df_granger = df_mean_hour[cols]

# In[189]:
df_granger

# In[190]:
df_granger.hist(column = 'GPS_V_MproH')

# In[191]:
df_granger.hist(column = 'GPS_Temp')

# In[192]:
df_granger.plot(y = 'GPS_Temp', figsize=(12,3))
plt.suptitle('Pre differentiation: GPS_Temp', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('GPS_Temp [°C]', fontsize=14)

# In[193]:
from statsmodels.tsa.stattools import adfuller, kpss

# ADF Test
result = adfuller(df_granger.GPS_V_MproH.values, autolag='AIC')
print(f'\nADF Statistic: {result[0]}')
print(f'p-value: {result[1]}')
for key, value in result[4].items():
    print('Critical Values:')
    print(f'    {key}, {value}')

# KPSS Test
result = kpss(df_granger.GPS_V_MproH.values, regression='c')
print(f'\nKPSS Statistic: %f' % result[0])
print(f'p-value: %f' % result[1])
for key, value in result[3].items():
    print('Critical Values:')
    print(f'    {key}, {value}')

# In[194]:
df_granger['GPS_V_MproH_log'] = np.log(df_granger['GPS_V_MproH'])
df_granger['GPS_V_MproH_log_diff'] = df_granger['GPS_V_MproH_log'] - df_granger['GPS_V_MproH_log'].shift(1)
df_granger['GPS_V_MproH_log_diff'].dropna().plot()

# In[195]:
from statsmodels.tsa.stattools import adfuller, kpss

# ADF Test
result = adfuller(df_granger.GPS_Temp.values, autolag='AIC')
print(f'\nADF Statistic: {result[0]}')
print(f'p-value: {result[1]}')
for key, value in result[4].items():
    print('Critical Values:')
    print(f'    {key}, {value}')

# KPSS Test
result = kpss(df_granger.GPS_Temp.values, regression='c')
print(f'\nKPSS Statistic: %f' % result[0])
print(f'p-value: %f' % result[1])
for key, value in result[3].items():
    print('Critical Values:')
    print(f'    {key}, {value}')

# In[196]:
df_granger['GPS_Temp_log'] = np.log(df_granger['GPS_Temp'])
df_granger['GPS_Temp_log_diff'] = df_granger['GPS_Temp_log'] - df_granger['GPS_Temp_log'].shift(1)
df_granger['GPS_Temp_log_diff'].dropna().plot()

# In[197]:
df_granger = df_granger[['GPS_V_MproH_log_diff', 'GPS_Temp_log_diff']]

```

```

df_granger.replace([np.inf, -np.inf], np.nan, inplace=True)
df_granger = df_granger.dropna()

# In[198]:
df_differentiatet = df_differentiatet.append(df_granger)

# In[199]:
res = grangercausalitytests(df_granger, maxlag=12, verbose=True)

# In[200]:

df_differentiatet

# INTERPOL_POINT_temp_AGL_C_CALCULATED
# -----

# In[201]:
cols = ['GPS_V_MproH',
        'INTERPOL_POINT_temp_AGL_C_CALCULATED']

# In[202]:
df_granger = df_mean_hour[cols]

# In[203]:
df_granger

# In[204]:
df_granger.hist(column = 'GPS_V_MproH')

# In[205]:
df_granger.hist(column = 'INTERPOL_POINT_temp_AGL_C_CALCULATED')

# In[206]:
df_granger.plot(y = 'INTERPOL_POINT_temp_AGL_C_CALCULATED', figsize=(12,3))
plt.suptitle('Pre differentiation: INTERPOL_POINT_temp_AGL_C_CALCULATED', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('INTERPOL_POINT_temp_AGL_C_CALCULATED [°C]', fontsize=14)

# In[207]:
from statsmodels.tsa.stattools import adfuller, kpss

# ADF Test
result = adfuller(df_granger.GPS_V_MproH.values, autolag='AIC')
print(f'\nADF Statistic: {result[0]}')
print(f'p-value: {result[1]}')
for key, value in result[4].items():
    print('Critical Values:')
    print(f'    {key}, {value}')

# KPSS Test
result = kpss(df_granger.GPS_V_MproH.values, regression='c')
print(f'\nKPSS Statistic: %f' % result[0])
print(f'p-value: %f' % result[1])
for key, value in result[3].items():
    print('Critical Values:')
    print(f'    {key}, {value}')

# In[208]:
df_granger['GPS_V_MproH_log'] = np.log(df_granger['GPS_V_MproH'])
df_granger['GPS_V_MproH_log_diff'] = df_granger['GPS_V_MproH_log'] - df_granger['GPS_V_MproH_log'].shift(1)
df_granger['GPS_V_MproH_log_diff'].dropna().plot()

# In[209]:
from statsmodels.tsa.stattools import adfuller, kpss

# ADF Test
result = adfuller(df_granger.INTERPOL_POINT_temp_AGL_C_CALCULATED.values, autolag='AIC')
print(f'\nADF Statistic: {result[0]}')
print(f'p-value: {result[1]}')
for key, value in result[4].items():
    print('Critical Values:')
    print(f'    {key}, {value}')

# KPSS Test

```

```

result = kpss(df_granger.INTERPOL_POINT_temp_AGL_C_CALCULATED.values, regression='c')
print('\nKPSS Statistic: %f' % result[0])
print('p-value: %f' % result[1])
for key, value in result[3].items():
    print('Critical Values:')
    print(f'    {key}, {value}')

# In[210]:
df_granger['INTERPOL_POINT_temp_AGL_C_CALCULATED_log'] = np.log(df_granger['INTERPOL_POINT_temp_AGL_C_CALCULATED'])
df_granger['INTERPOL_POINT_temp_AGL_C_CALCULATED_log_diff'] = df_granger['INTERPOL_POINT_temp_AGL_C_CALCULATED_log'] - df_granger['INTERPOL_POINT_temp_AGL_C_CALCULATED_log'].shift(1)
df_granger['INTERPOL_POINT_temp_AGL_C_CALCULATED_log_diff'].dropna().plot()

# In[211]:
df_granger = df_granger[['GPS_V_MproH_log_diff', 'INTERPOL_POINT_temp_AGL_C_CALCULATED_log_diff']]
df_granger.replace([np.inf, -np.inf], np.nan, inplace=True)
df_granger = df_granger.dropna()

# In[212]:
df_differentiated = df_differentiated.merge(df_granger, left_on=['UTC1', 'GPS_V_MproH_log_diff'],
right_on=['UTC1', 'GPS_V_MproH_log_diff'])

# In[213]:
res = grangercausalitytests(df_granger, maxlag=12, verbose=True)

# In[214]:
df_differentiated

# INTERPOL_POINT_dewpoint_AGL_C_CALCULATED
# -----

# In[215]:
cols = ['GPS_V_MproH',
        'INTERPOL_POINT_dewpoint_AGL_C_CALCULATED']

# In[216]:
df_granger = df_mean_hour[cols]

# In[217]:
df_granger

# In[218]:

df_granger.hist(column = 'GPS_V_MproH')

# In[219]:
df_granger.hist(column = 'INTERPOL_POINT_dewpoint_AGL_C_CALCULATED')

# In[220]:
df_granger.plot(y = 'INTERPOL_POINT_dewpoint_AGL_C_CALCULATED', figsize=(12,3))
plt.suptitle('Pre differentiation: INTERPOL_POINT_dewpoint_AGL_C_CALCULATED', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('INTERPOL_POINT_dewpoint_AGL_C_CALCULATED [°C]', fontsize=14)

# In[221]:
from statsmodels.tsa.stattools import adfuller, kpss

# ADF Test
result = adfuller(df_granger.GPS_V_MproH.values, autolag='AIC')
print(f'ADF Statistic: {result[0]}')
print(f'p-value: {result[1]}')
for key, value in result[4].items():
    print('Critical Values:')
    print(f'    {key}, {value}')

# KPSS Test
result = kpss(df_granger.GPS_V_MproH.values, regression='c')
print('\nKPSS Statistic: %f' % result[0])
print('p-value: %f' % result[1])
for key, value in result[3].items():
    print('Critical Values:')
    print(f'    {key}, {value}')

```

```

# In[222]:
df_granger['GPS_V_MproH_log'] = np.log(df_granger['GPS_V_MproH'])
df_granger['GPS_V_MproH_log_diff'] = df_granger['GPS_V_MproH_log'] - df_granger['GPS_V_MproH_log'].shift(1)
df_granger['GPS_V_MproH_log_diff'].dropna().plot()

# In[223]:
from statsmodels.tsa.stattools import adfuller, kpss

# ADF Test
result = adfuller(df_granger.INTERPOL_POINT_dewpoint_AGL_C_CALCULATED.values, autolag='AIC')
print(f'ADF Statistic: {result[0]}')
print(f'p-value: {result[1]}')
for key, value in result[4].items():
    print('Critical Values:')
    print(f'    {key}, {value}')

# KPSS Test
result = kpss(df_granger.INTERPOL_POINT_dewpoint_AGL_C_CALCULATED.values, regression='c')
print(f'\nKPSS Statistic: %f' % result[0])
print(f'p-value: %f' % result[1])
for key, value in result[3].items():
    print('Critical Values:')
    print(f'    {key}, {value}')

# In[224]:
df_granger['INTERPOL_POINT_dewpoint_AGL_C_CALCULATED_log'] = np.log(df_granger['INTERPOL_POINT_dew-
point_AGL_C_CALCULATED'])
df_granger['INTERPOL_POINT_dewpoint_AGL_C_CALCULATED_log_diff'] = df_granger['INTERPOL_POINT_dew-
point_AGL_C_CALCULATED_log'] - df_granger['INTERPOL_POINT_dewpoint_AGL_C_CALCULATED_log'].shift(1)
df_granger['INTERPOL_POINT_dewpoint_AGL_C_CALCULATED_log_diff'].dropna().plot()

# In[225]:
df_granger = df_granger[['GPS_V_MproH_log_diff', 'INTERPOL_POINT_dewpoint_AGL_C_CALCULATED_log_diff']]
df_granger.replace([np.inf, -np.inf], np.nan, inplace=True)
df_granger = df_granger.dropna()

# In[226]:
df_differentiated = df_differentiated.merge(df_granger, left_on=['UTC1', 'GPS_V_MproH_log_diff'],
right_on=['UTC1', 'GPS_V_MproH_log_diff'])

# In[227]:
res = grangercausalitytests(df_granger, maxlag=12, verbose=True)

# INTERPOL_POINT_Niederschlag_Stundensumme_mm
# -----

# In[228]:
cols = ['GPS_V_MproH',
'INTERPOL_POINT_Niederschlag_Stundensumme_mm']
]

# In[229]:
df_granger = df_mean_hour[cols]

# In[230]:
df_granger

# In[231]:
df_granger.hist(column = 'GPS_V_MproH')

# In[232]:
df_granger.hist(column = 'INTERPOL_POINT_Niederschlag_Stundensumme_mm')

# In[233]:
df_granger.plot(y = 'INTERPOL_POINT_Niederschlag_Stundensumme_mm', figsize=(12,3))
plt.suptitle('Pre differentiation: INTERPOL_POINT_Niederschlag_Stundensumme_mm', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('INTERPOL_POINT_Niederschlag_Stundensumme_mm [mm]', fontsize=14)

# In[234]:
from statsmodels.tsa.stattools import adfuller, kpss

# ADF Test
result = adfuller(df_granger.GPS_V_MproH.values, autolag='AIC')
print(f'ADF Statistic: {result[0]}')

```

```

print(f'p-value: {result[1]}')
for key, value in result[4].items():
    print('Critical Values:')
    print(f'    {key}, {value}')

# KPSS Test
result = kpss(df_granger.GPS_V_MproH.values, regression='c')
print('\nKPSS Statistic: %f' % result[0])
print('p-value: %f' % result[1])
for key, value in result[3].items():
    print('Critical Values:')
    print(f'    {key}, {value}')

# In[235]:
df_granger['GPS_V_MproH_log'] = np.log(df_granger['GPS_V_MproH'])
df_granger['GPS_V_MproH_log_diff'] = df_granger['GPS_V_MproH_log'] - df_granger['GPS_V_MproH_log'].shift(1)
df_granger['GPS_V_MproH_log_diff'].dropna().plot()

# In[236]:
from statsmodels.tsa.stattools import adfuller, kpss

# ADF Test
result = adfuller(df_granger.INTERPOL_POINT_Niederschlag_Stundensumme_mm.values, autolag='AIC')
print(f'ADF Statistic: {result[0]}')
print(f'p-value: {result[1]}')
for key, value in result[4].items():
    print('Critical Values:')
    print(f'    {key}, {value}')

# KPSS Test
result = kpss(df_granger.INTERPOL_POINT_Niederschlag_Stundensumme_mm.values, regression='c')
print('\nKPSS Statistic: %f' % result[0])
print('p-value: %f' % result[1])
for key, value in result[3].items():
    print('Critical Values:')
    print(f'    {key}, {value}')

# In[237]:
df_granger['INTERPOL_POINT_Niederschlag_Stundensumme_mm_log'] = np.log(df_granger['INTERPOL_POINT_Nieder-
schlag_Stundensumme_mm'])
df_granger['INTERPOL_POINT_Niederschlag_Stundensumme_mm_log_diff'] = df_granger['INTERPOL_POINT_Nieder-
schlag_Stundensumme_mm_log'] - df_granger['INTERPOL_POINT_Niederschlag_Stundensumme_mm_log'].shift(1)
df_granger['INTERPOL_POINT_Niederschlag_Stundensumme_mm_log_diff'].dropna().plot()

# In[238]:
df_granger = df_granger[['GPS_V_MproH_log_diff', 'INTERPOL_POINT_Niederschlag_Stundensumme_mm_log_diff']]
df_granger.replace([np.inf, -np.inf], np.nan, inplace=True)
df_granger = df_granger.dropna()

# In[239]:
df_differentiated = df_differentiated.merge(df_granger, left_on=['UTC1', 'GPS_V_MproH_log_diff'],
right_on=['UTC1', 'GPS_V_MproH_log_diff'])

# In[240]:
res = grangercausalitytests(df_granger, maxlag=12, verbose=True)

# INTERPOL_POINT_Windgeschwindigkeit_ms
# -----

# In[241]:
cols = ['GPS_V_MproH',
'INTERPOL_POINT_Windgeschwindigkeit_ms']
]

# In[242]:
df_granger = df_mean_hour[cols]

# In[243]:
df_granger

# In[244]:
df_granger.hist(column = 'GPS_V_MproH')

# In[245]:
df_granger.hist(column = 'INTERPOL_POINT_Windgeschwindigkeit_ms')

```

```

# In[246]:
df_granger.plot( y = 'INTERPOL_POINT_Windgeschwindigkeit_ms', figsize=(12,3))
plt.suptitle('Pre differentiation: INTERPOL_POINT_Windgeschwindigkeit_ms', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('INTERPOL_POINT_Windgeschwindigkeit_ms [m/s]', fontsize=14)

# In[247]:
from statsmodels.tsa.stattools import adfuller, kpss

# ADF Test
result = adfuller(df_granger.GPS_V_MproH.values, autolag='AIC')
print(f'ADF Statistic: {result[0]}')
print(f'p-value: {result[1]}')
for key, value in result[4].items():
    print('Critical Values:')
    print(f'    {key}, {value}')

# KPSS Test
result = kpss(df_granger.GPS_V_MproH.values, regression='c')
print(f'\nKPSS Statistic: %f' % result[0])
print(f'p-value: %f' % result[1])
for key, value in result[3].items():
    print('Critical Values:')
    print(f'    {key}, {value}')

# In[248]:
df_granger['GPS_V_MproH_log'] = np.log(df_granger['GPS_V_MproH'])
df_granger['GPS_V_MproH_log_diff'] = df_granger['GPS_V_MproH_log'] - df_granger['GPS_V_MproH_log'].shift(1)
df_granger['GPS_V_MproH_log_diff'].dropna().plot()

# In[249]:
from statsmodels.tsa.stattools import adfuller, kpss

# ADF Test
result = adfuller(df_granger.INTERPOL_POINT_Windgeschwindigkeit_ms.values, autolag='AIC')
print(f'ADF Statistic: {result[0]}')
print(f'p-value: {result[1]}')
for key, value in result[4].items():
    print('Critical Values:')
    print(f'    {key}, {value}')

# KPSS Test
result = kpss(df_granger.INTERPOL_POINT_Windgeschwindigkeit_ms.values, regression='c')
print(f'\nKPSS Statistic: %f' % result[0])
print(f'p-value: %f' % result[1])
for key, value in result[3].items():
    print('Critical Values:')
    print(f'    {key}, {value}')

# In[250]:
df_granger['INTERPOL_POINT_Windgeschwindigkeit_ms_log'] = np.log(df_granger['INTERPOL_POINT_Windgeschwindigkeit_ms'])
df_granger['INTERPOL_POINT_Windgeschwindigkeit_ms_log_diff'] = df_granger['INTERPOL_POINT_Windgeschwindigkeit_ms_log'] - df_granger['INTERPOL_POINT_Windgeschwindigkeit_ms_log'].shift(1)
df_granger['INTERPOL_POINT_Windgeschwindigkeit_ms_log_diff'].dropna().plot()

# In[251]:
df_granger = df_granger[['GPS_V_MproH_log_diff', 'INTERPOL_POINT_Windgeschwindigkeit_ms_log_diff']]
df_granger.replace([np.inf, -np.inf], np.nan, inplace=True)
df_granger = df_granger.dropna()

# In[252]:
df_differentiated = df_differentiated.merge(df_granger, left_on=['UTC1', 'GPS_V_MproH_log_diff'],
right_on=['UTC1', 'GPS_V_MproH_log_diff'])

# In[253]:
res = grangercausalitytests(df_granger, maxlag=12, verbose=True)

# INTERPOL_POINT_pressure_AGL_hPa_CALCULATED
# -----

# In[254]:
cols = ['GPS_V_MproH',
        'INTERPOL_POINT_pressure_AGL_hPa_CALCULATED']

# In[255]:
df_granger = df_mean_hour[cols]

```

```

# In[256]:
df_granger

# In[257]:
df_granger.hist(column = 'GPS_V_MproH')

# In[258]:
df_granger.hist(column = 'INTERPOL_POINT_pressure_AGL_hPa_CALCULATED')

# In[259]:
df_granger.plot( y = 'INTERPOL_POINT_pressure_AGL_hPa_CALCULATED', figsize=(12,3))
plt.suptitle('Pre differentiation: INTERPOL_POINT_pressure_AGL_hPa_CALCULATED', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('INTERPOL_POINT_pressure_AGL_hPa_CALCULATED [hPa]', fontsize=14)

# In[260]:
from statsmodels.tsa.stattools import adfuller, kpss

# ADF Test
result = adfuller(df_granger.GPS_V_MproH.values, autolag='AIC')
print(f'ADF Statistic: {result[0]}')
print(f'p-value: {result[1]}')
for key, value in result[4].items():
    print('Critical Values:')
    print(f'    {key}, {value}')

# KPSS Test
result = kpss(df_granger.GPS_V_MproH.values, regression='c')
print(f'\nKPSS Statistic: %f' % result[0])
print(f'p-value: %f' % result[1])
for key, value in result[3].items():
    print('Critical Values:')
    print(f'    {key}, {value}')

# In[261]:
df_granger['GPS_V_MproH_log'] = np.log(df_granger['GPS_V_MproH'])
df_granger['GPS_V_MproH_log_diff'] = df_granger['GPS_V_MproH_log'] - df_granger['GPS_V_MproH_log'].shift(1)
df_granger['GPS_V_MproH_log_diff'].dropna().plot()

# In[262]:
from statsmodels.tsa.stattools import adfuller, kpss

# ADF Test
result = adfuller(df_granger.INTERPOL_POINT_pressure_AGL_hPa_CALCULATED.values, autolag='AIC')
print(f'ADF Statistic: {result[0]}')
print(f'p-value: {result[1]}')
for key, value in result[4].items():
    print('Critical Values:')
    print(f'    {key}, {value}')

# KPSS Test
result = kpss(df_granger.INTERPOL_POINT_pressure_AGL_hPa_CALCULATED.values, regression='c')
print(f'\nKPSS Statistic: %f' % result[0])
print(f'p-value: %f' % result[1])
for key, value in result[3].items():
    print('Critical Values:')
    print(f'    {key}, {value}')

# In[263]:
df_granger['INTERPOL_POINT_pressure_AGL_hPa_CALCULATED_log'] = np.log(df_granger['INTERPOL_POINT_pressure_AGL_hPa_CALCULATED'])
df_granger['INTERPOL_POINT_pressure_AGL_hPa_CALCULATED_log_diff'] = df_granger['INTERPOL_POINT_pressure_AGL_hPa_CALCULATED_log'] - df_granger['INTERPOL_POINT_pressure_AGL_hPa_CALCULATED_log'].shift(1)
df_granger['INTERPOL_POINT_pressure_AGL_hPa_CALCULATED_log_diff'].dropna().plot()

# In[264]:
df_granger = df_granger[['GPS_V_MproH_log_diff', 'INTERPOL_POINT_pressure_AGL_hPa_CALCULATED_log_diff']]
df_granger.replace([np.inf, -np.inf], np.nan, inplace=True)
df_granger = df_granger.dropna()

# In[265]:
df_differentiated = df_differentiated.merge(df_granger, left_on=['UTC1', 'GPS_V_MproH_log_diff'],
right_on=['UTC1', 'GPS_V_MproH_log_diff'])

# In[266]:
res = grangercausalitytests(df_granger, maxlag=12, verbose=True)

```

```

# INTERPOL_POINT_Luftdruckaenderung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa
# -----

# In[267]:
cols = ['GPS_V_MproH',
        'INTERPOL_POINT_Luftdruckaenderung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa'
]

# In[268]:
df_granger = df_mean_hour[cols]

# In[269]:
df_granger

# In[270]:
df_granger.hist(column = 'GPS_V_MproH')

# In[271]:
df_granger.hist(column = 'INTERPOL_POINT_Luftdruckaenderung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa')

# In[272]:
df_granger.plot(y = 'INTERPOL_POINT_Luftdruckaenderung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa', figsize=(12,3))
plt.suptitle('Pre differentiation: INTERPOL_POINT_Luftdruckaenderung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('INTERPOL_POINT_Luftdruckaenderung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa [hPa]', fontsize=14)

# In[273]:
from statsmodels.tsa.stattools import adfuller, kpss

# ADF Test
result = adfuller(df_granger.GPS_V_MproH.values, autolag='AIC')
print(f'ADF Statistic: {result[0]}')
print(f'p-value: {result[1]}')
for key, value in result[4].items():
    print('Critical Values:')
    print(f'    {key}, {value}')

# KPSS Test
result = kpss(df_granger.GPS_V_MproH.values, regression='c')
print(f'\nKPSS Statistic: %f' % result[0])
print(f'p-value: %f' % result[1])
for key, value in result[3].items():
    print('Critical Values:')
    print(f'    {key}, {value}')

# In[274]:
df_granger['GPS_V_MproH_log'] = np.log(df_granger['GPS_V_MproH'])
df_granger['GPS_V_MproH_log_diff'] = df_granger['GPS_V_MproH_log'] - df_granger['GPS_V_MproH_log'].shift(1)
df_granger['GPS_V_MproH_log_diff'].dropna().plot()

# In[275]:
from statsmodels.tsa.stattools import adfuller, kpss

# ADF Test
result = adfuller(df_granger.INTERPOL_POINT_Luftdruckaenderung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa.values, autolag='AIC')
print(f'ADF Statistic: {result[0]}')
print(f'p-value: {result[1]}')
for key, value in result[4].items():
    print('Critical Values:')
    print(f'    {key}, {value}')

# KPSS Test
result = kpss(df_granger.INTERPOL_POINT_Luftdruckaenderung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa.values, regression='c')
print(f'\nKPSS Statistic: %f' % result[0])
print(f'p-value: %f' % result[1])
for key, value in result[3].items():
    print('Critical Values:')
    print(f'    {key}, {value}')

# In[276]:
df_granger['INTERPOL_POINT_Luftdruckaenderung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa_log'] = np.log(df_granger['INTERPOL_POINT_Luftdruckaenderung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa'])
df_granger['INTERPOL_POINT_Luftdruckaenderung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa_log_diff'] = df_granger['INTERPOL_POINT_Luftdruckaenderung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa_log'] - df_granger['INTERPOL_POINT_Luftdruckaenderung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa_log'].shift(1)
df_granger['INTERPOL_POINT_Luftdruckaenderung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa_log_diff'].dropna().plot()

```

```

# In[277]:
df_granger = df_granger[['GPS_V_MproH_log_diff', 'INTERPOL_POINT_Luftdruckkaende-
rung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa_log_diff']]
df_granger.replace([np.inf, -np.inf], np.nan, inplace=True)
df_granger = df_granger.dropna()

# In[278]:
df_differenziert = df_differenziert.merge(df_granger, left_on=['UTC1', 'GPS_V_MproH_log_diff'],
right_on=['UTC1', 'GPS_V_MproH_log_diff'])

# In[279]:
res = grangercausalitytests(df_granger, maxlag=12, verbose=True)

# INTERPOL_POINT_rel_Luftfeuchtigkeit_Stundenmittel_prozent
# -----

# In[280]:
cols = ['GPS_V_MproH',
'INTERPOL_POINT_rel_Luftfeuchtigkeit_Stundenmittel_prozent'
]

# In[281]:
df_granger = df_mean_hour[cols]

# In[282]:
df_granger

# In[283]:
df_granger.hist(column = 'GPS_V_MproH')

# In[284]:
df_granger.hist(column = 'INTERPOL_POINT_rel_Luftfeuchtigkeit_Stundenmittel_prozent')

# In[285]:
df_granger.plot(y = 'INTERPOL_POINT_rel_Luftfeuchtigkeit_Stundenmittel_prozent', figsize=(12,3))
plt.suptitle('Pre differentiation: INTERPOL_POINT_rel_Luftfeuchtigkeit_Stundenmittel_prozent', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('INTERPOL_POINT_rel_Luftfeuchtigkeit_Stundenmittel_prozent [%]', fontsize=14)

# In[286]:
from statsmodels.tsa.stattools import adfuller, kpss

# ADF Test
result = adfuller(df_granger.GPS_V_MproH.values, autolag='AIC')
print(f'ADF Statistic: {result[0]}')
print(f'p-value: {result[1]}')
for key, value in result[4].items():
    print('Critical Values:')
    print(f'    {key}, {value}')

# KPSS Test
result = kpss(df_granger.GPS_V_MproH.values, regression='c')
print(f'\nKPSS Statistic: %f' % result[0])
print(f'p-value: %f' % result[1])
for key, value in result[3].items():
    print('Critical Values:')
    print(f'    {key}, {value}')

# In[287]:
df_granger['GPS_V_MproH_log'] = np.log(df_granger['GPS_V_MproH'])
df_granger['GPS_V_MproH_log_diff'] = df_granger['GPS_V_MproH_log'] - df_granger['GPS_V_MproH_log'].shift(1)
df_granger['GPS_V_MproH_log_diff'].dropna().plot()

# In[288]:
from statsmodels.tsa.stattools import adfuller, kpss

# ADF Test
result = adfuller(df_granger.INTERPOL_POINT_rel_Luftfeuchtigkeit_Stundenmittel_prozent.values, autolag='AIC')
print(f'ADF Statistic: {result[0]}')
print(f'p-value: {result[1]}')
for key, value in result[4].items():
    print('Critical Values:')
    print(f'    {key}, {value}')

# KPSS Test
result = kpss(df_granger.INTERPOL_POINT_rel_Luftfeuchtigkeit_Stundenmittel_prozent.values, regression='c')

```

```

print('\nKPSS Statistic: %f' % result[0])
print('p-value: %f' % result[1])
for key, value in result[3].items():
    print('Critical Values:')
    print(f'    {key}, {value}')

# In[289]:
df_granger['INTERPOL_POINT_rel_Luftfeuchtigkeit_Stundenmittel_prozent_log'] = np.log(df_granger['INTER-
POL_POINT_rel_Luftfeuchtigkeit_Stundenmittel_prozent'])
df_granger['INTERPOL_POINT_rel_Luftfeuchtigkeit_Stundenmittel_prozent_log_diff'] = df_granger['INTER-
POL_POINT_rel_Luftfeuchtigkeit_Stundenmittel_prozent_log'] - df_granger['INTERPOL_POINT_rel_Luftfeuchtig-
keit_Stundenmittel_prozent_log'].shift(1)
df_granger['INTERPOL_POINT_rel_Luftfeuchtigkeit_Stundenmittel_prozent_log_diff'].dropna().plot()

# In[290]:
df_granger = df_granger[['GPS_V_MproH_log_diff', 'INTERPOL_POINT_rel_Luftfeuchtigkeit_Stundenmittel_pro-
zent_log_diff']]
df_granger.replace([np.inf, -np.inf], np.nan, inplace=True)
df_granger = df_granger.dropna()

# In[291]:
df_differenziert = df_differenziert.merge(df_granger, left_on=['UTC1', 'GPS_V_MproH_log_diff'],
right_on=['UTC1', 'GPS_V_MproH_log_diff'])

# In[292]:
res = grangercausalitytests(df_granger, maxlag=12, verbose=True)

# INTERPOL_POINT_sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min
# -----

# In[293]:
cols = ['GPS_V_MproH',
'INTERPOL_POINT_sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min'
]

# In[294]:
df_granger = df_mean_hour[cols]

# In[295]:
df_granger

# In[296]:
df_granger.hist(column = 'GPS_V_MproH')

# In[297]:
df_granger.hist(column = 'INTERPOL_POINT_sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min')

# In[298]:
df_granger.plot(y = 'INTERPOL_POINT_sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min', figsize=(12,3))
plt.suptitle('Pre differentiation: INTERPOL_POINT_sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('INTERPOL_POINT_sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min [min]', fontsize=14)

# In[299]:
from statsmodels.tsa.stattools import adfuller, kpss

# ADF Test
result = adfuller(df_granger.GPS_V_MproH.values, autolag='AIC')
print(f'ADF Statistic: {result[0]}')
print(f'p-value: {result[1]}')
for key, value in result[4].items():
    print('Critical Values:')
    print(f'    {key}, {value}')

# KPSS Test
result = kpss(df_granger.GPS_V_MproH.values, regression='c')
print('\nKPSS Statistic: %f' % result[0])
print('p-value: %f' % result[1])
for key, value in result[3].items():
    print('Critical Values:')
    print(f'    {key}, {value}')

# In[300]:
df_granger['GPS_V_MproH_log'] = np.log(df_granger['GPS_V_MproH'])
df_granger['GPS_V_MproH_log_diff'] = df_granger['GPS_V_MproH_log'] - df_granger['GPS_V_MproH_log'].shift(1)
df_granger['GPS_V_MproH_log_diff'].dropna().plot()

```

```

# In[301]:
from statsmodels.tsa.stattools import adfuller, kpss

# ADF Test
result = adfuller(df_granger.INTERPOL_POINT_sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min.values, autolag='AIC')
print(f'ADF Statistic: {result[0]}')
print(f'p-value: {result[1]}')
for key, value in result[4].items():
    print('Critical Values:')
    print(f'    {key}, {value}')

# KPSS Test
result = kpss(df_granger.INTERPOL_POINT_sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min.values, regression='c')
print(f'\nKPSS Statistic: %f' % result[0])
print(f'p-value: %f' % result[1])
for key, value in result[3].items():
    print('Critical Values:')
    print(f'    {key}, {value}')

# In[302]:
df_granger['INTERPOL_POINT_sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min_log'] = np.log(df_granger['INTERPOL_POINT_sonnen-
scheindauer_stundensumme_min'])
df_granger['INTERPOL_POINT_sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min_log_diff'] = df_granger['INTERPOL_POINT_sonnen-
scheindauer_stundensumme_min_log'] - df_granger['INTERPOL_POINT_sonnenscheindauer_stunden-
summe_min_log'].shift(1)
df_granger['INTERPOL_POINT_sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min_log_diff'].dropna().plot()

# In[303]:
df_granger = df_granger[['GPS_V_MproH_log_diff', 'INTERPOL_POINT_sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min_log_diff']]
df_granger.replace([np.inf, -np.inf], np.nan, inplace=True)
df_granger = df_granger.dropna()

# In[304]:
df_differentiated = df_differentiated.merge(df_granger, left_on=['UTC1', 'GPS_V_MproH_log_diff'],
right_on=['UTC1', 'GPS_V_MproH_log_diff'])

# In[305]:
res = grangercausalitytests(df_granger, maxlag=12, verbose=True)

# INTERPOL_POINT_Globalstrahlung_wm2
# -----

# In[306]:
cols = ['GPS_V_MproH',
'INTERPOL_POINT_Globalstrahlung_wm2']

# In[307]:
df_granger = df_mean_hour[cols]

# In[308]:
df_granger

# In[309]:
df_granger.hist(column = 'GPS_V_MproH')

# In[310]:
df_granger.hist(column = 'INTERPOL_POINT_Globalstrahlung_wm2')

# In[311]:
df_granger.plot(y = 'INTERPOL_POINT_Globalstrahlung_wm2', figsize=(12,3))
plt.suptitle('Pre differentiation: INTERPOL_POINT_Globalstrahlung_wm2', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('INTERPOL_POINT_Globalstrahlung_wm2 [W/m^2]', fontsize=14)

# In[312]:
from statsmodels.tsa.stattools import adfuller, kpss

# ADF Test
result = adfuller(df_granger.GPS_V_MproH.values, autolag='AIC')
print(f'ADF Statistic: {result[0]}')
print(f'p-value: {result[1]}')
for key, value in result[4].items():
    print('Critical Values:')
    print(f'    {key}, {value}')

```

```

# KPSS Test
result = kpss(df_granger.GPS_V_MproH.values, regression='c')
print('\nKPSS Statistic: %f' % result[0])
print('p-value: %f' % result[1])
for key, value in result[3].items():
    print('Critical Values:')
    print(f'    {key}, {value}')

# In[313]:
df_granger['GPS_V_MproH_log'] = np.log(df_granger['GPS_V_MproH'])
df_granger['GPS_V_MproH_log_diff'] = df_granger['GPS_V_MproH_log'] - df_granger['GPS_V_MproH_log'].shift(1)
df_granger['GPS_V_MproH_log_diff'].dropna().plot()

# In[314]:
from statsmodels.tsa.stattools import adfuller, kpss

# ADF Test
result = adfuller(df_granger.INTERPOL_POINT_Globalstrahlung_wm2.values, autolag='AIC')
print(f'ADF Statistic: {result[0]}')
print(f'p-value: {result[1]}')
for key, value in result[4].items():
    print('Critical Values:')
    print(f'    {key}, {value}')

# KPSS Test
result = kpss(df_granger.INTERPOL_POINT_Globalstrahlung_wm2.values, regression='c')
print('\nKPSS Statistic: %f' % result[0])
print('p-value: %f' % result[1])
for key, value in result[3].items():
    print('Critical Values:')
    print(f'    {key}, {value}')

# In[315]:
df_granger['INTERPOL_POINT_Globalstrahlung_wm2_log'] = np.log(df_granger['INTERPOL_POINT_Globalstrahlung_wm2'])
df_granger['INTERPOL_POINT_Globalstrahlung_wm2_log_diff'] = df_granger['INTERPOL_POINT_Globalstrahlung_wm2_log'] - df_granger['INTERPOL_POINT_Globalstrahlung_wm2_log'].shift(1)
df_granger['INTERPOL_POINT_Globalstrahlung_wm2_log_diff'].dropna().plot()

# In[316]:
df_granger = df_granger[['GPS_V_MproH_log_diff', 'INTERPOL_POINT_Globalstrahlung_wm2_log_diff']]
df_granger.replace([np.inf, -np.inf], np.nan, inplace=True)
df_granger = df_granger.dropna()

# In[317]:
df_differentiated = df_differentiated.merge(df_granger, left_on=['UTC1', 'GPS_V_MproH_log_diff'],
right_on=['UTC1', 'GPS_V_MproH_log_diff'])

# In[318]:
res = grangercausalitytests(df_granger, maxlag=12, verbose=True)

# INTERPOL_POINT_Foehnindex
# -----

# In[319]:
cols = ['GPS_V_MproH',
        'INTERPOL_POINT_Foehnindex']
]

# In[320]:
df_granger = df_mean_hour[cols]

# In[321]:
df_granger

# In[322]:
df_granger.hist(column = 'GPS_V_MproH')

# In[323]:
df_granger.hist(column = 'INTERPOL_POINT_Foehnindex')

# In[324]:
df_granger.plot(y = 'INTERPOL_POINT_Foehnindex', figsize=(12,3))
plt.suptitle('Pre differentiation: INTERPOL_POINT_Foehnindex', fontsize=18)
plt.ylabel('INTERPOL_POINT_Foehnindex [0-3]', fontsize=14)

```

```

# In[325]:
from statsmodels.tsa.stattools import adfuller, kpss

# ADF Test
result = adfuller(df_granger.GPS_V_MproH.values, autolag='AIC')
print(f'ADF Statistic: {result[0]}')
print(f'p-value: {result[1]}')
for key, value in result[4].items():
    print('Critical Values:')
    print(f'    {key}, {value}')

# KPSS Test
result = kpss(df_granger.GPS_V_MproH.values, regression='c')
print(f'\nKPSS Statistic: %f' % result[0])
print(f'p-value: %f' % result[1])
for key, value in result[3].items():
    print('Critical Values:')
    print(f'    {key}, {value}')

# In[326]:
df_granger['GPS_V_MproH_log'] = np.log(df_granger['GPS_V_MproH'])
df_granger['GPS_V_MproH_log_diff'] = df_granger['GPS_V_MproH_log'] - df_granger['GPS_V_MproH_log'].shift(1)
df_granger['GPS_V_MproH_log_diff'].dropna().plot()

# In[327]:
from statsmodels.tsa.stattools import adfuller, kpss

# ADF Test
result = adfuller(df_granger.INTERPOL_POINT_Foehnindex.values, autolag='AIC')
print(f'ADF Statistic: {result[0]}')
print(f'p-value: {result[1]}')
for key, value in result[4].items():
    print('Critical Values:')
    print(f'    {key}, {value}')

# KPSS Test
result = kpss(df_granger.INTERPOL_POINT_Foehnindex.values, regression='c')
print(f'\nKPSS Statistic: %f' % result[0])
print(f'p-value: %f' % result[1])
for key, value in result[3].items():
    print('Critical Values:')
    print(f'    {key}, {value}')

# In[328]:
df_granger['INTERPOL_POINT_Foehnindex_log'] = np.log(df_granger['INTERPOL_POINT_Foehnindex'])
df_granger['INTERPOL_POINT_Foehnindex_log_diff'] = df_granger['INTERPOL_POINT_Foehnindex_log'] -
df_granger['INTERPOL_POINT_Foehnindex_log'].shift(1)
df_granger['INTERPOL_POINT_Foehnindex_log_diff'].dropna().plot()

# In[329]:
df_granger = df_granger[['GPS_V_MproH_log_diff', 'INTERPOL_POINT_Foehnindex_log_diff']]
df_granger.replace([np.inf, -np.inf], np.nan, inplace=True)
df_granger = df_granger.dropna()

# In[330]:
df_differentiated = df_differentiated.merge(df_granger, left_on=['UTC1', 'GPS_V_MproH_log_diff'],
right_on=['UTC1', 'GPS_V_MproH_log_diff'])

# In[331]:
res = grangercausalitytests(df_granger, maxlag=12, verbose=True)

# Correlation
# -----

# In[332]:
df_corr1 = df.corr()

# In[333]:
df_corr1

# In[334]:
plt.figure(figsize = (15,10))

sns_plot = sns.heatmap(df_corr1,xticklabels=True, yticklabels=True).set_title('Correlation Heatmap Hourly
Mean')

```

```

fig = sns_plot.get_figure()

fig.savefig(path_to_output + 'Corr_Heatmap_Mean.jpg',bbox_inches='tight')

sns.heatmap(df_corr1)

# In[335]:
df_mean_corr = df_mean.corr()

# In[336]:
df_mean_corr

# In[337]:
plt.figure(figsize = (15,10))

sns_plot = sns.heatmap(df_mean_corr,xticklabels=True, yticklabels=True).set_title('Correlation Heatmap Hourly Mean')

fig = sns_plot.get_figure()

fig.savefig(path_to_output + 'Mean_hourly_Corr_Heatmap.jpg',bbox_inches='tight')

sns.heatmap(df_mean_corr)

# In[338]:
df_differentiatet_corr = df_differentiatet.corr()

# In[388]:
# write df_new to csv output
print('write df_new to csv output')
df_differentiatet_corr.to_csv(path_to_output + 'DF_Differentiatet_corr.csv', index = False)
print('-- successfull \n')

# In[389]:
df_differentiatet_corr

# In[340]:
plt.figure(figsize = (15,10))

sns_plot = sns.heatmap(df_differentiatet_corr,xticklabels=True, yticklabels=True).set_title('Correlation Heatmap Hourly Mean - Differentiatet')

fig = sns_plot.get_figure()

fig.savefig(path_to_output + 'Mean_hourly_Cor_Differentiatetr_Heatmap.jpg',bbox_inches='tight')

sns.heatmap(df_differentiatet_corr)

# In[341]:
colsdeer = ['GPS_DISTANCE_ABSOLUTE','GPS_TierID']

# In[342]:
df_tier_tagessumme = df_original[colsdeer]

# In[343]:
df_tier_tagessumme = df_tier_tagessumme.reset_index()

# In[344]:
df_tier_tagessumme = df_tier_tagessumme.groupby(['GPS_TierID',df_tier_tagessumme.UTC1.dt.date])

# In[345]:
df_tier_tagessumme = df_tier_tagessumme.sum()

# In[346]:
df_tier_tagessumme = df_tier_tagessumme.reset_index()

# In[347]:
df_tier_tagessumme = df_tier_tagessumme.set_index('UTC1')

# In[348]:
df_tier_tagessumme

```

```

# In[349]:
cols_weather_day = ['GPS_TierID',
                    'GPS_Temp',
                    'INTERPOL_POINT_Foehnindex',
                    'INTERPOL_POINT_Globalstrahlung_wm2',
                    'INTERPOL_POINT_Luftdruckaenderung_seit_letzte_Stunde_hPa',
                    'INTERPOL_POINT_Neuschnee_Momentanwert_cm',
                    'INTERPOL_POINT_Niederschlag_Stundensumme_mm',

                    'INTERPOL_POINT_Windgeschwindigkeit_ms',
                    'INTERPOL_POINT_Windrichtung_grad',
                    'INTERPOL_POINT_dewpoint_AGL_C_CALCULATED',
                    'INTERPOL_POINT_pressure_AGL_hPa_CALCULATED',
                    'INTERPOL_POINT_rel_Luftfeuchtigkeit_Stundenmittel_prozent',
                    'INTERPOL_POINT_sonnenscheindauer_stundensumme_min',
                    'INTERPOL_POINT_temp_AGL_C_CALCULATED',
                    ]

# In[350]:
df_variables_by_deer_day_mean = df_original[cols_weather_day]

# In[351]:
df_variables_by_deer_day_mean = df_variables_by_deer_day_mean.reset_index()

# In[352]:
df_variables_by_deer_day_mean = df_variables_by_deer_day_mean.groupby(['GPS_TierID',df_variables_by_deer_day_mean.UTC1.dt.date]).mean()

# In[353]:
df_variables_by_deer_day_mean = df_variables_by_deer_day_mean.reset_index()
df_variables_by_deer_day_mean

# In[354]:
df_day_deer_mean_distance_sum = pd.merge(df_variables_by_deer_day_mean,df_tier_tagessumme, how='left',
left_on=['GPS_TierID','UTC1'], right_on = ['GPS_TierID','UTC1'])

# In[355]:
df_day_deer_mean_distance_sum

# In[356]:
df_day_deer_mean_distance_sum.plot(x="INTERPOL_POINT_temp_AGL_C_CALCULATED", y="GPS_DISTANCE_ABSOLUTE",
kind='scatter')
plt.suptitle('Temperature vs Distanve per Day', fontsize=18)
#plt.savefig(path_to_output + 'velocity_pressurechange.jpg')

# In[357]:
df_day_deer_mean_distance_sum = df_day_deer_mean_distance_sum.set_index(['GPS_TierID', 'UTC1'])

# In[358]:
df_day_deer_mean_distance_sum

# In[359]:
df_day_deer_mean_distance_sum_Norm = (df_day_deer_mean_distance_sum-df_day_deer_mean_distance_sum.min())/(df_day_deer_mean_distance_sum.max()-df_day_deer_mean_distance_sum.min())

# In[360]:
df_day_deer_mean_distance_sum_Norm

# df_day_deer_mean_distance_sum_Norm.info()

# TEST: ML Random Forest Regression
# -----

# https://towardsdatascience.com/random-forest-in-python-24d0893d51c0

# One-Hot Encoding
# The first step for us is known as one-hot encoding of the data. This process takes categorical variables,
such as days of the week and converts it to a numerical representation without an arbitrary ordering. Days of
the week are intuitive to us because we use them all the time. You will (hopefully) never find anyone who
doesn't know that 'Mon' refers to the first day of the workweek, but machines do not have any intuitive
knowledge. What computers know is numbers and for machine learning we must accommodate them.
#
# One-hot encoded categorical variables
# Split data into features and labels

```

```

# Converted to arrays
# Split data into training and testing sets

# ML mean per Hour df_differentiatet

# In[361]:
df_differentiatet

# In[362]:
df_nan = df_differentiatet[df_differentiatet.isna().any(axis=1)]
df_nan

# Establish Baseline
# Before we can make and evaluate predictions, we need to establish a baseline, a sensible measure that we hope
to beat with our model. If our model cannot improve upon the baseline, then it will be a failure and we should
try a different model or admit that machine learning is not right for our problem. The baseline prediction for
our case can be the historical max temperature averages. In other words, our baseline is the error we would get
if we simply predicted the average max temperature for all DIFFs.

# In[363]:
df_differentiatet['rolling_DIFF_avg_vel'] = df_differentiatet['GPS_V_MproH_log_diff'].rolling(4).mean()
df_differentiatet['rolling_DIFF_avg_vel'] = df_differentiatet['rolling_DIFF_avg_vel'].fillna(df_differentiatet['rolling_DIFF_avg_vel'].rolling(2).mean())
df_differentiatet['rolling_DIFF_avg_vel'] = df_differentiatet['rolling_DIFF_avg_vel'].fillna(df_differentiatet['GPS_V_MproH_log_diff'])

# In[364]:
df_differentiatet

# One-Hot Encoding
# The first step for us is known as one-hot encoding of the data. This process takes categorical variables,
such as DIFFs of the week and converts it to a numerical representation without an arbitrary ordering. DIFFs of
the week are intuitive to us because we use them all the time. You will (hopefully) never find anyone who
doesn't know that 'Mon' refers to the first DIFF of the workweek, but machines do not have any intuitive
knowledge. What computers know is numbers and for machine learning we must accommodate them.
#
# One-hot encoded categorical variables
# Split data into features and labels
# Converted to arrays
# Split data into training and testing sets

# In[365]:
features7 = pd.get_dummies(df_differentiatet)

# In[366]:

# Labels are the values we want to predict
labels = np.array(features7['GPS_V_MproH_log_diff'])
# Remove the labels from the features
# axis 1 refers to the columns
features7 = features7.drop('GPS_V_MproH_log_diff', axis = 1)
# Saving feature names for later use
feature_list = list(features7.columns)
# Convert to numpy array
features7 = np.array(features7)

# In[367]:
# Using Skicit-learn to split data into training and testing sets
from sklearn.model_selection import train_test_split
# Split the data into training and testing sets
train_features, test_features, train_labels, test_labels = train_test_split(features7, labels, test_size =
0.15, random_state = 42)

# In[368]:
print('Training Features Shape:', train_features.shape)
print('Training Labels Shape:', train_labels.shape)
print('Testing Features Shape:', test_features.shape)
print('Testing Labels Shape:', test_labels.shape)

# In[369]:
# The baseline predictions are the historical averages
baseline_preds = test_features[:, feature_list.index('rolling_DIFF_avg_vel')]
# Baseline errors, and display average baseline error
baseline_errors = abs(baseline_preds - test_labels)
#baseline_errors = baseline_errors[np.logical_not(np.isnan(baseline_errors))]

print(baseline_errors)
print('Average baseline error: ', round(np.mean(baseline_errors), 2))

```

```

# In[370]:
features8 = pd.get_dummies(df_differentiated)

# In[371]:
features8

# In[372]:
# Labels are the values we want to predict
labels = np.array(features8.GPS_V_MproH_log_diff)
# Remove the labels from the features
# axis 1 refers to the columns
features8= features8.drop('GPS_V_MproH_log_diff', axis = 1)
features8= features8.drop('rolling_DIFF_avg_vel', axis = 1)
#features8= features8.drop('Hour', axis = 1)

# Saving feature names for later use
feature_list = list(features8.columns)
# Convert to numpy array
features8 = np.array(features8)

# In[373]:
# Using Skicit-learn to split data into training and testing sets
from sklearn.model_selection import train_test_split
# Split the data into training and testing sets
train_features, test_features, train_labels, test_labels = train_test_split(features8, labels, test_size =
0.20, random_state = 42)

# In[374]:
print('Training Features Shape:', train_features.shape)
print('Training Labels Shape:', train_labels.shape)
print('Testing Features Shape:', test_features.shape)
print('Testing Labels Shape:', test_labels.shape)

# In[375]:
# Import the model we are using
from sklearn.ensemble import RandomForestRegressor
# Instantiate model with 1000 decision trees
rf = RandomForestRegressor(n_estimators = 1000, random_state = 42)

# In[376]:
train_features

# In[377]:
train_labels

# In[378]:
# Train the model on training data
rf.fit(train_features, train_labels);

# In[379]:
# Use the forest's predict method on the test data
predictions = rf.predict(test_features)
# Calculate the absolute errors
errors = abs(predictions - test_labels)
# Print out the mean absolute error (mae)
print('Mean Absolute Error:', round(np.mean(errors), 2), 'degrees.')
```

```

# In[380]:
errors

# In[381]:
test_labels

# In[382]:
# Calculate mean absolute percentage error (MAPE)
mape = 100 * (errors / test_labels)
# Calculate and display accuracy
accuracy = 100 - np.mean(mape)
print('Accuracy:', round(accuracy, 2), '%.')
accuracy = round(accuracy, 2)

# In[383]:
```

```

# Import tools needed for visualization
from sklearn.tree import export_graphviz
import pydot

# In[384]:
# Pull out one tree from the forest
tree = rf.estimators_[5]
# Export the image to a dot file
export_graphviz(tree, out_file = path_to_output + 'DIFF_tree.dot', feature_names = feature_list, rounded =
True, precision = 1)
# Use dot file to create a graph
(graph, ) = pydot.graph_from_dot_file(path_to_output + 'DIFF_tree.dot')
# Write graph to a png file
graph.write_png(path_to_output + 'DIFF_tree.png')

# In[385]:
# Limit depth of tree to 3 levels
rf_small = RandomForestRegressor(n_estimators=10, max_depth = 3)
rf_small.fit(train_features, train_labels)
# Extract the small tree
tree_small = rf_small.estimators_[5]
# Save the tree as a png image
export_graphviz(tree_small, out_file = path_to_output + 'DIFF_small_tree.dot', feature_names = feature_list,
rounded = True, precision = 1)
(graph, ) = pydot.graph_from_dot_file(path_to_output + 'DIFF_small_tree.dot')
graph.write_png(path_to_output + 'DIFF_small_tree.png');

# In[386]:
# Get numerical feature importances
importances = list(rf.feature_importances_)
# List of tuples with variable and importance
feature_importances = [(feature, round(importance, 2)) for feature, importance in zip(feature_list, impor-
tances)]
# Sort the feature importances by most important first
feature_importances = sorted(feature_importances, key = lambda x: x[1], reverse = True)
# Print out the feature and importances
[print('Variable: {:20} Importance: {}'.format(*pair)) for pair in feature_importances];

# In[390]:
# Import matplotlib for plotting and use magic command for Jupyter Notebooks
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
get_ipython().run_line_magic('matplotlib', 'inline')
# Set the style
plt.style.use('fivethirtyeight')
# list of x locations for plotting
x_values = list(range(len(importances)))
# bar chart
plt.bar(x_values, importances, orientation = 'vertical')
# labels for x axis
plt.xticks(x_values, feature_list, rotation='vertical')
# labels and title
plt.ylabel('Importance'); plt.xlabel('Variables - Accuracy %: ' +str(accuracy)); plt.title('Variable Impor-
tances of hourly differentiatet / stationary');
plt.savefig(path_to_output + 'Diff_hour_mean_Variable_Importances.jpg', bbox_inches='tight')

```